

European
Guanxi

European Youth Perspectives on
International Relations of China

Volume 2, Issue 1 (July 2025)

EU-China at 50: Cooperation, Competition, and Shifting Paradigms

European Youth Perspectives on International Relations of China (EYPIC)

Coordinating Committee

Douglas Brenton ANDERSON
Editor-in-Chief

Sardor ALLAYAROV
Deputy Editor-in-Chief

Kalos LAU
Lead Editor

Design

Kalos LAU

René NEUMANN

Editors

Susanna AGHAJANYAN

George BANOS

Audrey BERDER

Stefano BERTOLI

Daria BOGOLYUBOVA

Marina FERRERO

Franzi KÄNDLER

Maria KIENZLE

Angelo M'BA

Robin MILLET

Agnes MONTI

Barcelona - Volume 2, Issue 1 (July 2025)

© European Guanxi 2020-2025

European
Guanxi

Foreword

The fiftieth anniversary of diplomatic ties between the European Union and the People’s Republic of China invites both retrospection and a critical re-evaluation.

Over the past five decades, this relationship has significantly deepened, shaping developments across politics, economics, technology, trade, security, human rights, culture, and beyond. As the world navigates mounting uncertainties—from the United States’ retreat from the rules-based trading order and the rise of disruptive technologies to broader geopolitical uncertainties—the EU-China relationship has reached a critical juncture. It does not exist in a silo; it is necessary to grasp the far-reaching implications of this relationship in order to address asymmetries and foster constructive engagement in face of uncertainty.

As Editor-in-Chief, I am delighted to welcome a diverse group of young authors from across Europe and beyond, whose contributions explore the nuances of EU-China relations. This edition of *EYPIC* seeks to provide a multifaceted perspective on issues of cooperation, competition, and the shifting paradigms that define this relationship. Through this publication, it is my hope that *European Guanxi* will meaningfully contribute to the broader critical discourse on EU-China relations and continue to serve as a leading platform for youth-driven scholarship.

I would like to extend my sincerest gratitude to the authors, the Coordinating Committee, and the entire Editorial Team at *European Guanxi*, whose dedication has played an instrumental role in shaping the development of this journal. Your dedication and hard work stand as a testament to the power of collaborative scholarship.

Douglas Brenton Anderson
Editor-in-Chief

European Guanxi is dedicated to fostering dialogue between the EU and China, with a core mission to amplify young scholarship. Building on the inaugural edition of *EYPIC*, *Unveiling EU Strategic Autonomy: The Many Faces of a Global Project*, this year’s edition assesses the complexities of EU-China relations through a broad lens—exploring cooperation, challenges, and emerging opportunities across critical areas such as minerals, green technology, climate change, media narratives, diplomacy, and beyond.

This analysis comes at an inflection point in EU-China relations. The EU has characterized China as a “partner for cooperation, an economic competitor, and a systemic rival,” setting the stage for a more complex and calibrated engagement (European External Action Service, 2023). At the same time, relations have fluctuated, particularly as China has engaged in a diplomatic charm offensive to expand its influence globally following the election of President Donald Trump. Against this backdrop, it is vital that the EU adopt a strategic and balanced approach—one that prioritizes European values and interests, balances engagement with the U.S., and pursues mutually beneficial collaboration with China.

Through this journal, we aim to present a diverse array of perspectives that not only reflect the depth and breadth of the EU-China relationship but also comment on its potential trajectory amid global uncertainty.

We would like to thank all of the members of the Editorial Team, without whom this project would not have been possible. We would also like to thank the authors for placing their trust in our mission by contributing their scholarly research and choosing to publish with *European Guanxi*.

EYPIC Coordinating Committee
The European Guanxi Editorial Board

Coordinating Committee

Douglas Brenton Anderson

Douglas Brenton Anderson is Editor-in-Chief at European Guanxi. He holds a double master's from Tsinghua University and the University of Geneva in Public Policy Administration for the Sustainable Development Goals, where he explored the intersection of experimental policymaking and sustainable development in China and Europe. He has held internship roles at the Asia Society Policy Institute, the Center for Strategic and International Studies, and the Hudson Institute in Washington, D.C. His interests include China's economic and security influence, trade policy, and sanctions evasion, on which he has contributed writings to *The Diplomat* and the *Central Asian Bureau for Analytical Reporting*.

Kalos Lau

Kalos Lau is Lead Editor at European Guanxi. He holds a master's degree in Contemporary Chinese Studies from the University of Oxford, where he focused on the interaction of Chinese law, society, and domestic institutional reform. He is currently a Governance and Law Analyst at China Policy, a strategic analysis firm that tracks and interprets policy trends in the People's Republic of China. He was previously funded by the University of Warwick to conduct research on the evolving structure and policy lines of the Chinese state. His research interests include PRC central-local governance, institutional reforms, state-market relations and China's foreign policy, on which he has contributed short commentaries to *Europinion*.

Sardor Allayarov

Sardor Allayarov is Deputy Editor-in-Chief at European Guanxi and a Research Assistant at Urgench State University (Uzbekistan). He graduated with summa cum laude from the University of Szeged, majoring in MA International Relations. Sardor has previously worked as a Research Assistant at the Institute for Foreign Affairs and Trade (Hungary), the Centre for Analysis, Monitoring and Reporting (Slovakia), and the Institute of International Relations (Czech Republic). As a Belt and Road Initiative Scholar, he joined Lanzhou Jiaotong University in the People's Republic of China as a Visiting Research Fellow. He is an expert in international relations with a research focus on theories of international relations, international order, China, Eurasia, and foreign policy.

Contents

1	Maintaining Mutual Understanding: The European Union's Diplomacy in Hong Kong and Macau <i>Alixia BRÛLE</i>	6
2	Charging Ahead: Assessing China's Leverage and the EU's Strategic Dilemma in the EV Transition <i>Caroline SEIL</i>	15
3	Exporting the Chinese School: How Convincing is the Relational Theory of World Politics as Formulated by Yaqing Qin? <i>Carys HOSKING</i>	34
4	Clashing Paradigms and Converging Imperatives of EU-China Climate Diplomacy in the Anthropocene <i>Tin Maung HTWE</i>	49
5	Navigating EU-China Electric Vehicles Trade Disputes: A Game Theory Analysis <i>Dr. Ruotong SHI & Hanyi ZHANG</i>	74
6	China's Dominance in the Rare Earth Supply Chain and the EU's Strategic Response <i>Audrey BERDER</i>	89
7	Climate Cooperation or Challenge: European Media Perception of China in the Context of Climate Change <i>Marie Sophie MAYER</i>	113
8	Navigating the Evolving Landscape: Intellectual Property and Technology Transfer in China's Electric Vehicle Industry <i>Carolina FABARA</i>	131
9	European Guanxi 2024 Essay Competition Winner: Ecocide as a Threat to Global Security: Exploring the Recognition of Ecocide as an International Crime and its Implications <i>Agata BIDAS</i>	149

Maintaining Mutual Understanding: The European Union's Diplomacy in Hong Kong and Macau

Alixia BRÛLE

Introduction

Since its establishment in 1993, the Office of the European Union to Hong Kong and Macau has sought to facilitate dialogue and mutual understanding between its Headquarters in Brussels and the two Special Administrative Region (SAR) Governments. The author had the privilege of interviewing His Excellency Ambassador Harvey Rouse, Head of the EU Office, whose tenure highlights the dynamic nature of the Union's diplomacy in this unique political context. Throughout his career, the Ambassador has dedicated himself to promoting European values and interests, contributing to open and vibrant societies, and reinforcing economic partnerships.

This paper explores the multifaceted mission of the EU Office to Hong Kong and Macau, delving into its role and historical significance while highlighting the diverse areas of cooperation with the two SARs. The article also provides a glimpse into the objectives of the European External Action Service (EEAS), and its crucial role in shaping the EU's foreign policy agenda.

1. Policy Coordination among the Twenty-Seven Member States

The creation of the EEAS, in the wake of the ratification of the Treaty of Lisbon, marked a pivotal evolution in European foreign policy in 2009. The 27 Member States now entrusted a shared diplomatic corps, serving as the compass for their collective external action. In practice, over 5,000 officials work under the direction of the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy—at the time of writing, Kaja Kallas—to ensure a strategic and coherent direction in

the EU's external engagements. With a presence spanning all six continents, the EEAS not only prepares policy proposals but also implements them after European Council approval. The Service further assists the President of the European Council, António Costa, and the President of the European Commission, Ursula von der Leyen, in advancing the Union's diplomatic agenda (European Union, 2025).

Operating within the EEAS structure, 145 EU Delegations and Offices across the planet function similarly to embassies, fostering mutual understanding and monitoring political and economic development locally (EEAS, 2025). These European representations have enhanced a TeamEurope Approach, ensuring that the collective efforts of Brussels and the 27 EU capitals lead to more impactful outcomes on the ground. Among them, the EU Office in Hong Kong and Macau has been a crucial player in promoting the EU's visibility in the Greater Bay Area.

2. History of Diplomatic Ties between the European Union, Hong Kong, and Macau

As the European Union and China mark half a century of diplomatic ties this year, it presents a timely opportunity to examine the evolution of the EU's engagement with the Special Administrative Regions of Hong Kong and Macau. These territories were formally handed over to the People's Republic of China by the United Kingdom in 1997 and 1999, respectively. Since then, Hong Kong and Macau have embodied a distinctive governance model characterized by the coexistence of central government oversight and a high degree of local autonomy, necessitating a tailored diplomatic approach. In this interview, Ambassador Rouse offered an insightful retrospective on the major moments that shaped the EU's unique framework to the two SARs.

Ambassador Rouse: *“The Office of the European Union to Hong Kong and Macau was established in October 1993 as the ‘Office of the European Commission to Hong Kong and Macau,’ before the EU as we know it today was born.*

Following 1 July 1997 and 20 December 1999, the EU has always supported the implementation of ‘one country, two systems’ and ‘high degree of autonomy’ in Hong Kong and Macau, as well as a smooth transition of sovereignty. This spirit ran through several official documents published before the handovers.

In 1996, the European Council stated the EU’s stance on the transition in Hong Kong and Macau. With regards to Hong Kong, the High Representatives reiterated that ‘the European Union’s strong interest in the future peace and prosperity of Hong Kong’ and ‘the European Union’s desire to do anything possible to contribute to a smooth transition.’ The EU stated its commitment to ‘strong continuing relations with the SAR in the World Trade Organization and in all other matters where the SAR will enjoy autonomy under the Basic Law.’

With regards to Macau, the Conclusions of the European Council hoped that the Sino-Portuguese Joint Declaration ‘will continue to contribute to the progress and social stability’ of Macau.

In April 1997, the EU concluded that ‘far from being a time to downgrade links with Hong Kong, 1997 should mark another step forward in the progressive enhancement of ties between the European Union and Hong Kong’ in ‘The European Union and Hong Kong: Beyond 1997—Communication from the Commission to the Council.’

The EU acknowledged that while the primary responsibility for making Hong Kong a success ‘must lie with the Hong Kong government and the Chinese authorities,’

Europe can ‘play its part in helping the SAR as an autonomous administration to operate as foreseen.’ For example, the EU pledged to deal directly with Hong Kong and Macau in areas within the responsibility of the SAR governments.

This may sound a bit abstract. Let me give an example that actually had an impact on millions of residents in Hong Kong and Macau. Back then, for the purposes of the EU’s common visa list, we promised access to residents from Hong Kong and Macau on their own merits.

And we did live up to our promise. In 2001, the EU Parliament and the Council of Ministers approved a European Commission proposal in favor of visa-free access to the EU for Hong Kong and Macau SAR passport holders. This rule became effective on 10 April 2001 and was welcomed by both the Hong Kong and Macau SAR authorities.

The EU took action to demonstrate confidence in the future of Hong Kong and Macau and believed that freer access to the EU would be in the interests of all three places.

Following the visit of former European Commission President José Barroso to Hong Kong and Macau in July 2005, the EU published ‘The European Union, Hong Kong and Macau: Possibilities for cooperation 2007-2013.’ The Communication from the Commission to the Council and the Parliament laid out areas for cooperation: trade and customs, finance, people-to-people and academic links, transport, health and food safety and environment. The former President visited Hong Kong again in 2013.

More challenging relations between the EU and Hong Kong started in 2020. On 30 June that year, the Standing Committee of China’s National People’s Congress adopted the National Security Law for Hong Kong. In the Council conclusions on Hong Kong adopted on 24 July, the EU stated that ‘China’s actions and the new legislation are not in conformity with China’s international commitments under 24 July, the EU stated that ‘China’s actions and the new

legislation are not in conformity with China's international commitments under the Sino-British Joint Declaration of 1984 or with the Hong Kong Basic Law.'

Upholding international commitments is important and in the following years, further developments of concern took place, including the conviction of pro-democracy activists. The EU has also voiced concerns via public statements and private conversations with Hong Kong and mainland Chinese authorities.

With this change in the political atmosphere, I have seen media outlets and local interlocutors trying to paint the EU as a negative foreign influence in Hong Kong. However, many of the examples I recalled above show that the EU genuinely wants the 'one country, two systems' to succeed and we continue to contribute to this objective. Our voiced concerns are all well-intended and we wish to strengthen our relations based on the principles of the one country, two systems."

3. The Engagement of the EU Office

A reflection on its history reveals that the role of the Office to Hong Kong and Macau has been multifaceted. Its primary task is to foster bilateral relations between the European Union and the governments of Hong Kong and Macau. The Office aims to present the interests and positions of the 27 Member States as a Union to the local authorities.

Moreover, the European representation facilitates communication between the Headquarters of the Commission in Brussels and the SAR officials. Its staff monitors, analyzes and reports on local policy developments, ensuring that EU decision-makers are well-informed about regional affairs. Additionally, the team coordinates visits from EU representatives, providing briefing materials and reports before their meeting with local stakeholders (EEAS, 2025).

Public diplomacy is another important facet of the EEAS. Through its social media platforms or official website, the Office seeks to promote the visibility of the European Union. It offers a better understanding of the affairs, interests and values of the institution to Hong Kongers and Macanese. The Office hosts diverse events throughout the year, enhancing the cultural richness of European countries while deepening ties with the local civil society. In parallel, the organization remains committed to promoting academic exchange, creating opportunities for students and researchers from Hong Kong, Macau, and Europe to travel and learn from one another.

Crucially, the European Union Office maintains close coordination with the diplomatic missions of all EU Member States represented in Hong Kong and Macau. Ambassador Rouse and his team regularly convene meetings with the fifteen Consuls General based locally. The objective is to maintain a coherent and unified voice on key regional issues. Particular emphasis is placed on monitoring political and economic developments, as well as human rights.

4. Diplomatic Profile: Ambassador Harvey Rouse

Ambassador Rouse has a distinguished diplomatic career, marked by a strong commitment to promoting the values of the European Union across continents. From a young age, Mr. Rouse has been dedicated to contributing to the EU's integration and cooperation. He began his professional journey in European affairs in Brussels, where he worked with both the European Parliament and the European Commission on EU trade policy. Ambassador Rouse has served at three European Union Delegations, including as Head of the Trade and Economic Section in Indonesia, Brunei Darussalam, and ASEAN. His expertise was also celebrated at the Political and Trade Sections in Uganda and in Kenya, where he participated in the EU election monitoring in 2007. Ambassador Rouse gained significant experience in working

with political stakeholders with diverse backgrounds and identifying pathways to reinforce EU diplomatic relations.

Before his assignment in Hong Kong and Macau, the Ambassador held a significant position at the Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport (DG-MOVE) at the European Commission. As the Head of the Unit on International Relations, Mr. Rouse played a critical role in fostering strategic partnerships with third countries and promoting European interests outside the Schengen borders. Among his most significant tasks was his support for Ukraine in establishing alternative land routes for the export of agricultural goods after the 2022 bombing of Odessa, a city on the northwestern shore of the Black Sea. Since the onset of Russia's invasion of Ukraine, Ambassador Rouse has remained steadfast in his commitment to the EU stance—supporting Kiev and advocating for a just and lasting peace.

In addition to his diplomatic journey, Harvey Rouse has extensive experience in the cinematographic sector. In 1994, he became the youngest Vice President at the Motion Picture Association of America (MPAA), which represents seven of the most preeminent Hollywood studios. Mr. Rouse was responsible for overseeing and lobbying on matters related to television, theater, and digital platforms in the EU.

His deep passion for the film industry is often reflected in the themes and references of his official speeches. Ambassador Rouse understands that movies can transcend language and cultures and share ideas and perspectives more effectively than any other diplomatic tool.

With his inspiring and international background, Ambassador Rouse has developed a unique perspective and deep understanding of foreign policy in Asia and elsewhere. This expertise equips him to

effectively lead the EU's representation in Hong Kong and Macau and to make informed and strategic decisions on behalf of the European Commission.

5. The Role of Head of the EU Office to Hong Kong and Macau

Ambassador Rouse officially began his tenure as the Head of the EU Office to Hong Kong and Macau in September 2024. The Ambassador took the time to offer insights into his specific responsibilities and the complexities of his position:

Ambassador Rouse: *“The EU has long enjoyed close, broad and deep relations with both Hong Kong and Macau. As the EU Ambassador to these two Special Administrative Regions, I aim to strengthen these ties and explore new avenues for cooperation that will benefit both sides, whilst upholding universal values.*

I am committed to ensuring that the existing economic partnerships will continue to expand, facilitating more opportunities for trade, investment, and collaboration in key sectors such as technology, green energy, and finance. Meanwhile, I stand ready to support both Special Administrative Regions' uniqueness, their high degree of autonomy and their commitment to these principles. It is through open dialogue and mutual respect that we can address any challenges that arise and work towards solutions that uphold the dignity and rights of all individuals.

I am committed to fostering partnerships that are dynamic, forward-looking, and mutually beneficial. I believe that we can seize opportunities for growth, and promote a future where prosperity, sustainability, and human rights go hand in hand.”

6. The Economic Connector with Mainland China

One of the crucial tasks of the Office is to facilitate trade and dialogue between business communities in Europe, Hong Kong and Macau

(EEAS, 2025). The status of Hong Kong and Macau (EEAS, 2025). The status of Hong Kong as China's primary gateway to the world may be eroded by the tariff escalation between Beijing and Washington. Amid a challenging international environment this year, the EU is intensifying its efforts to uphold the robustness of its economic relationships with local stakeholders. Brussels cooperates with Consulate Generals to maintain a welcoming environment for European investors and workers.

Author: *"As of June 2024, the European Union has imposed 70 anti-dumping measures and 10 countervailing duties on China. Yet, Hong Kong and the EU have maintained a relatively stable trade relationship. Do you foresee any potential impact of these economic tensions on Hong Kong? And do you believe Hong Kong will continue to be the preferred hub for EU companies' regional headquarters in Asia?"*

Ambassador Rouse: *"Hong Kong has been a separate customs region and is indeed a separate member of the WTO under the arrangement of 'one country, two systems.' Preserving this uniqueness is vitally important. In 2024, the EU remained the largest non-Chinese foreign business community in the city (1,640 EU companies), ahead of Japan, the U.S., and the UK, according to an annual Hong Kong government survey. For half of the EU companies present in Hong Kong, their office is also the regional headquarters.*

Furthermore, the EU presence grew by 6% in 2024. It should also be underlined that EU companies are not just concentrated in one sector but present in a wide range of domains which are essential to the Hong Kong economy, including financial and business services, trading and logistics, retail, food and beverage, construction and engineering, and environmental services. EU companies see many advantages in Hong Kong (ease of doing business, low corruption, robust and efficient financial markets, low and simple tax system).

But they do also have concerns over changes to the 'uniqueness' of Hong Kong in terms of 'one country two systems,' and stress the importance of an open society with a diverse vibrant talent pool."

The EU Office is thus committed to sustaining the presence of its young professionals, entrepreneurs, industry leaders, and engineers in Hong Kong, recognizing their valuable contributions to the local business landscape. These actors play a crucial role in diversifying the economy, creating employment, and enhancing innovation. The continued presence of European workers is vital for the international status of the leading business hub.

With its freedom of capital movement and favorable tax policies, Hong Kong is a highly attractive destination for European and global investment. By the end of 2022, the 27 EU Member States had invested a total of US\$34 billion in Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Hong Kong—with France, the Netherlands, and Germany among the leading investors. In contrast, the SAR had invested US\$67.9 billion in the European Union, with the Netherlands, Luxembourg, and Portugal serving as the primary destinations. Europe is Hong Kong's second-largest source of foreign direct investment globally (European Commission, 2022).

Yet, Hong Kong's significance to the EU extends beyond the exact volume of trade and investment between the two regions. The SAR certainly plays a crucial connecting role, facilitating trade and investment flows between Mainland China and the EU. The Free Trade Agreement signed in 2003 between Hong Kong and the Mainland not only strengthens their bilateral exchanges, but also serves as a key platform for foreign investors. Notably, EU companies make extensive use of the Hong Kong-Mainland China Closer Economic Partnership Arrangement (CEPA). In practice, the CEPA allows European firms to establish manufacturing operations in Hong Kong, enabling their products to qualify for CEPA's rules of origin and be exported tariff-free to the Mainland Chinese market.

This stable economic relationship creates opportunities for the Office to foster deeper cooperation between European and local businesses, such as artificial intelligence, green finance or sustainable energies.

7. Promising Cooperation on the Sustainability Agenda

Climate change is *“a shared challenge that requires collective action,”* according to the EU Ambassador. The European Union and Hong Kong share the same objective of attaining climate neutrality in 2050, which creates potential for mutual support and collaboration.

Last year, the EU Office coordinated the third edition of the Green Way Forward Forum. This pivotal event was organized in collaboration with the Department of Foreign Direct Investment (InvestHK), as well as the European and Hong Kong Chambers of Commerce. The high-level dialogue gathered representatives from industry, civil society, academia, and local government. It provided a platform for participants to exchange perspectives and potential solutions for sustainable housing, green innovation, and environmentally responsible trade practices (EuroCham, 2024). Actionable policy recommendations were subsequently presented to Hong Kong officials. Notably, the Financial Secretary of the HKSAR Government, Mr. Paul Chan, warmly welcomed this guidance, concluding that *“Hong Kong has what it takes to rise as a world leader in green tech and green finance.”* The previous edition was successfully hosted in Macau in 2023. European industry experts explored how sustainable development could help the SAR in diversifying its economy and attracting new actors, a key objective of the government.

Ambassador Rouse hopes to promote closer synergies between EU and local stakeholders on sustainable finance and manufacturing: *“Hong Kong is the third largest financial*

services hub globally and is therefore also very important vis-à-vis green financing. Hong Kong is the world’s number one aviation cargo hub, and addressing the sustainability of this important sector (including sustainable aviation fuels) is its license to grow.”

The Head of the EU Office emphasizes that multiple *“European companies have state-of-the-art green technologies, and they have brought them to Hong Kong to benefit the people in the city. The presence of European companies in the financial, transport and waste management sectors has contributed to the positive development in green transition in both Hong Kong and Macau.”* As an illustration, waste management has become an increasingly important challenge for Hong Kong. Facing this obstacle, the HKSAR Government was assisted by Veolia, a French transnational company specializing in environmental public services, to build one of the largest waste-to-energy facilities in the world, T-Park in Tuen Mun (Tsang & Woo, 2023).

In 2021, local authorities announced the urban development of the Northern Metropolis to further integrate the city into the Greater Bay Area. While promoting cross-border synergy in the technological sector with Shenzhen, this initiative also seeks to alleviate the housing shortage in Hong Kong by offering more affordable flats (Global Connectivities, 2024). European investors, talents and industries could play an active role in the process.

8. The Strength of People-to-People Exchanges

The EU greatly values intercultural exchanges with local residents and has a strong presence across multiple social media channels. The Ambassador underscored their close collaboration with influential local vloggers, notably the content-creator Yi-fu. The objective is to offer a broader understanding of European affairs to Hong Kong and Macau citizens: *“I am proud to share that the video—produced in Hong Kong’s daily language, Cantonese—already attracted a large audience, and it is still growing.”*

In 2025, my Office will continue to undertake more initiatives to engage with the public and encourage more people-to-people exchanges in public diplomacy activities.”

The Office also hopes to boost academic exchanges and research programs in European countries through Erasmus+ and Horizon Europe: *“A most recent example is the ‘Study in Europe Education Fair’ that we organized with EU Member State Consulates General in Hong Kong in November last year. We decided to undertake a #TeamEurope approach in encouraging students from Hong Kong to explore education opportunities in European countries that are also home to world-leading education institutions. Hong Kong and many of our Member States also have active, wide-ranging cultural exchange programs and initiatives, which are another vital part of our relations.”*

In parallel with strategic communication and education, art is instrumental in bridging different communities through shared emotions. The EU Office organizes a variety of events to promote cultural connections, including the annual European Film Festival or the HKWalls Festival (Culture Plus Asia, 2023).

Since the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine three years ago, the EU representation has organized multiple events to demonstrate the unwavering support of the 27 Member States to Ukraine. To mark the third anniversary of the conflict, the EU Office collaborated with the Ukrainian Society of Hong Kong to host the photo exhibition “Ukraine: War and Resistance.” In his opening speech at the ceremony, Ambassador Rouse declared: *“To give visual representation to the bonds between Hongkongers and Ukraine, we have invited three outstanding photographers from Hong Kong, who have traveled to Ukraine multiple times since the beginning of the full-scale invasion.”* The Ambassador also noted the deep compassion shown by Hongkongers during the screening

of the Oscar-winning documentary “20 Days in Mariupol,” co-organized with the Journalism School of the University of Hong Kong in November 2024 (Press and information team of the Delegation to Hong Kong and Macau, 2024).

Finally, one of the core values uniting the 27 Member States is individual liberty. In line with this commitment, the EU staff regularly organizes events for human rights safeguarding, including the surge of human trafficking, conferences on women’s rights, and discussions on LGBTI rights. This engagement is crucial for the protection of fundamental freedoms in Hong Kong and Macau, and encourages continued discussion on these systemic issues.

9. The Future of the EU-Hong Kong-Macau Dialogue

Looking ahead, the European Union Office to Hong Kong and Macau remains committed to further strengthening diplomatic, economic, and cultural engagement with the two SARs. The European Union’s representation emphasizes key strategic issues, notably the imperative to safeguard Hong Kong’s uniqueness to maintain its appeal for European businesses, as well as the need to deepen cooperation with Macau. Yet, the EU will continue to express concerns responsively and when necessary under the One Country, Two Systems principle. These objectives are at the core of the mandate of Ambassador Rouse for the next four years.

With a rapidly evolving geopolitical environment marked by the recent onset of a global trade war, diplomatic relations are undergoing a profound paradigm shift. China and the European Union may potentially seek to strengthen their economic ties, as highlighted by the official call between European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen and Chinese Premier Li Qiang on Hong Kong is well-positioned to play a key role as a connector between Mainland China and the Union. Its strategic location and unique financial infrastructure equip the SAR to strengthen trade between these two crucial regions. Will the

European Union and China seize this moment to re-engage with one another?

References

- Culture Plus Asia. (n.d.). *EU street art meets Hong Kong*. <https://cultureplus.asia/event/eu-street-art-meets-hong-kong/>
- EEAS. (2021, July 26). *Who we are*. European External Action Service. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/hong-kong/who-we-are_en?s=239
- EEAS. (2025). *Office of the European Union to Hong Kong and Macau*. European External Action Service. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/delegations/hong-kong_en?s=239
- EuroCham. (n.d.). *Greenway 2024: The Dialogue*. <https://www.eurocham.com.hk/greenway-thedialogue>
- European Commission. (2024, May 21). *EU trade relations with Hong Kong*. https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/eu-trade-relationships-country-and-region/countries-and-regions/hong-kong-sAr_en
- Global Connectivities. (2024, January 21). *The Northern Metropolis: Hong Kong's new development strategy*. <https://globalconnectivities.com/2024/01/hk-northern-metropolis/>
- Rouse, H. R. (2025, February 24). *Photoexhibition "Ukraine: War and Resistance" opening speech*. European External Action Service. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/delegations/hong-kong/photo-exhibition-%E2%80%9Cukraine-war-and-resistance%E2%80%9D-opening-speech_en
- Tsang, A., & Woo, S. (2023, October 5). *Delivering ESG Development in Hong Kong: Waste-to-Energy Solutions*.
- HKTDC Research. <https://research.hktdc.com/en/article/MTQ5NTgzNDk2Ng>

Alixia BRÛLE

alixia.brule@mail.mcgill.ca

Alixia Brûlé is a young professional specialized in Sino-European diplomatic relations from France. With academic experiences in Hong Kong, Canada, and Japan, she has cultivated a keen interest in East Asian politics, international security, and defense policy. Currently serving as a Podcast Officer for European Guanxi and Partnership Officer for the STEAR think-tank, Alixia is passionate about the security environment of the Indo-Pacific region.

Charging Ahead: Assessing China's Leverage and the EU's Strategic Dilemma in the EV Transition

Caroline SEIL

Abstract

This article explores China's growing geoeconomic leverage in the global electric vehicle (EV) and battery supply chain, examining its implications for the European Union's industrial strategic autonomy while advancing its ambitious green transition. Applying the framework of Blackwill & Harris (2016), it analyzes three core drivers of China's leverage: centrality in global supply chains, monopoly over key technologies and raw materials, and monopsony power as a dominant buyer and processor. China's dominance is underpinned by its control of critical minerals, vast manufacturing capacity, and technological innovation, particularly in lithium-iron-phosphate (LFP) battery technology. This paper then examines the EU's response through tariffs, industrial policies, and diversification efforts under its "de-risking" strategy. However, this paper argues that these measures are insufficient to resolve Europe's structural dependencies on Chinese imports. Challenges such as slow domestic capacity development, higher production costs, fragmented political consensus, and regulatory constraints hinder the EU's ability to reshape the status quo. The article concludes that while China's leverage can act as both a tool of cooperation and coercion, the EU must urgently scale domestic production, incentivize critical raw material investments, and strengthen regulatory coherence to safeguard industrial competitiveness and climate goals. Without deeper structural reforms and greater strategic unity, the EU remains vulnerable to external pressures in the rapidly evolving green economy.

Keywords: EU-China relations, green transition, electric vehicles (EVs), battery supply chain, critical raw materials, strategic autonomy, geoeconomic leverage

Introduction

The race to dominate green transition has transformed clean energy technologies and critical resources into powerful tools of geopolitical leverage, reshaping alliances and sparking new rivalries in the global quest for sustainable supremacy. For instance, in August 2022, the U.S. introduced the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), aiming to invest \$369 billion in clean energy initiatives. The act focuses on boosting domestic production of key technologies like electric vehicles and renewable energy components, with the dual goals of reducing emissions and reestablishing the U.S. as a global leader in green technology manufacturing (Zabelin & von Dongen, 2024). The European Union has similarly introduced the Green Deal Industrial Plan, which seeks to maintain competitiveness and reduce dependency on key imports while accelerating the transition to a net-zero economy (Temple-West, 2024). Key pillars of the Plan include the Critical Raw Materials Act and the Net-Zero Industry Act, both passed in 2024, which aim to secure resources, boost domestic clean technology manufacturing, and address global competition for critical materials essential for decarbonization efforts (Canestrini, 2024). In Asia, China is spearheading clean energy technology by producing over 80% of the world's solar panels, leveraging its dominance in those supply chains to "entrench its global leadership" (International Energy Agency, 2022; Zabelin & von Dongen, 2024, para. 2). Indeed, this global shift towards green infrastructure reflects the growing recognition that energy security, technological innovation, and climate action are deeply interconnected (Zabelin and von Dongen,

2024). This quest for geopolitical leverage amid the green transition is especially pronounced amid international efforts to decrease dependence on fossil fuels by investing in batteries to power the new age of electric vehicles.

As Leslie Gelb—a longtime foreign policy expert, and former New York Times commentator—expressed, “Beijing has been playing the new economic game at a maestro level” (Walt, 2010, para. 9). Indeed, China has emerged as a global leader in electric vehicles (EVs) and battery manufacturing, producing 62% of global EVs in 2022 and accounting for 77% of global battery manufacturing capacity. Dominated by giants like CATL and FDB, Chinese manufacturers now produce 75% of the world’s lithium-ion batteries, underscoring their pivotal role in the EV supply chain (Ezell, 2024). Furthermore, with batteries accounting for 40% of the costs to produce EVs, China aims to solidify its dominance over critical raw materials (Vox, 2024).

In response to China's role as a globally significant supplier and manufacturer in EV production and its potential geopolitical leverage, the EU has implemented measures to protect its automotive industry and reduce dependence on Chinese imports. In October 2024, the EU imposed additional tariffs on Chinese EVs, with rates reaching up to 45.3% for certain manufacturers (Blenkinsop, 2024). This decision followed an investigation that concluded Chinese EV producers benefited from substantial state subsidies, enabling them to offer vehicles at lower prices and posing a threat to European manufacturers and European competitiveness (Blenkinsop, 2025).

While the EU's pursuit of strategic autonomy and its de-risking strategy, as outlined by von der Leyen, highlight the bloc's urgent need to diversify energy imports and reduce dependencies, Russia's invasion of Ukraine served as a critical tipping point (Center for

European Policy Studies, 2023). The crisis exposed Europe's over-reliance on external suppliers, particularly for energy, reinforcing the imperative to secure more resilient and diversified supply chains in key sectors, including renewable energy and battery production. However, despite numerous reports and academic articles documenting China's dominant role in the energy transition and battery production, a gap exists in understanding how China's market position translates into geopolitical power (Chan, 2025; Zhang and Chen, 2022). Further research, through analytical explorations of case studies, is needed to analyze how China's control over critical mineral supply chains and its strategic investments in renewable technologies enhance its geopolitical influence, and how this leverage impacts global energy security and bilateral relations with the EU (Downie, 2022). Thus, this article aims to investigate the following research question: How does China's dominance in the EV and battery supply chain translate into geoeconomic leverage, thereby reshaping EU-China relations and de-risking strategies?

This study fills a critical research gap and presents a novel application of Blackwill & Harris' (2016) framework to analyze China's geoeconomic leverage. This paper argues that China's dominance in the EV and battery supply chain grants it significant geoeconomic leverage, driven by its centrality in global value chains, monopoly over key technologies and materials, and monopsony power as the world's largest buyer and processor of critical minerals. While the EU has introduced defensive measures like tariffs to reduce dependency, these responses fail to address the structural vulnerabilities in Europe's green technology sector, leaving it exposed to China's leverage, which can function both as a tool of cooperation and coercion in shaping the future of EU-China relations.

This research will explain Blackwill & Harris' (2016) theoretical framework before analyzing the three factors contributing to China's position and ability to achieve geoeconomic leverage. The

analysis then illustrates how this geoeconomic leverage has geopolitical implications, especially in the context of EU-China relations, as the EU is navigating the dual challenge of strategic autonomy or strategic dependence. The critical discussion attempts to elucidate the limitations constraining the EU's leverage and ability to alter the status quo. The analysis then moves to a review of key policy recommendations, followed by concluding reflections and suggestions for future research directions.

1. Theoretical Framework

Geoeconomic endowments refer to the inherent resources, capabilities, and structural advantages that a nation possesses, which can be strategically utilized to achieve geopolitical and economic objectives (Blackwill & Harris, 2016). Certain structural features, or geoeconomic endowments, determine how effectively a country can wield geoeconomic tools. While geopolitical power is well-studied, geoeconomics lacks a comprehensive framework, leaving ambiguity about the tools available and the factors that enable states to use them successfully (Blackwill & Harris, 2016).

Blackwill & Harris (2016) argue that effective geoeconomic leverage depends on economic endowments. Their book proposes four different endowments: control over outbound investments, domestic market features, influence over commodity and energy flows, and centrality to the global financial system. This analysis will exclusively focus on the influence over commodity and energy flows to assess China's ability to achieve geoeconomic leverage on the global battery and EV markets (Blackwill & Harris, 2016). According to Blackwill & Harris (2016), three specific variables constitute this endowment and can determine how successfully a country can leverage its geoeconomic standing. First, centrality as an endowment involves a country's role as a key transit hub or

manufacturing centre. Second, monopoly power refers to a state's market ownership and lastly, monopsony power refers to the influence that is derived from being the world's leading customer. This article will explore the centrality of China as a transit point and a hub of strategic investments in efforts to reduce fossil fuel dependence. China's monopoly power will be analyzed in terms of the dominance of the supply chain and market influence through technological innovation. Lastly, China's monopsony power is under-explored, which is why this article aims to shed light on how China's domestic demand and purchasing power contribute to the consolidation of geoeconomic leverage. In the next section, this essay will conduct an in-depth analysis of the three variables underpinning China's geoeconomic endowment to evaluate its capacity to influence commodity and energy flows.

2. Analysis

2.1 Centrality

First, Blackwill & Harris' (2016) variable of centrality, refers to a nation's importance within a global economic system. This importance is determined by its role in connecting buyers, sellers, and markets, acting as a critical hub in supply chains. Recent scholarship in International Political Economy (IPE) has increasingly investigated the structural context of the international economic system in which states are embedded and faced with structural power asymmetries (Snidal et al., 2024). IPE scholars conceptualize the global economic system as a hierarchical network of interdependencies where states hold varying degrees of influence based on their position within these interconnected structures (Slaughter, 2018). This emerging body of literature, called "new structuralism," highlights the increasing concentration of power within global economic networks. It emphasizes how these networks have evolved into "hub-and-spoke" systems, where states that establish themselves as central hubs gain significant power (Farrell and Newman, 2023; Snidal et al., 2024). Controlling such central hubs allows the

beneficiary of this power to manipulate or even weaponize interdependence for strategic advantages, potentially turning economic ties into tools of influence or coercion. Since hubs provide significant benefits and are challenging to bypass, states that dominate them wield substantial leverage. At the same time, those excluded from these critical networks may face severe economic and geopolitical repercussions (Farrell & Newman, 2019).

When assessing the centrality of China as a transit point between major buyers and sellers in the battery and EV production, the reality is apparent that China's integration into the global value chains derives from dominating raw material processing, manufacturing, and export (Blackwill & Harris, 2016). China has become a central player in the global EV and battery industry by connecting upstream suppliers of raw materials with downstream global EV manufacturers. To understand this centrality, one must understand how China was able to position itself at the center of these markets. Indeed, as early as the 2000s, Chinese companies realized that they would struggle to achieve global competitiveness in internal combustion engine technologies (Yang, 2023). As a result, policymakers shifted their focus toward developing a globally competitive domestic industry in EVs to reduce reliance on foreign automotive technologies and dependence on oil imports (Ezell, 2024). China's reliance on crude oil imports, which amounted to 11.29 million bpd (barrels per day), made it the most significant oil importer in the world (Russell, 2024). However, this dependence on oil imports renders the state vulnerable to external oil shocks, market disruptions, price volatility, and geopolitical tensions (Russell, 2025). For example, trade disputes leading to tariffs on energy imports can disrupt supply chains and increase costs, as seen in recent U.S.-China trade tensions (Donovan & Nikoladze, 2024). With EV competitiveness becoming a national priority, China sought to position itself as a frontrunner

in the clean energy transition and reduce fossil fuel dependence, while simultaneously addressing the escalating air pollution crisis in China's densely populated megacities (Ezell, 2024).

To secure its central position in EV and battery manufacturing, China requires a stable and long-term access to the critical raw materials essential for battery production. This strategic necessity led to extensive upstream investments aimed at securing control over the global supply of minerals vital to the green energy transition. The materials demanded for EV battery production are graphite, lithium, cobalt, copper, phosphorus, manganese, and nickel (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2024). The reality of controlling critical minerals for the green technological transition has prompted China to ramp up investments in both domestic and international mining sectors. In line with this strategy, Chinese investment in the metal and mining sector, particularly through the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), surged to its highest level in a decade in 2023, reaching \$19.4 billion (138 billion RMB), representing a 160% increase from 2022 (International Energy Agency, 2024, see p. 63). Under the BRI, China has also been actively investing in the acquisition of overseas mines, especially in Africa (Cooper, 2024). Another example is Indonesia, which, while contributing 52% of global mined nickel production, Chinese companies control 40% of Indonesia's total mined nickel output in 2023 (International Energy Agency, 2024).

Consequently, China's dominance across the global supply chain is reinforced by its position as an indispensable hub for battery component extraction and subsequent extensive refining and processing capabilities. BBC (2024) documented at least 62 mining projects worldwide where Chinese companies hold investment stakes (see Figure 1). Furthermore, China currently dominates the global supply of key battery materials, producing 99% of battery-grade graphite, over 60% of lithium chemicals, 40% of refined copper, more than 80% of refined magnet

rare earths, and 70% of refined cobalt (Cooper, 2024; Minnis, 2024). Domestically, China has been expanding its lithium production, increasing its share of global lithium mining from 6% in 2016 to 17% in 2023. By the mid-2020s, it is projected to surpass Chile as the world's second-largest lithium producer (Cooper, 2024). With 2/3 of the global "EV lithium-ion battery production capacities located in China" (Wang, 2022, p. 1), it is effectively spearheading control of this critical sector, giving domestic companies a stable supply chain (Yang, 2023). Thus, China's centrality in the EV and battery supply chains, contributes to its geo-economic leverage.

Figure 1

China has business interests in mining around the world

Location of lithium, cobalt, nickel and manganese projects with a Chinese stake

Note. From BBC (2024).

2.2 Monopoly Power

Building on the previous analysis of China's role as a critical hub in global supply chains, its geo-economic leverage through a central transit position is closely intertwined with monopoly power, which it achieves through market dominance. Blackwill & Harris (2016) determine that monopoly power, which refers to a state's market ownership, is a key factor towards ensuring geo-economic leverage.

First, given China's strategic investments and control over supply chains to maintain its centrality and resource security in the critical raw materials industry, it has also established dominance in exporting refined battery materials, further solidifying its geo-economic leverage. Indeed, natural and refined battery-grade graphite are already under strict export controls from China (International Energy Agency, 2024). In addition to these controls, in January 2025, China's Commerce Minister declared plans to impose further export restrictions on the technology required to produce battery components and critical mineral processing. These restrictions would help China "retain its 70% grip on the global processing of lithium into the material needed to make EV batteries" (Reuters, 2025a, para. 4).

Second, China's global dominance in the battery and EV industry (see figure 2) is predated by companies such as BYD, which was a major producer of batteries for electronics in the 90s before EV manufacturing was pushed as a national priority and manufacturing capabilities were heavily expanded. From 2009 to 2022, the government invested over 200 billion RMB (\$29 billion) into subsidies and tax breaks for EV industries to incentivize critical growth in this sector (Yang, 2023). While this number is more narrowly focused on direct financial investments, Kennedy (2024) estimates the total accumulative government support from 2009 to 2023 to amount to \$230.9 billion. This amount includes broader categories of government aid such as infrastructure investment, industrial policy

initiatives, subsidies, tax incentives, research and development grants, and direct investments. As Yang (2023) demonstrates, these government subsidies were not limited to domestic companies but were also aimed at benefiting rising foreign companies, such as one of the biggest EV companies globally, Tesla. Tesla's Shanghai Gigafactory is its most productive manufacturing facility, responsible for producing over half of all Tesla vehicles delivered in 2022 (Yang, 2023).

Additionally, to qualify for consumer subsidies, even companies like GM and Tesla, who wanted to share their cars on the Chinese market, were required to use Chinese-made batteries (Yang, 2023). This expansion and subsequent market dominance became a wake-up call for American and European industries when CATL came to control almost two-thirds of the global EV battery market and supplied major Western companies such as Tesla, BMW, and Volkswagen (Hawkins, 2024a). In 2023, China accounted for 60% of worldwide EV sales, and in 2024, BYD surpassed Tesla in EV production, making it the new leading EV manufacturer worldwide (Ezell, 2024; Richter, 2025) (see figure 3). Indeed, in 2024, China's passenger car exports surged by nearly 20%, reaching almost five million vehicles (Euronews, 2025; Reuters, 2025b). Summarizing this argument, the accrued benefits of dominating the EV industry are two-fold. China can reduce dependence on Western-manufactured cars and simultaneously create lucrative export opportunities to sustain its economy.

Third, while critiques of China's increasing monopoly power in the EV industry often focus on political tensions, unfair trade practices, and government subsidies, this narrow perspective overlooks a fundamental reality: China's success is also driven by innovation and technological advancements, which have played a crucial role in its global competitiveness.

Figure 2

Note. From Swieboda (2025).

Figure 3

Note. The figure highlights EV sales by country and EVs as a share of all car sales. From Ezell, (2024).

As Kennedy (2024) reports, China argues that its global competitiveness and growing exports are the results of its own comparative advantage and high-quality products. Notably, China has been leading innovation in battery technology by eliminating the most expensive components, namely nickel, and cobalt, by replacing them with lithium-iron-phosphate (LFP). For much of the 21st century, LFP batteries were considered outdated and inferior to nickel manganese cobalt (NMC) batteries in energy density. From 2016 to 2018, LFP batteries only made up 10% of the global EV battery market, but today, their share has surged to 40% (Ezell, 2024). This shift was primarily driven by Chinese companies, particularly CATL (EV battery maker), which advanced LFP battery technology through research and innovation, challenging previous industry assumptions. In 2024, CATL unveiled

a new battery that could power a driving range of up to 1000 kilometers (621 miles) on a single charge (Reuters, 2024). Interestingly, LFP batteries are more environmentally friendly, safer, and cheaper, with previously critical components such as nickel and cobalt, no longer required (Reuters, 2024; Yang, 2023). Recent findings indicate that Chinese EV companies are approximately 30% faster in developing and launching new car models than traditional American, European, and Japanese automakers. This rapid innovation means Chinese brands rival and surpass other established names such as Tesla and BMW (Ezell, 2024).

China's economic partners contend that unfair trade practices and Chinese industrial strategy are to blame for current tensions. China defends itself by arguing that the high caliber of its businesses' output and the nation's inherent comparative advantage are the reasons behind its expanding exports. There is some truth to all perspectives, complicating the decision for appropriate responses. The reality is that Chinese EV companies have received extensive industrial policy support. Still, at the same time, their quality has improved, making them more and more appealing to both domestic and foreign consumers (Kennedy, 2024).

2.3 Monopsony Power

Monopsony power refers to the dominance of a buyer who faces little competition, allowing them to dictate terms to suppliers (Blackwill & Harris, 2016). This power is demonstrated on the market in multiple ways. First, China is leading the market in refining capabilities, refining almost three-quarters of the global supply of cobalt, despite not having any domestic production (Sall and Gross, 2025). A monopsony situation is subsequently created as mineral producers face one dominant client, namely Chinese refining facilities (Gulley, 2024). This poses a risk, as China's dominant position in critical material procurement could

enable it to exert pressure on suppliers or manipulate pricing to its advantage (Sall and Gross, 2025). Indeed, this monopsony power has already been visible as China increased restrictions on the export of these critical minerals nine times between 2009 and 2020 (Sall and Gross, 2025). In 2021, China released a negative list and banned foreign direct investments (FDI) in China's rare-earth mining projects (Global Times, 2021). These measures strengthen China's domestic control over rare-earth resources, safeguarding its supply while reinforcing its dominance in refining and processing capabilities. By restricting foreign investment, China ensures that global industries remain reliant on its rare-earth processing and exports, further solidifying its strategic position in the supply chain.

A second example is the Democratic Republic of Congo, which accounts for 70% of global cobalt production. However, Chinese companies own approximately 80% of the country's cobalt output, which is refined in China and then sold worldwide (Congressional-Executive Commission on China, 2023). Under a "resource-for-infrastructure" model (Baskaran, 2023, para. 5), China signed the Sino-Congolais des Mines (Sicomines) agreement in 2007, committing approximately \$3 billion in infrastructure investments in exchange for mining rights to deposits valued at \$93 billion. Linking this to monopsony power, China can dictate terms to suppliers as the DRC is left disadvantaged by limiting its ability to award extraction rights to the highest bidder. This not only restricts competition on price but also prevents the DRC from selecting investors that offer broader benefits, such as strong environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices or commitments to developing local industries and infrastructure (Baskaran, 2023). Even on the Latin American continent, in Chile, China accounted for over 65% of Chile's mineral exports in 2021, totaling \$22.5 billion, representing approximately 6% of Chile's GDP (Hernandez-Roy et al., 2024).

Besides dominating refining capabilities, China's

market share in EV production has steadily increased and surpassed 76% in 2024 (Hawkins, 2024b). From January to October 2024, China accounted for 69% of global EV sales (Hawkins, 2024b). The surge in EV sales is, among other factors, driven by consistent advancements in the quality of Chinese EVs, particularly with innovations like LFP battery technology. These qualitative improvements have significantly boosted China's EV exports to high-income countries, with their share rising from 5% in 2018 to 60% in 2023 (Sall & Gross, 2025). This exponential growth can be explained by China shifting its policies to allow foreign automakers to produce their EVs in China without an “equal-share Chinese partner” (Sall & Gross, 2025, para. 20). Consequently, companies such as Tesla, BMW or Renault capitalized on these policy changes and established their production sites in China. As export shares increase, Western governments grow worried about being outcompeted by lower-priced EVs from China. However, Western tariffs on Chinese-made EVs and battery components cannot ignore the fact that a robust domestic demand has helped China stabilize and grow its industry. While the new energy vehicles (NEV) consumer subsidies have started to be phased out in 2022, the domestic demand has been successfully created (Hongpei, 2023). Indeed, in July 2024, over 50.8% of car sales were new energy vehicles (Bloomberg, 2024). According to a survey from AlixPartners (2021), over 50% of Chinese respondents expressed interest in purchasing EV cars, representing the highest proportion worldwide and two times the global average. This demand gives manufacturers a growing market that allows them to maintain high production volumes, achieve economies of scale, and remain competitive globally despite external trade barriers (Hawkins, 2024b). This section argues that China's monopsony power—rooted in its dominance as the world's leading buyer, refiner, and consumer of critical minerals—grants it significant geoeconomic leverage. By controlling demand and shaping supplier

terms, China is able to consolidate its influence across EV and battery supply chains.

3. Strategic Autonomy or Strategic Dependence? The EU's Response to China's Dominance of EV and Battery Supply Chain

The first part of this analysis demonstrated China's geoeconomic leverage in the global EV and battery industry. Understanding the three factors of centrality, monopsony, and monopoly power and their geopolitical implications is crucial in the subsequent analysis and contextualization of EU-China relations. With geopolitical leverage understood as a “function of the export state's leverage and the target state's vulnerability” (Downie, 2022, p. 2), China's strides to consolidate its dominance in EV and battery supply chains presents a critical urgency to assess the implications for the EU's strategic autonomy.

This next section will elaborate on some of the main challenges faced by the EU in achieving strategic autonomy in the EV and battery market before presenting recommendations for policies and future windows of opportunity. Understanding China's leverage not only helps explain Europe's vulnerabilities but also highlights the urgent need for a comprehensive response. This response needs to move beyond reactive measures like tariffs and instead address structural dependencies, foster innovation, and strengthen Europe's green technology sector.

In the context of EU-China relations, it is crucial to recognize the double-edged nature of China's leverage. Downie (2022) argues that geoeconomic leverage operates along a spectrum, ranging from coercion to strategic incentives. At one extreme, energy exports and supply chain control can be weaponized to exert economic pressure and impose costs on dependent states. On the other, leverage can function as a diplomatic tool, encouraging cooperation or offering economic advantages to influence strategic decisions. Importantly, the leverage of exporting states will depend on “excess

resources, a supportive institutional environment, and market dominance” (Downie, 2022, p. 1). Furthermore, the scope of geopolitical leverage that the exporting state can gain depends on the importing states’ vulnerabilities. These vulnerabilities are, in turn, shaped by the latter’s level of exposure and ability to withstand market disruptions or external shocks.

The EU is the single largest market for China’s EV exports by value, as China’s global EV exports have surged since 2021 to reach over \$44 billion in 2024 (Webster, 2025). From 2020 to 2023, EV exports increased by 851%, while the largest share of these exports (40%) went to Europe (Ezell, 2024). Concerning batteries, China accounts for half of all EU battery imports, equaling €11bn worth of EV batteries (Spisak, 2024). Furthermore, China supplies 100% of the EU’s heavy rare earth elements (European Commission, 2023). The main challenge facing the EU in light of China’s growing geoeconomic leverage is to prevent a scenario where meeting EV targets comes at the cost of industrial decline or geopolitical weakness.

3.1 Limitations of EU Leverage that Constrain its Abilities to Alter the Status-quo

First, while intended industrial policies can boost domestic production, operationalizing these industries is not an instant result. In 2018, the Commission designated battery self-sufficiency as a strategic imperative for the EU’s clean energy transition. By 2021, total investments in the battery value chain had reached €127 billion. Looking ahead, an estimated €382 billion in further funding is anticipated by 2030 to establish a fully self-sufficient battery industry (European Commission, 2022). However, while battery production is set to increase, the looming shortage of raw materials and building infrastructure capacities is set to delay self-sufficiency until 2030 (European Court of

Auditors, 2023). Additionally, despite significant investments in battery production, the Swedish battery manufacturer Northvolt recently declared bankruptcy (Do Prado et al., 2025). These challenges ranging from innovation bottlenecks to high costs and startup failures, contribute to the EU’s continued vulnerability and dependence on Chinese-imported batteries to meet the surging EV demand.

Second, Europe’s higher energy and labor costs and stricter environmental rules can make European-made batteries pricier. This reality will test the limits of subsidy support and the willingness of consumers to pay more. These findings become even more critical, as by 2023, China’s “battery cell production was more than double its domestic demand” (International Energy Agency, 2024, p. 31) and companies provided price advantages based on mass production and economy of scale (Wang, 2022). This means that as manufacturing capabilities exceed domestic demand, they will lead to increased export pushes. China’s excess production could push global battery prices down, which in turn will complicate Western producers’ ability to compete and increase their reliance on Chinese imports (International Energy Agency, 2024). These geoeconomic leverages have geopolitical implications, as they risk undermining the EU’s de-risk strategies of diversifying its supply chains and seeking alternative sources of critical minerals.

Third, trade measures such as tariffs present a double-edged sword. On the one hand, they can promote more fair competition, protect domestic industries, shield them from being undercut by cheaper imports, and encourage local investments to enhance job creation and technological advancements (McHugh & Moritsugu, 2024). On the other hand, tariffs are not considered to be the proper response to strengthening EU competitiveness. Interestingly, the anti-subsidy probes were not launched from industry complaints but from the Commission’s own investigation into what it considers to be Chinese industrial dominance undermining EU

competitiveness. In response to investigations, the EU has imposed tariffs of 38% on Chinese EVs, while the U.S. has imposed tariffs exceeding 100% (Ezell, 2024). However, the imposition of tariffs overlooks the reality of China's leverage and risks provoking retaliatory tariffs. As the combined EV market share of Volkswagen, BMW, Audi, Mercedes, and Porsche in China is about 5%, China can still exert considerable pressure (Tyborski & Fasse, 2025). Leading up to the EU's decision to impose tariffs on Chinese EVs in 2024, Chinese officials lobbied Member States against these tariffs, with reports, although unofficial, emerging that Chinese authorities were informally requesting automakers to pause investments in EU countries that supported the tariffs (Featherston, 2024). With production in China, EU car makers will likely transfer the increased costs onto European consumers (Spisak, 2024). Only the EU would profit from such tariffs by cashing in 2.3 to 3 billion euros in tariff revenue (Spisak, 2024).

The vote on increasing tariffs from 10% to 35% on Chinese EVs passed narrowly in October 2024, as many Member States abstained (see figure 4) (Spisak, 2024). These retaliatory actions have the power to divide the EU members, who, amid the unease of provoking a trade war, only 10 out of the 27 governments firmly voted in favor of the EV tariff decision (Featherston, 2024). Germany requested lower tariffs in fear of Chinese retaliatory actions against the German auto industry, while France's President Macron argued that "We don't protect enough" (Chen and Rose, 2024, para. 3; Verhelst and Zimmermann, 2024). Another example is how each member state has the final say on investment screenings, which renders the patchwork that is the EU position more difficult to navigate and construct collective leverage. This shows how, amid fear of economic fallout, the EU is unable to ensure unity, which further challenges the management of EU-China relations in pursuing

Figure 4

Note. From Featherston (2024).

a unified and strong strategic autonomy. Fourth, the EU prides itself on operating within a rules-based trade system, meaning its tools must be WTO-compliant and evidence-based. Naturally, it is operating with more constraints and cannot, for example, copy the U.S.'s Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), as such discriminatory incentives of providing tax credits to encourage the consumption of domestic products would violate EU internal market rules and likely WTO rules. Furthermore, the EU is already facing retaliatory actions by China, in response to the EV tariffs. China launched its own trade probes, conducting anti-dumping and anti-subsidy investigations into EU exports of pork and dairy (Ledman et al., 2024). Thus, while upholding global norms, the legal caution can be seen as limiting Europe's geo-economic leverage vis-à-vis a state-capitalist China.

Lastly, the biggest challenge facing the EU is not only how to manage economic and political trade-offs but also the trade-off between Europe's consumer and climate goals. This trilemma of balancing the green transition, affordability for consumers, and economic sovereignty, will test EU decision-makers on whether to hit climate targets despite relating to Chinese imports or to

prioritize the protection of industries and resilience, which is accompanied by high costs or slower EV rollouts. The European Court of Auditors' (2023) report notes that although the strategic action plan outlines relevant goals, it lacks quantified, time-bound targets, particularly regarding EU battery production. This omission makes it harder to assess whether Europe can meet its 2035 zero-emission targets with domestic capacity or whether it will remain reliant on imports, jeopardizing supply security and the competitiveness of the European battery value chain. This inherent tension limits how far the EU can push on any lever without undermining another goal. Politically, leaders must answer to voters on both the cost of living, jobs, and security, making the path fraught. Already, Chinese car manufacturers such as BYD and Geely and battery manufacturer CATL have invested in EV facilities across Spain, Slovakia, Germany, and Hungary (CATL, 2024; Piovaccari, 2025; Reuters, 2024). Some EU policymakers consider such strategies of solidifying a European presence through joint ventures to benefit the European market by localizing production and providing manufacturing jobs. However, these ventures also raise questions about technological dependence. They could face fierce barriers through the EU's foreign subsidies regulation, which allows the blocking of companies from operating in the EU if they are deemed to profit from foreign governmental subsidies (European Commission, n.d.; Spisak, 2024). The delicate balance between permitting Chinese state-subsidized companies to develop facilities on European soil and opposing their integration into the European EV supply chain remains unresolved. The ensuing political debate centers on the trade-off between safeguarding European competitiveness in this strategic industry by bolstering domestic production and enabling European consumers to benefit from more affordable Chinese-made EVs to accelerate the green transition (Spisak, 2024).

4. Policy Recommendations

First, the EU should scale up domestic production, which the European Commission and the European Investment Bank (EIB) hope to boost by launching a new partnership to strengthen the EU's battery manufacturing industry, which includes a €200 million top-up to the InvestEU program via the Innovation Fund. These commitments aim to help fund innovative battery projects and bridge the gap between research and development and commercial deployment. Additionally, the Innovation Fund currently offers €1 billion in grants to support EV battery cell manufacturing. At the same time, the EIB plans to invest another €1.8 billion across the battery value chain, from raw materials to recycling (European Commission, 2024). Furthermore, the EU's new Industrial Action Plan for the automotive sector (2025) rightly prioritizes batteries in its "Battery Booster" package. However, many of its pledges still need to materialize in actual funding and projects on the ground. Accelerating the disbursement of funds, simplifying grant procedures, and mobilizing private capital via public-private partnerships are considered urgent steps (European Commission, 2025).

In addition, Webster's (2025) analysis proposed that Germany should step up with the other Member States, playing a critical supporting role, as it "has the fiscal space for transformational investments" (para. 8). Indeed, Germany's government debt-to-gross domestic product (GDP) stands at 63% compared to other countries like France with 111% (Webster, 2025). Furthermore, the European Commissioner for Trade, Valdis Dombrovskis, argues that one of the primary causes of Germany's ongoing underinvestment is the debt brake (Sorgi, 2024). Among the G7, Germany's economy was the only one that shrank in 2023, which warrants the need for reforms of the debt brake to encourage investments in infrastructure and defense (Webster, 2025). Nonetheless, as Connolly (2025) reported in

March 2025, newly elected Chancellor Merz was able to secure the Green party's support to push ahead with his proposal to relax the debt brake. Investing in domestic electric vehicle production is also a strategic move for Germany and other European countries. By decreasing dependence on Chinese EVs, Europe can address a potential security vulnerability while safeguarding jobs in a sector that supports 6.1% of the EU's total employment directly and indirectly (Webster, 2025).

Second, a key vulnerability for Europe is its dependence on imported critical raw materials (CRMs), such as lithium, cobalt, nickel, and rare earths, which are essential for batteries and EV motors. To counter this dependence, the EU has initiated a new strategy, which aims to sign strategic partnerships with resource-rich countries. However, as Tenev (2024) warns, these partnerships will only fulfill their intended purpose of de-risking, if the European industries invest in CRM supply chains in those partner countries. As for now, "the incentives for European companies to enter mining and processing operations in these markets are too weak" (Tenev, 2024, para. 3). One example is Namibia, where EU partnership has not produced significant results, and "may even be benefitting Chinese firms at European expense" (Tenev, 2024, para. 4). Indeed, the laws in Namibia require local processing of CRMs, which adds costs and complexity. Consequently, EU firms face increased operational costs in the short term, as they are required to comply with international environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards. Chinese companies do not face such constraints and can absorb costs, thus enjoying greater freedom in negotiating minerals-for-infrastructure deals under the Belt and Road initiative (Tenev, 2024). Instead of de-risking from China, EU efforts may entrench China's dominance by improving the investment environment without ensuring that EU firms can participate. In its attempts to secure

critical raw materials, the EU should refocus resources from general support toward financial incentives for European private sector entry into CRM supply chains. Furthermore, strategic public-private partnerships (PPPs) must be deployed to provide de-risking guarantees, long-term offtake agreements, and subsidized financing to EU companies willing to invest in CRM mining and refining.

Third, in a globalized world, considering China's non-negligible geoeconomic power and leverage over the supply chain, the EU cannot sever ties and economic relations with China overnight. This means that conditioned engagement is essential when dealing with China via investment or joint ventures. The EU must be careful not to inadvertently transfer crucial assets or become a trojan horse for Chinese influence on the continent. Thus, the EU should rely on instruments such as investment screenings through the FDI Screening Regulation (2019) (EIES, 2025). This regulation ensures that scrutiny and screening are conducted for strategic investment sectors. This initiative allows the EU to strengthen and synchronize its cooperation across Member States to amplify defensive mechanisms and prevent China from exploiting the weakest link (EIES, 2025).

Finally, around all the discussion of competitiveness and growth, a sinister agenda is trying to creep in: the proposed simplification omnibus by the European Commission seeks to slash sustainability regulations and allow for "deregulation that rewards laggards" (Mendiluce & Hooper, 2025, para. 7). These proposals claim to scale back sustainability regulations, under the guise of reducing red tape, which could undermine long-term industrial competitiveness and climate objectives. Mendiluce & Hooper (2025) argue that the clear and consistent implementation of the Green Deal and its regulations provides a stable context for sustainable investment and serves as the EU's de facto growth strategy, necessitating strong ambition, regulatory clarity, and significant investment to maintain global competitiveness.

While simplifying regulations to support small and medium enterprises and avoiding overlaps and contradictory demands to accelerate the transition to clean energy is beneficial, a wholesale rollback of sustainability reporting and due diligence requirements would be detrimental (Gros, 2025; Mendiluce & Hooper, 2025). Such measures are essential for companies to manage risks, attract investment, and capitalize on market opportunities, especially in a global context where China continues to expand its influence in the low-carbon market.

Conclusion

This article has utilized a new geoeconomic framework by Blackwill & Harris (2016) to assess how China's dominance in the EV and battery value chain translates into significant geopolitical leverage. This study demonstrated China's centrality in global value chains, market monopolies over key battery materials, and monopsony power as the world's largest buyer and processor of critical minerals. This dominance over global battery, EV production and innovation, while promising for the green transition, not only cements China's economic leadership but also grants it significant geopolitical leverage. By controlling key materials, refining capacity, and advanced battery technology, China can dictate market conditions, influence trade policies, and potentially use supply restrictions as a strategic tool in international negotiation. Thus, as global efforts aim to transition to clean energy, other economies will increasingly rely on Chinese supply chains.

Over the last five years, the European Union has shifted its approach to the EV and battery market in light of China's rise and dominance. What once was a market-driven relationship, where European car brands were selling in China and Chinese batteries were powering the European shift towards electric vehicles and the green transition, this sector has become a strategic concern to the EU.

Bolstered by Russia's aggression of Ukraine which exposed critical dependencies, the EU is on a mission to bolster its resilience and plug into alternative networks and markets to reduce single-point failures, meaning not relying on one country alone for certain needs and services (Tenev, 2024). Consequently, the EU has coalesced around von der Leyen's infamous "de-risking" agenda, which aims to reduce critical dependencies on China through domestic capacity-building and targeted defensive trade measures (Arendse, 2023).

Despite the EU implementing defensive measures like strategic alliances and tariffs, these are insufficient to solve the structural weaknesses in the European green technology industry. Internal conflicts, legislative restrictions, and an excessive reliance on imported resources further hinder the EU's efforts, making it vulnerable to both strategic dependence and economic pressure. The EU must increase domestic capacity, encourage private sector participation in CRM supply chains, improve investment screening, and uphold legislative ambition under the Green Deal to restore leverage and guarantee strategic autonomy and remain competitive in the global low-carbon race.

References

- AlixPartners. (2021, October 27). *AlixPartners 2021 electric vehicles consumer sentiment survey*. <https://www.alixpartners.com/newsroom/the-alixpartners-2021-electric-vehicles-consumer-sentiment-survey/>
- Altiparmak, S. O. (2022). China and lithium geopolitics in a changing global market. *Chinese Political Science Review*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41111-022-00227-3>
- Arendse, H. (2023, July 13). The EU's China strategy - How to understand its "de-risking" approach? *China Briefing News*. <https://www.china-briefing.com/news/the-eus-china-strategy-understanding-the-concept-of-de-risking/>

- Baskaran, G. (2023, October 10). A window of opportunity to build critical mineral security in Africa. Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS). <https://www.csis.org/analysis/window-opportunity-build-critical-mineral-security-africa>
- BBC. (2024, April 29). Tensions grow as China ramps up global mining for green tech. BBC News. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-68896707>
- BBC World Service. (2025, February 6). *DeepSeek, TikTok, Temu: How China is taking the lead in tech* [Video]. BBC World Service. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z7do1hbb6fE>
- Bikales, J. (2024, May 3). Biden's final EV tax credit rules please automakers, anger China hawks. *Politico*. <https://www.politico.com/news/2024/05/03/biden-ev-tax-credit-rules-automakers-china-00155917>
- Blackwill, R. D., & Harris, J. M. (2016). *War by other means: geoeconomics and statecraft*. The Belknap Press Of Harvard University Press.
- Blenkinsop, P. (2024, October 29). EU slaps tariffs on Chinese EVs, risking Beijing backlash. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/autos-transportation/eu-slaps-tariffs-chinese-evs-risking-beijing-payback-2024-10-29/>
- Blenkinsop, P. (2025, January 23). Chinese EV makers file challenges to tariffs at EU court. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/autos-transportation/chinese-ev-makers-file-challenges-tariffs-eu-court-2025-01-23/>
- Bloomberg. (2024, August 7). EVs, hybrids set to exceed 50% of China car sales for first time. *Bloomberg News*. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2024-08-07/evs-hybrids-set-to-exceed-50-of-china-car-sales-for-first-time?embedded-checkout=true>
- Canestrini, C. (2024, March 20). *The Green Deal Industrial Plan*. Florence School of Regulation. <https://fsr.eui.eu/the-green-deal-industrial-plan/>
- CATL. (2024). Stellantis and CATL to invest up to €4.1 billion in joint venture for large-scale LFP battery plant in Spain. CATL. <https://www.catl.com/en/news/6328.html>
- Center for European Policy Studies. (2023). What ways and means for a real strategic autonomy of the EU in the economic field? (pp. 1–85). The European Economic and Social Committee (EESC). https://www.eesc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/qe-02-23-358-en-n_0.pdf
- Chan, B. Y. (2025, January 17). How China is helping to power the world's green transition. *World Economic Forum*. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/why-china-matters-to-the-worlds-green-transition/>
- Chen, L., & Rose, M. (2024, May 3). *Xi's trip to Europe may lay bare West's divisions over China strategy*. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/xi-trip-europe-may-lay-bare-west-divisions-over-china-strategy-2024-05-02/>
- Congressional-Executive Commission on China. (2023, November 14). *From cobalt to cars: How China exploits child and forced labor in the Congo*. <https://www.cecc.gov/events/hearings/from-cobalt-to-cars-how-china-exploits-child-and-forced-labor-in-the-congo>
- Connolly, K. (2025, March 14). "Germany is back": Merz secures Greens' support for defence spend boost. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2025/mar/14/friedrich-merz-germany-greens-support-defence-funding-plan>
- Cooper, K. (2024, September 10). *A deep dive into China's role as "critical mineral monolith."* Mining Technology. <https://www.mining-technology.com/features/a-deep-dive-into-chinas-role-as-critical-mineral-monolith/?cf-view>
- Dempsey, J. (2023). *Europe's dangerous dependence on China*. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. <https://carnegieendowment.org/europe/strategic-europe/2023/04/europes-dangerous-dependence-on-china?lang=en>
- Do Prado, V., Fabry, E., González Laya, A., Köhler-Suzuki, N., Lamy, P., & Praetorius, S. (2025, January). The road to a new European automotive strategy: Trade and industrial policy options. Institut Jacques Delors.

- <https://institutdelors.eu/en/publications/the-road-to-a-new-european-automotive-strategy-trade-and-industrial-policy-options/>
- Donovan, K., & Nikoladze, M. (2024, March 28). The axis of evasion: Behind China's oil trade with Iran and Russia. Atlantic Council.
<https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/new-atlanticist/the-axis-of-evasion-behind-chinas-oil-trade-with-iran-and-russia/>
- Downie, C. (2022). Geopolitical leverage in the energy transition: A framework for analysis and the case of Australian electricity exports. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 93.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102826>
- European Initiative for Energy Security. (2025). *European Initiative for Energy Security*.
<https://www.secureenergyeurope.org/press-release-securing-strategic-autonomy-100-billion-for-ev-battery-independence>
- Euronews. (2025, January 13). China sees a boom in EV sales while petrol-filled cars tank. *Euronews*.
<https://www.euronews.com/business/2025/01/13/china-sees-a-boom-in-ev-sales-while-petrol-filled-cars-tank>
- European Commission. (n.d.). *Foreign Subsidies Regulation*. Competition Policy.ec.europa.eu.
https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/foreign-subsidies-regulation_en
- European Commission. (2022, February 23). *Questions and answers: The European Battery Alliance: Progress made and the way forward*. European Commission.
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/sk/qanda_22_1257
- European Commission. (2023). Critical raw materials. European Commission.
https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials_en
- European Commission. (2024, December 3). Commission and EIB announce new partnership to support investments in the European battery manufacturing value chain. European Commission.
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ippr_24_1203
- European Commission. (2025). Industrial Action Plan for the European automotive sector. European Commission.
https://transport.ec.europa.eu/document/download/89b3143e-09b6-4ae6-a826-932b90ed0816_en?filename=Communication%20-%20Action%20Plan.pdf
- European Court of Auditors. (2023, June 19). *Special report 15/2023: The EU's industrial policy on batteries*. European Court of Auditors.
<https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications/SR-2023-15>
- Ezell, S. (2024, July 29). *How innovative is China in the electric vehicle and battery industries?* Information Technology & Innovation Foundation.
<https://itif.org/publications/2024/07/29/how-innovative-is-china-in-the-electric-vehicle-and-battery-industries/>
- Farrell, H., & Newman, A. (2023). *The uses and abuses of weaponized interdependence*. Penguin Books Ltd.
- Farrell, H., & Newman, A. L. (2019). Weaponized interdependence: How global economic networks shape state coercion. *International Security*, 44(1), 42–79.
https://doi.org/10.1162/isec_a_00351
- Featherston, R. (2024, December 16). *Slamming the brakes: The EU votes to impose tariffs on Chinese EVs | Trustee China Hand*. Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS).
<https://www.csis.org/blogs/trustee-china-hand/slamming-brakes-eu-votes-impose-tariffs-chinese-evs>
- Global Times. (2021, December 27). Foreign investment banned in rare-earth sector, new negative lists show. *Global Times*.
<https://www.globaltimes.cn/page/202112/1243515.shtml>
- Gros, M. (2025, February 26). Brussels confirms dramatic U-turn on corporate green rules. Politico.
<https://www.politico.eu/article/most-eu-firms-exempted-from-green-reporting-under-proposed-omnibus-bill/>
- Gulley, A. L. (2024). The development of China's monopoly over cobalt battery materials. *Mineral Economics*, 37.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13563-024-00447-w>
- Hawkins, A. (2024a, March 18). CATL, the

- little-known Chinese battery maker that has the U.S. worried. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2024/mar/18/catl-chinese-battery-maker-evs-electric-vehicles>
- Hawkins, A. (2024b, December 3). China's share of global electric car market rises to 76%. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/business/2024/dec/03/chinas-share-of-global-electric-car-market-rises-to-76>
- Hernandez-Roy, C., Ziemer, H., & Laske, N. (2024, April 11). *De-risking Critical Mineral Supply Chains: the Role of Latin America*. Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS). <https://www.csis.org/analysis/de-risking-critical-mineral-supply-chains-role-latin-america>
- Hongpei, Z. (2023, January 3). As government subsidies expire, China's NEV sector is to embrace rising competition. *The Global Times*. <https://www.globaltimes.cn/page/202301/1283120.shtml>
- Hont, I. (2005). *Jealousy of trade: international competition and the nation state in historical perspective*. Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- International Energy Agency. (2022, July). *Solar PV global supply chains*. International Energy Agency. <https://www.iea.org/reports/solar-pv-global-supply-chains/executive-summary>
- International Energy Agency. (2024). *Global Critical Minerals Outlook 2024*. <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/ee01701d-1d5c-4ba8-9df6-abeeac9de99a/GlobalCriticalMineralsOutlook2024.pdf>
- International Renewable Energy Agency. (2024, September 30). Critical materials: Batteries for electric vehicles. International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). <https://www.irena.org/Publications/2024/Sep/Critical-materials-Batteries-for-electric-vehicles>
- Kennedy, S. (2024, June 20). The Chinese EV dilemma: Subsidized yet striking. Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS). <https://www.csis.org/blogs/trustee-china-hand/chinese-ev-dilemma-subsidized-yet-striking>
- Ledman, M., Huang, M., & Higgins, E. (2024, September 18). Navigating trade tension: Potential impacts of China's probe into EU dairy subsidies. Rabobank. <https://www.rabobank.com/knowledge/q0-11441493-navigating-trade-tension-potential-impacts-of-chinas-probe-into-eu-dairy-subsidies>
- McHugh, D., & Moritsugu, K. (2024, October 30). What to know about Europe's tariffs on Chinese electric vehicles. *AP News*. <https://apnews.com/article/eu-tariffs-china-evs-24e19ab4277e61d624df2d3c75c15bc5>
- Mendiluce, M., & Hooper, L. (2025, February 17). The dangers of ditching Europe's Green Deal. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/sustainability/boards-policy-regulation/comment-dangers-ditching-europes-green-deal-2025-02-17/>
- Minnis, H. (2024, December 3). *The geopolitical power of graphite: China's latest export restrictions*. GraphiteHub. <https://graphitehub.com/the-geopolitical-power-of-graphite-chinas-latest-export-restrictions/>
- Piovaccari, G. (2025, March 17). BYD considers Germany for third plant in Europe. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/auto-s-transportation/byd-considers-germany-third-plant-europe-2025-03-17/>
- Reuters. (2024a, April 25). Chinese EV battery maker CATL unveils LFP battery with 1,000 km range. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/auto-s-transportation/chinese-ev-battery-maker-catl-unveils-lfp-battery-with-1000-km-range-2024-04-25/>
- Reuters. (2024b, December 10). Stellantis, China's CATL to invest \$4.33 bln in EV battery factory in Spain. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/auto-s-transportation/stellantis-chinas-catl-invest-433-bln-ev-battery-factory-spain-2024-12-10/>
- Reuters. (2025a, January 2). China proposes further export curbs on battery, critical minerals tech. *Reuters*.

- <https://www.reuters.com/technology/china-proposes-further-export-curbs-battery-critical-minerals-tech-2025-01-02/>
- Reuters. (2025b, January 13). China vehicle export growth to slow in 2025, association data shows. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/autos-transportation/china-vehicle-export-growth-slow-2025-association-data-shows-2025-01-13/>
- Richter, F. (2025, January 3). *BYD pulls ahead of Tesla to become largest EV maker*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/chart/33709/tesla-byd-electric-vehicle-production/>
- Russell, C. (2024, August 22). Passed the peak? China's crude oil imports trend down. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/markets/commodities/passed-peak-chinas-crude-oil-imports-trend-down-russell-2024-08-22/>
- Russell, C. (2025, January 29). Russia oil sanctions create different winners at different times. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/energy/russia-oil-sanctions-create-different-winners-different-times-russell-2025-01-29/>
- Sall, L., & Gross, S. (2025, January 13). *How do China and America think about the energy transition?* Brookings. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/how-do-china-and-america-think-about-the-energy-transition/>
- Slaughter, A.-M. (2018). *The chessboard and the web: strategies of connection in a networked world*. Yale University Press.
- Snidal, D., Hale, T., Jones, E., Mertens, C., & Milewicz, K. (2024). The power of the "weak" and international organizations. *The Review of International Organizations*, 19, 385–409. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11558-024-09531-w>
- Sorgi, G. (2024, December 18). *EU to Germany: Your lack of investment isn't our fault*. Politico. <https://www.politico.eu/article/lack-investment-not-our-fault-eu-germany-valdis-dombrovskis/>
- Spisak, A. (2024, October 31). *The EU's drive on China: What EV tariffs mean for Europe*. Center for European Reform. <https://www.cer.eu/insights/eus-drive-china-what-ev-tariffs-mean-europe>
- Swieboda, P. (2025, March 31). *The art of turning the corner: Towards a competitive comeback for Europe's EV battery sector*. European Policy Center. <https://www.epc.eu/en/publications/The-art-of-turning-the-corner-Towards-a-competitive-comeback-for-Euro~63b370>
- Temple-West, P. (2024, December 9). Global green subsidy race draws investor attention. *Financial Times*. <https://www.ft.com/content/852a8031-ed91-49fe-9372-73a57edbd033>
- Tenev, M. (2024, November 7). *Material world: How Europe can compete with China in the race for Africa's critical minerals*. European Council on Foreign Relations (ECFR). <https://ecfr.eu/publication/material-world-how-europe-can-compete-with-china-in-the-race-for-africas-critical-minerals/>
- Tyborski, R., & Fasse, M. (2025). *E-Auto-Krise der deutschen Hersteller in China verschärft sich* [German manufacturers' e-car crisis in China worsens]. Handelsblatt. <https://www.handelsblatt.com/unternehmen/industrie/autobauer-e-auto-krise-der-deutschen-hersteller-in-china-verschaerft-sich/100102260.html>
- Verhelst, K., & Zimmermann, A. (2024, June 14). *EU presents China with clear way to avert EV duties — good luck with that*. Politico. <https://www.politico.eu/article/eu-china-relations-electric-cars-duties-subsidies-wto-g7-summit/>
- Vox. (2024, June 7). *Why China is winning the EV war* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rkxMdmipYqM>
- Walt, S. M. (2010, October 29). *Signs of realism in U.S. grand strategy*. Foreign Policy. <https://foreignpolicy.com/2010/10/29/signs-of-realism-in-u-s-grand-strategy/>
- Wang, X. (2022). *How China Came to Dominate the Global EV Lithium-ion Battery Value Chain: Lessons and Opportunities for Africa*. Center for Business and Development Studies. https://research-api.cbs.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/86571236/xieshu_wang_how_china_came_to_dominate_publishersversion.pdf
- Webster, J. (2025, March 19). *As Chinese EVs*

threaten to overrun Europe, Germany should ramp up supply-chain investment. Atlantic Council.
<https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/new-atlanticist/as-chinese-evs-threaten-to-overrun-europe-germany-should-ramp-up-supply-chain-investment/>

Yang, Z. (2023, February 21). *How Did China Come to Dominate the World of Electric cars?* MIT Technology Review.
<https://www.technologyreview.com/2023/02/21/1068880/how-did-china-dominate-electric-cars-policy/>

Zabelin, D., & von Dongen, D.-M. (2024, October 28). *How geopolitics will both hinder and accelerate the global energy transition.* World Economic Forum.
<https://www.weforum.org/stories/2024/10/geopolitics-energy-transition/>

Zhang, S., & Chen, W. (2022). Assessing the energy transition in China towards carbon neutrality with a probabilistic framework. *Nature Communications*, 13(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27671-0>

Caroline Seil

c.seil@umail.leidenuniv.nl

Caroline Seil is an Advanced Master's candidate in International Relations and Diplomacy at Leiden University and the Clingendael Institute. She has acquired a deep understanding and appreciation of Chinese foreign policy during her Bachelor while honing her proficiency in Mandarin through academic exchanges in Shanghai and Hong Kong. During her internship at the Permanent Mission of Luxembourg to the United Nations in New York and in the office of MEP Charles Goerens at the European Parliament, Caroline worked closely on multilateral negotiations, covering topics ranging from development cooperation, human rights, sustainable development, and international peace and security.

Exporting the Chinese School: How Convincing is the Relational Theory of World Politics as Formulated by Yaqing Qin?

Carys HOSKING

Abstract

Does a theory rooted in Confucian thought have intellectual value beyond its cultural origin? A consistent charge advanced by critics to challenge the credibility of Relational Theory (RT), as posited by Qin Yaqing, pertains to its scarce applicability beyond Confucian cultural spaces. This paper defends Qin's Relational Theory against such charges, proposing that Qin's Relational Theory of International Relations is convincing insofar as (1) explaining social phenomena beyond its alleged cultural departure point and (2) offering answers to policy questions that dominant theories in the current Western scholarship cannot. By exporting Qin's relational theory outside of its Confucian cultural birthplace and identifying spaces RT has been engaged with as a viable international relations (IR) theory, this paper finds that RT has the capacity to fill empirical gaps in the explanatory capacity of existing IR theories via their ontological differences—namely, Constructivism (as RT's Western comparison), English School (as a fellow theory charged with indigenization), and Liberal Feminism (as another relational approach). This paper contributes to the theoretical literature on RT by setting the ontological groundwork for re-evaluating persistent policy problems that mainstream IR has yet to fully account for.

Keywords: Relational Theory, relationality, Confucianism, Chinese School, Hegelian philosophy, *zhongyong* dialectic

Introduction

Mainstream International Relations (IR) theory has tended to appeal to similar notions posited in Rudyard Kipling's adage: "East is East, and West is West, and never the twain shall meet" (Kipling, 1899, p. 5). Calls for Asian universalism have flooded the post-colonial literature on IR theory, challenging understandings of non-Western theories as indigenous and the "worlding" of Western mainstream IR (Spivak, 1985, p. 247). Others have suggested that Asian IR better explains cultural specificity rather than posing as a form of scientific universalism (Kang, 2012). These discussions are of particular relevance in assessing the cogence of Qin Yaqing's "Relational Theory of World Politics" of the Chinese School of IR (Qin, 2018). Does a theory rooted in Confucian thought have intellectual value outside of its cultural origin?

The Relational Theory of World Politics, formulated by Qin Yaqing, is a theory of IR that takes relations as its ontological and analytical referent point, taking meaning from human practice (Qin, 2016, pp. 33–47). That is to say, it assumes individuals, states, and international institutions are the product of relations, rather than isolated substances, to account for behavior in international relations. By extension, it therefore troubles the dominant Hegelian dialectic that is so prevalent in Western international relations theory, which views the individual (and by extension, states) as a self-contained and pre-constituted actor that then interacts with others (Raspa, 2016).

Underpinning Relational Theory is three primary assumptions. IR is a realm of interrelatedness between entities; these actors are thus always relationally co-constitutive; relations are always in motion i.e. amenable to change (Qin, 2016, pp. 36–37). Human practice, and by extension states, are informed by the totality of their relational

spheres. Orienting Relational Theory towards this theoretical position is its Confucian cultural origin, and more specifically, the *zhongyong* dialectics (中庸), which emphasizes inclusivity, complementation, and harmony (Qin, 2016, pp.152–194). This involves polarities as co-theses rather than the anti-thesis found in Western, Hegelian philosophy that emphasizes non-contradiction through rationality (Qin, 2016, pp. 153–169). Thus, harmony is the natural organizing logic of IR, rather than anarchy and conflict through differences in rationalist approaches such as neorealism (Zhao, 2009). Despite its Confucian founding, Qin does not intend for the theory to be indigenized. Indeed, whilst relationality is most evident in Confucian communities, imbricating relational spheres are ubiquitous in IR. Qin proposes that Relational Theory is to be exported beyond its cultural and geographical birthplace (Qin, 2016, p.45).

The most common criticism of Relational Theory pertains to its scarce applicability beyond Confucian spaces. Choi (2022) addresses the apparent essentialist framing of Chinese cultural identity in Qin’s theory, suggesting that equating relationality strictly with Confucian traditions risks oversimplifying cultural dynamics and may hinder the theory’s universal applicability. This is one of several factors turned to when discussing the credibility problem of Relational Theory. Others include how convincing the relational ontology is in comparison with rationalist positions, and how Qin’s theory departs from other forms of relational theorizing such as post-colonial and feminist approaches. Due to scope, this paper deals with one of these questions—the traveling capability of Qin’s Relational Theory—to assess its cogence.

This paper argues that Qin’s Relational Theory is convincing, as it can explain social phenomena beyond its cultural departure point. Indeed, it can offer answers to policy questions that dominant theories in the

current Western scholarship *cannot*. This will be exemplified through a critical analysis of its theoretical assumptions in conjunction with its ability to fill empirical gaps in the explanatory capacity of existing theories—Constructivism (as Relational Theory’s Western comparison), English School (as a fellow theory charged with indigenization), and Western Feminism (as an approach critiqued for its universalism). To operationalize “convincing,” the explanatory capacity of Relational Theory will be evaluated on two criteria. Firstly, what the author’s ambitions for the theory are. Qin intends to offer a lens for understanding the world beyond Confucian cultural communities (Zalewski, 1996, pp. 340–353). If Qin Yaqing insists the theory is not limited to Confucian settings, and one of its primary charges is its cultural particularism, the theory must *travel* well (Kang, 2012; Qin, 2018). Secondly, as an external measure of success, Cox (1981) argues that a theory has utility if it allows us to see the world differently. That is to say, it does not simply describe what fits the dominant model of thinking. To prove this, this paper asks whether Relational Theory offers analytical advantages over Constructivism, English School, and Liberal Feminism in understanding policy questions.

Through a critical analysis of Relational Theory’s theoretical counterparts, this paper evaluates its explanatory power relative to other theories that dominate the theoretical space. In doing so, this paper highlights what impact Relational Theory can make as a viable theory of international relations that offers something the theories identified above cannot. This paper will not be measuring how convincing Relational Theory is based on assessments within mainstream American IR, given that the inclusion of theories in this space is contingent on its development of cause-effect arguments under rationalist thought, thus making for biased analysis (Hoffmann, 1977, pp. 212–241). Rather, this paper references less-obvious spaces Relational Theory has been engaged with to testify to the attention it has received as a viable IR theory.

Due to scope, the paper also does not seek to evaluate the internal coherence of Qin Yaqing's Relational Theory. The existing literature has laid the necessary conceptual groundwork for further inquiry into the theory's utility, by establishing its foundational coherence (Guzzini, 2024; Kavalski, 2017; Qin, 2016, 2018).

The following three sections represent the main analysis. The literature review outlines how Qin Yaqing's Relational Theory of World Politics has mainly been primarily engaged conceptually with limited empirical application, particularly beyond Confucian cultural contexts. The theory and methods outlines Relational Theory and introduces how the lexicon of postcolonial feminist insights can articulate a critique of mainstream theories. This section also sets the criteria for what makes a theory "convincing"—explanatory power, critical depth, and practical utility. It sets the basis to explore the primary research question in the main analysis, which demonstrates the theory's empirical value through case studies like the EU's Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) and rule-of-law disputes, revealing how relational logics can explain political behavior in non-Confucian settings where Western theories fall short.

1. Literature Review

The existing literature on Qin's Relational Theory has largely prioritized its conceptual clarity over empirical veracity. While understandable—conceptual clarity and internal consistency are essential to lay the groundwork for further critical engagement with its utility, it has hitherto remained underdeveloped beyond this point. This has denied Relational Theory its due diligence. Much of the literature can be divided into roughly two groups:- (1) conceptual and (2) practical engagement with the theory.

The conceptual literature has typically focused on the extent to which Relational Theory offers an internally coherent alternative to its Western counterparts—by introducing Confucian concepts to the study of international relations, it challenges the ontological individualism of mainstream Western approaches. It does so by emphasizing relationality as the foundational model of social being (Jiang, 2018; Nordin and Smith, 2018; Qin, 2016, 2018). While useful in laying the essential conceptual groundwork from which to develop the theory, its empirical engagement is comparatively weaker. Qin's theory introduced an entirely new lexicon of conceptualizing international relations, which requires significant attention: a theory is of little use until (1) its empirical applicability is proven and (2) it can offer something different to what existing theories purport to account for (Cox, 1981). Stefano Guzzini (2024) seeks to reconcile the imbalance in the literature between theoretical discussion and empirical engagement by critically examining Qin's attempt to explain relationalism at four levels of analysis (ontological, theoretical, interpretative, and strategic). Guzzini argues that while admirable, Qin's attempt to cover *all* four levels of analysis makes for limited explanatory capacity (Guzzini, 2024). Guzzini argues that despite this, the relational theoretical aspect of the theory remains valuable for understanding the co-constitution of identities and interests through interactions (Guzzini, 2024). Guzzini thus applied Qin's vision of open, trust-based diplomacy to study the Helsinki Accords, deeming it a prime example of true multilateralism which embodied a foreign policy strategy aimed at transforming adversarial international relations into a productive partnership (Guzzini, 2024). While holding significant merit in its deviation from the oft-insular approach in the existing literature, Guzzini's empirical engagement is tied to outdated examples that provide minimal insight into contemporary international relations. As Qin articulates a vision for a relational world order today, that is, an order focused on the mutual influence of, and thus governing of *relations among interconnected actors*, rather than actors

as isolated entities, critical engagement with his theory requires a commitment to proving its contemporary relevance (Qin, 2016, 2018).

The literature which attempts to export Relational Theory is scarce. This literature tends to prematurely reconcile the theory with Western theoretical concepts before giving it due diligence, suggesting that its Confucian-based lexicon inherently Sinicizes the theory, reproducing a form of cultural essentialism (Callahan, 2008). As a result, its universal applicability is undermined by its reliance on culturally reliant assumptions (Callahan, 2008). Such literature assumes that taking Relational Theory seriously requires a complete overhaul of the current international order. However, while engagement with the theory requires critical engagement with complex concepts, it challenges it without requiring a wholesale replacement of the existing order.

While acknowledging this work's contribution to articulating a global IR, this paper argues that the existing literature on Relational Theory has yet to produce a study solely dedicated to demonstrating the empirical applicability of Qin's Relational Theory beyond its cultural origins and assessing its distinct explanatory value.

2. Theory and Methods

2.1 Theory

This paper takes Qin's "Relational Theory of World Politics" as its ontological point of departure, which is supported by a critical post-colonial approach to understanding emancipation, to articulate a critique of the limits of Liberal Feminism. Qin's Relational Theory has yet to articulate a cohesive critique of contending IR theories. The lack of theoretical engagement limits Relational Theory's ability to carve out a distinct position in the existing theoretical landscape. Consequently, Relational Theory's embryonic

status, relative to other pervasive theories of IR, is not yet equipped with the adequate tools to critically engage with other theories. While engaging other theories may not be Qin's primary objective, doing so is essential for establishing Relational Theory as a viable alternative in IR.

To strengthen its critical footing, this paper draws on Postcolonial Feminism to articulate the limitations of Liberal Feminism. In doing so, this does not suggest the limitations of Relational Theory as a theory in isolation. Rather, this paper acknowledges that the Postcolonial Feminist critique offers the most compelling and comprehensive framework for exposing the limitations of Liberal Feminism, while Relational Theory can offer something unique by providing the lexicon of the *tianxia* worldview, which can provide a measure of good governance as the ability to effectively manage relations between entities.

This paper draws on Mohanty's critique of the "othering" inherent in Western feminist discourse, which often marginalizes non-Western visions of emancipation (Mohanty, 1988). In other words, Western feminism, shaped largely by Liberal Feminist thinking, which focuses on individual rights and equality within existing systems rather than challenging those systems—it is both dependent on and reinforces a rights-based vision of emancipation. This vision limits the way emancipation is understood, keeping it confined within a state-centered framework. Liberal Feminism thus renders itself void of a truly transnational definition of liberation by universalizing a highly context-specific form of oppression. Hence, this paper equips itself with a Postcolonial Feminist approach to articulate more inclusive concepts of emancipation and reveal the limitations of the dominant Liberal Feminism (Parashar, 2016).

This paper defines "convincing" based on what the theory sets out to achieve, drawing from Zalewski's framework on how theory functions in IR (Zalewski, 1996). This paper maintains that Qin Yaqing endeavors to offer an alternative lens

for understanding the world outside of its Confucian cultural origin—theory as explanation (Zalewski, 1996). It also functions to trouble the fixed, static, and binary-focused ontological assumptions of mainstream (Western) IR—*theory as critique* (Zalewski, 1996). Finally, relational theorizing itself constitutes a practice of world-making, in that by adopting a relational understanding, political practice can move toward harmony and dynamic equilibrium, rather than assuming a predisposition to balance of power politics—*theory as practice* (Zalewski, 1996). Thus, to satisfy this criterion of “convincing,” this paper uses Relational Theory to exemplify how it offers an alternative understanding of IR that not only deviates from, but troubles the assumptions underpinning the Hegelian dialectic. It also indicates how Relational Theory operates to not only explain but *inform* political practice.

2.2 Methods

To prove that Relational Theory satisfies the criterion of “convincing” outlined above, this paper identifies instances of policy decision-making at the international and state level (excluding states shaped by Confucian cultural communities), assuming that international institutions are, at least to a large extent, the sum of their relations (Wendt, 1999). Rather than conducting interviews with policymakers, this analysis uses publicly available documents, policy statements, and foreign policy decisions. This methodological choice reflects the theoretical orientation of the paper: Relational Theory emphasizes the dynamics and patterns of interaction among actors, which are often more legible in formal articulations of policy and institutional behavior than through individual perspectives. Reinforcing this, as Relational Theory seeks to understand the logic and structure of relationships rather than subjective motivations of actors, the procedural outputs of states and institutions appear the most appropriate empirical sites.

Supporting the definitional criteria of “convincing” as outlined in the Theory section, this paper strictly refers to less conspicuous areas in which Relational Theory has been applied to highlight the growing recognition it has garnered as a credible theoretical framework. This methodological framework ultimately serves as an external measure of Relational Theory’s success as a cogent theory, which isn’t defined solely by the terms delineated by its author.

To clarify, this paper does not seek to validate the persuasiveness of Relational Theory through its reception within the positivist IR scholarship. Given that the literature is largely grounded in rational-choice models of thinking, often overlooking the centrality of identity and culture in international relations, such an approach would risk analytical bias. That is to say, the paper’s methodological framework would rely on evaluations from scholars who are, by disciplinary orientation, already predisposed to frameworks rooted in the very intellectual tradition that Relational Theory troubles. The paper testifies to the theory’s plausibility and analytical utility by examining its resonance within less conventional or peripheral contexts. If Relational Theory is to hold any explanatory capacity, then its main tenets should be observable within these referents. The following comprises the main analysis.

3. Main Analysis

3.1 “Politics As The Art Of Coexistence”: Understanding The Limitations Of The EU CFSP Relationally

Qin’s Relational Theory can best exemplify its empirical and theoretical value by offering answers to critical research questions left unanswered in Constructivism’s understandings of EU security identity. During the 1990s, Constructivism provided an indispensable shift in approaches to EU governance analysis that seemingly departed from the rationalist approach stressing neo-functionalism and fixed preferences as a materially-based ontology

(Pollack, 2005, pp. 357–98). By emphasizing the dynamic social construction of state interests, identities, and norms, Constructivism highlights how shared ideas, discourse, and institutional norms can shape integration dynamics within institutions (Checkel, 1998). This distinguished itself from existing neo-functional approaches that stressed fixed state preferences and integration driven by “functional spillover”—that integration in one area necessitates integration in others (Nicoli, 2019).

More specifically, it provided interpretive approaches to the development of the EU’s CFSP as a security community by taking the maintenance of global norms and identity as ontologically significant in human behavior (Adler and Barnett, 1998, pp. 3–28). However, in emphasizing the communicative pathway of norms formed by international organizations and transmitted to individual actors, constructivism remains divorced from, and negligent of, theoretical frameworks that stress relationality *between* institutions. As a result, Constructivism has been unable to explain why the CFSP has fallen short of delivering a cohesive EU foreign policy through a shared security identity, if by taking normative rationality as the basis for human action, the most probable outcome would be so.

Norm-based constructivist approaches assume that what motivates human action is a “logic of appropriateness”—actors internalize understandings of what is socially designated as “true,” “right,” or “good,” and make decisions based on what satisfies this criterion (March & Olsen, 1998, p. 949). This does not necessarily render relations unimportant in human decision-making, nor should it be suggested that the “logic of appropriateness” does not inform human action (March & Olsen, 1998). However, this paper maintains that if the *primary* motivation for human action is an assessment of the normative appropriateness of taking a particular action, then one would

expect the EU’s CFSP to have achieved greater coherence and cohesion. In this view, Member States would be inclined to support a unified foreign policy because regional cooperation is largely perceived as normatively legitimate (Jupille et al., 2003). Why does an effective EU common foreign policy find itself stymied?

This paper maintains that Qin’s Relational Theory offers answers to these questions emerging from constructivist approaches to EU security. Qin argues that examining the connate imbrication of multiple relational circles as the basis for action can offer useful insights into the barriers to, and opportunities for, cooperation within institutions (Qin, 2018). The logic of relationality, an alternative to the logic of appropriateness, assumes two things—firstly, that actors are both enabled and restrained by the totality of their relational circles (Qin, 2016, p. 38). Actions in one relational circle can modify the context in which a decision is made, influencing which course of action appears more rational or favorable than another. Absent of their relational context, an actor has little basis to ascertain what is rational and what is not. Secondly, actors use their relational circles to pursue their self-interests, and view their relational circles as a means to satisfy them (Qin, 2016, p. 38–39). In other words, if an actor’s needs in a particular realm are satisfied by a relational circle, it will not necessarily pursue it in another. The logic of relationality can apply directly to the EU’s CFSP to account for its shortcomings.

That is to say, the barriers to common EU foreign policy reside in an enduring condition in which EU members are unwilling to dedicate further resources to the CFSP when their security, in both status and materiality, is already accounted for nationally and through other security organizations such as NATO. The CFSP currently has no authority to impose an impetus for action on individual states—policy decisions are initiated either nationally or through unanimity in the Council of the European Union (Denza, 2002, p. 121). As a result, most states (22 out of 27 EU states are also a part of NATO), recognizing

the collective of their relational circles as comprising a robust security identity, are unwilling to dedicate themselves to common EU foreign policy, when institutions such as NATO offer the same security identity through territorial defense and peacekeeping that the CFSP offers.

An alternative interpretation within the literature highlights that Constructivism hasn't failed to explain the lack of cohesion in EU foreign policy, but instead indicates that a fragmented or evolving European identity explains the difficulty in forming a united CFSP (Arkan, 2014). Theorists such as Thomas Risse-Kappen (2010) contend that as the European identity is formed through public discourse and socialization within and across EU Member States, it is so amenable to change that the CFSP's weakness merely reflects an enduring identity struggle among EU members, rather than a theoretical shortcoming of Constructivism. While this paper acknowledges such counter-arguments, it does not change the enduring condition in which Constructivism struggles to divorce itself from a rationalist, agency-driven worldview. That is to say, despite the Constructivist critique of theories undergirded by a rationalist ontology, much of the Constructivist literature still operates within the same representational logic, in which the individual is seen as an autonomous agent, and the system is structured by utility-maximizing behavior, even when couched in norm-following terms (Price & Reus-Smit, 1998).

Relational Theory is vulnerable to the charge that in this particular case, EU states "maximize utility" by opting against further integration into the CFSP, thus situating itself within a rationalist ontology. To clarify, Relational Theory does not deny that actors do not act in accordance with self-interest, nor does it deny the "self" as significant. Rather, Relational Theory assumes that an individual's understanding of its self-interest is, to a larger extent than is assumed under rationalist

logics, by the totality of its relational circles (Guzzini, 2024). Such arguments conflate acting in self-interest with a commitment to a rationalist ontology. Rather, Relational Theory can provide an alternative lens for understanding the ideational framework in which one makes choices by conceptualizing the self as constituted through relations with others.

Relational Theory can offer a different interpretation of policy issues that accounts for social phenomena based on the interaction between *relational circles*. In this particular example of the CFSP, it provides an alternative framework for understanding its limitations. Qin's emphasis on relational circles as ontologically significant in decision-making answers existing calls in the intellectual space to recognize the centrality of inter-institutional relationships in IR. It also answers empirical questions that have troubled the policy realm since the Constructivist-led "governance turn" in EU analysis (Berenskoetter, 2007, pp. 647–676). As a result, Relational Theory provides a theoretical alternative that deviates from a Constructivist orientation towards the logic of normative rationality, by offering an account of relational context as preceding rational social action (Qin and Nordin, 2019, pp. 601–614). What Qin's Relational Theory ultimately provides is a convincing account of the relationship between relationality and social action that can (1) not only apply to policy questions beyond its Confucian birthplace but (2) answer policy questions relating to CFSP that has troubled Constructivism that existing (Western) theories cannot. This is a significant testament to its cogence.

3.2 Responding To Barry Buzan And Jiangli Wang—Exporting The Chinese School

Similar to the English School, Qin's Relational Theory has been criticized for its inability to travel beyond its cultural origin. Martha Finnemore argues that the lack of engagement of American IR with the English School is a result of its remote proximity to positivist

methodologies—given that the English School and Relational Theory renounce cause-effect hypotheses, similar explanations can be attributed to Relational Theory’s marginalization (Finnemore, 2001). Wang and Buzan (2014, pp.1–43) outline multiple charges the English School faces that Qin’s Relational Theory should avoid as a newer IR theory—of most concern is that the English School has offered weak accounts of IR at the regional level. Indeed, in its focus on “international” or “world” typologies of “system” and “society,” the ES provides little on how regionalism can shape such phenomena. Ironically too, the ES also offers an account of such typologies that are inherently regionalized through its account of primary institutions as rooted in the warring, international law and balance of power of the 17th/18th centuries in Europe (Stivachtis, 2014, pp. 109–126). Whilst these charges of indigenization against the English School are valid, the same cannot be said for Relational Theory. Indeed, Relational Theory can offer more to Western regional policy than the ES can offer reciprocally.

Relational Theory insulates itself from criticisms that it only produces an Asia-specific account of IR, by offering a regional account through its emphasis on the complementation of opposing entities (Qin, 2018, p.178). Complementation, one of the founding principles underpinning the *zhongyong* dialectic, which Relational Theory takes as its epistemological and methodological foundation, refers to the dynamic interplay between actions in the international system, where relationships are characterized by mutual adaptation and co-evolution (Qin, 2016). The concept aligns with one interpretation of Confucianism—the ideal of harmony, in which balance is achieved not through uniformity but through the integration of differences (Qin, 2024). Under the *zhongyong* dialectic, harmony is taken as the basic and natural state of nature, and conflict as the exception (Babones, 2017; Qin, 2024).

A charge often waged against Qin’s Relational Theory suggests it cannot account for subject/object relationships and by extension, the power differential between the two, meaning Relational Theory undermines the role of power dynamics in shaping international relations (Guzzini, 2024). However, assuming that one can only assess a theory based on what it purports to do, rather than what it does not, such a charge reads Relational Theory through the very dichotomous lens that the *zhongyong* dialectic refutes. Relational Theory’s emphasis on the complementation of opposing entities can account for spaces in IR where conflicts of interest have laid the groundwork for productive partnerships.

For example, the EU’s evolving relationship with Hungary and Poland amid ongoing rule-of-law disputes between 2020 and 2023 illustrates a complementary assimilation of differing strategic priorities between opposing entities. From 2020 to 2023, Hungary and Poland faced criticism and legal action from EU institutions over policies that undermined judicial independence, media freedom, and democratic standards (Kos, 2023). Rather than leading to a decisive rupture of ties, the EU’s response was marked by a dynamic process of negotiation and incremental adaptation—namely, the Rule-of-Law Conditionality Mechanism, which tied access to EU funds to compliance with core democratic norms (Baraggia & Bonelli, 2022). While Hungary and Poland resisted this conditionality, suggesting it challenged its national sovereignty, the EU withheld certain budgetary disbursements while simultaneously maintaining open channels for legal and political dialog (Baraggia & Bonelli, 2022). In response, both the EU, and Hungary and Poland, made concessions—the EU refined the scope of conditionality, while Hungary and Poland executed partial reforms and made amendments sufficient to unlock portions of the funds.

Such an example bears a strong resemblance to the complementary relationship between opposing entities as posited by Qin’s Relational

Theory, in which difference can be the basis for the “dynamic reproduction” of a complementary relationship (Qin, 2018, p.178). That is to say, differing strategic interests between the EU and Poland and Hungary were renegotiated to achieve mutual benefit. Rather than operating within a rigid framework of compliance or punishment, both sides engaged in an iterative process of dialog, which reasoned through relational balance (integration, rather than elimination, of difference) (Qin, 2016, 2018). Understood through the lens of Relational Theory, the EU’s concessions are not indicators of a breakdown of norms, nor institutional weakness, but a relational system in which actors co-evolve through conflict. That is to say, in accordance with the *zhongyong* perspective, harmony arises not through uniformity but through the respectful integration of difference.

This indicates that Qin’s Relational Theory can offer more comprehensive insights into the relational and regional dynamics of states extraneous from Confucian culture. Where policy analysts have doggedly focused on conflicts of interest in commentary on the long-running rule of law dispute between the EU, and Poland and Hungary, there is complementation and harmony to be found that makes for a productive partnership. This example exemplifies that Qin’s Relational Theory can offer an account of relationalism that considers the complementation of competing interests and its prospects for regional dynamic developments, as opposed to the focus of the English School on “world” or “international” orientations. Compounding this, the theory’s conceptual flexibility, notably its foundational principle of mutual adaptation through difference, Relational Theory can offer a more appropriate conceptual framework for both understanding and facilitating processes of conflict resolution, mediation, and reconciliation. This is a significant testament to its ability to travel beyond its cultural origins, and offer more than current Western IR.

3.3 Globalizing A Regional Project - How Do Other Relational Theories Fair?

Assessments of the cogence of Qin’s Relational Theory and its usefulness for the study of IR ultimately necessitate a discussion of its utility vis-à-vis other forms of relational theorizing, to determine if Qin’s Relational Theory offers a unique lens. Relational Theory can help advance an intellectual project of universal emancipation where other relational theories like Western feminism have engaged in intellectual processes of “othering” and other marginalized non-Western concepts of liberation. Spivak (1981, pp. 154–184) argues that Western Feminism has taken the rationality embedded in liberalism as its primary object of criticism to trouble the violence it has permitted against populations deemed a threat to civil order along ethno-gendered lines. This focus on critiquing the violence embedded in liberal epistemology as a dominant Liberal Feminist posture works to prioritize the Eurocentric experience and ultimately mobilizes it to generate understanding of how to emancipate *all* women. This is to the detriment of non-Western women whose issues with traditional institutions that marginalize and oppress them are not positivist by nature, but more frequently religious or cultural.

In fact, the lexicon of rights-based individuality has been valuable in many emancipatory feminist movements in the non-West. South Korea’s urban redevelopment projects of the 1980s under President Chun Doo-hwan displaced families residing in shantytowns who had largely moved from rural areas to developing cities in the 1960s (Shin, 2017). In the midst of a tumultuous dynamic between civic society and the authoritarian regime, women grew increasingly emboldened to engage in political forms of resistance. By 1987, women had formed the Seoul City Association of the Evacuated Urban Poor to address their grievances over being dislocated (Moon, 2002a, p. 482). Protest activity by the group was met with disapproval by the general public, seeing it as incongruous with the polite and quiet expectations of women (Moon, 2002b).

That said, when the KWAU, a prominent association of women's organizations, joined the National Federal of Nationalistic and Democratic Movements (NFNDM), a democracy-promoting association comprised primarily of men, KWAU were denounced for being too moderate in their approach to challenge entrenched political structures (Moon, 2002a, p.482). The women were fixed to a position where they were too radical for civil society's expectations of them, but too moderate to activist groups. The women's grievances with gender inequality were therefore not linked to the lexicon of democratic reform or rights-based discourse coming out of the Western liberal epistemology—to the contrary, it has emboldened them to find methods of resistance. Rather, their grievances rested in very cultural understandings of the expectations of women. Deeply rooted gender norms informed a highly masculinized civil society that still made it difficult for women to fully participate in public activism (Moon, 2002a, pp. 473–500). Thus, Western Feminism has engaged itself in an intimate relationship with colonial projects by universalizing a regionalized experience, at the expense of a transnational feminist vision.

The emphasis on the *tianxia* (天下) worldview and harmony in Qin's Relational Theory has potential to offer a truly transnational feminist interpretation of gender order (Qin, 2016). At its core, the *tianxia* worldview advances an understanding of world politics as capable of constituting "the exclusion of nothing and no one" (Feng, 2005, p. 109). Basing *tianxia* on the idea of human nature found in the *zhongyong* dialectic, no two entities are intrinsically antithetical, making the *tianxia* worldview a geographically expansive project. Further to this, as *tianxia's* focal point is relations, effective governance is recognized as the ability to manage relations between entities, to the extent that the state of relations can be viewed as harmonious amongst a polity. This helps advance a transnational feminist project

more so than Western Feminism in two ways. Firstly, where rules-based governance has been the primary target of criticism in Western feminism to challenge rights and laws, governance based on managing relations goes beyond this. Secondly, markers of failed governance are indicated by a failure to appropriately manage these relations, as opposed to conceptions of order as a law-abiding polity. Qin's Relational Theory can thus account for sites of epistemic and cultural violence against women, where Western Liberal Feminism has only been concerned with legal injustice against women. Relational Chinese IR thus makes a useful contribution, both to the transnational feminist vision that current relational thinking in the West doesn't offer, as well as more broadly helping to trouble exclusive West/non-West binary logics that have been reproduced by current IR theory (Acharya and Buzan, 2009). That is to say, Relational Theory's vision of harmony as the state of nature can not only provide a useful entry point into the theoretical incorporation of hitherto labeled non-West IR theories into the mainstream, but also the practical emancipation of a collective that is too often excluded by the Western vision of emancipatory success based on rights. In Qin's words, inclusivity is the route to transformative "progress, co-evolution, and sustainable order" (Qin, 2016, p. 45).

Conclusion

This paper has argued that Qin's Relational Theory offers a convincing account of world politics by wielding an explanatory capacity that (1) empirically transcends its cultural Confucian roots and (2) can offer explanations for policy questions that much of mainstream IR cannot. Firstly, Relational Theory can explain the limitations of the EU CFSP through a relational analysis *between* institutions that Constructivism doesn't offer. Secondly, Relational Theory gives a comprehensive account of regional dynamics between Western states where the English School pays little attention to regionalism. Thirdly, where other relational theories of IR, such as Liberal Feminism, universalize a culturally

specific project of emancipation that risks ignoring other forms of oppression, Relational Theory's vision of transnational feminism moves beyond the troubling of legal/institutional sites by recognizing cultural/religious violence. Qin's Relational Theory can make a significant contribution beyond its cultural origins, providing intellectual contributions that are indispensable to the mainstream IR canon. Much of the theoretical groundwork has been laid to convincingly testify to the internal cogence of Qin Yaqing's Relational Theory of World Politics (Acharya & Buzan, 2019; Nordin et al., 2019; Qin, 2016;). However, there remains significant scope to prove Relational Theory's explanatory capacity in the empirical realm. Although this paper provides an empirical illustration of Relational Theory's explanatory strengths, its scope is intentionally narrow, having to engage with both the theoretical/conceptual, and the empirical. Future research is needed to build on this foundation and fully explore the theory's broader applicability beyond its Confucian origin. Further inquiry into (1) the applicability of Qin's relational framework across diverse regional contexts, (2) how regional organizations reflect relational principles versus rule-based (liberal) structures, and if they do not, (3) how Qin's concept of harmony with difference can inform global governance models, particularly in relation to inter-state mediation. Only then, by paying Qin's Relational Theory due diligence, conditions for a global IR can begin to be satisfied (Acharya and Buzan, 2019, pp. 285–320).

References

- Acharya, A., & Buzan, B. (Eds.). (2009). *Non-Western international relations theory: Perspectives on and beyond Asia*. Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203861431>
- Acharya, A., & Buzan, B. (2019). Towards global international relations. In A. Acharya & B. Buzan (Eds.), *The making of global international relations: Origins and Evolution of IR at its Centenary* (pp. 285–320). Cambridge University Press.
- Adler, E., & Barnett, M. (1998). Security communities in theoretical perspective. In E. Adler & M. Barnett (Eds.), *Security Communities* (1st ed., pp. 3–28). Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511598661>
- Arkan, Z. (2014). "Via media" vs. the critical path: Constructivism(s) and the case of EU identity. *All Azimuth: A Journal of Foreign Policy and Peace*, 3(2), 21–36.
<https://doi.org/10.20991/allazimuth.167325>
- Babones, S. (2017). Taking China seriously: Relationally, Tianxia, and the "Chinese School" of international relations. In W. Thompson, *Encyclopedia of Empirical International Relations Theory* (pp. 1–16). Oxford University Press.
- Baraggia, A., & Bonelli, M. (2022). Linking money to values: The new rule of law conditionality regulation and its constitutional challenges. *German Law Journal*, 23(2), 131–156.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/glj.2022.17>
- Berenskoetter, F. (2007). Friends, there are no friends? An intimate reframing of the international. *Millennium: Journal of International Studies*, 35(3), 647–676.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/03058298070350031501>
- Callahan, W. A. (2008). Chinese Visions of World Order: Post-hegemonic or a new hegemony? *International Studies Review*, 10(4), 749–761.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2486.2008.00830.x>
- Checkel, J. T. (1998). The Constructive turn in international relations theory. *World Politics*, 50(2), 324–348.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S004388710008133>
- Choi, I. (2022). On being Chinese and being

- complexified: Chinese IR as a transcultural project. *Review of International Studies*, 49(3), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s026021052000481>
- Cox, R. (1981). Social forces, states and world orders: Beyond international relations theory. *Millennium: Journal of International Studies*, 10(2), 126–155. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03058298810100020501>
- Denza, E. (2002). *The intergovernmental pillars of the European Union*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198299356.001.0001>
- Feng, Z. (2005). *The Tianxia system: World order in a Chinese utopia* [Review of *The Tianxia System: An Introduction to the philosophy of a world institution*, by Z. Tingyang]. 1–160.
- Finnemore, M. (2001). Exporting the English School? *Review of International Studies*, 27(3). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210501005095>
- Finnemore, M., & Sikkink, K. (1998). International norm dynamics and political change. *International Organization*, 52(4), 887–917. <https://doi.org/10.1162/002081898550789>
- Hoffmann, S. (1977). An American social science: International relations. In J. Der Derian (Ed.), *International Theory* (pp. 212–241). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-23773-9_9
- Jiang, S. (2018). Yaqing Qin, A relational theory of world politics. *Journal of Chinese Political Science*, 24(1), 171–172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11366-018-9578-z>
- Jupille, J., Caporaso, J. A., & Checkel, J. T. (2003). Integrating institutions: Rationalism, Constructivism, and the study of the European Union. *Comparative Political Studies*, 36(1-2), 7–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0010414002239370>
- Kang, D. C. (2012). *East Asia before the West: Five centuries of trade and tribute*. Columbia University Press.
- Kavalski, E. (2017). *The Guanxi Of relational international theory*. Routledge. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4324/9781315109657>
- Kipling, R. (1899). *Ballad of East and West*. Mansfield and Wessels.
- Kos, U. A. (2023). Signalling in European rule of law cases: Hungary and Poland as case studies. *Human Rights Law Review*, 23(4), 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hrlr/ngad035>
- March, J. G., & Olsen, J. P. (1998). The institutional dynamics of international political orders. *International Organization*, 52(4), 943–969. <https://doi.org/10.1162/002081898550699>
- Mohanty, C. (1988). Under Western eyes: Feminist scholarship and colonial discourses. *Feminist Review*, 30(1), 61–88. <https://doi.org/10.1057/fr.1988.42>
- Moon, S. (2002a). Carving out space: Civil society and the women’s movement in South Korea. *The Journal of Asian Studies*, 61(2), 473–500. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2700298>
- Moon, S. (2002b). Women and democratization in the Republic of Korea. *The Good Society*, 11(3), 36–42. <https://doi.org/10.1353/gso.2003.0012>
- Nicoli, F. (2019). Neofunctionalism revisited: integration theory and varieties of outcomes in the Eurocrisis. *Journal of European Integration*, 42(7), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2019.1670658>
- Nordin, A., Smith, G., Bunskoek, R., Huang, C., Hwang, Y., Thaddeus Jackson, P., Kavalski, E., Ling, L., Martindale, L., Nakamura, M., Nexon, D., Premack, L., Qin, Y., Shih, C., Tyfield, D., Williams, E., Zalewski, M (2019). *Towards global relational*

- theorizing: A dialogue between Sinophone and Anglophone scholarship on relationalism. *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, 32(5), 570–581. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09557571.2019.1643978>
- Nordin, A., & Smith, G. (2018). Reintroducing friendship to international relations: relational ontologies from China to the West. *International Relations of the Asia-Pacific*, 18(3), 369–396. <https://doi.org/10.1093/irap/lcy011>
- Parashar, S. (2016). Feminism and Postcolonialism: (En)gendering encounters. *Postcolonial Studies*, 19(4), 371–377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13688790.2016.1317388>
- Pollack, M. A. (2005). Theorizing the European Union: International organization, domestic polity, or experiment in new governance? *Annual Review of Political Science*, 8(1), 357–398. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.polisci.8.082103.104858>
- Price, R., & Reus-Smit, C. (1998). Dangerous liaisons? *European Journal of International Relations*, 4(3), 259–294. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354066198004003001>
- Qin, Y. (2016). A relational theory of world politics. *International Studies Review*, 18(1), 33–47. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24758336>
- Qin, Y. (2018). *A relational theory of world politics*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316869505>
- Qin, Y. (2024). The Zhongyong dialectic: A bridge into the relational world. *The Chinese Journal of International Politics*, 17(2), 206–221. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjip/poae011>
- Qin, Y., & Nordin, A. H. M. (2019). Relationality and rationality in Confucian and Western traditions of thought. *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, 32(5), 601–614. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09557571.2019.1641470>
- Raspa, V. (2016). What makes a thing what it is? Aristotle and Hegel on identity. *Acta Analytica*, 31(4), 345–361. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12136-016-0287-y>
- Risse-Kappen, T. (2010). *A Community of Europeans?: Transnational identities and public spheres*. Cornell University Press.
- Shin, H. B. (2017). Urban movements and the genealogy of urban rights discourses: The case of urban protesters against redevelopment and displacement in Seoul, South Korea. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 108(2), 356–369. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2017.1392844>
- Stivachtis, Y. (2014). The regional dimension of international society. In *Guide to the English School in International Studies* (pp. 1–246). WILEY Blackwell.
- Spivak, G. C. (1981). French feminism in an international frame. *Yale French Studies*, 62, 154–184. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2929898>
- Spivak, G. C. (1985). Three women's texts and a critique of imperialism. *Critical Inquiry*, 12(1), 243–261. <https://doi.org/10.1086/448328>
- Guzzini, Stefano. (2024). Relationalism(s) unpacked: Engaging Yaqing Qin's theory of world politics. *The Chinese Journal of International Politics*, 17(2), 187–205. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjip/poae010>
- Wang, J., & Buzan, B. (2014). The English and Chinese schools of international relations: Comparisons and lessons. *The Chinese Journal of International Politics*, 7(1), 1–46. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjip/pot017>
- Wendt, Alexander. (1999). "Ideas all the way down?": On the constitution of power and interest. In *Social Theory of International Politics* (pp. 92–138). Cambridge University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511612183.004>

Zalewski, M. (1996). "All these theories yet the bodies keep piling up": theories, theorists, theorising. In *International Theory: Positivism and Beyond* (pp. 340–353). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511660054.020>

Zhao, T. (2009). A Political World Philosophy in terms of All-under-heaven (Tianxia). *Diogenes*, 56(1), 5–18. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0392192109102149>

Carys Hosking

caryshosking74@gmail.com

Carys Hosking is a recent graduate of King's College London, where she earned a BA (Hons) in International Relations and received the Professor Jack Spence Award for her exceptional academic performance during her time there. Specializing in East Asian affairs, her interest in geopolitical developments in the Indo-Pacific is complemented by her study of Chinese philosophy, which led her to complete the Hudson Institute's Political Studies Program in Washington, D.C in 2023. As an intelligence analyst, she has provided actionable insights on a broad range of complex and evolving threats affecting various stakeholders.

Clashing Paradigms and Converging Imperatives of EU-China Climate Diplomacy in the Anthropocene

Tin Maung HTWE

Abstract

The intersection of ideological paradigms and strategic state interests defines global climate governance. Nowhere is this dynamic more evident than in the climate diplomacy of the European Union (EU) and China, as these two dominant actors navigate the Anthropocene from vastly different governance traditions. The EU seeks to universalize climate norms through liberal-oriented regulatory mechanisms such as the European Green Deal and the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), positioning itself as the architect of a rules-based global environmental order. In contrast, China adopts a state-capitalist approach, leveraging ecological modernization as a strategic tool for geopolitical and economic expansion through green infrastructure investments in the Global South.

Employing a Constructivist framework, this paper investigates these contrasting models—one normative, the other pragmatic—and reflects on the deeper ideological currents shaping the evolution of climate governance. While both actors acknowledge the existential imperative of decarbonization, their approaches diverge on key issues. Carbon pricing, renewable energy competition and sovereignty in transnational regulatory frameworks are debatable issues in global green governance, as the EU's commitment to binding multilateralism often clashes with China's insistence on policy autonomy. This paper argues that EU-China climate diplomacy serves as a test case for whether the liberal international order can absorb competing models or must evolve into a hybrid framework. Reconciling normative ambition with pragmatic leadership, the climate

governance of China and the EU becomes an arena for geopolitical influence. Therefore, this paper argues that the trajectory of EU-China engagement will not only shape future decarbonization strategies but also redefine the balance of power in an era of ecological crisis.

Keywords: EU-China relations, green diplomacy, climate leadership, CBAM, constructivism, renewable energy, carbon trade policy

Introduction

The Anthropocene is defined as the epoch in which humanity's imprint on the planet has become the dominant force driving geological and ecological transformation (Davies, 2016). As Koyzis (2019) argues, the belief that politics and economics function independently of nature is a long-standing illusion. In reality, nature forms the foundation of both political and economic systems, shaping everything from governance structures to global markets (Dryzek, 2022). Environmental degradation has increasingly exposed the fundamental contradiction at the heart of the international system: while environmental problems are transboundary, political authority remains state-based. Democratic governance, in particular, faces structural limitations in addressing climate change, due to its short-term focus and susceptibility to special interest influence (Shearman & Smith, 2007). Compounding these challenges, the principle of state sovereignty over nature continues to hinder the effectiveness of international climate regulations (Olsen, 2023).

Exceeding the 1.5°C threshold outlined in the Paris Agreement will unleash irreversible ecological and societal upheaval (Bendell & Read, 2021). According to the Copernicus Climate Change Service (2024, para. 2), 2024 has been confirmed as the first year in which

global temperatures surpassed 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels. In this unfolding crisis, the European Union (EU) and China have emerged as central actors in shaping the trajectory of global climate governance (Liu & Wu, 2021), given their worldwide economic and economic impact (Zhu et al., 2024). Yet, the divergence in their approaches reveals a deeper ideological struggle. The EU universalizes climate norms through multilateral frameworks, regulatory mechanisms, and legally binding commitments under the tradition of liberal institutionalism. International organizations adopt liberal norms primarily due to strategic incentives and legitimacy concerns (Tallberg et al., 2020). The European Green Deal Framework and the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), two of the EU's hallmark environmental policies, illustrate its ambition to make climate governance an extension of European normative power (Sampson & Theuns, 2023; Leonard et al., 2021). On the one hand, CBAM is designed to prevent carbon leakage while ensuring compliance with WTO rules (Leal-Arcas et al., 2022, p. 5). By institutionalizing climate initiatives and leveraging multilateral frameworks, the EU positions its environmental standards as universal norms, expecting global convergence toward its model of climate responsibility (Kopra, 2018). In contrast, China's model of state-capitalist pragmatism treats ecological modernization not as a moral imperative, but as a strategic instrument for economic expansion, and it is through this in which China develops energy security and geopolitical influence in the global market (Hug, 2024). While China leads the world in renewable energy investment, EV production, and solar panel manufacturing (Nakano, 2021), it simultaneously expands coal power capacity in the Global South (Hassan et al., 2024). This dual-track strategy underscores the fundamental distinction between climate governance as a normative project versus climate policy as a tool of economic statecraft. Employing a Constructivist framework, this

paper argues that these contrasting approaches reflect the deeper ideological currents shaping global governance and correspond to deeper ideological and identity-based contestations over global climate leadership. The contest between these paradigms is not merely about carbon pricing or renewable energy markets, but about shaping the emerging global world order. Disagreements over CBAM's impact on Chinese exports are turning into a race to leading battery and solar supply chains (Meng, 2024). However, despite these tensions, both actors share a core belief: decarbonization is inevitable. The challenge, then, is whether the existing liberal framework can adapt to accommodate China's state-driven model or whether climate governance itself will evolve into a hybrid system that reconciles normative ambition with pragmatic leadership. As the Anthropocene forces states to reimagine sovereignty, economy, and cooperation, the EU-China dynamic shall serve as a test case for the future of international climate diplomacy, and by extension, the future of the global order itself.

1. A Constructivist Analysis of EU-China Climate Diplomacy

The study of EU-China climate diplomacy reveals an evolving contest over governance models in international relations. Unlike realist accounts that reduce diplomacy to power struggles or liberal narratives that assume institutional convergence, constructivism frames climate governance as a dynamic social process (Pease, 2018). The U.S., the EU, and China negotiate their respective roles within an emerging normative order (Ross et al., 2010). Norms, identity, and social interaction shape diplomatic engagement (Zehfuss, 2002). Ideational factors of states often underestimate the enduring role of economic interests, power asymmetries, and geopolitical competition (Rueda, 2023). Bell and Hindmoor (2009) argue that despite neoliberal trends, the state remains central to governance and policy-making in modern societies. Political asymmetry plays a critical role in shaping the modern state's governance and development trajectories

(Oberthür & Dupont, 2021). Emphasizing national priorities such as energy security, economic modernization, and social stability, China's approach to sustainable development embodies strategic pragmatism. Rather than rejecting global norms outright, China selectively engages with international regulatory frameworks in ways that reinforce its domestic development agenda through reflecting a state-centric model of governance rather than a normative alignment with multilateral standards (Moore, 2022; Zhang, 2021). At its core, EU-China climate diplomacy is not merely about the spread of environmental norms but a broader contest over who has the power to define and control the framework of global climate governance.

Alexander Wendt's *Social Theory of International Politics* (1999) provides a valuable foundation for this discussion, positing that international relations are socially constructed through state interaction rather than determined by material structures alone. His assertion that "anarchy is what states make of it" suggests that climate diplomacy is shaped by evolving norms rather than fixed geopolitical realities (Art et al., 2023). However, this perspective risks overstating the degree to which norms drive state behavior (Beeson, 2021). While the EU pursues a vision of climate governance rooted in rule-based multilateralism (Lazard & Youngs, 2021), China engages in what might be called strategic norm adaptation (Peña, 2020). Esteban and Lin (2023) examine that China navigates and influences international norms through the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Through investments, China leverages sustainability discourse for economic (Economy & Levi, 2014) and political advantage while maintaining sovereignty over regulatory implementation (Sun, 2022). The problem here is twofold. First, a transition by China from its conventional prioritization of sovereignty and non-interference to a normative foreign policy framework would expose it to complex policy dilemmas (Mazarr

et al., 2021). Second, constructivism's focus on identity and norm evolution often overlooks the material asymmetries that define EU-China relations, particularly China's dominance in critical minerals, green technology supply chains, and climate finance (Ralph, 2023). Patey (2024) argues that the EU must take proactive measures to reduce its dependence on China for critical minerals essential to green energy technologies. The EU heavily relies on China for solar panels, permanent magnets, and other critical components necessary for its green transition (Rietveld et al., 2022).

Martha Finnemore and Kathryn Sikkink (1998) add nuance that norms evolve through emergence, cascade, and internalization. The EU actively positions itself as a *norm entrepreneur* (Zwolski & Kaunert, 2011). The EU embeds climate governance into its broader regulatory and trade frameworks, enhancing climate security and promoting environmental norms. China, in turn, engages in *norm localization* (Acharya 2004; Yang, 2022) through selectively incorporating global norms (Repnikova, 2022) into domestic policy while resisting external oversight (Mavraganis, 2021; Potter, 2021). Its 2060 carbon neutrality pledge in terms of energy flexibility and policy adaptation (Li et al., 2022) appears to align with EU-led climate commitments (Ferenczy, 2019; Schunz, 2021). Such an approach remains embedded in a *developmental environmentalism* model (Nakai, 2025) that prioritizes economic modernization alongside decarbonization (Thurbon et al., 2023). China's ambition plays a pivotal role in accelerating green energy transformation through targeted industrial policies.

While constructivist approaches highlight the social construction of norms, they often overlook how norms can be strategically instrumentalized by states. Yet at the same time, some norms evolve independently of great power influence, creating a tension that remains underexplored (Bower, 2016; Feenberg, 2022). China's engagement with climate diplomacy is not a function of deep normative transformation, but

a strategic move to position itself as a leader in green technology and renewable energy markets without direct confrontation (Yıldırımçakar, 2024). In global climate governance, China's leadership increasingly engages with the principle of Common but Differentiated Responsibilities (CBDRs). The decision is made not only to assert China's role as a responsible power, but also to legitimize differentiated obligations that accommodate its continued economic development and strategic interests. This approach allows China to uphold international climate norms while protecting its policy autonomy, ensuring it can meet domestic growth targets and maintain influence in the Global South (Ferenczy, 2019; Jiang, 2022; Lian & Li, 2024). This divergence illustrates a key limitation in constructivist scholarship. While this perspective acknowledges that norms shape state behavior, the China-EU dynamic reveals its limitations in explaining instances where norm adoption is driven more by strategic interests than by genuine ideological commitment. However, this approach remains valid for understanding the China-EU relationship in green development because both actors engage with and reinterpret climate norms (Xing, 2021) to align with their broader geopolitical and economic interests (Xia, 2024).

Peter Katzenstein's work on identity politics (1996) provides further insight into China's selective engagement with global climate norms. Constructivists often assume that sustained diplomatic interaction leads to norm internalization, yet China's state-centric governance and postcolonial sovereignty concerns create a fundamentally different epistemological approach to climate diplomacy. The EU's strategic use of soft power in international cultural relations continues to evolve in response to global shifts (Szucs, 2023). Meanwhile, China leverages normative power as a tool to counter Western dominance and advocate for an alternative global order (Yıldırımçakar, 2024). Emanuel

Adler (2019) shifts the discussion from formal norms to shared practices as drivers of cooperation.

Despite ideological differences, the EU and China share a nuanced relationship, collaborating in multiple areas. EU-China joint-efforts in green technology, infrastructure development, and emissions reduction fosters a form of functional interdependence (Zaman, 2023), wherein both actors pursue distinct yet complementary strategies to advance green innovation and achieve shared sustainability goals (Illynskyy et al., 2024). The trilateral energy cooperation framework among China, the EU, and the U.S. has evolved in tandem with global environmental governance efforts (Podriez & Zhukov, 2022). Joint ventures in solar energy, electric vehicles, and carbon trading platforms demonstrate that economic and technological engagement fosters climate governance, even in the absence of shared regulatory commitments (Cai, 2023). However, this perspective risks an overly optimistic reading of cooperation (Sattich et al., 2021).

Oran Young (2011) highlights another key structural tension. The EU's regulatory emphasis on carbon pricing and legal frameworks frequently clashes with China's preference for bilateral partnerships and state-led innovation (Boute & Zhang 2018). China's dominance in rare earth minerals and renewable energy supply chains creates a dependency that the EU cannot easily offset (Kalantzakos, 2017). Global climate governance is geo-economic rivalry rather than normative convergence (Ji, 2021). Constructivism tends to assume that norm diffusion is a cooperative process; however, in practice, climate diplomacy has become an arena for strategic competition (Oh & Matsuoka, 2017). China's investments in renewables are not simply an expression of environmental responsibility but a means of consolidating economic leadership (Bengtsson, 2022; D. Wang et al., 2024). Jeffrey Checkel (1997) provides a counterpoint that the diffusion of international norms is contingent upon domestic political

structures and elite perceptions. Suggesting sustained engagement can foster deeper norm internalization over time, EU-China climate dialogues may function as platforms for persuasion and knowledge exchange (Dupont et al., 2023). However, persuasion theory assumes that China will eventually converge with EU climate governance standards (Wunderlich, 2020). This paper adopts the view that norm diffusion operates primarily as a cooperative process embedded in shared understandings and mutual engagement, rather than merely as a site of political contestation. While norms and identities significantly influence international diplomacy, they are shaped by and situated within broader structural and strategic contexts (Payne & Samhat, 2004). Climate diplomacy is not simply an arena for cooperation, but is an arena where competing governance models, economic interests, and political identities collide. The challenge for constructivism is to reconcile its focus on social interaction with a more rigorous account of material power, economic interdependence, and geopolitical strategy (Guzzini, 2000). In an era of climate crisis, understanding these tensions is crucial. This understanding is not essential just for EU-China relations but for the future of global governance itself.

2. The EU's Normative Framework in Climate Diplomacy Constructivist Analysis of EU-China Climate Diplomacy

2.1 Ideological Foundations of the EU's Green Leadership

In the post-Cold War era, the EU has sought to lead through regulatory influence and the projection of liberal norms (Gheciu, 2005). The transition from bipolarity to a new international order required European states to undertake strategic recalibrations, utilizing institutional frameworks to navigate shifting power dynamics (Keohane et al., 1993). European governments leveraged these structures to reconcile national interests with

broader collective stability through cooperative mechanisms rather than unilateral action (Keohane et al., 1993). Lacking traditional hard power capabilities in each state, the European Union's climate diplomacy is best understood as an extension of its broader ideological commitment to multilateralism, democratic governance, and a rules-based international order (Creutz et al., 2019). From this perspective, European climate governance is not merely a matter of policy, but rather leads to both synergy and conflict in global governance (Oberthür & Gehring, 2006). This institutionalized commitment to legally binding agreements enforces processes through multilateral mechanisms that contribute to climate governance and integration in EU institutions (Rietig, 2021). Unlike China's instrumentalist approach to climate policy that functions as a tool for economic expansion and geopolitical leverage (Heggelund, 2021), the EU embeds sustainability within a normative framework (Schunz, 2021). The policies of the European Union seek to universalize environmental responsibility as a core principle of global governance (Xing, 2021).

Launched in 2019, the European Green Deal exemplifies this approach (Durmaz, 2024). More than a domestic transition plan, it functions as a blueprint for global climate governance to reinforce the EU's role as a regulatory superpower (Graham & Yilmaz, 2023). The implementation of the Green Deal (Beatriz, 2024) through initiatives like the 2022 REPowerEU Plan accelerated in response to Russia's invasion of Ukraine, and the impact on the global green transition efforts changes the external dimensions of the European Green Deal itself (Medinilla et al., 2022). The EU adapted its sustainability agenda to accommodate shifting geopolitical conditions, exemplified by energy policies, which requires balancing between green ambitions and geopolitical dependencies on Russian fossil fuels (Siddi, 2023). Embedding green policies into trade, foreign aid, and investment frameworks, the EU positions itself as a counterweight to both China's state-led climate modernization and the U.S.' subsidy-driven

Inflation Reduction Act (IRA). The IRA represents a major shift in industrial and climate policy, challenging the EU's competitiveness and regulatory approach (Suárez-Cuesta & Latorre, 2024). The European Green Deal inadvertently shifts environmental burdens to other countries and raises concerns about sustainability and global justice (Fuchs et al., 2020).

One of the most tangible demonstrations of the EU's green leadership is its investment in cross-border clean energy projects. The North Sea Wind Power Hub renewable energy project between the Netherlands, Germany, and Denmark underscores the EU's ambition to integrate regional energy markets and reduce dependency on fossil fuels (Verkooijen, 2024). These offshore hybrid projects play a pivotal role in advancing Europe's energy transition by improving cross-border electricity transmission. By fostering collaboration among Member States and external partners, the project aligns with the EU's commitment to regional decarbonization and regulatory coherence (Leal-Arcas, 2024). However, particularly in the context of REPowerEU and internal market integration, the challenges stemming from intergovernmental coordination delay, lack of funding, and achieving strategic autonomy in the EU's energy market highlight the complexities of executing large-scale sustainability projects within a diverse political and economic bloc (Hancher & De Hauteclouque, 2024).

Additionally, CBAM entered its transitional phase in October 2023, integrating climate policies within its economic and regulatory frameworks. CBAM is crucial for economic governance and highlights the EU's efforts to ensure a level playing field in global carbon pricing (Kendrick, 2024). By mitigating internal policy negotiations and external geopolitical pressures (Wettestad, 2024), CBAM represents a fundamental assertion of the EU's regulatory reach through the

imposition of carbon tariffs on imports in high-emission sectors, such as steel, cement, and fertilizers. While framed as an instrument to curb carbon leakage and incentivize global carbon pricing (Jonassen et al., 2023), it has provoked resistance from major trading partners, including China, India, and Brazil (Kareckaite, 2020). This approach obscures economic protectionism yet strengthens institutionalized approaches to global governance (Delimatsis, 2023). The EU defends CBAM as a necessary measure to uphold its climate commitments while ensuring fair competition in a decarbonizing global economy (Delbeke, 2024).

However, the EU's ability to consolidate its climate leadership remains constrained by internal and external challenges. Domestically, Member States remain divided over the pace and scope of climate action. Germany and Denmark have been advocating for aggressive decarbonization through free-market environmentalism (Wang & Zhao 2021), whereas Poland, the Czech Republic, and Hungary resist measures perceived as economically burdensome (Kalistová & Huttmanová, 2020). Particularly in Central and Eastern Europe, public engagement in the European Green Deal remains a structural weakness, limiting societal participation in climate initiatives (Nagy et al., 2025). Populism is an additional factor that impacts climate politics in EU countries: climate change narratives in populist political contexts often prioritize national interests over transnational cooperation, thereby shaping public discourse and policy making (Gruber, 2025). The results indicate that economic expansion in the EU remains coupled with rising CO₂ emissions and still necessitates stronger policy interventions (Onofrei et al., 2022). Public support for climate policies in the EU has grown significantly following the Paris Agreement. Yet tangible climate actions remain uneven across EU Member States (Schwerdtle et al., 2023). Meanwhile, the EU finds itself in a delicate balancing act on the external front.

The introduction of CBAM has led to diplomatic

tensions with China and many Global South countries (Erdogdu, 2025). Because their manufacturing sectors rely heavily on carbon-intensive energy sources, China, India, and much of the Global South face increased costs and trade barriers under CBAM (Gupta et al., 2024). CBAM could serve as a crucial incentive for global decarbonization (Dev & Goswami, 2024), but its success depends on international cooperation and equitable policy implementation (Sejdiu, 2023). In response, China has intensified its push for renewable energy investment.

With the launch of the China Green Manufacturing Plan in 2023, China aims to lower emissions in its heavy industries. China's strategies for achieving carbon peak and carbon neutrality emphasize policy measures, technological innovations and economic incentives (Liu et al., 2023). Moreover, the concentration of high-tech industries fosters innovation-driven sustainable growth in China's manufacturing sector (Song et al., 2023). India has also sought exemptions and trade negotiations with the European Union to mitigate CBAM's impact on its export sectors, particularly in steel and cement. The associated impact on India's export sectors includes increased compliance costs, reduced competitiveness of carbon-intensive industries such as steel, cement, and aluminum, and pressure to accelerate the country's low-carbon transition (Sharma & Gupta, 2022). Similarly, Brazil has intensified its efforts to decarbonize its industrial and agricultural exports. Brazil's green agricultural policies seek to balance between economic growth and environmental sustainability (Piao et al., 2021) by expanding its carbon credit market and advancing policies under the Amazon Green Economy Plan (Alves et al., 2024). The country is leveraging its biofuels sector—including ethanol and biodiesel—as a strategic response to CBAM (Follador et al., 2021). These cases illustrate the complex geopolitical implications of the EU's climate regulatory framework. They also demonstrate

that while the EU may set ambitious norms, the global response is shaped by competing economic and political interests. Dev and Goswami (2024) analyze that the Global South is responding to CBAM and its impact on international trade relations. The European Green Deal not only reshapes internal EU policies but also projects environmental standards onto global trade and governance structures (Eritja & Fernández-Pons, 2024). The EU's environmental policies reflect a growing ideological shift towards sustainability as a core political priority (Hörber & Weber, 2021). The shift from fossil fuels to renewables is not only an environmental necessity, but also a major geopolitical transformation that affects global alliances (Hafner & Tagliapietra, 2020).

Positioned as a sustainable alternative to China's BRI, the EU's Global Gateway initiative underscores these competitive dynamics in respective regions (Tagliapietra, 2024). However, its implementation in regions like Africa and Latin America highlights the inherent tensions between normative aspirations and geopolitical realities (Heldt, 2023). For example, in Kenya, the EU has funded renewable energy projects as part of its broader efforts to drive green investment in the Global South (Rotich et al., 2024). At the same time, due to more flexible financing options than the EU, China has aggressively expanded its solar and hydroelectric projects under the BRI framework (Di Ciommo et al., 2024). Moreover, the EU's Mercosur trade agreement also seeks to impose stricter environmental regulations (Palmieri et al., 2024). As a result, this agreement faces pushback from Brazilian agribusiness lobbies and delays in ratification (Arima et al., 2021). This scenario highlights the limitations of regulatory diplomacy when confronted with entrenched economic interests that are resistant to rapid change. The juxtaposition of these strategies raises questions about the effectiveness of the EU's normative approach in regions where economic pragmatism often outweighs regulatory alignment.

2.2 Institutionalizing Climate Norms

The European Union's climate diplomacy is an extension of its broader commitment to institutionalized multilateralism (Anderson et al., 2024). Leveraging global platforms such as the UNFCCC, the G20, and the WTO, the EU and international trade policies are adapting to environmental and social sustainability demands and shaping future economic agreements and global trade norms (Vidigal & Claussen, 2024). Unlike ad hoc or bilateral approaches to environmental governance, the EU operates within a structured regulatory framework to universalize climate action as an essential pillar of the international order (Oberthür, 2019). The EU's climate leadership has been marked by institutional continuity and strategic multilateralism. Its pivotal role in negotiating the Paris Agreement (2015) demonstrated the bloc's capacity to institutionalize long-term climate commitments (Beaudoin, 2024). In 2021, the EU spearheaded the Global Methane Pledge, using coalition-building to drive international policy consensus (Görlach et al., 2024). At COP27 (2022), its advocacy for the Loss and Damage Fund reinforced its normative power in addressing climate-induced vulnerabilities through institutional mechanisms (Kristensen, 2023). At COP28 (2023), the EU played a key role in advancing the first-ever global commitment to "transition away" from fossil fuels, reaffirming its leadership in global climate governance (Mesarović, 2024). While lacking formal enforcement mechanisms, it reflects the EU's broader strategy of shaping global climate governance through normative influence and institutional agenda-setting (Wurzel et al., 2019). Beyond multilateral forums, the EU extends its climate influence through economic instruments. By integrating environmental clauses into trade agreements, the EU leverages economic power to institutionalize climate commitments within global trade (Brandi & Morin, 2023). This approach reflects a broader strategy of regulatory statecraft and extends European

governance beyond its borders through reinforcing the alignment of trade with sustainability objectives (Eliasson & Garcia-Duran, 2024).

Regionally, the EU has codified its climate commitments and reinforced its self-perception as a regulatory superpower (Oberthür, & Dupont, 2021). The European Climate Law (2021) legally enshrined the bloc's commitment to reducing emissions by 55% by 2030 (compared to 1990 levels) and achieving net zero by 2050 (Dutov, 2024). An example of this is the Fit for 55 Package, which operationalizes these goals through systemic reforms (Schlacke et al., 2022). The Package calls for building a strengthened EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) and fostering stricter CO₂ standards for vehicles (Pahle et al., 2023). Such efforts are accompanied by the creation of a Social Climate Fund to mitigate energy poverty (Štreimikienė et al., 2020). This regulatory architecture extends beyond Europe's borders, with the EU actively promoting global carbon pricing models (Wang & Zhao, 2021). China, for instance, launched its national ETS in 2021, reflecting Europe's influence in shaping global carbon market structures (Wang, 2022). The China National Emission Trading System (CETS) proposes a linkage framework based on global carbon market experiences of climate governance, emissions trading, and carbon pricing strategies (Pan et al., 2021). However, resistance persists, particularly among fossil fuel-dependent economies in Africa and the Middle East. In those regions, EU climate policies are perceived as prioritizing European economic interests over developmental needs (Nathaniel et al., 2020).

Yet, as the EU seeks to position itself as the world's climate regulator, it faces growing geopolitical and economic headwinds. The U.S. IRA, with its \$369 billion in green subsidies, has triggered fears of a European industrial decline. In reaction to measures taken by the U.S., the EU announced the Green Deal Industrial Plan (2023), safeguarding its domestic clean tech manufacturing sector (Suárez-Cuesta & Latorre,

2024). The EU's CBAM imposes carbon tariffs on imports from high-emission industries (Pietzcker et al., 2021) and has further exacerbated tensions with China and other major emerging economies. Hackenbroich, et al. (2022) argue that such measures amount to economic coercion rather than genuine climate cooperation. Many governments of the Global South see the EU's regulatory approach as disproportionately burdening developing economies. Bearing historical responsibility for climate change, this friction underscores a fundamental challenge in climate diplomacy: the difficulty of reconciling normative ambition with the realities of economic asymmetry and state sovereignty (Magacho et al., 2023).

3. China's Pragmatic Ecological Modernization: A Constructivist Analysis of EU-China Climate Diplomacy

3.1 State-Capitalist Diplomacy

China's approach to climate governance is best understood as a function of its broader political economy. Historically, China was seen as an obstacle in international climate negotiations, but it has transitioned to a more central and constructive role. This change is attributed to both international pressures and domestic policy shifts towards low-carbon economic development (Hilton & Kerr, 2017). In China, the state plays a central role in structuring markets, directing capital, and orchestrating industrial policy in pursuit of strategic objectives (Petry, 2020). Unlike the EU's regulatory frameworks of liberal democracies and environmental policies, which emerge from negotiation between state and civil society (Diez & Von Lucke, 2023), China's climate governance is rooted in the logic of party-state capitalism. This model takes shape as the state maintains ultimate authority over economic direction while selectively incorporating market mechanisms to bolster national competitiveness (Wu et al., 2024b).

At the core of this strategy is the concept of Ecological Civilization, a doctrine embedded in successive Five-Year Plans (FYPs). China frames environmental sustainability as a function of state-led modernization (Gürcan & Donduran, 2024). This is not climate governance as an end in itself, but as an extension of China's national development strategy.

Designed to balance the imperative of economic growth with long-term geopolitical positioning, China aims to achieve peak carbon emissions by 2030 and carbon neutrality by 2060 (Shi et al., 2023; Zhao, 2022). Therefore, its strategy is not a departure from its developmental logic but rather a recalibration. This attempt harnesses the green transition as a means of consolidating power at home and influence abroad. The most striking manifestation of China's climate strategy is its dominance in renewable energy production. Having positioned itself as the leading producer of solar panels, wind turbines, and EV batteries (Saeed & Siraj, 2024), China accounted for nearly half of the world's total renewable energy capacity by 2024 (Hove, 2024). This is not a by-product of free-market competition but a deliberate outcome of state-directed investment, industrial policy, and supply chain control.

Under the framework of the BRI, the construction of massive renewable energy projects such as the Tengger Desert Solar Park in Central China (Peplow, 2018), the Quaid-e-Azam Solar Park in Pakistan (Khosa et al., 2020), and the Lake Turkana Wind Power Project in Kenya (Simberg-Koulumies, 2023) has significantly reshaped the energy mix of their respective countries. These projects reflect China's strategic use of green infrastructure to expand its global influence and reshape the energy mix of the respective countries' energy sources. These investments do more than simply provide energy. They demonstrate both China's ability to mobilize capital on an unprecedented scale, and its capacity to set the global agenda for clean energy development. Through infrastructure diplomacy with the BRI, Beijing has leveraged green finance to expand its economic footprint across the

Global South (Pearson et al., 2023). Under Xi Jinping, the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) positions China as the principal architect of a new global climate order. Challenging the Western-dominated model of environmental governance, Chinese investments offer an alternative and development-driven approach.

For all its progress in renewables, China's climate governance is confronted with contradicting realities, as the country continues to rely on coal. In 2023 alone, China approved over 100 GW of new coal power capacity (Greenpeace East Asia, 2023). However, in early 2024, approvals significantly declined by 79.5%, suggesting a possible shift in energy strategy. Yet, construction of nearly 100 GW of coal power plants in 2024 indicates a persistent reliance on coal for energy security (Moritsugu, 2025). This reflects a deeper reality and distinguishes China from many of its Western counterparts. While liberal democracies often frame environmental policy as a normative commitment rooted in values and global responsibility, China adopts a more pragmatic approach to neighboring the Global South, treating it as a strategic equation tied to economic growth, energy security and technological competitiveness (Friedberg, 2022; Htwe, 2025). China's current approach represents a calculated pragmatism, or whether it signals a gradual shift toward incorporating normative environmental commitments into its broader strategic agenda (Yu, 2024).

Decarbonization must not come at the expense of industrial stability. Expanding green energy while sustaining traditional power sources exemplifies a broader principle of Chinese governance: the prioritization of national stability over external expectations (Yu et al., 2023). For Beijing, climate leadership is not about aligning with international norms, but about shaping them to fit its own strategic imperatives. By dominating the supply chains of green technology, expanding its EV market,

and investing in AI-driven smart grids, China is not merely transitioning toward sustainability; it is also restructuring the global energy system in ways that reinforce its geopolitical standing (Qin et al., 2023).

This is particularly evident in China's engagement with the developing world. Across Africa, Latin America, and Southeast Asia, its renewable energy investments are rapidly outpacing those of the West. Positioning itself as the central actor in the green transformation of emerging economies, China is crafting an alternative model of climate governance. China's climate governance is not about a singular commitment to sustainability but about the broader logic of state capitalism. The use of industrial policy, strategic finance, and technological leadership advances national power (Rikap, 2022). On the other hand, the tension between its vast renewable expansion and its enduring dependence on coal is not contradictory. It is the natural outcome of a system designed to maximize national resilience while gradually reshaping the international order (Liu et al., 2024). How effectively China navigates this contradiction will determine not only its own environmental trajectory but the broader balance of power in the 21st century.

3.2 Strategic Adaptation of Climate Norms

China's engagement with global climate governance through a strategy of selective adaptation and pragmatic assertion reflects its broader approach to international institutions. While an active participant in COP negotiations and a signatory of the Paris Agreement, Beijing resists binding mechanisms that could constrain state sovereignty or disrupt its economic model (Liu, 2024). Unlike the European Union's push for universal climate regulations, China adopts and reshapes international climate norms in ways that align with its state-capitalist framework and long-term industrial strategy (Mtui, 2024). This distinction underscores a fundamental divide in climate governance. Through mechanisms such as concessional loans, technology transfers, and

infrastructure partnerships, China's approach prioritizes state-driven investment over market-based regulation (Beck & Larsen, 2024) and emphasizes developmental pragmatism over normative commitments to environmental justice.

One of the clearest manifestations of this strategic pragmatism is China's approach to carbon pricing. Although Beijing has established the world's largest emissions trading scheme (ETS), covering over 4 billion metric tons of CO₂ (Yan et al., 2025), its carbon pricing remains significantly lower than that of the EU's ETS or U.S. regional markets (Cheng et al., 2023; Zi-Jie & Lu-Tao, 2020). This reflects China's preference for market mechanisms tailored to national priorities, allowing it to balance emissions reductions with industrial competitiveness (L. Wang et al., 2024). Rather than accepting externally imposed regulatory structures, China constructs climate policy on its own terms by integrating market reforms without ceding control over its economic trajectory.

Nowhere is China's climate diplomacy more visible than in the BRI. In response to global scrutiny, China has shifted its focus toward the green transition by prioritizing investments in renewable energy, low-carbon infrastructure, and climate resilience, China has pivoted toward renewable energy, low-carbon infrastructure, and climate resilience investments (Clarke, 2024). By 2023, over 40% of BRI energy projects were directed toward renewables, a dramatic shift from earlier coal-heavy investments. Institutions such as the China Development Bank and the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB) have expanded financing for solar, wind, and hydroelectric projects in Africa, South Asia, and Latin America (White, 2024).

In spite of this, China remains resistant to transnational regulatory mechanisms that could restrict its economic autonomy (White, 2024). Beijing has repeatedly opposed EU-led

carbon border measures, arguing them as unfairly burdening developing economies and disrupting free trade. At the same time, China rejects legally binding emissions reduction targets, favoring voluntary commitments and technology transfers over "Western-style" regulatory enforcement (Yue et al., 2024). This deliberate non-alignment allows China to dictate the terms of its climate engagement, advancing a parallel climate governance model that prioritizes economic growth over external accountability.

Despite these tensions, EU-China cooperation remains a crucial factor in global decarbonization efforts. While the EU champions regulatory governance, China prioritizes state-driven industrial transformation. Yet both share strategic interests in green economic development, technological innovation, and the energy transition. As China continues its ecological modernization, its approach will not only shape domestic sustainability but also redefine the future of climate leadership in the Anthropocene. Whether China's model of pragmatic state-led climate governance will supplant the EU's normative regulatory approach remains an open question, but the outcome will determine the trajectory of global climate policy in the future.

4. Discussion: Bridging EU-China Climate Identities Through Shared Narratives, Hybrid Institutions, and Subnational Diplomacy

Norms are not simply imposed but negotiated, resisted, and localized. The EU's attempts to universalize its carbon pricing and sustainability standards clash with China's strategy of norm localization. Adapting global climate norms to align with domestic priorities, China's BRI remains a tool for exporting its developmental model. Despite its recent "green" rebranding, China prioritizes infrastructure speed over participatory governance.

The EU, meanwhile, faces a paradox, as its normative influence depends on recognition from

other actors, including China. When Beijing adopts EU-style policies, e.g., renewable energy targets, it legitimizes the EU's role as a norm-setter. Yet, China's selective adoption undermines the EU's universalist claims. Revealing the limits of top-down norm diffusion, the tension between the EU's "normative power Europe" identity and China's "civilizational modernity" mirrors broader debates about whose norms matter (Sampson & Theuns, 2023). Challenging the EU's assumed monopoly on ethical governance, non-Western states increasingly localize global norms to fit their historical and cultural contexts. Multilateral forums like the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) serve as social arenas where EU-China climate identities are performed, contested, and occasionally reconstituted. The Paris Agreement's bottom-up structure, for instance, allowed China to reframe its role from obstructionist to responsible great power and leverage climate diplomacy to bolster its soft power (Falkner, 2016). Similarly, the EU's insistence on the highest possible ambition in global pledges reflects its need to validate its self-image as a normative leader. However, these interactions are mediated by external geopolitical narratives. The U.S.-China rivalry has socialized both actors into viewing climate cooperation through a lens of strategic competition (Htwe, 2025). With the reelection of Donald Trump, his administration's approach toward China is expected to be significantly more confrontational than that of Biden. Trump's return marks a resurgence of economic nationalism, trade wars, and an aggressive decoupling strategy (China Briefing, 2025). It can reinforce Beijing's perception that Western climate policies and technology restrictions are extensions of broader containment efforts. As such, the EU's alignment with U.S. tech restrictions on China undermines trust.

Climate engagement between the EU and China is not merely a transactional exchange of policies, but a dynamic interplay of socially

constructed identities, norms, and discourses that shape their strategic choices. This relationship is deeply embedded in political self-conceptions, intersubjective understandings, and evolving narratives to drive both cooperation and competition. At its core, the relationship reflects a struggle over the meaning of climate governance: whether it is a technocratic exercise in emissions reduction, a vehicle for ideological influence, or a platform for redefining global power structures in the Anthropocene. The EU and China derive their climate strategies from distinct identity narratives that are socially constructed and perpetuated through domestic and international discourse. The EU frames itself as a "normative power" (Ciambra, 2008) and anchors its legitimacy in the diffusion of liberal environmental norms, rules-based multilateralism and a post-national vision of sustainability. Having institutionalized climate goals within the internal market through mechanisms like the European Green Deal and the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, the EU's insistence on "green conditionality" in trade agreements (Petersmann, 2022) reflects its belief that environmental norms must be universalized to ensure fairness rooted in its post-war identity as a guardian of the liberal international order.

Conversely, China constructs its climate identity through the discourse of ecological civilization (Lord, 2018). This term has been embedded in CCP ideology that merges environmental stewardship with national rejuvenation (Shambaugh, 2008). This narrative reframes sustainability as a civilizational achievement, tying it to China's historical narrative of overcoming humiliation and reclaiming global leadership. Unlike the EU's universalist approach, China's climate strategy is performative and emphasizes sovereignty and "development rights" for the Global South (Ife, 2009). Its dominance in green technology supply chains is not just an economic strategy but a bid to redefine global climate norms as pluralistic rather than Western-centric. These identities are not static but are continually reinforced through practice. For instance, the EU's emphasis on

CBAM as a “leveling mechanism” reinforces its self-image as a regulatory pioneer, while China’s resistance to external climate conditionality strengthens its narrative of defending developing nations against neocolonial “green imperialism” (Frame, 2022).

Trust-building in climate diplomacy relies on repeated interactions that reshape mutual perceptions. Joint initiatives, such as the EU-China Environmental and Climate High-Level Dialogue, create shared epistemic frameworks and foster incremental norm convergence (Wunderlich, 2020). Yet, as Alexander Wendt (1992) notes, “anarchy is what states make of it”—the adversarial or cooperative nature of EU-China relations is not predetermined but constructed through discourse and practice. The competition over green technology illustrates how material rivalries are underpinned by clashing normative visions. This is not merely an economic dispute but a contest over epistemic authority. To answer the question of “Who gets to define the rules of the green transition,” it can be seen that China’s rise as a tech powerhouse disrupts the EU’s narrative of Western technological superiority and forces Europe to adopt uncharacteristic industrial policies like the Critical Raw Materials Act (European Commission, 2022). This shift reflects a renegotiation of the EU’s identity from detached regulator to strategic competitor. The EU-China climate relationship is neither destined for conflict nor primed for harmony. Instead, its trajectory hinges on whether both actors can construct shared meanings around climate governance.

Looking ahead, the EU’s ability to sustain its climate leadership will depend on its capacity to navigate these competing pressures. Recognizing the limits of regulatory unilateralism (Jansen, 2000), Brussels has sought to balance enforcement with strategic partnerships. Exemplified by initiatives such as the Just Energy Transition Partnerships

(JETPs) with South Africa and Indonesia (Seiler, et al., 2023) and the Global Gateway Initiative in Africa (Tagliapietra, 2024), the EU could channel effective investments into renewable energy infrastructure in the Global South. As the EU moves forward, its success in shaping a climate-resilient global order will rest on its ability to adapt its regulatory framework to shifting geopolitical realities, while maintaining the institutional coherence necessary to sustain its role as the architect of global climate governance. The EU’s climate strategy represents an attempt to institutionalize sustainability as a defining feature of global economic governance. But in a world where regulatory power competes with state-driven industrial policy and geopolitical rivalries, the question remains: can Europe’s vision of climate leadership prevail against China’s pragmatism? The coming years will test whether the EU’s commitment to green norms can shape international climate governance, or whether realpolitik considerations will force adaptations to its regulatory ambitions.

Therefore, this paper posits that the EU-China climate dynamic underscores constructivism’s central tenet. International relations are shaped not just by material power, but by the stories states tell about themselves and each other. The EU’s identity as a normative leader and China’s vision of civilizational modernity are mutually constitutive to each other—each reinforces the other’s strategic choices. While their normative contestation risks fragmentation, it also opens space for creative institutional hybridization. The Anthropocene, in this sense, is not just a geological epoch but a discursive battleground. The “rules” of climate governance will be written through the interplay of competing identities, practices, and social constructions of legitimacy.

Conclusion

The relationship between the European Union and China in the realm of climate diplomacy is emblematic of the broader ideological tensions shaping the international order. The EU, as a champion of liberal multilateralism, views

climate governance as an extension of the rules-based system it has helped build since the postwar era. China, by contrast, approaches the issue through a lens of state sovereignty and economic pragmatism, leveraging climate leadership to enhance its geopolitical position. These competing worldviews create friction, particularly in areas like emission reduction commitments, climate financing, and technological standards. Yet, despite these clashes, cooperation persists, particularly in the domains of renewable energy and carbon markets, revealing the strategic necessity of engagement between these two major actors.

The implications of this rivalry extend beyond climate policy. The liberal international order, once seen as inevitable in its expansion, now faces a fundamental challenge as alternative governance models gain traction. China's growing influence in climate diplomacy reflects a broader shift toward a multipolar world, where emerging powers reject the premise that Western-led institutions should set the terms of global governance. This development raises the question of whether the liberal order is capable of adapting to these changes, or whether it will instead fragment under the weight of competing visions.

The Anthropocene demands a level of global cooperation that no single power can dictate alone. If climate governance is to be effective, it will require either accommodation between these competing models or the emergence of an entirely new framework that transcends the ideological divides of the past. The stakes are high: not only for the future of the planet, but for the survival of the very institutions that have long defined international politics.

References

- Acharya, A. (2004). How ideas spread: Whose norms matter? Norm localization and institutional change in Asian regionalism. *International Organization*, 58(2), 239–275.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020818304582024>
- Adler, E. (2019). *World ordering: A social theory of cognitive evolution*. Cambridge University Press.
- Alves, L., Angelo, H., Almeida, A., Silva, G., Matricardi, E., Nunes, A., & De Souza, C. (2024). Strategic analysis of the forest carbon market in Brazil. *Sustainability*, 16(16), 6898.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su16166898>
- Anderson, E., Mugo, W. N., Taim, A., Davis, I., & Lehmann, S. (2024). *Global geopolitics*. IPR Journals and Book Publishers.
- Arima, E., Barreto, P., Taheripour, F., & Aguiar, A. (2021). Dynamic Amazonia: The EU–mercosur trade agreement and deforestation. *Land*, 10(11), 1243.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/land10111243>
- Art, R. J., Crawford, T. W., & Jervis, R. (Eds.). (2023). *International politics: Enduring concepts and contemporary issues*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Beatriz, P. A. (2024). EU green transition in times of geopolitical pressures: Accelerating or slowing the pace towards climate neutrality? *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 13(2), 1–11.
<https://doi.org/10.14207/ejsd.2024.v13n2p1>
- Beaudoin, S. (2024). Negotiating the climate long-term global goal. *International Negotiation*, 1(aop), 1–32.
<https://doi.org/10.1163/15718069-bja10104>
- Beck, K., & Larsen, M. (2024). Financialization and an emerging “green investor state”: Examining China's use of state-backed funds for green transition. *Regulation & Governance*, 19(2), 349–369.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/rego.12625>
- Beeson, M. (2021). *Environmental Anarchy? Security in the 21st Century*. Policy Press.
- Bell, S., & Hindmoor, A. (2009). *Rethinking governance: The centrality of the state in modern society*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bendell, J., & Read, R. (Eds.). (2021). *Deep*

- adaptation: Navigating the realities of climate chaos*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bengtsson, R. (2022). The European Union's self-conception of its roles in global affairs. In M. Grossman, F. Schortgen, & G. M. Friedrichs (Eds.), *National role conceptions in a new millennium* (pp. 115–127). Routledge.
<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781003092506-10/european-union-self-conception-roles-global-affairs-rikard-bengtsson>.
- Boute, A., & Zhang, H. (2018). Fixing the emissions trading scheme: Carbon price stability in the EU and China. *European Law Journal* 25(3), 333–347.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/eulj.12307>
- Bower, A. (2016). *Norms without the great powers: International law and changing social standards in world politics*. Oxford University Press.
- Brandi, C., & Morin, J. F. (2023). *Trade and the environment: Drivers and effects of environmental provisions in trade agreements*. Cambridge University Press.
- Cai, W. (2023). Research on the path of practical cooperation between China and European Union countries under the environment of carbon neutrality and peak carbon dioxide emissions. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 11.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2023.1177291>
- Checkel, J. T. (1997). International norms and domestic politics: Bridging the rationalist-constructivist divide. *European Journal of International Relations*, 3(4), 473–495.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1354066197003004003>
- Cheng, Q., Qiao, H., Gu, Y., & Chen, Z. (2023). Price dynamics and interactions between the Chinese and European carbon emission trading markets. *Energies*, 16(4), 1624.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/en16041624>
- China Briefing. (2025, March 4). *US-China relations in the Trump 2.0 era: A timeline*. China Briefing.
<https://www.china-briefing.com/news/us-china-relations-in-the-trump-2-0-implications/>
- Ciambra, A. (2008). *'Normative Power' Europe: Theory and practice of EU norms: The case of Macedonia*. University of Catania.
<https://www.academia.edu/726932/>
- Clarke, A. (2024). *Corporate law and climate change: Theory, risk, governance*. Taylor & Francis.
- Copernicus Climate Change Service. (2024, March). *2024: The first year to exceed 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels*. European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).
<https://climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus-2024-first-year-exceed-15degc-above-pre-industrial-level>
- Creutz, K., Iso-Markku, T., Raik, K., & Tiilikainen, T. H. (2019). *The changing global order and its implications for the EU*. Finnish Institute of International Affairs (FIIA).
- Davies, J. (2016). *The birth of the Anthropocene*. University of California Press.
- Delbeke, J. (2024). Conclusion. In J. Delbeke (Ed.), *Delivering a climate neutral Europe*. Taylor & Francis (pp. 295-97).
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003493730>
- Delimatsis, P. (2023). *The political economy of economic integration*. TILEC Discussion Papers.
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4590759
- Dev, T., & Goswami, A. (2024). *Carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM): The Global South's response to a changing trade regime in the era of climate change*. Center for Science and Environment.
- Di Ciommo, M., Veron, P., & Ashraf, N. (2024). *The EU and China in the Global South: Perspectives from African countries*. ECDPM Discussion Paper 373. Maastricht: ECDPM.
<https://ecdpm.org/application/files/2417/2604/7280/EU-China-Global-South-Perspectives-African-Countries-ECDPM-Discussion-Paper-373-2024.pdf>
- Diez, T., & Von Lucke, F. (2023). Global justice and EU climate policy in a contested liberal international order. *International Affairs*.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ia/iia231>
- Dryzek, J. S. (2022). *The politics of the earth: Environmental discourses*. Oxford University Press.
- Dupont, C., Rosamond, J., & Zaki, B. (2023). Investigating the scientific knowledge-policy interface in EU climate policy. *Policy & Politics*.

- <https://doi.org/10.1332/030557321x16861511996074>
- Durmaz, G. (2024). *European Green Deal from a neo-Gramscian perspective: A case of green trasformismo* [Doctoral dissertation, Middle East Technical University].
<https://search.proquest.com/openview/cc69701c6048586a6824565befad6542/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=2026366&diss=y>
- Dutov, M. (2024). Analysis of the provisions of the Communication on the implementation of the European Green Deal "Fit for 55." *Analytical and Comparative Jurisprudence*.
<https://doi.org/10.24144/2788-6018.2024.02.47>
- Economy, E., & Levi, M. (2014). *By all means necessary: How China's resource quest is changing the world*. Oxford University Press.
- Eliasson, L. J., & Garcia-Duran, P. (2024). EU trade policy in light of a fragmented liberal international order. In *EU foreign policy in a fragmenting international order* (pp. 27–54). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-64060-5_2
- Erdogdu, E. (2025). The carbon border adjustment mechanism: Opportunities and challenges for non-EU countries. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Energy and Environment*, 14(1), e70000.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.70000>
- Eritja, M. C., & Fernández-Pons, X. (Eds.). (2024). *Deploying the European Green Deal: Protecting the environment beyond the EU borders*. Taylor & Francis.
- Esteban, M., & Lin, Y. (Eds.). (2023). *China and international norms: Evidence from the Belt and Road Initiative*. Taylor & Francis.
- European Commission. (2022). *Critical Raw Materials Act. Single Market Economy*.
https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials/critical-raw-materials-act_en
- Falkner, R. (2016). The Paris Agreement and the new logic of international climate politics. *International Affairs*, 92(5), 1107–1125. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2346.12708>
- Feenberg, A. (2022). Critical constructivism: An exposition and defense. In D. Cressman (Ed.), *In The Necessity of Critique: Andrew Feenberg and the Philosophy of Technology* (Vol. 41, pp. 15–38). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-07877-4_2
- Ferenczy, Z. A. (2019). Green power? European normative influence on Chinese environmental policy. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of European Studies*, 11(1).
<https://openjournals.library.sydney.edu.au/ANZJES/article/view/15207>
- Finnemore, M., & Sikkink, K. (1998). *International norm dynamics and political change*. *International Organization*, 52(4), 887–917.
<https://doi.org/10.1162/002081898550789>
- Follador, M., Soares-Filho, B., Philippidis, G., Davis, J., De Oliveira, A., & Rajão, R. (2021). Brazil's sugarcane embitters the EU-Mercosur trade talks. *Scientific Reports*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-93349-8>
- Frame, M. L. (2022). *Ecological imperialism, development, and the capitalist world-system: Cases from Africa and Asia*. Routledge.
- Friedberg, A. L. (2022). *Getting China Wrong*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Fuchs, R., Brown, C., & Rounsevell, M. (2020). Europe's Green Deal offshores environmental damage to other nations. *Nature*, 586, 671–673.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-02991-1>
- Gheciu, A. (2005). *NATO in the "New Europe": The politics of international socialization after the Cold War*. Stanford University Press.
- Görlach, B., Martini, L., Lehtilä, S., Löther, N., Hocksell, T., Calipel, C., Hilke, A., Moore, B., Dicke, F., de Vries, M., Kampman, B., Voulis, N., Nauta, M., Vendrik, J., Fontanet Perez, P., & Kulovesi, K. (2024). *Integrated assessment of the policy avenues for transformative climate policies*.
<https://dspace.uef.fi/handle/123456789/33231>

- Graham, N. A., & Yilmaz, Ş. (2023). *Energy, Environment and Geopolitics in Eurasia: Search for Security in the Water-Energy-Food Nexus*. Taylor & Francis.
- Greenpeace East Asia. (2023, April 24). *China has already approved more new coal in 2023 than it did in all of 2021*. Greenpeace. <https://www.greenpeace.org/eastasia/press/7939/china-has-already-approved-more-new-coal-in-2023-than-it-did-in-all-of-2021-greenpeace/>
- Gruber, M. (2025). *Climate Politics in Populist Times: Climate Change Communication Strategies in Germany, Spain, and Austria*. Taylor & Francis.
- Gupta, A., Pandey, R., & Sapatnekar, S. (2024). *Potential implications of the EU's carbon border adjustment mechanism*. National Institute of Public Finance and Policy.
- Gürçan, E. C., & Donduran, C. (2024). *China on the Rise: The transformation of structural power in the era of multipolarity*. Taylor & Francis.
- Guzzini, S. (2000). A reconstruction of constructivism in international relations. *European Journal of International Relations*, 6, 147–182. <https://doi.org/10.1177/135406610006002001>
- Hackenbroich, J., Oertel, J., Sandner, P., & Zerka, P. (2022). *Defending Europe's economic sovereignty: New ways to resist economic coercion*. European Council on Foreign Relations.
- Hafner, M., & Raimondi, P. (2020). Priorities and challenges of the EU energy transition: From the European Green Package to the new Green Deal. *Russian Journal of Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.32609/j.ruje.6.55375>.
- Hafner, M., & Tagliapietra, S. (2020). *The geopolitics of the global energy transition*. Springer Nature.
- Hancher, L., & De Hauteclocque, A. (2024). Strategic autonomy, REPowerEU and the internal energy market: untying the Gordian Knot. *Common market law review*, 61(1), 55–92. <https://doi.org/10.54648/cola2024003>
- Hassan, Q., Viktor, P., Al-Musawi, T. J., Ali, B. M., Algburi, S., Alzoubi, H. M., ... & Jaszczur, M. (2024). The renewable energy role in the global energy transformations. *Renewable Energy Focus*, 48, 100545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ref.2024.100545>
- Heggelund, G. (2021). China's climate and energy policy: at a turning point? *International Environmental Agreements*, 21, 9–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-021-09528-5>
- Heldt, E. (2023). Europe's Global Gateway: A New Instrument of Geopolitics. *Politics and Governance*, 11(4), 223–234. <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.v11i4.7098>
- Hilton, I., & Kerr, O. (2017). The Paris Agreement: China's 'new normal' role in international climate negotiations. *Climate Policy*, 17, 48–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2016.1228521>
- Hörber, T., & Weber, G. (Eds.). (2021). *The European environmental conscience in EU politics: A developing ideology*. Routledge.
- Hove, A. (2024). *Clean energy innovation in China: Fact and fiction, and implications for the future (No. 14)*. OIES Paper: CE.
- Htwe, T. M. (2025). China's global south strategy in the Mekong region in geopolitical implications, economic prospects, and challenge: The dragon's reach into southern arc. In E. Yazdani (Ed.), *Implications, prospects, and challenges in China's Global South strategy* (pp. 149–182). IGI Global Scientific Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3373-0938-5.ch006>
- Hug, F. (2024). *China's free trade agreement strategies: Securing the Chinese developmental state and socialist market economy*. Springer Nature.
- Ife, J. (2009). *Human rights from below: Achieving rights through community development*. Cambridge University Press.
- Ilnytskyy, D., Drobotiuk, O., & Andrusyk, V. (2024). Sustainable development through green innovations: Economic strategies of China and the EU compared. *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Economics and Social Sciences*, 512–528. <https://doi.org/10.24818/icess/2024/048>
- Jansen, B. (2000). The limits of unilateralism from a European perspective.

- European Journal of International Law*, 11, 309–313.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/EJIL/11.2.309>
- Ji, X. (2021). *Mega-regionalism and great power geo-economic competition*. Routledge.
- Jiang, C. (2022). Revisiting “leadership” in global climate governance: China’s normative engagement with the CBDRs principle. *The Chinese Journal of International Politics*, 15(2), 183–208.
<https://academic.oup.com/cjip/article-abstract/15/2/183/6552254>
- Jonassen, R., Andersen, M. S., Cottrell, J., & Bhattacharya, S. (2023). *Carbon pricing and fossil fuel subsidy rationalization tool kit*. Asian Development Bank.
- Kalistová, A., & Huttmanová, E. (2020). Attitudes to climate change from the perspective of the Czech Republic, Hungary and Poland. *Individual & Society*, 23(4), 32–56.
<https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=954701>
- Kareckaite, E. (2020). *Addressing climate change through unilateral action: The implications of adopting a European Union-wide border carbon adjustment*. Master Thesis Series in Environmental Studies and Sustainability Science.
<https://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/search/publication/9012961>
- Kalantzakos, S. (2017). *China and the geopolitics of rare earths*. Oxford University Press.
- Katzenstein, P. J. (1996). *The culture of national security: Norms and identity in world politics*. Columbia University Press.
- Kendrick, M. (2024). The emissions trading scheme (ETS) and the carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM). In F. Fabbrini & C. A. Petit (Eds.), *Research handbook on post-pandemic EU economic governance and NGEU law* (pp. 272–281). Edward Elgar Publishing.
<https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/book/9781035328161/book-part-9781035328161-29.xml>
- Keohane, R. O., Nye, J. S., & Hoffmann, S. (Eds.). (1993). *After the Cold War: international institutions and state strategies in Europe, 1989-1991*. Harvard University Press.
- Khosa, A., Rashid, T., Shah, N., Usman, M., & Khalil, M. (2020). Performance analysis based on probabilistic modelling of Quaid-e-Azam Solar Park (QASP) Pakistan. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 29, 100479.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2020.100479>
- Kopra, S. (2018). *China and great power responsibility for climate change*. Taylor & Francis.
- Koyzis, D. T. (2019). *Political visions & illusions: A survey & Christian critique of contemporary ideologies*. InterVarsity Press.
- Kristensen, A. (2023). *Geopolitical Dynamics and the moral imperative of addressing loss and damage in the Global South* [Master’s Thesis, Aalborg University].
https://vbn.aau.dk/ws/files/595417334/THESIS__pdf.pdf
- Lazard, O., & Youngs, R. (2021). *The EU and climate security: toward ecological diplomacy*. Carnegie Europe.
https://carnegieendowment.org/files/Youngs_and_Lazard_EU_Climate_FINAL_07.08.21.pdf
- Leal-Arcas, R. (Ed.). (2024). *Research handbook on EU energy law and policy*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Leal-Arcas, R., Faktaufon, M., & Kyprianou, A. (2022). A legal exploration of the European Union’s carbon border adjustment mechanism. *European Energy and Environmental Law Review*, 31(4), 223–240.
<https://doi.org/10.54648/eelr2022016>
- Leonard, M., Pisani-Ferry, J., Shapiro, J., Tagliapietra, S., & Wolf, G. (2021). The geopolitics of the European Green Deal. *International Organizations Research Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.17323/1996-7845-2021-02-10>
- Li, J., Ho, M. S., Xie, C., & Stern, N. (2022). China’s flexibility challenge in achieving carbon neutrality by 2060. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 158, 112112.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032122000417>
- Lian, C., & Li, J. (2024). Legitimacy-seeking: China’s statements and actions on combating climate change. *Third World Quarterly*, 45(1), 171–188.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2023.2216135>
- Liu, L., & Wu, T. (2021). *EU-China relationship*

in a new era of global climate governance. Robert Schuman Center for Advanced Studies, European University Institute.

<https://www.eui.eu/Documents/RSCAS/JMF-25-Presentation/EU-China-relationship-Jul-14.pdf>

- Liu, L., Wang, X., & Wang, Z. (2023). Recent progress and emerging strategies for carbon peak and carbon neutrality in China. *Greenhouse Gases: Science and Technology*, 13(5), 732–759. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ghg.2235>
- Liu, P., Guo, K., & Wu, J. (2024). Research on alternative relationship between Chinese renewable energy and imported coal for China. *Sustainability*, 16(8), 3446. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16083446>
- Liu, T. (2024). Challenges and countermeasures for China's participation in international cooperation on climate change under the framework of the Paris Agreement—Take paragraph 2 of Article 6 of the Paris Agreement as an example. *Science of Law Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.23977/law.2024.030113>
- Lord, E. (2018). *Building an ecological civilization across the rural/urban divide and the politics of environmental knowledge production in contemporary China*. University of Toronto.
- Magacho, G., Espagne, É., & Godin, A. (2023). Impacts of the CBAM on EU trade partners: consequences for developing countries. *Climate Policy*, 24, 243–259. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2023.2200758>
- Meng, H. (2024). Challenges and controversies to the European CBAM from a legal perspective. *Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences (AEMPS)*, 81, 201–206. <https://doi.org/10.54254/2754-1169/81/20241752>
- Mavraganis, K. (2021). Europe versus an emerging China: Rivalry, partnership, or something else? Policymakers and experts comment on EU–China relations. *Future Europe Journal*, 1(1), 4. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=8478768>
- Mazarr, M. J., Frederick, B., Drennan, J. J., Ellinger, E., Eusebi, K., Rooney, B., Stravers, A., & Yoder, E. (2021). *Understanding influence in the strategic competition with China*. RAND Corporation.
- Medinilla, A., Dekeyser, K., & Karaki, K. (2022, June). *Promoting a global green transition following the Russian invasion of Ukraine*. European Center for Development Policy Management (ECDPM). <https://ecdpm.org/application/files/8016/5779/6051/Promoting-Global-Green-Transition-Russian-Invasion-Ukraine-External-Dimensions-European-Green-Deal-ECDPM-Discussion-Paper-325-2022.pdf>
- Mesarović, M. (2024). Greening industry in aace towards net-zero And beyond. *IX Regionalna konferencija Industrijska energetika i zaštita životne sredine u zemljama Jugoistočne Evrope* (pp. 24–50). <https://doi.org/10.46793/ieep24.024m>
- Moore, S. M. (2022). *China's next act: How sustainability and technology are reshaping China's rise and the World's future*. Oxford University Press.
- Moritsugu, K. (2025, February 13). New coal power plant projects in China hit the highest level in nearly 10 years, report says. *AP News*. <https://apnews.com/article/china-coal-power-plant-carbon-climate-change-ba86e7584e3afe1826eed5cffa25354a>
- Mtui, G. (2024). *China's rise as a global power: A comprehensive analysis Of China's influence in global climate governance* [Doctoral dissertation, Master in International Relations, Strategy and Security, School of Social Science and Humanities, Neapolis University Pafos]. <https://hephaestus.nup.ac.cy/handle/11728/12845>
- Nagy, G., Heiner, S. Á., & Kovács, Z. (2025). Exploring the presence and absence of academic discourse on public participation in the European Green Deal: A Central and Eastern European perspective. *Societies*, 15(3), 49. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc15030049>
- Nakai, R. (2025). Nationalism and environmentalism from the global perspective: A comparative survey analysis of eco-nationalism. *Nations and Nationalism*, 31(1), 128–145. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nana.13018>

- Nakano, J. (2021). *Defending and investing in US competitiveness*. Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS).
- Nathaniel, S., Anyanwu, O., & Shah, M. (2020). Renewable energy, urbanization, and ecological footprint in the Middle East and North Africa region. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27, 14601–14613. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-08017-7>
- Oberthür, S. (2019). Hard or soft governance? The EU's climate and energy policy framework for 2030. *Politics and Governance*. <https://doi.org/10.17645/PAG.V7I1.1796>
- Oberthür, S., & Dupont, C. (2021). The European Union's international climate leadership: towards a grand climate strategy? *Journal of European Public Policy*, 28, 1095–1114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2021.1918218>
- Oberthür, S., & Gehring, T. (Eds.). (2006). *Institutional interaction in global environmental governance: Synergy and conflict among international and EU policies*. MIT Press.
- Oh, C., & Matsuoka, S. (2017). The genesis and end of institutional fragmentation in global governance on climate change from a constructivist perspective. *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*, 17, 143–159. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-015-9309-2>.
- Olsen, T. (2023). *A critical perspective on the principle of state sovereignty over natural resources and its role in hindering the effective regulation of climate change at the international stage* [Master's thesis, UiT The Arctic University of Norway]. Munin Open Research Archive. <https://hdl.handle.net/10037/33349>
- Onofrei, M., Vatamanu, A., & Cigu, E. (2022). The relationship between economic growth and CO₂ emissions in EU countries: A cointegration analysis. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.934885>
- Pahle, M., Günther, C., Osorio, S., & Quemina, S. (2023). The emerging endgame: The EU ETS on the road towards climate neutrality. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4373443>
- Palmieri, R., Amice, C., Amato, M., & Verneau, F. (2024). Beyond the finish line: Sustainability hurdles in the EU–Mercosur free trade agreement. *Social Sciences*, 13(7), 362. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci13070362>
- Pan, C., Shrestha, A., Wang, G., Innes, J., Wang, K., Li, N., Li, J., He, Y., Sheng, C., & Niles, J. (2021). A linkage framework for the China national emission trading system (CETS): Insight from key global carbon markets. *Sustainability*, 13(13), 7459. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU13137459>
- Patey, L. (2024, February 21). *The European Union can go green and lower dependencies on China*. Danish Institute for International Studies (DIIS). <https://www.diis.dk/en/research/the-european-union-can-go-green-and-lower-dependencies-on-china>
- Payne, R. A., & Samhat, N. H. (2004). *Democratizing global politics: Discourse norms, international regimes, and political community*. Suny Press.
- Pearson, M. M., Rithmire, M., & Tsai, K. (2023). *The state and capitalism in China*. Cambridge University Press.
- Pease, K.-K. S. (2018). *International organizations: Perspectives on governance in the twenty-first century* (6th ed.). Routledge.
- Peña, A. (2020). *China's assertive turn: China's grand strategy and foreign policy adjustment through the belt and road initiative* [PhD Dissertation, University of Barcelona]. https://ddd.uab.cat/pub/tesis/2020/hdl_10803_669352/mapg1de1.pdf
- Peplow, M. (2018). Taking a gamble on kesterites. *Chemical & Engineering News*. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cen-09607-scitech1>
- Petersmann, E. U. (2022). *Transforming world trade and investment law for sustainable development*. Oxford University Press.
- Petry, J. (2020). Same same, but different: Varieties of capital markets, Chinese state capitalism and the global financial order. *Competition & Change*, 25, 605–630. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1024529420964723>
- Piao, S., Silva, V., Del Aguila, I., & De Burgos

- Jiménez, J. (2021). Green growth and agriculture in Brazil. *Sustainability*, 13(3), 1162.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/SU13031162>
- Pietzcker, R., Osorio, S., & Rodrigues, R. (2021). Tightening EU ETS targets in line with the European Green Deal: Impacts on the decarbonization of the EU power sector. *Applied Energy*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2021.116914>
- Podriez, Y., & Zhukov, A. (2022). Strategic partnership between China, the EU, and the United States in the field of energy and international environmental protection (2000–2016). *Consensus*, 2, 67–76..
<https://doi.org/10.31110/consensus/2022-02/067-076>
- Potter, P. B. (2021). *Exporting virtue? China's international human rights activism in the Age of Xi Jinping*. UBC Press.
- Qin, Y., Rao, Y., Xu, Z., Du, J., & Ouyang, M. (2023). Toward flexibility of user side in China: Virtual power plant (VPP) and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) interaction. *eTransportation*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etrans.2023.100291>
- Ralph, J. (2023). *On global learning: pragmatic constructivism, international practice and the challenge of global governance*. Cambridge University Press.
- Repnikova, M. (2022). *Chinese soft power*. Cambridge University Press.
- Rietig, K. (2021). *Learning in governance: Climate policy integration in the European Union*. MIT Press.
- Rietveld, E., Bastain, T., van Leeuwen, T., Wieclawska, S., Bonenkamp, N., Peck, D., Klebba, M., Le Mouel, M., & Poitiers, N. (2022). *Strengthening the security of supply of products containing Critical Raw Materials for the green transition and decarbonization*. European Parliament.
[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/740058/IPO_L_STU\(2022\)740058_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/740058/IPO_L_STU(2022)740058_EN.pdf)
- Rikap, C. (2022). Becoming an intellectual monopoly by relying on the national innovation system: the State Grid Corporation of China's experience. *Research Policy*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104472>
- Ross, R., Tunsjø, Ø., & Tuosheng, Z. (Eds.). (2010). *US-China-EU relations: Managing the new world order*. Routledge.
- Rotich, I. K., Chepkirui, H., & Musyimi, P. K. (2024). Renewable energy status and uptake in Kenya. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 54, 101453.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101453>
- Rueda, R. (Ed.). (2023). *Cognitive Governance and the Historical Distortion of the Norm of Modern Development: A Theory of Political Asymmetry*. IGI Global.
- Saeed, S., & Siraj, T. (2024). Global renewable energy infrastructure: Pathways to carbon neutrality and sustainability. *Solar Energy and Sustainable Development Journal*, 13(2), 183–203.
<https://doi.org/10.51646/jsesd.v13i2.243>
- Sampson, M., & Theuns, T. (2023). Comparing Chinese and EU trade agreement strategies: lessons for normative power Europe? *International Relations*, 39(1), 101–124.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00471178231153554>
- Sattich, T., Freeman, D., Scholten, D., & Yan, S. (2021). Renewable energy in EU-China relations: Policy interdependence and its geopolitical implications. *Energy Policy*, 156, 112456.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2021.112456>
- Schlacke, S., Wentzien, H., Thierjung, E. M., & Köster, M. (2022). Implementing the EU Climate Law via the 'Fit for 55' package. *Oxford Open Energy*, 1, oiab002.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ooenergy/oiab002>
- Schunz, S. (2021). *The European Union's strategic turn in climate diplomacy: 'Multiple bilateralism' with major emitters*. College of Europe.
- Schwerdtle, P., Cavan, E., Pilz, L., Oggioni, S., Crosta, A., Kaleyeva, V., Karim, P., Szarvas, F., Naryniecki, T., & Jungmann, M. (2023). Interlinkages between climate change impacts, public attitudes, and climate action—Exploring trends before and after the Paris Agreement in the EU. *Sustainability*, 15(9), 7542.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097542>

- Seiler, A. A., Brown, H., & Matthews, S. (2023). *The JETPs of South Africa and Indonesia*. Center for Global Development. <https://www.cgdev.org/sites/default/files/jetps-south-africa-and-indonesia-blueprint-move-away-coal.pdf>
- Sejdiu, E. (2023). Decarbonizing the world: Can the EU CBAM provide the incentive we need? *Energy Law Journal*, 44, 219. https://heinonline.org/hol-cgi-bin/get_pdf.cgi?handle=hein.journals/energy44§ion=18
- Shambaugh, D. L. (2008). *China's communist party: Atrophy and adaptation*. University of California Press.
- Sharma, V., & Gupta, K. (2022). Implications of carbon border adjustment mechanism: A case of India's exports to European Union. *Journal of Resources, Energy and Development*, 18(1-2), 55–76. <https://doi.org/10.3233/RED-181204>
- Shearman, D., & Smith, J. W. (2007). *The climate change challenge and the failure of democracy*. Bloomsbury Publishing USA.
- Shi, C., Zhi, J., Yao, X., Zhang, H., Yu, Y., Zeng, Q., Li, L., & Zhang, Y. (2023). How can China achieve the 2030 carbon peak goal—A crossover analysis based on low-carbon economics and deep learning. *Energy*, 269, 126776. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.126776>
- Siddi, M. (2023). *European energy politics: The green transition and EU–Russia energy relations*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Simberg-Koulumies, N. (2023). Just sustainabilities: lessons from the Lake Turkana wind power project in Kenya. *Local Environment*, 29, 40–56. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2023.2249497>
- Song, Y., Yang, L., Sindakis, S., Aggarwal, S., & Chen, C. (2023). Analyzing the role of high-tech industrial agglomeration in green transformation and upgrading of manufacturing industry: The case of China. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 14(4), 3847–3877. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-022-00899-x>
- Štreimikienė, D., Lekavičius, V., Baležentis, T., Kyriakopoulos, G., & Abrhám, J. (2020). Climate change mitigation policies targeting households and addressing energy poverty in European Union. *Energies*, 13(13), 3389. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13133389>
- Suárez-Cuesta, D., & Latorre, M. (2024). Governance and policy implications of the Inflation Reduction Act: A European perspective. *Global Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.13448>
- Sun, Y. (2022). *Certifying China: The rise and limits of transnational sustainability governance in emerging economies*. MIT Press.
- Szucs, T. (2023). *Beyond the battle of narratives: Global soft power dynamics and the EU's strategic approach on international cultural relations in the context of the emerging new world order*. European University Institute. <https://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/75787>
- Tagliapietra, S. (2024). The European Union's Global Gateway: An institutional and economic overview. *The World Economy*, 47(4), 1326–1335. <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.13551>
- Tallberg, J., Lundgren, M., Sommerer, T., & Squatrito, T. (2020). Why international organizations commit to liberal norms. *International Studies Quarterly*, 64(3), 626–640. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isq/sqaa046>
- Thurbon, E., Kim, S. Y., Tan, H., & Mathews, J. A. (2023). *Developmental environmentalism: state ambition and creative destruction in East Asia's green energy transition*. Oxford University Press.
- Verkooijen, D. (2024). *Unlocking Offshore Hybrid Projects* [Master's Thesis, Delft University of Technology]. https://repository.tudelft.nl/file/File_828dd801-4dd9-4775-ba97-cba61cc0719a
- Vidigal, G., & Claussen, K. (2024). *The sustainability revolution in international trade agreements*. Oxford University Press.
- Wang, D., Sun, Y., & Wang, Y. (2024). Comparing the EU and Chinese carbon trading market operations and their spillover effects. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 351, 119795. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.119795>
- Wang, L., He, Y., & Wu, R. (2024). The green engine of growth: assessing the influence of renewable energy consumption and

- environmental policy on China's economic sustainability. *Sustainability*, 16(8), 3120.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su16083120>.
- Wang, Z.-J., & Zhao, L.-T. (2021). The impact of the global stock and energy market on EU ETS: A structural equation modelling approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 289, 125140.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125140>
- Wang, X. (2022). The impact of China's entry into the carbon trading market on European carbon prices. *BCP Business & Management*, 34, 1542–1550.
<https://doi.org/10.54691/bcpbm.v34i.3210>
- Wendt, A. (1992). Anarchy is what states make of it: The social construction of power politics. International Organization, 46(2), 391–425.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020818300027764>
- Wendt, A. (1999). *Social theory of international politics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Wettestad, J. (2024). The EU's carbon border adjustment mechanism: Shaped and saved by shifting multi-level reinforcement? *Review of Policy Research*, 42(3), 423–756
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ropr.12597>
- White, J. K. (2024). *The truth about energy: our fossil-fuel addiction and the transition to renewables*. Cambridge University Press.
- Wu, F., Deng, H., Feng, Y., Wang, W., Wang, Y., & Zhang, F. (2024). Statecraft at the frontier of capitalism: A grounded view from China. *Progress in human geography*, 48(6), 779–804.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/03091325241268953>
- Wunderlich, J. (2020). Positioning as normative actors: China and the EU in climate change negotiations. *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 58(5), 1107–1123.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jcms.13019>
- Wurzel, R., Liefferink, D., & Di Lullo, M. (2019). The European Council, the Council and the Member States: changing environmental leadership dynamics in the European Union. *Environmental Politics*, 28, 248–270.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2019.1549783>
- Xia, L. Q. (2024). *The diplomatic making of EU-China relations: structure, substance and style*. Taylor & Francis.
- Xing, L. (Ed.). (2021). *China-EU relations in a new era of global transformation*. Routledge.
- Yan, G., Ruan, J., Qin, Z., Lyu, C., Qian, S., Jia, M., Zhang, Z., Cai, B., Wang, S., Wang, J., & Tang, L. (2025). Unit-level monitoring data reveal the effectiveness of China's national emissions trading scheme. *Cell Reports Sustainability*.
[https://www.cell.com/cell-reports-sustainability/fulltext/S2949-7906\(25\)00035-7](https://www.cell.com/cell-reports-sustainability/fulltext/S2949-7906(25)00035-7)
- Yang, J. (2022). Understanding China's changing engagement in global climate governance: a struggle for identity. *Asia Europe Journal*, 20(4), 357–376.
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10308-021-00643-1>
- Yıldırımçakar, E. (2024). China's ambition to balance power within the framework of soft and normative power concepts. *Current Research in Social Sciences*, 10(2), 194–210.
<https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/curesos/c/issue/88321/1498132>
- Young, O. R. (2011). Effectiveness of international environmental regimes: Existing knowledge, cutting-edge themes, and research strategies. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(50), 19853–19860.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1111690108>
- Yu, Y. (2024). Holistic pragmatism: The Chinese approach on international relations. *Stosunki Międzynarodowe–International Relations*, 4(9).
<https://doi.org/10.12688/stomiedintrela.t.17810.1>
- Yu, L., Wang, Y., Wei, X., & Zeng, C. (2023). Towards low-carbon development: The role of industrial robots in decarbonization in Chinese cities. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 330, 117216 .
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117216>
- Yue, T., Tong, J., Qiao, Y., & Chen, L. (2024). Carbon governance or trade gaming: China's approach to addressing the EU's Carbon

border adjustment mechanism.
Journal of Cleaner Production.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.144359>

Zaman, H. (2023). China–EU climate complex interdependence amid COVID-19 and geopolitical tensions: Prospects for future. *China Quarterly of International Strategic Studies*.
<https://doi.org/10.1142/s2377740022500166>

Zehfuss, M. (2002). *Constructivism in international relations: the politics of reality*. Cambridge University Press.

Tin Maung Htwe

tinmaughtwe.peace@gmail.com

Tin Maung Htwe is a Research Fellow at Chiang Mai University's RCSD, specializing in migration, geopolitics, and China's regional strategy in Southeast Asia. He holds an MA in Development Studies from City University of Hong Kong. His interest in EU-China relations deepened through the 2025 Global China Summer School at Lund University. He has published widely on China's development, infrastructure, and geoeconomic expansion, including with IGI Global, Hong Kong Review of Belt and Road Studies and other scholarly journals.

Navigating EU-China Electric Vehicles Trade Disputes: A Game Theory Analysis

Ruotong SHI & Hanyi ZHANG

Abstract

This paper investigates potential trade disputes stemming from environmental subsidies and competition in green technologies between China and the EU. Specifically, it analyzes the EU's imposition of tariffs on Chinese electric vehicles (EVs), examining the responses and strategies of the EU, specifically from Germany, and China, along with their respective EV manufacturers. In this regard, game theory is selected as a theoretical framework to explore the short and long-term impacts of these disputes on EU-China EV trade dynamics, predicting outcomes and strategic responses. The analysis finds that sustained bilateral cooperation and reciprocal market engagement between German and Chinese EV manufacturers constitute the most viable strategy for long-term mutual benefit, whereas escalating tariff measures tend to generate suboptimal, mutually detrimental outcomes.

Keywords: Trade disputes, environmental subsidies, electric vehicles (EVs), game theory analysis, strategic interactions

Introduction

Trade frictions between China and the EU over products in the sustainability sector have escalated recently, covering a wide range of industries, including photovoltaic (PV) and wind turbine production. This scenario leads to fierce competition between the two parties, with both being major players in the field. For instance, in 2013, the EU imposed tariffs on Chinese PV products to protect domestic companies, arguing that Chinese products were sold below market prices with unfair

subsidies (Kanter & Bradsher, 2013).

This approach brought short-term gains. Despite temporary boosts for European PV companies, China supplied critical resources to Europe, including rare earth elements, and maintained its dominance. Chinese exports accounted for over 70% of global PV module production in 2013 and supplied key resources like rare earth elements to Europe (International Energy Agency, 2014). This trend is also evident in the lithium-ion battery industry, where Beijing controls essential segments of the global supply chain. According to EVTank data, China's lithium-ion battery shipments reached 887.4 GWh in 2023, representing 73.8% of the total global market share, a proportion that continues to increase (EVTank, 2024). In 2024, China's share of global EV sales increased from 64.8% in 2023 to 70.5%, further underscoring its dominant position in the industry (EVTank, 2025).

In response to concerns over overcapacity and unfair subsidization, the EU has imposed provisional countervailing duties on battery electric vehicles (BEVs) imported from China. The European Commission argues that the Chinese EV value chain benefits from distortive subsidies, posing a threat to fair competition, European automakers, and employment, while China regards the tariffs as an unreasonable trade barrier and maintains that its industry operates within WTO rules (European Commission, 2024). Thus, this paper investigates the EU's tariffs on Chinese EVs, analysing the responses and strategies of the EU, China, Germany, and their respective car manufacturers. Employing game theory, it explores how these tariffs impact trade patterns and structures among the EU, China, and Germany.

1. Background of EV tariffs in China

Europe's dependence on China for imports has increased over the past five years, rising from 22 % in 2017 to a peak of nearly 27 % in 2022, before leveling off at around 25 % in 2023 (Kratz et al., 2024). The 2% drop is underscored by fluctuations in trade deficits and surpluses in recent years (Matthes, 2024). Despite a temporary reduction in the overall trade deficit during the COVID-19 pandemic, the EU's dependence on Chinese imports remains significant. This dependence has become more pronounced amid efforts to diversify supply chains, especially after the Russia-Ukraine conflict. As a result, concerns associated with potential vulnerabilities in economic and trade relations with China have urged the EU to adopt a cautious approach (Sundari, 2024).

The automotive sector, including the electric vehicle (EV) industry, plays a pivotal role in this shifting dynamic. Engagement levels with China vary across EU Member States, reflecting divergent economic interests. This divergence was particularly evident when EU governments displayed split opinions on proposed tariffs for China-built EV imports. Germany, which maintains strong industrial ties with China in the EV sector, opposed the tariffs, while France, Italy, and Spain backed the measure (Blenkinsop, 2024). These differences reflect underlying disparities in the competitiveness of national automotive industries, which shape the fragmented policy preferences of EU Member States in the ongoing trade dispute with China over new energy vehicles (Ding et al., 2024).

The EU's strategic decisions on tariff escalation have critical strategic implications: balanced measures could support the domestic economy, inter alia, industries, and help sustain strong trade ties with Beijing amid evolving global dynamics. For Chinese EV manufacturers, Europe is the most important export destination, with the trend expected to

intensify (Sebastian, 2021). There is a growing trend among Chinese EV makers and suppliers to invest in European markets. For instance, Xpeng has entered the French market (Xpeng Motors, 2024), and BYD is building an EV plant in Hungary and eyeing another in Europe (Reuters, 2025).

Chery Auto is partnering with Spain's EV Motors to open a plant in Catalonia, and SAIC is searching for its first European plant. The world's largest battery maker, CATL, has ramped up production in Europe, with other Chinese battery suppliers aiding France in building its "battery valley" (Wu & Blenkinsop, 2024). The Kiel Institute for the World Economy estimates that punitive tariffs could reduce Chinese EV exports to Europe by a quarter, which might result in surges in automobile prices for consumers. The EU aims to balance the need for EVs with fair competition, encouraging China to reduce subsidies and overcapacity (Riegert, 2024). This is due to China's heavy use of subsidies that enable its manufacturers to produce electric vehicles at lower costs, which can lead to overcapacity and market imbalances, pressuring the EU to protect its own industries and consumers from unfair competition.

In his final year in office, President Biden initiated efforts to impose 100% tariffs on EVs from China, emphasizing the need for fair competition and addressing concerns over subsidies benefiting Chinese manufacturers (The White House, 2024). It is true that Biden's stance was partly aimed at bolstering his campaign for the 2024 U.S. presidential election, and is an example of a firm stance against China's economic threats (Sink, 2024). However, this policy also reflects a firm position he has held throughout his time in office, and is not a tactical shift influenced solely by electoral pressures. Most importantly, the effects of his policies extended beyond U.S.-China relations. The imposition of significant U.S. tariffs on Chinese EVs, for instance, had significant implications for European policies. It pressured the EU to reconsider its trade relations with China,

especially in sectors like EVs, where both regions compete globally (Tan, 2025). This created a situation where the EU was faced with potentially aligning with U.S. policies or strengthening its trade defense measures. Xi Jinping's visit to France in 2024 included significant meetings with President Emmanuel Macron and European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen, focusing on trade disputes, particularly China's dominance in the global EV market (Pineau et al., 2024). Discussions included potential tariff increases on Chinese EV imports to Europe. In this regard, the EU, led by von der Leyen, has expressed concerns about the impact of Chinese subsidies on EV production costs, potentially undermining European automakers' competitiveness. However, the absence of former German Chancellor Scholz during the visit pointed out internal EU divisions over trade policy towards China, particularly in the automotive sector. A strong economic relationship between Berlin and Beijing could be explained by major automakers like Mercedes-Benz, Volkswagen, and BMW, which operate plants in the mainland, emphasizing the importance of these relations (Sebastian, 2022). The divided stance notwithstanding, the German Minister for Economic Affairs and Climate at the time highlighted that there is a need for a unified, long-term strategy towards China (Reuters, 2024).

In response to concerns over Chinese EV industry subsidies, the EU initiated an anti-subsidy investigation in 2023. The findings reveal widespread complaints about unfair market access and significant industry overcapacity. Scholz suggested that the EU should avoid implementing EV tariffs, which could lead to a trade dispute with China. However, unsatisfactory negotiations led to the implementation of tariffs on EVs in April. In response, China levied tariffs on EU goods in May 2024, which raised concerns within the EU, particularly in Germany. German automakers hold significant market shares in

China, and the German government worried that tariffs on Chinese EVs could provoke retaliatory measures against German products. France also feared Chinese retaliation against its exports of wine and luxury goods. In early June 2024, the EU announced plans to impose additional tariffs on Chinese EVs to address market imbalance caused by Chinese subsidies. In June 2024, the EU announced plans to impose additional tariffs on Chinese EVs to address market imbalance caused by Chinese subsidies. The proposed tariffs ranged from 17.4% to 38.1%, with the final decision expected in early November (European Commission, 2023). This move marks the EU's largest subsidy investigation at the time, with the potential for significant economic retaliation from China. China retaliated by initiating an anti-dumping investigation into EU pork products, targeting primarily Spain, the Netherlands, and Denmark (Cash, 2024). In June 2024, former German Vice Chancellor Robert Habeck visited China and aimed to negotiate with Chinese officials, stressing that tariffs are necessary to offset unfair advantages from state subsidies (Cater, 2024). Habeck clarified that the EU tariffs are meant as compensatory rather than punitive, and expressed hope for political dialogue to avoid further escalation before the provisional measures take effect in July. However, skepticism remains about his ability to persuade Chinese officials of his version of the story.

Since Friedrich Merz officially assumed office as Germany's Chancellor in April 2025, the country's stance on EU-China electric vehicle (EV) tariffs has undergone a subtle but notable shift. Leading the Christian Democratic Union (CDU), Merz has placed greater emphasis on "reciprocal openness" and "industrial defense" in his economic policy. Under Chancellor Merz, Germany's China policy is entering a phase of cautious recalibration, with the Merz administration aiming to reduce strategic dependencies on China while preserving strong economic ties—a policy that is often described as "de-risking without decoupling" (Interesse, 2025).

In a public address, Merz stated that “Germany and Europe can no longer tolerate structural asymmetries in market access” (Rinke, 2025). This suggests that while Merz does not fully endorse the EU’s aggressive tariff policy, he also no longer opposes it as strongly as the previous administration. Instead, he appears to seek a new balance between safeguarding industrial security and maintaining economic ties with China. As the EU moves forward with its decision to impose countervailing duties of up to 38.1% on Chinese EVs—referring to provisional tariffs that the EU announced in June 2024 during its anti-subsidy investigation to penalize uncooperative companies, despite with the rate later adjusted to 35.3% in the final October decision— Merz’s government has adopted a more pragmatic approach. On the one hand, the government attempts to reassure German automakers that are concerned about losing Chinese market access; on the other, it aims to ensure that Germany does not appear weak within the EU in shaping trade rules. Merz’s government is also trying to stabilize Germany’s industrial base by strengthening external trade regulations, especially in the context of renewed U.S. tariffs under former President Trump’s return to office (Lunday, 2025).

Nonetheless, please note that as of 2024, when the core part of the analysis was drafted, the German government was still led by Chancellor Olaf Scholz under the “traffic light” coalition of the SPD, the Greens, and the FDP. As such, subsequent discussions may be unable to cover the direct influence brought by Merz’s policies.

2. The Basic Model of Game Theory in EU-China EV Tariff Dispute

Game theory is a framework for predicting behavior in competitive scenarios where one participant’s outcomes hinge on others’ decisions (Myerson, 1991). Originally used to analyze games and competitive strategies, it’s now essential across disciplines like

economics and political science. In economics, game theory models markets, strategic interactions among firms, and negotiations between buyers and sellers (Osborne, 2004). It illuminates decision-making based on expectations and strategic goals, facilitates equilibrium analysis, predicts outcomes in different scenarios, and informs predictions about negotiations and conflicts (Fudenberg et al., 1991). This article uses game theory to examine the strategic interactions among key players—the governments of China, the EU, and Germany, as well as major EV manufacturers on both sides—in response to the EU’s 2024 decision to impose tariffs on Chinese electric vehicles. By modeling these actors as rational decision-makers in a multi-stage game, this approach aims to capture how their choices influence each other’s outcomes and to predict possible responses and trade dynamics arising from this dispute. Each participant pursues their own interests and objectives. Strategic choices and reaction analyses are important aspects analyzed through game theory. The Prisoner’s Dilemma is a fundamental visual model within game theory that simplifies complex decision-making scenarios in international trade (Lewis, 2010).

Table 1
Game Theory Matrix: EU and China Raise or Lower Tariffs in the EV Tariff Dispute

	China Lower Tariffs	China Raises Tariffs
EU Lower Tariffs	EU: +1, China: +1	EU: +1, China: -1
EU Raises Tariffs	EU: -1, China: +1	EU: -1, China: -1

Note. Authors’ own visualization.

Take into account the EU-China interactions as an example here. It is a basic model where we assume that both parties are promoting tariff reductions during import and export, which is beneficial for market openness. In such cases, lowering tariffs is advantageous for the trade relationship between the two parties and is the most ideal approach in international trade, avoiding economic distortion. Conversely, any party raising tariffs results in a zero-sum game. In

the worst-case scenario, if both parties impose tariffs, especially punitive tariffs, it leads to a lose-lose situation. It is important to note that the above scenarios apply to any trade interactions between the EU and China, but the ideal state may not be realized in practice. The following game theory tables—related to EU-China government interactions, Germany-China government interactions, and Germany-China major electric vehicle negotiations, respectively—are all expansions and interpretations based on this foundational table.

Table 2
Game Theory Matrix: EU vs. China Tariff Strategies

	China Cooperates (Soft Response) (Jian, 2024)	China Retaliates (Hard Response)
EU Does Not Raise EV Tariffs	(+1, +1)	(+1, -1)
EU Raises EV Tariffs	(-1, +1)	(-1, -1)

Note. Authors' own visualization.

This table illustrates various scenarios based on the decisions made by the EU and China regarding EV tariffs. In the first scenario, if the EU chooses not to increase EV tariffs and maintains its current approach, both parties benefit (+1, +1). This decision promotes increased trade opportunities and deeper cooperation between the EU and China. It also allows China to achieve its goal of avoiding additional EV tariffs, ensuring business continuity without significant tensions escalating. This outcome signifies a stable yet cautious interaction where both sides manage trade tensions carefully to prevent them from escalating into a full-scale trade conflict. This approach reflects the strategy adopted until July 2024, particularly following Chancellor Scholz and Minister Habeck's visit to China, where their influence in the EU persuaded other Member States to refrain from making definitive judgments on China until the tariffs officially were to take effect in November.

However, the EU may have also perceived a disadvantage, as it aims to maintain competitiveness within its market while balancing relations with China.

In the second scenario, if the EU decides to implement tariffs as a protective measure, two potential outcomes arise depending on China's response. Firstly, China opts not to retaliate immediately (-1, +1), preferring to continue negotiations and uphold international trade norms to resolve disputes. In the short term, the EU's imposition of tariffs on Chinese EVs serves as a protective measure for its domestic market. By increasing the cost of imported Chinese EVs, the EU aims to shield European manufacturers from competitive pressure. This protection allows domestic companies to invest in innovation and scale up production. Meanwhile, in the context of protecting market share and technological advantages, the EU's tariffs are designed to create a level playing field for European manufacturers. The EU seeks to enforce fair competition rules to ensure mutual benefits. However, increasing tariffs may harm the overall development of the EU's other industries dependent on China, such as French luxury brands, wine, and perfume, and Spain's pork industry, which may experience negative repercussions. Additionally, it can be seen that China executes a soft response and compromise, but the process doesn't stop. China doesn't retaliate with tariffs against the EU; it seems that China has downplayed the trade issue, but in the long term, it can still pursue other diplomatic avenues to balance this downplayed scenario. For example, China might exploit internal divisions within the EU regarding EV policies, seeking to align with non-EU countries like Norway or geopolitically China-friendly countries such as Hungary and Serbia, thus exacerbating EU internal disagreements. Regarding other European car manufacturers, those less connected to China are more supportive of increased tariffs. For instance, the joint venture between Stellantis (STLAM.MI) and Leapmotor (9863.HK) highlights how established automakers can view China as either a threat or

an opportunity (Wu & Blenkinsop, 2024). This approach will lead to more far-reaching impacts. In the long term, the EU may aim to diversify its supply chain and seek alternative production markets outside China to reduce dependency on Chinese imports. By broadening its economic partnerships, the EU not only mitigates the risk of over-reliance on a single source but also enhances its bargaining power in trade negotiations. Conversely, the second possible outcome (-1, -1) occurs if China chooses to retaliate with increased tariffs on key EU exports in response to EU tariffs. In this scenario, the EU faces economic repercussions as its exports to China become more expensive and less competitive. This escalation could lead to a detrimental trade conflict, resulting in economic losses for both the EU and China – a lose-lose situation that highlights the risks of escalating tariff disputes in international trade relations. For China, its primary objective is to reduce the high tariffs imposed by the EU on its EV products and expand its market share in Europe. In response to the EU's protectionist measures, China has implemented countermeasures such as increasing tariffs on EU products. This tit-for-tat strategy is characteristic of a repeated game, where each party's actions are contingent on the other's moves. The threat of retaliation serves as a deterrent, potentially forcing the EU to reconsider its tariff policies to avoid an escalating trade war. In the meantime, China considers enhancing economic ties with more China-friendly Eastern European countries represents a strategic move to bypass tariff barriers and maintain its market presence in Europe.

However, the final scenario (+1, -1) – where the EU does not impose tariffs (Open Market) and China retaliates (Hard Response) – though theoretically a Nash equilibrium, is unlikely to occur in reality, because the EU's imposition of tariffs is pivotal; should the EU abandon tariffs, China would likewise refrain from escalating retaliatory measures. The reasoning is that if

the EU decides to lift tariffs and open its market, China would have no incentive to impose retaliatory measures.

3. The German Government's Response to EU-China Tariff Dispute

In the ongoing tariff dispute between the EU and China, the German government faces significant implications due to its deep economic ties in the automotive sector with China. German automakers maintain significant exposure to the Chinese market, highlighting Germany's crucial role in EU-China trade dynamics.

In 2022, BMW delivered approximately 791,900 vehicles in China, including around 41,886 BEVs, accounting for about 5% of its Chinese sales (Lei, 2023). The most important markets for Mercedes-Benz Cars in 2023 were China with 36% of unit sales (Mercedes-Benz Group, 2023). Meanwhile, Volkswagen sold over 3.2 million vehicles in China in 2023, representing roughly 15% of its global sales (Oemisch, 2024). These numbers clearly show how closely connected German carmakers are to China, which plays a role in how Germany approaches the ongoing trade tensions between the EU and China.

Table 3
Game Theory Matrix: German and Chinese Governments in the EV Tariff Dispute

	Chinese Government: Cooperate	Chinese Government: Defect (counter tariff measures)
German Government: Seek Compromise	(+1, +1)	(+1, -1)
German Government: Support EU Tariffs	(-1, +1)	(-1, -1)

Note. Authors' own visualization.

In Scenario (+1, +1), both the German and Chinese governments seek a compromise and continue negotiations. This cooperative approach results in mutually beneficial outcomes, with both parties achieving positive payoffs. This is the

ideal scenario where both parties opt for more moderate strategies. Germany seeks a compromise, and China continues to cooperate with Germany, reaching an outcome where a trade war is avoided. Given Germany's substantial business stake in China, the government is also likely to push for negotiations that can lead to a mutually acceptable compromise. Recently, efforts by Habeck (Baden Württemberg International, 2024) and Scholz (Masengarb, 2024) in pushing forward have played a crucial role in addressing the EU's tariff dispute with China. This involves a mixed strategy, balancing defensive tariffs with diplomatic engagement. Germany must ensure that any protective measures do not escalate into a full-blown trade war, which could have broader economic repercussions. As a result, both sides benefit from maintaining stable economic relations and sharing mutual economic gains. German leaders are not only focused on domestic efforts but also exerting influence over other EU countries to reconsider the situation. For instance, in May 2025, Scholz was in discussions with Sweden and Hungary—which collectively hold over 50 percent of the EU seats—to explore opportunities to repeal the EV tariffs imposed on China. Scholz and Swedish Prime Minister Ulf Kristersson are actively working to influence EU internal policies aimed at mitigating the tariff impacts (Agence France-Presse, 2024). Afterward, new proposals have surfaced within EU-China trade talks to replace punitive tariffs with a minimum pricing scheme for Chinese-made EVs. According to a report in April 2025, this compromise could de-escalate the trade tensions by setting floor prices for imported Chinese vehicles rather than imposing rigid duties. This approach is gaining traction among EU officials as a more sustainable and balanced policy option (Jessen, 2025).

In Scenario (-1, +1), while Germany supports EU tariffs, China chooses to continue negotiations rather than retaliate. Despite indications that the German government

generally opposed tariffs, as they could lead to economic losses, it cannot be ruled out that Germany, having failed to mediate within the EU, is forced to “support” the EU's decision to impose additional tariffs. Such conflicting behaviors may stem from small parties with fewer seats, like AfD (Alternative for Germany), conflicts within Germany, where certain factions in parliament openly support tariffs similar to the EU, citing trade protectionism to safeguard domestic automotive industries. However, due to the German traffic coalition government, their influence to enforce effectively remained constrained. Looking ahead, Germany's strategy may prioritize reducing dependency on China while safeguarding its economic interests. To mitigate the risks associated with excessive reliance on China, Germany could pursue diversification of trade partnerships and production bases. This strategic shift resembles a multi-stage game, wherein Germany invests in alternative markets to establish new equilibria that enhance resilience and reduce vulnerability. By diversifying economic interests, Germany aims to bolster its negotiating power and resilience in future trade disputes. Balancing protectionist measures with the promotion of open markets is crucial, necessitating a cooperative approach to establish equitable competition rules that benefit all stakeholders. On the other hand, China opts to negotiate rather than retaliate. Although this appears to be a positive move to keep the market open in the short term, it indicates that the reliability of German-Chinese EV businesses is too strong to abandon. As a result, the Chinese government needs to win over the German side to withstand significant tariff pressures and maintain cooperation with German EV manufacturers. This represents a highly unequal trade relationship, which is unsustainable in the long run.

In Scenario (+1, -1), the German government seeks a compromise, but China implements retaliatory tariffs, which is the same as the EU-China scenario (+1, -1). However, this scenario seems unlikely, as China's position indicates that as long as the EU reverses tariffs without

hindering the development of China's EV industry, punitive measures against other EU industries would not be necessary.

In Scenario (-1, -1), the German government supports the EU's imposition of tariffs on Chinese EVs, prompting the Chinese government to retaliate with tariffs on EU products. This could escalate into a trade war, resulting in significant economic losses for both parties. Germany, heavily reliant on the Chinese automotive market, faces severe repercussions, leading to negative outcomes for both sides (-1, -1). Germany maintains market access but loses bargaining power, as China might no longer trust Germany's influence within the EU. Despite appearing to protect its domestic EV market to some extent in the short term, Germany forfeits future cooperation opportunities with China and fails to reach a consensus in negotiations. Moreover, Germany not only loses its advantageous market share in China but also suffers a devastating blow to its GDP and domestic job positions. On the other hand, China's retaliatory measures harm its own consumers, particularly affecting products like wine and pork. Amid China's economic slowdown, tariff implementation further clouds consumer confidence.

4. Game Theory Matrix: German and Chinese EV Manufacturers on the EU-China Tariff Dispute

Suppose that the main EV manufacturers on the German side include BMW, Mercedes-Benz, and Volkswagen (excluding small and medium-sized German EV companies, which have a smaller share in China and are relatively less relevant to international trade). On the Chinese side, the focus is on purely domestic brands such as SAIC, BYD, and Geely, with Tesla not included due to its unique position. In this context, the most likely strategies for German car manufacturers are twofold: accelerating localization efforts in China, such as hiring local managers and

deepening their presence in the Chinese market, or searching for other markets and attempting to replace the Chinese market to diversify their supply chains worldwide. Meanwhile, Chinese manufacturers are considering two strategies: cutting profit margins to preserve competitive advantages and increasing investments in Germany or bearing the negative results of possible EU anti-subsidy investigations, abandoning the German market, and expanding their presence in other export markets. Both sides are engaged in strategic maneuvers to protect and enhance their market positions amidst evolving trade dynamics and regulatory environments. According to the analysis of the EU-China government game theory matrix above, there are two possible scenarios for German and Chinese EV manufacturers.

4.1 The First Scenario: EV Tariffs Ease

The first scenario is EU-China (+1, +1): Germany successfully mediates, completely convincing the EU not to impose tariffs on China while China also refrains from taking retaliatory measures.

Table 4
Game Theory Matrix: German and Chinese Manufacturers in the EV Tariff Dispute

	Chinese Manufacturers: Cooperate (Expand Market in Germany)	Chinese Manufacturers: Defect (Search Other Markets)
German Manufacturers: Cooperate (Localization or Expand Market in China)	(+1, +1)	(+1, -1)
German Manufacturers: Defect (Search Other Markets)	(-1, +1)	(-1, -1)

Note. Authors' own visualization.

4.1.1 Scenario (+1, +1)

This represents the optimal outcome for both

parties. When Chinese and German manufacturers cooperate, they maintain competitiveness and expand their market presence. This mutual cooperation allows growth and prosperity. In the short term, both benefit from expanded market access and sustained competitiveness. This sets the stage for long-term competition, fostering innovation and growth in the global market. However, this may lead to losses for small and medium-sized German enterprises. By focusing on market expansion and maintaining competitive advantages, both sides ensure ongoing development and penetration. Short-term gains include access to new markets and increased investments. Over time, both profit from diversified market access and significant investments.

4.1.2 Scenarios (+1, -1) and (-1, +1)

Whether it is German manufacturers expanding in China and Chinese manufacturers giving up in Germany, or German manufacturers giving up the Chinese market to seek other markets while Chinese manufacturers invest further in Germany, these scenarios do not exist without tariffs. In the case of successful negotiations, German manufacturers would not abandon their advantages in China, and China would not give up the German market. Moreover, the German government's credibility in mediating would significantly increase, bolstering confidence between German and Chinese car manufacturers and promoting rational and stable investment behaviors.

4.1.3 Scenario (-1, -1)

Both sides mutually abandoning investment in each other's markets is clearly non-existent. In the short term, they remain in a honeymoon phase of cooperation. Looking ahead, following this mediation turmoil, this opens up the possibility that some car manufacturers may reassess their geopolitical strategies and shift focus to other markets. Chinese manufacturers

might view the avoidance of tariffs this time as a temporary reprieve, but they could anticipate future challenges. This could potentially lead to divergences from each other's markets, though this remains a low-probability scenario.

4.2 The Second Scenario: EV Tariffs Escalate

The second scenario is EU-China (-1, +1) or (-1, -1): Germany's mediation fails, resulting in the EU imposing tariffs on China, while China either refrains from or implements retaliatory measures. Regarding the imposition of tariffs and whether the Chinese government imposes punitive tariffs on the EU, these punitive measures do not directly impact German EV manufacturers since the targeted industries are not in the German EV sector but wine, luxury or pork businesses for France and Spain. Therefore, the investment behaviors of German EV companies remain unaffected.

4.2.1 Scenario (+1, +1)

The third scenario is (+1, +1): German manufacturers expand in China and Chinese manufacturers expand in Germany. Although tariffs increase costs for German manufacturers and make market expansion in China less promising, some expectations persist, preventing them from fully abandoning the Chinese market. According to current surveys, despite the anticipation of tariffs, German manufacturers cannot quickly abandon the Chinese market. Instead, they are adopting a localization strategy to focus more on local production, sales, and profits (Baur, 2024). For instance, major German DAX companies such as Siemens and BASF have accelerated their localization processes. Siemens is not solely relying on China; while enhancing its localization efforts in China, such as the Marco Polo project in Sichuan, it is also shifting its focus towards Singapore. Similarly, BASF continues to increase its investments in China, undertaking its fifth major investment in Zhanjiang, Guangdong (Zhang & Shi, 2023). Despite many problems both within and outside China, more than a third (38%) of German companies, according to the

survey, remain optimistic and anticipate an improvement in the economic situation. Nearly half do not expect any change, and 16% foresee a deterioration. Only approximately 25% of the surveyed companies projected an increase in profits for the year 2024. In the next two years, just over half intend to increase their investments in China (German Press Agency, 2024). Additionally, for China, continuing to expand in the German market after the imposition of tariffs is detrimental, especially as Chinese firms lose their competitive edge due to compliance with anti-subsidy regulations. Chinese firms must adapt to new regulatory environments and work to regain their competitiveness in the international market. However, given Germany's leading position in the automotive industry, particularly in innovation and technology, and the worsening economic relationship between China and the US, cooperation with Europeans, especially Germans, is crucial. This is evident from the series of agreements signed between the Chinese government and large German car companies during Scholz's visit to China earlier in April 2024. Even with EV tariffs, it is challenging for Chinese EV manufacturers to quickly abandon their cooperation with German ones. Therefore, despite mutual harm and the distortions caused by tariffs, it remains a win-win situation. In the long run, it can benefit the global electric vehicle market by sharing human resources and technology, thereby enhancing the overall competitiveness of the industry.

4.2.2 Scenarios (+1, -1) and (-1, +1)

Although in both scenarios, the imposition of tariffs does not significantly alter the presence of German EV manufacturers in the Chinese market or Chinese manufacturers in the German market. Whether German manufacturers continue to expand in China while Chinese manufacturers withdraw from Germany, or German manufacturers exit China while Chinese ones continue to invest in

Germany, these situations are rare under tariff implementation. Tariffs are merely policy directives and do not profoundly impact the entire Sino-German EV supply chain.

However, in the case of unsuccessful negotiations with the EU, the capacity of the German government is not only questioned by German manufacturers but also creates unease among Chinese ones. Therefore, with negotiations failing, both sides lose their sense of economic predictability, destabilizing mutual investment behaviors. This instability is particularly evident in the long term, where it represents a dual play or transitional strategy, influenced largely by the underlying mistrust between China and Germany amid efforts to mitigate risks. Both sides are forced to seek alternative markets to avoid greater geopolitical risks, with tariffs playing a supporting role rather than a primary one. Chinese manufacturers, by focusing on expanding their reach into new markets in Norway (which is exempt from EV import tariffs), Asia, Latin America, and Africa, reduce their dependence on the EU market. Therefore, in the long run, both German and Chinese manufacturers will build a more diversified global market presence. This strategic diversification enables them to mitigate risks associated with over-reliance on any single market.

4.2.3 Scenario (-1, -1)

Both sides mutually abandon each other's markets. In the scenario where tariffs are imposed, based on current practices of German manufacturers, even if the EU imposes tariffs and German government mediation fails, German manufacturers would scale back their operations in China to some extent, while Chinese manufacturers would correspondingly reduce their activities in Germany. This results in a lose-lose situation. Lastly, if both Chinese and German manufacturers choose to defect, the result is a lose-lose situation (-1, -1). Both sides suffer from diminished competitiveness and market presence, illustrating the detrimental effects of defection on both parties.

In summary, whether the EU successfully avoids EV tariffs or not, the win-win situation for Sino-German businesses lies in continuing to invest in each other's markets, while the lose-lose scenario arises from diverging from this path. Some German manufacturers remain optimistic about the Chinese market, especially in the short-term outlook for the EV market. However, under a risk-averse backdrop, some companies may harbor concerns about potential tariff losses and geopolitical risks, leading them to consider scaling back their presence in China. Concurrently, Chinese manufacturers would integrate and diversify their supply chains in response to competitors' actions. Nevertheless, this dynamic remains a zero-sum game, offering no benefits to the overall development of the EV industry. The inefficiencies caused by tariffs are challenging to resolve. In essence, on this issue, German and Chinese manufacturers alike, regardless of their strategic choices, will suffer as victims of EV tariff policies.

Conclusion

This article employs game theory to analyze the potential interactions between the EU, Germany, and China in the context of the EU levying additional duties on Chinese EVs. It also examines the responses and strategies of these actors following the tariff implementation, drawing an analysis of the resulting outcomes.

Based on the analysis, we conclude that the optimal scenario would ideally involve the EU refraining from imposing tariffs on Chinese EVs to avoid triggering retaliatory measures from China, as tariffs can distort trade for both parties. Given the current state of affairs, it is evident that this has not occurred. Therefore, to mitigate additional negative consequences, the next best approach would be for the EU to incrementally impose tariffs on Chinese EVs, recognizing the zero-sum nature of the situation. This measured strategy aims to

balance protecting domestic industries with maintaining stable trade relations, albeit within a competitive framework. For the German government, as a pivotal player in both the EU and Chinese markets, the challenge lies in navigating these tensions while securing its automotive sector's competitiveness and future growth. The best way is to engage in negotiations aimed at mitigating the risks associated with tariffs. From the Chinese perspective, the government has implemented retaliatory tariffs but has also shown a willingness to negotiate with Germany, acknowledging the need for cooperation in EV development amid strained relations with the US. This approach will undergo constructive dialogue that balances economic interests and minimizes potential disruptions to bilateral trade relations. German and Chinese manufacturers should continue expanding their presence in their respective markets to counter protectionist measures, aiming to sustain mutual economic benefits and foster ongoing growth and cooperation in the global EV market.

Looking ahead, the resolution of these disputes will likely hinge on diplomatic negotiations and strategic compromises that balance protectionist measures with maintaining open and fair global trade. The game theory analysis suggests that increased tariffs harm the interests of most stakeholders. The focus should be on sustainable strategies for engaging with China, the world's largest EV stakeholder, rather than relying on short-term tariff solutions.

References

- Agence France-Presse. (2024, May 14). Germany, Sweden lukewarm on tariffs on Chinese electric cars. *New Straits Times*. <https://www.nst.com.my/news-cars-bikes-trucks/2024/05/1050699/germany-sweden-lukewarm-tariffs-chinese-electric-cars>
- Baur, A. (2024, February 12). *German manufacturing focuses on diversifying supply chains* [Press release]. IFO

- Institute.
<https://www.ifo.de/en/press-release/2024-02-12/german-manufacturing-focuses-diversifying-supply-chains>
- Blenkinsop, P. (2024, July 16). EU countries divided on Chinese EV tariffs in vote, sources say. *Reuters*.
<https://www.reuters.com/business/autos-transportation/eu-members-give-mixed-view-vote-chinese-ev-tariffs-sources-say-2024-07-16/>
- Baden Württemberg International. (2024, June 25). *The first high-level dialogue under the China-Germany dialogue and cooperation mechanism on climate change and green transition*.
<https://bw-i.cn/en/news/537.html>
- Cash, J. (2024, June 17). China opens tit-for-tat anti-dumping probe into EU pork. *Reuters*.
<https://www.reuters.com/markets/commodities/china-opens-anti-dumping-probe-into-imported-pork-by-products-eu-2024-06-17/>
- Cater, L. (2024, June 22). Habeck blames China's Russia support for worsening Berlin-Beijing relations. *Politico*.
<https://www.politico.eu/article/germany-robert-habeck-blames-china-russia-putin-support-ukraine-war-berlin-beijing-relations/>
- Interesse, G. (2025, May 26). *China-Germany economic relations 2025: What Merz's leadership means for trade and investment*. China Briefing.
<https://www.china-briefing.com/news/china-germany-relations-2025-merz-leadership-trade-investment/>
- Ding, C., Zhang, M. & Sun, L. (2024). 中欧新能源汽车产业争端：现状、原因和前景 [Sino-European disputes over the new energy vehicle industry: Status, causes, and prospects]. *欧洲研究*, 42(2), 36-62, 173-174.
<http://ies.cass.cn/cn/periodical/202406/W020240612614461842282.pdf>
- German Press Agency. (2024, June 17). China: Deutsche Firmen in China klagen über Preisdruck. *Handelsblatt*.
<https://www.handelsblatt.com/politik/international/china-deutsche-firmen-in-china-klagen-ueber-preisdruck/100045798.html>
- European Commission. (2023, October 4). *Commission launches investigation on subsidised electric cars from China* [Press release].
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_4752
- European Commission. (2024, July 4). *Commission imposes provisional countervailing duties on imports of battery electric vehicles from China while discussions with China continue* [Press release].
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_24_3630
- EVTank. (2024, January 19). 2023年全球锂离子电池出货量达1202.6GWh · 2030年远期出货量预测值调低至5000GWh [Global lithium-ion battery shipments reached 1,202.6 GWh in 2023; 2030 long-term forecast revised down to 5,000 GWh]. China YiWei Institute of Economics.
<http://www.evtank.cn/DownloadDetail.aspx?ID=547>
- EVTank. (2025, January 15). 2024年全球新能源汽车销量达1823.6万辆 · 中国占比超过70% [Global new energy vehicle sales reached 18.236 million in 2024, with China accounting for over 70%]. China YiWei Institute of Economics.
<http://www.evtank.cn/DownloadDetail.aspx?ID=596>
- Fudenberg, D., & Tirole, J. (1991). *Game Theory*. MIT Press.
- International Energy Agency. (2014). *Trends 2014 in photovoltaic applications: Survey report of selected IEA countries between 1992 and 2013* [Fact sheet]. https://iea-pvps.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/IEA_PVPS_Trends_2014_in_PV_Applications_-_lr.pdf
- Jessen, J. (2025, April 11). China & EU: Could

- minimum EV prices replace tariffs? *Sustainability Magazine*.
<https://sustainabilitymag.com/articles/china-eu-could-minimum-ev-prices-replace-tariffs>
- Jian, B. (2024, June 14). 欧盟要对中国电车加征关税 · 中国可用两套打法应对 [The EU plans to impose additional tariffs on Chinese EVs; China can respond with two strategies]. *澎湃新闻 The Paper*.
https://www.thepaper.cn/newsDetail_forward_27730842
- Kanter, J., & Bradsher, K. (2013, July 27). Europe and China agree to settle solar panel fight. *The New York Times*.
<https://www.nytimes.com/2013/07/28/business/global/european-union-and-china-settle-solar-panel-fight.html>
- Kratz, A., Boullenois, C., & Smith, J. (2024). *Why isn't Europe diversifying from China?* [Research note]. Rhodium Group.
<https://rhg.com/research/why-isnt-europe-diversifying-from-china/>
- Lei, K. (2023, January 11). BMW sells 41,886 BEVs in China in 2022. *CNEV Post*.
https://cnevpost.com/2023/01/11/bmw-sells-41886-bevs-china-2022/?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Lewis, M. K. (2010). The prisoner's dilemma posed by free trade agreements: Can open access provisions provide an escape? *Chicago Journal of International Law*, 11, 631–661.
<https://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/cjil/vol11/iss2/24>
- Lunday, C. (2025, April 07). *Trump's tariffs add urgency to Germany's coalition talks, says Merz*. Politico.
<https://www.politico.eu/article/friedrich-merz-pivots-competitiveness-donald-trump-tariffs-jolt-german-coalition-talks/>
- Masengarb, C. (2024, June 27). Aus ampel-not will Scholz den deal mit China - und stellt sich damit gegen die EU. *Focus*.
https://www.focus.de/finanzen/news/bruessel-genervt-vom-kanzler-scholz-unterwandert-die-eu-strafzoelle-gegen-chinesische-e-autos_id_260088406.html
- Matthes, J. (2024). China's trade surplus—implications for the world and for Europe. *Intereconomics*. 59(2). 104–111.
<https://www.intereconomics.eu/contents/year/2024/number/2/article/china-s-trade-surplus-implications-for-the-world-and-for-europe.html>
- Mercedes-Benz Group. (2023). *Annual report 2023*. <https://group.mercedes-benz.com/documents/investors/reports/annual-report/mercedes-benz/mercedes-benz-annual-report-2023-incl-combined-management-report-mbg-ag.pdf>
- Myerson, Roger B. (1991). *Game theory: Analysis of conflict*. Harvard University Press.
- Oemisch, C. (2024, January 12). *Volkswagen Group posts solid growth in deliveries in 2023 and strong increase in all-electric vehicles* [Press release]. Volkswagen Group. https://www.volkswagen-group.com/en/press-releases/volkswagen-group-posts-solid-growth-in-deliveries-in-2023-and-strong-increase-in-all-electric-vehicles-18057?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Osborne, M. J. (2004). *An introduction to game theory*. Oxford University Press.
- Pineau, E., Irish, J., & Melander, I. (2024, May 6). Macron, von der Leyen press China's Xi on trade in Paris talks. *Reuters*.
<https://www.reuters.com/world/chinas-xi-paris-meet-macron-with-trade-ukraine-talks-planned-2024-05-06/>
- Reuters. (2024, September 17). Germany's Habeck calls for political solution to EV tariff dispute with China. *Reuters*.
<https://www.reuters.com/business/autos-transportation/germanys-habeck-calls-political-solution-ev-tariff-dispute-with-china-2024-09-17/>
- Reuters. (2025, March 18). China's BYD to complete process to choose location for third plant in Europe in 7-8 months. *Reuters*.

<https://www.reuters.com/business/autos-transportation/chinas-byd-complete-process-choose-location-third-plant-europe-7-8-months-2025-03-18/>

Riegert, B. (2024, June 12). 關稅爭議：歐盟對中國電動汽車加徵最高38%關稅

[Tariff dispute: EU imposes up to 38% additional duties on Chinese electric vehicles]. Deutsche Welle.

<https://www.dw.com/zh/关税争议欧盟对中国电动汽车加征最高38关税/a-69344436>

Rinke, A. (2025, April 7). Exclusive: Fearing further market meltdown, Germany's Merz calls for swift action on tariffs. *Reuters*.

<https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/fearing-further-market-meltdown-germanys-merz-calls-swift-action-tariffs-2025-04-07/>

Sebastian, G. (2021). *In the driver's seat: China's electric vehicle makers target Europe* [Report]. Mercator Institute for China Studies.

<https://merics.org/en/report/drivers-seat-chinas-electric-vehicle-makers-target-europe>

Sebastian, G. (2022). *The bumpy road ahead in China for Germany's carmakers* [Report]. Mercator Institute for China Studies.

https://merics.org/sites/default/files/2022-10/MERICS_China_Monitor_No79-Automotive-RD-in-China_EN_0.pdf

Sink, J. (2024, May 13). Biden aims to show voters he's as tough on China as Trump. *Bloomberg*.

<https://www.bloomberg.com/news/newsletters/2024-05-13/biden-aims-to-show-voters-he-s-as-tough-on-china-as-trump>

Sundari, S. (2024). Tensions in EU-China trade relations: The impact of China's competitive advantage in strategic industries. *International Journal of Economic Research and Financial*

Accounting. 2(4). 905–913.

<https://doi.org/10.55227/ijerfa.v2i4.142>

Tan, H. (2025, April 14). US tariffs could give the EU exactly what it doesn't want: even more Chinese products. *Yahoo News*.

<https://www.yahoo.com/news/us-tariffs-could-eu-exactly-091640202.html>

The White House. (2024, May 14). *President Biden takes action to protect American workers and businesses from China's unfair trade practices* [Fact sheet]. The White House Archives.

<https://bidenwhitehouse.archives.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2024/05/14/fact-sheet-president-biden-takes-action-to-protect-american-workers-and-businesses-from-chinas-unfair-trade-practices/#:~:text=Ship%2Dto%2DShore%20Cranes,-The%20tariff%20rate&text=The%20Administration%20continues%20to%20deliver,cranes%20or%20other%20heavy%20equipment>

Wu, S., & Blenkinsop, P. (2024, May 29). China gears up to make a deal with Europe as EV tariffs loom. *Reuters*.

<https://www.reuters.com/business/autos-transportation/china-gears-up-make-deal-with-europe-ev-tariffs-loom-2024-05-29/>

Xpeng Motors. (2024, May 16). Xpeng announces its arrival in France. *Xpeng*.

<https://www.xpeng.com/news/018f94cca0c78f6136512c9e8d4f0178>

Zhang, H. & Shi, R. (2023). Global localization: German corporations between EU policies and China's innovation surge—Case studies of Siemens and BASF. *European Youth Perspectives on International Relations of China*.

<https://www.europeanguanxi.com/eypic>

Ruotong Shi

ow12srt@gmail.com

Ruotong Shi is a lecturer in the School of Foreign Languages at Nanjing Normal University. She earned her Ph.D. in German Studies from Shanghai International Studies University. She holds a B.A. degree in German Studies from Nanjing University of Technology and an M.A. degree in German Translation and Interpreting from Tongji University in Shanghai. She focuses on the historical and contemporary relationship between China and Germany.

Hanyi Zhang

henyazhang@gmail.com

Hanyi Zhang is a PhD student at the Chair for Religious Studies and Intercultural Theology at Humboldt-Universität of Berlin. She received her M.A. in Religion and Culture from Humboldt-Universität of Berlin, B.Sc. in Economics from Freie Universität Berlin, and B.A. and M.A. degrees in German Studies. Her research interests include Sino-German relations.

China's Dominance in the Rare Earth Supply Chain and the EU's Strategic Response

Audrey BERDER

This paper investigates the critical strengths and vulnerabilities of China and the European Union (EU) in the rare earth element (REE) supply chain, exploring strategies to enhance resilience both independently and through cooperation. The analysis unfolds in four key sections. First, it outlines the geopolitical and economic importance of REEs in strategic technologies, identifying five major choke points in the global supply chain and China's dominance across these nodes. Second, it examines China's dual advantages—such as processing control—and challenges, including environmental costs. Third, it assesses the EU's emerging recycling efforts and external processing dependencies. Finally, the paper proposes actionable solutions, emphasizing unilateral measures and EU-China collaboration in recycling, technology transfer, and sustainable mining to mitigate supply chain risks. This research contributes to the discourse on global resource security, sovereignty and fair trade by offering a nuanced framework for addressing REE supply challenges.

Keywords: Rare earth, supply chain, geopolitics, imbalance, environmental cost, technological sovereignty, dual-use item

Introduction

Rare earth elements (REEs)—a group of seventeen metals with unique magnetic and electrochemical properties—have become the lifeblood of modern technological and military supremacy. REEs are categorized into two groups: heavy (HREEs) and light (LREEs). Heavy rare earths are far more strategically valuable—critical for advanced technologies like precision-guided weapons, electric

vehicles, and wind turbines—yet they are significantly scarcer in nature. Light rare earths, by contrast, are more abundant but less essential for cutting-edge applications. From the precision-guided missiles defending Ukraine to the electric vehicles powering Europe's green transition, these unassuming elements now occupy center stage in 21st-century geopolitics. While geologically abundant, their supply chain has become dangerously concentrated, with China controlling about 70% of the global REE supply, around 90% of REE processing and supplying about 90% of global rare earth magnets in 2025 (Baskara & Schwartz (2025); Mining Technology, 2025). The European Union's near-total dependence—importing nearly 99% of its REE supply and 98% of its rare earths magnets from China (European Commission, 2023b)—represents one of the most acute vulnerabilities in its industrial ecosystem.

This dependency crisis did not emerge overnight. Since the 80s, then the 90s marked the collapse of the U.S.-led rare earth industry, China executed a decades-long strategy of market consolidation through state subsidies, export quotas, human capital training and vertical integration (Hart, 2025). By 2008, China had secured numerous REE technologies and assets overseas—including acquisitions in the U.S.—solidifying its dominance in global production. At its peak, China accounted for 97% of the world's rare earth output, leveraging these strategic investments to control the industry's supply chain (Bauk et al., 2023). By 2010, China controlled all aspects of the global REE value chain, with this monopoly, its rare earth embargo against Japan in autumn 2010, caused a dramatic price surge—250% to 600%—over several months (Bradsher, 2010). Today, amid the triple shocks of the Russo-Ukrainian War, U.S.-China decoupling with Trump's more aggressive trade policies, and Europe's re-industrialization push, REEs have transformed from industrial commodities into strategic

weapons.

This paper examines a pivotal issue in global resource security: *What are the current strengths and weaknesses of China and the European Union in the rare earth element supply chain, and how can both regions address their challenges individually and collaboratively?* To answer this question, the analysis proceeds in four sections. First, it assesses the contemporary political-economic significance of REEs in strategic technologies, clarifying five critical choke points in the global supply chain and China’s dominant positions within each node. Second, it evaluates China’s supply chain advantages and vulnerabilities, including its control over processing capacity and environmental trade-offs. Third, it analyzes the EU’s nascent recycling initiatives and reliance on external processing. Finally, the paper proposes policy recommendations—both unilateral and bilateral—to strengthen supply chain resilience, with a focus on EU-China partnerships ensuring greater recycling, fair technology transfer, and sustainable mining.

Figure 1

Note. China remains dominant in rare-earth production and processing, while the EU relies heavily on imports despite sizable consumption. Author’s own visualization. Data source from USGS (2024), IEA (2023), and European Commission (2023a).

1. The Political-Economic Significance of Rare Earths

At its core, REEs are a matter of sovereignty. Rare earths, like all strategic resources, are inherently political assets. Their control translates directly into geopolitical capital—the greater a nation’s dominance over such materials, the more weight it carries in shaping global norms, alliances, and technological trajectories. (Scholvin & Wigell, 2018) This phenomenon, often termed "resource statecraft" or "mineral mercantilism," underscores a fundamental truth: in an era of urgent green transitions and intense tech competition. China’s near full control over the global REE supply chain has afforded it substantial leverage in international technological innovation, and therefore also in global trade, diplomacy, defense and security. (Klinger, 2018).

Figure 2

Note. The chart illustrates China’s rapid rise in rare-earth-elements (REE) output from 1980 to 2023, the peak of its global market share in 2010, and the subsequent decline in share to 55 percent by 2023 as other countries expanded their own production. Author’s own visualization. Data sourced from USGS (2024).

As early as the 80s, China has clearly declared REEs to be a strategic asset with its industry fully controlled by state-owned enterprises (SOE) (BGR Group,2024). China has strategically integrated its rare earth policies into broader economic statecraft, using export controls and

production quotas as tools to exert influence (Wübbecke, 2013). A defining moment in the geopolitical significance of rare earths occurred in 2010, when China imposed export restrictions around key heavy and light REEs on Japan amid a territorial dispute, demonstrating its ability to weaponize rare earth supply chains (Wübbecke, 2013). While the direct link between the territorial dispute and China's rare earth export restrictions remains debated, the policy shift had an undeniable market impact—triggering a dramatic surge in rare earth prices, with some elements increasing tenfold or more (Bradsher, 2010). At the peak of the crisis, Dysprosium oxide, a key mineral for electric vehicles and missiles, jumped from \$110 to \$508 a kilogram in a year. (Bradsher, 2010). At that time, China controlled 97% of global REE production (USGS, 2011) making Dysprosium and Terbium particularly susceptible to price shocks. According to the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) and trade reports, in 2010, around 90-93% of Japan's rare earth element imports did indeed come from China, with only 3% coming from non-Chinese sources (e.g., India, Vietnam), with the rest stockpiled (USGS, 2011). Facing severe dysprosium shortages, Japanese automakers were among the hardest hit by this shock, U.S. and European automakers such as Ford and GM also faced shortages of EV components. This also affected the wind turbine industry and electronic industry, such as Siemens, Vestas, Hitachi, and Philips. (U.S. Department of Energy, 2011) This incident served as a global wake-up call, exposing the strategic vulnerabilities of many nations due to their heavy reliance on Chinese exports. In response, countries around the world began intensifying efforts to diversify their supply chains and reduce dependency.

Another case is China's 2023 export restrictions on gallium and germanium, which had global ramifications, directly affecting semiconductor, defense, and renewable energy supply chains worldwide. The United States responded by accelerating partnerships

with alternative suppliers—including Canada's Teck Resources—and invoking the Defense Production Act to boost domestic production and build strategic stockpiles of gallium and germanium, for which it previously lacked sufficient reserves. (Merwat, 2025; Defense Production Act, 1950). Similarly, the European Union fast-tracked its Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) (European Commission, 2023b) to diversify sources and boost recycling, including German industry leaders lobbying for expedited mining permits in Namibia and Rwanda. On December 3, 2024, China escalated its approach with an official ban on exports of gallium, germanium, antimony, and other rare metals specifically to the U.S, in retaliation for U.S. semiconductor-export restrictions. It is therefore no exaggeration to say that the world is witnessing an increasingly aggressive weaponization of strategic resources, with rare earth metals being a prime example—and with all the pawns aligned in China's favor, the global balance of power hangs in the balance.

The growing demand for REEs is driven not only by clean energy technologies but also by their critical role in modern military systems and advanced industrial applications. For instance, a single American F-35 fighter jet requires more than 400 kilograms of REE, while a Virginia-class nuclear submarine needs around 4000 kilograms (Defence Express 2025). Precision-guided munitions, radar systems, and electronic warfare equipment all depend on REEs for their superior magnetic and conductive properties. Beyond defense, the renewable energy sector consumes vast quantities—each 3-megawatt wind turbine contains roughly 600 kilograms of rare earth magnets, primarily neodymium (IEA, 2021). Meanwhile, in the electric vehicle (EV) industry, a single EV battery requires between 1 to 3 kilograms of REEs, depending on the motor design (European Commission, 2020). REEs are also crucial for consumer electronics, including smartphones, laptops, and LED screens, where they enable miniaturization and energy efficiency. This is precisely why REEs are classified as 'dual-use' commodities—a strategic

resource that influences everything from high-stakes national policies to the everyday lives of ordinary citizens.

To understand the geopolitical and economic challenges surrounding REEs, this analysis identifies five critical choke points in the global supply chain where China currently maintains dominant market positions.

1. Exploration and Mining

The initial stage involves geological surveys, exploratory drilling, and extraction of rare earth-bearing ores through open-pit or underground mining (USGS, 2023).

1.1 China's Position:

- Controls \approx 37% of global REE reserves (USGS, 2023)
- Produces \approx 70% of global mined REEs (its Bayan Obo mine alone yields 45%) (Hart, 2025)
- *Vulnerability:* As of 2022, about 50% of China's heavy REEs depend on Myanmar where illegal mining activities remain very important (USGS, 2023).

2. Processing

The transformation of raw ore into purified rare earth compounds through:

The REE processing is split into three key parts:

- *Beneficiation:* Physical concentration via crushing/flotation (Jordens et al., 2013)
- *Separation:* Chemical isolation of individual REEs (Jordens et al., 2013)
- *Refining:* Final purification to \geq 99.9% purity (Gschneidner, 2015)

2.2 China's Position:

- As of 2025, it processes between 90% of global REEs (Baskaran & Schwartz, 2025)

- It has near total control (99%) of global heavy REE processing (Hale, 2025)
- *Vulnerability:* Generates 2,000 tons of radioactive waste per ton REE (Nayar, 2021)

3. Metal and Alloy Production

Conversion of refined oxides into functional metals/alloys via molten salt electrolysis (Gschneidner, 2015).

3.1 China's Position:

- In 2025, China produced 90% of global rare earths. (Waldersee & Steitz, 2025)
- In 2024, China produced 300,000 tons of NdFeB magnets. (Baskaran & Shwartz, 2025)
- *Vulnerability:* Relies on foreign technology for high-end alloy and high-purity metal production (Quest Metals, 2025)

4. Manufacturing (End-Use Products)

Integration of REE materials into final applications like EV motors and wind turbines (Alonso et al., 2012).

4.1 China's Position:

- Produces 90% of the world's rare earth magnets, essential for EV, wind turbines and consumer electronics (Emont, 2025)
- *Vulnerability:* Still depends on Western and Japan in aerospace-grade application

5. Recycling

Recovery of REEs from end-of-life products through hydrometallurgical processes (Binnemans et al., 2013).

5.1 China's Position:

- As of 2023, China recycles 30,500 tons REE recycles (Liu, 2025)
- *Opportunity:* New bioleaching techniques emerging (Collins, 2025)

2. China's Rare Earth Empire: Unrivaled Power, Hidden Fault Lines

China's dominance is both an economic triumph and a political weapon. However, beneath this formidable control lie vulnerabilities—environmental degradation, international pushback, labor and corruption issues, but also the looming specter of resource depletion (Hart, 2025). This section delves into the paradox of China's rare earth empire, first unpacking the key pillars of its strength while also exposing the cracks that could undermine its supremacy.

China's stranglehold on rare earths is not accidental but the result of decades of strategic planning and state-backed industrial policy. Unlike Western nations, which fragmented their rare earth supply chains in the face of environmental and economic pressures, China pursued vertical integration with ruthless efficiency. By controlling every stage—from mining and refining to high-end magnet production—Beijing has ensured that competitors remain dependent on its exports. In 2023 alone, China produced around 240,000 metric tons of rare earth oxides (REOs) enough to build over 200 million electric vehicle motors, dwarfing the United States' output of 43,000 metric tons and leaving the European Union, which lacks primary production entirely, scrambling for alternatives (USGS, 2023).

But raw production is only part of the story. The real power lies in processing, where China commands a staggering 90-99% share of global capacity, particularly for high-value products like neodymium-iron-boron (NdFeB) magnets, essential for electric vehicles and military-grade systems (Adamas Intelligence, 2022). China's dominance in REE processing is underpinned by three key structural advantages that have collectively created an ecosystem that global competitors struggle to replicate. These advantages are : mass production at lower costs, control over all

stages of its supply chain, and looser environmental rules in the past, important state subsidies, and a strong educational, training ecosystem.

First, China's economies of scale and its predominantly state-owned enterprise driven model, have created production volumes that render competition economically not viable for most international players. The Bayan Obo complex in Inner Mongolia alone processes over 120,000 metric tons of rare earth oxides annually—more than double the combined capacity of all non-Chinese processors (USGS, 2023).

Second, China's vertically integrated supply chains eliminate coordination costs that plague fragmented Western operations. Major producers like China Northern Rare Earth Group control almost every stage from mining through to magnet manufacturing within geographically compact industrial parks. China's REE supply chain is deliberately segmented across specialized regions, with Inner Mongolia's Bayan Obo—the world's largest rare earth mine—producing 70% of China's light REE and 40% of global supply (USGS, 2023). Jiangxi and Fujian provinces dominate in heavy REE extraction through ion-adsorption clay deposits (Hart, 2025). For midstream processing, Baotou Rare Earth Industrial Park in Inner Mongolia—China's largest processing site—processes raw rare earth concentrates into high-purity oxides and metals, handling over 60% of domestic output (Hart, 2025). Additionally, cities like Jingdezhen in Jiangxi province specialize in producing sintered rare earth permanent magnets (e.g., NdFeB magnets) critical for electric vehicles (EVs) and wind turbines (Adamas Intelligence, 2022). Downstream, Chinese manufacturers integrate rare earth materials into high-tech end products, including EV motors, wind turbine generators, and consumer electronics. Companies like Tesla's Shanghai Gigafactory and Goldwind (the world's largest wind turbine manufacturer) rely on China's REE supply chain for critical components. This geographic division is enforced by state

quotas and ownership—regional SOEs like China Northern Rare Earth Group (Baotou) and China Southern Rare Earth Group (Jiangxi) operate as oligopolies under Beijing's centralized planning (Hart, 2025). By locking in this end-to-end control—from mine to magnet—China minimizes export dependencies, dictates global pricing, and forces foreign competitors into niche roles.

Third, China's processing expansion benefited from decades of lax environmental enforcement that externalized ecological costs. Though recent environmental reforms have increased compliance costs, first-mover advantages allowed Chinese processors to establish irreversible technological leads.

Beyond its structural advantages in scale, integration, and regulatory history, China's rare earth processing dominance is further reinforced by two often-overlooked pillars: comprehensive state subsidies and a meticulously engineered human capital pipeline. These factors have created both economic and technological barriers to entry that compound the challenges faced by competing nations. China's system of generous subsidies to state-owned enterprises (SOEs) is a cornerstone of its political economy, designed to cultivate "national champions" that dominate global markets—particularly in strategic sectors like rare earths—while ensuring employment stability for key urban elites critical to regime cohesion. (Hart, 2025) Although comprehensive data on subsidies remains opaque, evidence reveals that rare earth producers benefit from extensive state support, including tax incentives, discounted land and energy, low-interest loans, and R&D funding, all outlined in China's industrial policies to suppress production costs and solidify market control. (Hart, 2025) These subsidies, often exceeding SOEs' reported profits, are enabled by systemic advantages such as state-mandated price controls on key inputs, protection from competition, and lax environmental enforcement, distorting market

efficiency in favor of political objectives. While this state-driven model grants China overwhelming competitive leverage—allowing it to dictate global supply chains and pricing—it constitutes unfair competition for other nations, as artificially suppressed costs and non-market advantages undermine fair trade and discourage private-sector innovation abroad, reinforcing China's monopolistic position through economic practices that rival economies cannot replicate under free-market conditions. (Hart, 2025)

Complementing these financial supports, China has established a comprehensive education and training ecosystem specifically tailored to rare earth metallurgy. China is actively establishing a comprehensive education and training ecosystem to cultivate future leaders in the rare earth industry, as evidenced by initiatives such as the Baotou Rare Earth High-Tech Zone's talent development programs, which have attracted 89 academic experts and assembled 3,228 R&D professionals to support innovation and industrial growth (Gao et al., 2023). Additionally, partnerships with leading universities, such as Shanghai Jiao Tong University and Tsinghua University, along with substantial investments in talent retention policies—including 7 million yuan in dedicated funding—demonstrate China's commitment to building a skilled workforce for the rare earth sector (Gao et al., 2023). Under China's Rare Earth Industry Development Plan (MIIT, 2021), rare earth talent development has been prioritized through inclusion in the national Catalog of 紧缺 Talents for New Materials Industry, prompting initiatives like Inner Mongolia University of Science and Technology's pioneering Rare Earth Engineering undergraduate program (2023) and the 14th Five-Year Plan's ambitious target to train 10,000 specialists in green smelting, high-purity separation, and magnetic materials by 2025. (State Council of China, 2016)

Yet, for all its strengths, China's rare earth empire is built on fragile foundations. The most glaring vulnerability is environmental degradation, a crisis so severe that it threatens the industry's

long-term viability. The Bayan Obo mine in Inner Mongolia, the world's largest rare earth mine, is infamous for its massive tailings pond—holding over 70,000 tons of radioactive thorium. Due to poor lining, toxic waste is leaking into groundwater and could contaminate the Yellow River, a vital drinking water source (Nayar, 2021). A report from the Atlantic Council shows toxic wastewater lakes, radioactive sludge, and cancer clusters in nearby communities, where farmers have seen their land rendered barren (Hart, 2025).

The problem is exacerbated by China's reliance on ion-adsorption clays in southern provinces like Jiangxi, where rare earth extraction has led to rampant deforestation and radioactive runoff (Liu, 2016). Ion-adsorption clays, which contain HREEs like dysprosium and terbium, are a major source of pollution due to their unique extraction process and the chemicals involved. Unlike conventional rare earth ores, these clays are mined through a method called in-situ leaching, where large amounts of ammonium sulfate or other acidic solutions are pumped into the ground to dissolve and extract rare earth ions (Xu et al., 2023). This process leads to severe environmental damage, including soil acidification, groundwater contamination, and deforestation. The primary pollution issue stems from the leaching chemicals, which remain in the soil and water long after extraction. Research indicates that even after mining stops, the land remains barren for decades because the leaching process destroys essential nutrients and microbial life needed for plant regrowth (Li et al., 2013). Ammonium sulfate, the most commonly used leaching agent, breaks down into ammonia and sulfates, increasing nitrogen levels in nearby water sources and causing algal blooms that disrupt aquatic ecosystems (Edwards et al., 2024). Additionally, the acids used in processing—such as hydrochloric or sulfuric acid—can mobilize toxic heavy metals like cadmium and lead, which then seep into rivers and farmland (Zhao et al., 2025). A 2025 Atlantic Council

report analyzing China's rare earth strategy revealed that tailings ponds from ionic clay mines in Jiangxi and Fujian provinces contain uranium and thorium radiation levels up to 15 times higher than regulatory limits—posing severe risks to local water supplies (Hart, 2025). Despite government pledges to curb pollution, 60% of rare earth refineries inspected in 2024 still lacked proper wastewater treatment systems, exacerbating heavy metal contamination in agricultural regions downstream (Hart, 2025).

In response to mounting environmental damage from rare earth mining, particularly in ion-adsorption clay regions, the Chinese government has introduced a series of regulatory measures aimed at reducing pollution while maintaining production output. The most significant of these initiatives, the Rare Earth Industry Development Plan (2016–2020), mandated that all mining enterprises implement wastewater recycling systems and soil remediation protocols by 2018 (Andrew-Speed & Hove, 2023). In October 2024, China enacted the Rare Earth Management Regulation, a comprehensive legal framework consisting of 32 articles. The regulation defines the supervisory roles of various government bodies, promoting greater accountability, standardization, and traceability across the rare earth supply chain (BGR Group, 2024). Notably, Article 27 explicitly mandates penalties for violations of laws related to energy conservation, environmental protection, clean production, workplace safety, and fire prevention. Non-compliant entities will face enforcement actions from the relevant authorities in accordance with legal provisions (BGR Group, 2024). China's state-owned rare earth firms, such as China Northern Rare Earth Group, have made measurable progress in reducing environmental harm, cutting wastewater emissions by 30% in some processing plants since 2020 through advanced green technologies (Hart, 2025). However, this contrasts sharply with small-scale and illegal mining operations, which still account for 20–30% of China's output and rely on highly polluting methods like unregulated acid leaching in Jiangxi, contaminating soil and water with

heavy metals (Hart, 2025). Even large, regulated facilities like the Baotou mining complex in Inner Mongolia continue to pose severe environmental risks, with its 10-square-kilometer toxic tailings lake leaching radioactive thorium and uranium into groundwater, damaging agriculture and public health (Hart, 2025). These disparities reveal a fragmented industry where state-led sustainability efforts are undermined by persistent illegal activity and the lingering ecological costs of legacy pollution.

Stricter environmental regulations will likely constrain rare earth production and increase operational costs, potentially raising consumer prices and accelerating global supply chain diversification toward alternative sources like Australia and the U.S., while market analysts predict price surges due to tightening supply, growing green energy demand, and speculative investor activity. (Walk the Street Capital, 2025). One of the key actions taken by the Chinese government to address the complex sustainability challenges in the rare earth sector was the 2022 Rare Earth Industry Consolidation Program. This policy mandated mergers among state-owned enterprises (SOEs) to centralize production, strengthen pricing power, and improve regulatory oversight—particularly in enforcing stricter environmental standards (Zhou & Brooke, 2022). China's sustained overexploitation has also led to a significant decline in its global share of these critical resources. According to the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS, 2023), China's rare earth reserves accounted for 37% of the global total in 2010 but have since decreased to 33% by 2023. Continuing at this speed and style, China is expected to lose its reserve dominance entirely by 2045, with some projections suggesting heavy rare earth deposits could be commercially exhausted as early as 2038 (Chen, 2025).

Despite China's dominance in rare earth production, its recycling sector remains underdeveloped especially compared to other

stages of the supply chain it has almost full control of globally, this is also because so far, recycling fills just 1/8 of China's REE demand (Qiao, 2025). As of 2023, China's REE recycling volume reaches approximately 30,500 tons, which represents only about 12 % of its 2023 REE total production. (Liu, 2025) Today China operates around 250 registered rare earth recycling plants, primarily concentrated in the Jiangxi, Guangdong, and Inner Mongolia provinces. (Qiao, 2025) Initiatives like the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) system supported by national policies require electronics and EV manufacturers to recover rare earths from end-of-life products (Tong et al, 2024). The government's 14th Five-Year Plan (2021–2025) explicitly prioritizes REE recycling innovation, with 2.1 billion RMB (€280 million) in annual subsidies for projects improving recovery efficiency (Qiao, 2025).

3. Europe's Recycling Capacity and Risky Dependence: Rebuilding Rare Earth Sovereignty

The European Union remains heavily reliant on imports for REEs, which are critical for its green technologies, defense systems, and digital infrastructure. According to the European Commission as of 2023, China supplies approximately 98% of the EU's rare earth magnets and 94% of its REE, creating significant supply chain vulnerabilities (European Commission, 2023b). This dependence was exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic and further strained by more recent geopolitical tensions, particularly China's export restrictions on gallium and germanium in July 2023 (Godek, 2025). The EU's rare earth import dependency rate stands at 100% for HREEs such as dysprosium and terbium, which are essential for high-performance magnets in electric vehicles (EVs) and wind turbines (European Commission, 2020).

A notable strength of the EU's rare earth strategy is its focus on recycling and circular economy principles. Belgium and France dominate the EU's

rare earth recycling efforts. The Franco-Belgium Solvay Group stands out as a leader, through its La Rochelle plant, specializes in extracting neodymium and dysprosium from end-of-life products like hard disk drives and hybrid vehicle motors, while achieving high purity levels. (Solvay, 2022). France's Rhodia (now part of Solvay) pioneered hydrometallurgical recycling techniques, processing 8,000 tons of fluorescent lamp waste annually to recover europium and yttrium (Solvay, 2022; European Commission, 2020). The French company Orano (formerly Areva), Germany's Hybrit Initiative and Estonia's company Silmet are all actively investing in different REE recycling, mostly from electronic waste and permanent magnets (Jaussaud, 2025; Go, 2022).

Germany, France, and Italy have come together and committed €2.5 billion in joint critical minerals investments by summer 2024, targeting domestic mining, processing, and recycling—particularly lithium, copper, and rare earths—to strengthen EU supply chains under the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) (Pacheco, 2024). German companies such as Schneider Electric and Desoltik are heavily involved in creating more circular economies including in the semiconductor industry to reduce waste while also conserving strategic resources such as REE (Germany Trade & Invest, 2025). The automotive sector is a major driver of recycling efforts, collaborating with recycling firms to recover rare earth elements from end-of-life electric vehicle motors, supporting a more sustainable supply chain. The EU's Battery Regulation, which mandates minimum recycled content in lithium-ion batteries, further incentivizes rare earth recovery (European Commission, 2023c). In terms of raw REE output, Sweden and Finland are the leading producers in the EU. Sweden's Per Geijer deposit and Finland's Sokli mine are among the most promising rare earth projects, with estimated reserves of over 1 million tons of rare earth oxides (Finnish Geological Survey [GTK], 2023; SGU, 2023).

Greenland, while not an EU member, is also a strategic partner with substantial rare earth deposits, particularly in the Kvanefjeld project, which could supply a significant portion of Europe's demand. (Innovation News Network, 2024) The recent geopolitical tensions—sparked by President Trump's 2019 proposal to buy Greenland and countered by Greenland's steps to strengthen ties with China—serve as a clear illustration of the global competition over rare earth mineral resources. For the EU, this underscores the urgent need to secure sustainable partnerships with resource-rich regions like Greenland, or risk falling further behind in the race for critical materials essential to its green and digital transitions (Christiansen, 2025)

Despite the EU's efforts to position itself in the global rare earth supply chain through recycling, it faces significant weaknesses in self-sufficiency, with fragmentation across the supply chain. The newly implemented Critical Raw Materials Act sets an ambitious target for recycled materials to cover 25% of the bloc's rare earth and critical mineral demand by 2030, current recycling rates remain alarmingly low at less than 1% of total consumption. (Onstad, 2024) A major bottleneck is the lack of domestic processing capacity, which creates critical dependencies at different stages of production.

While the EU has some mining projects, such as Norra Kärr in Sweden and Kvanefjeld through Greenland's strong ties with Denmark, the majority of rare earth ores must still be shipped to China for separation and refining, or processing (USGS, 2023). Such fragmentation combined with lengthy national permitting procedures and low levels of public acceptance for the mining industry imposes important financial and temporal burdens on the EU mining companies (European Commission, 2020). This stems primarily from Europe's lack of integrated rare earth facilities capable of performing both large-scale separation and refining, forcing companies to export concentrates to China. Moreover, the mining projects in Norra Kärr

remain in the development stages and face significant permitting and financing challenges before reaching commercial production (European Commission, 2023b). Norra Kärr specifically focuses on light REEs like neodymium and lanthanum, with the potential to supply approximately 5% of Europe's annual demand if fully operational, though ongoing environmental assessments and local opposition have delayed its progress (Geological Survey of Sweden, 2023). This exemplifies the broader difficulties the EU faces with lengthy approval processes, high capital costs, and competition from established global suppliers.

Beyond the mining stage, today the rare earth processing landscape in the European Union currently features two distinct operational facilities with fundamentally different roles. Neo Performance Materials' plant in Estonia operates as a full-scale separation facility, processing raw or semi-processed rare earth ores into pure oxides through conventional refining methods (Neo Material, 2023). This facility represents the EU's only industrial-scale operation capable of performing complete rare earth separation comparable to traditional refineries found in China or other major producing regions. In contrast, Solvay's French facility focuses primarily on circular economy applications, specializing in recovering REEs from post-consumer waste streams such as phosphors from fluorescent lamps rather than processing freshly mined materials (Sinha et al, 2022). While both plants incorporate separation technologies, their operational scopes differ significantly—the Estonian plant addresses primary production needs while the French facility contributes to sustainability through recycling. This dichotomy reflects the fragmented nature of Europe's rare earth supply chain, where no single facility currently combines large-scale primary processing with comprehensive recycling capabilities, this structural gap as a critical vulnerability in the bloc's efforts to achieve rare earth self-sufficiency (European

Commission, 2023b). The EU's reliance on third countries for midstream REE processing exacerbates supply risks. While partnerships with non-Chinese suppliers diversify feedstock, domestic recycling capabilities are still nascent and focused on select applications (ECRMA, 2023) Without a fully integrated supply chain—from mining to magnet production—the EU will remain dependent on external suppliers, leaving its green transition and technological sovereignty at risk. The current patchwork of capabilities, while promising in isolation, fails to address the systemic weaknesses created by supply chain fragmentation.

The geographical dispersion of capabilities further exacerbates inefficiencies. Sweden possesses Europe's largest known rare earth deposit at Kiruna, potentially supplying 18% of EU demand if fully developed (Mining Technology, 2025). However, without sufficient midstream processing infrastructure, these raw materials may still require export for refinement. Similarly, Estonia's projected separation capacity—producing 2,000 rare earth magnets in 2025—will still meet only a fraction of Europe's processed rare earth demand, leaving a significant supply gap (Go, 2022). France and Germany lead in downstream applications, such as magnet production and recycling, with France investing 100 million euros in rare earth magnet supply through initiatives like Orano's La Rochelle recycling facility (Mann, 2024). Yet, these efforts remain disconnected from upstream mining activities, creating a fractured value chain.

Another weakness of the EU is the long lead time for mining projects, compounded by regulatory hurdles, lack of incentives, and public opposition. Environmental concerns have delayed critical developments, such as Portugal's lithium project in the northern Barroso region led by Savannah Resources has been stalled due to local protests, including from local prosecutors, leading to licensing disputes. Likewise, in northern Sweden, climate activist Greta Thunberg joined local protesters—including Indigenous Sami communities—in opposing the development of a

Figure 3

Note. This map highlights key actors in the EU and Nordic region leading in different stages of the REE supply chain. Note that not all are fully operational yet. The largest rare earth element (REE) deposit in the European Union is the Per Geijer deposit in Kiruna, Sweden, owned by LKAB, a Swedish state owned company. Author's own visualization. Data sourced from USGS (2024), LKAB (2023), Neo Material (2023), Rare Earth Exchanges (2025a), Solvay (2022), USGS (2023), & Zadeh (2025).

rare earth deposit on their ancestral lands (Business & Human Rights Resource Centre, 2023). These delays prevent the EU from capitalizing on its resource base, Finland's Sokli projects, production will only start in the late 2030s (Solki, n.d.).

Investment shortfalls further undermine supply chain integration. The rare earth sector requires at least €15 billion investment to achieve its goals of 10-40% self-sufficiency by 2030, yet private investment remains scarce due to high costs and competition from China's subsidized industry (Gauß et al, 2021). While the European Investment Bank (EIB) has allocated € 3 billion for critical raw materials, this covers only a fraction of the necessary funding to achieve the EU's REE independence goals (Hoyer, 2023). This financial gap, if prolonged, will only perpetuate fragmentation,

as projects in mining, processing, and recycling struggle to scale without coordinated capital deployment. European Investment Bank President Werner Hoyer has emphasized the demonstrated efficacy of Europe's coordinated industrial strategy, citing as evidence the transformative outcomes of the 2017 Battery Alliance initiative (Hoyer, 2023). This collaborative framework facilitated the development of globally competitive production capabilities, exemplified by the EIB-financed Northvolt gigafactory, with projections indicating domestic supply will soon satisfy 66% of Europe's lithium-ion battery demand. This precedent holds significant implications for REE security: it demonstrates conclusively that Europe's industrial challenges require systemic, alliance-based solutions rather than fragmented approaches. The Battery Alliance model provides both institutional blueprint and empirical

validation for addressing REE supply vulnerabilities through coordinated action (Hoyer, 2023).

To mitigate these risks, the EU has launched several strategic initiatives. The REE4EU project ran from 2015 to 2019 as part of the EU's Horizon 2020 program, focusing on developing hydrometallurgical recycling processes to recover rare earth elements from end-of-life products like magnets and batteries. Following its conclusion, the EU intensified its efforts to secure REE supply chains with two key initiatives. First, the European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA), launched in 2020, to boost domestic production, processing, and recycling of critical raw materials (Gauß et al. 2021). The ERMA was established only 6 months after the new EU Industrial Strategy and has created a Raw Materials Investment Platform to facilitate large scale and blended finance projects. Second, the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA), 16th of March 2023, which sets binding targets for EU self-sufficiency in REEs by 2030 (European Commission, 2015; European Commission 2024). Together, these initiatives mark a strategic shift from research-driven projects like REE4EU to large-scale policy and industrial actions aimed at reducing reliance on foreign REE supplies.

The Critical Raw Materials Act, establishes ambitious targets to reduce reliance on foreign suppliers of REEs and other strategic minerals. By 2030, the bloc aims to domestically extract at least 10% of its annual consumption of critical raw materials and process 40% locally by 2030 (European Commission, 2023b). As of 2025, progress toward these goals remain in the early stages, with the EU recycling less than 1% of its REE, along with an almost absent and disintegrated production and processing capacity, despite the potential of some known deposits (European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), 2025; European Commission, 2024). To achieve these targets, the EU has

mobilized significant funding, including €1.7 billion for 14 mines to magnet projects across EU Member States, potentially allowing the EU to regain 20% of global REE production share, however greater efforts, unity and public-private investment partnerships are needed (Gauß et al., 2021).

4. Strategic Policy Recommendations for Local REE Supply Chain: Lessons from Global Precedents

4.1 Diversifying and Securing Upstream Supply Through Strategic Partnerships

China dominates with near full control over the global rare earth supply chain yet its position faces mounting pressures—depleting high-grade reserves, environmental constraints, and geopolitical vulnerabilities. As demand for rare earths surges in clean energy and defense technologies, China must future-proof its supply chain through strategic diversification, circular economy innovation, and ESG leadership.

China's rare earth industry faces two major challenges: declining high-grade domestic reserves and increasing environmental scrutiny. To address these issues, China should pursue strategic mining partnerships with resource-rich countries, particularly in Africa and Greenland. A successful precedent for this approach can be found in China's collaboration with Australian lithium producers. In the early 2020s, Chinese companies such as Tianqi Lithium and Ganfeng Lithium secured long-term supply agreements with Australian miners while providing technological expertise and infrastructure investments (IEA, 2023). This model could be replicated for rare earths by partnering with African nations like Namibia, which holds significant deposits of HREEs at the Lofdal project. Another instructive example is Japan's resource diplomacy strategy during the 2010s. Following China's rare earth export restrictions in 2010, Japan diversified its supply by investing in mines in Vietnam, India, and Kazakhstan. China could adopt a similar approach by offering

infrastructure investments and processing technology to African nations, thereby securing new sources of raw materials while strengthening diplomatic ties.

4.1.2 Scaling Up Rare Earth Recycling and Circular Economy Initiatives

China's rare earth recycling industry faces significant challenges, including price volatility due to fluctuating demand in sectors like wind energy, environmental concerns from wet-process recycling (e.g., wastewater pollution), and growing international competition from Southeast Asia and Western nations (Qiao, 2025). To address these issues, the Chinese government has implemented stringent policies such as the 2024 Rare Earth Management Regulations, which promote green technologies, enforce stricter recycling quotas, and incentivize industry consolidation (BGR Group, 2024). Despite these hurdles, opportunities abound, particularly in advancing eco-friendly fire-process recycling, expanding closed-loop supply chains for NdFeB magnets, and leveraging China's dominant position in global rare earth production (68% share in 2023) to secure strategic resource independence (Qiao, 2025). Looking ahead, China's rare earth recycling sector can quickly grow, driven by technological innovation, policy support, and the urgent need to balance economic competitiveness with sustainable resource management in an increasingly contested global market.

4.1.3 Enhancing Environmental and Social Governance (ESG) Standards

China's rare earth industry has faced international criticism for environmental pollution, particularly in Inner Mongolia's Bayan Obo mining district (Hart, 2025). To improve sustainability and market access, China should align its practices with global ESG standards, such as the OECD Due Diligence Guidance for Responsible Mineral

Supply Chains.

A relevant case study is MP Materials, one of the biggest U.S. rare earth companies that revitalized the Mountain Pass mine in California by prioritizing clean extraction technologies and transparency. By adopting stringent environmental controls, MP Materials secured partnerships with European and Japanese manufacturers (MP Materials, 2023). China could similarly attract international buyers by certifying its rare earth production under-recognized sustainability schemes, such as the Initiative for Responsible Mining Assurance (IRMA), already adopted or referenced by a large number of western mining, automaker and tech giants (IRMA, 2018).

4.2 How Can the EU Strengthen Its Rare Earth Supply Chains

To secure its rare earth supply chain, the EU must pursue a three-pronged strategy: (1) developing domestic refining capacity to break dependence on Chinese processing, (2) securing ethical mining partnerships to diversify sources, and (3) driving demand-side innovation to reduce overall reliance. This approach addresses vulnerabilities across the entire value chain while aligning with the EU's climate and technological sovereignty goals.

4.2.1 Building Domestic Refining and Separation Capacity

The European Union faces significant supply chain vulnerabilities, with China supplying 99% of its 17 critical rare earth elements and 98% of rare earth permanent magnets. This near-total dependence creates strategic risks for the European industrial and defense sector (Zimmermann, 2025). Closing this gap requires immediate investment in hydrometallurgical refineries to convert raw ores into usable materials.

The Horizon Europe-funded REEsilience project develops solvent extraction techniques compliant

with EU environmental standards (European Commission, 2023b). The EU can learn from Lynas Rare Earths, an Australian mining company which became the largest non-Chinese supplier after overcoming regulatory hurdles to build a Malaysian refinery (Hunt, 2025). Replicating this success requires tax incentives, faster permitting, and co-funding through the European Raw Materials Fund. Germany's €1 billion investment in domestic processing under its National Industrial Strategy 2030 provides an interesting model for other EU countries to follow. (Rare Earth Exchanges, 2025b). As the EU boosts its rare earth production—critical for wind turbines and electric vehicles—it must tackle the radioactive thorium waste generated during mining and refining. Strict zero-liquid-discharge (ZLD) regulations (to prevent water contamination) and recycling thorium into usable materials (like medical isotopes or new fuels) is essential for sustainable practices that could potentially turn into an economic opportunity (H2O Global News, 2025).

4.2.2 Securing Alternative Mining Partnerships

To reduce its reliance on China and strengthen its position in the global rare earth supply chain, the EU must pursue a strategy of diversified partnerships backed by strategic investments and equitable cooperation. Greenland's Kvanefjeld deposit, one of the world's largest untapped rare earth resources, could supply Europe with important quantities of critical materials—but only if the EU moves beyond passive trade agreements and actively co-invests in local refining infrastructure (Zadeh, 2025). The success of Namibia's Lofdal project, developed in partnership with Japan, demonstrates how joint investment in both extraction and downstream processing can establish resilient, independent supply chains (Mining Review Africa, 2022). The EU should replicate this model by integrating rare earth cooperation into its Just Energy Transition Partnerships, offering renewable energy

financing in exchange for long-term mineral access while ensuring technology transfer and local value addition. Beyond bilateral deals, the EU should deepen collaboration with the U.S.-led Mineral Security Partnership and Australia's Critical Minerals Office to pool resources, share infrastructure, and collectively counterbalance Chinese dominance. By aligning its Global Gateway Initiative with these priorities—prioritizing refining capacity over raw extraction, coupling mineral access with sustainable development, and fostering multilateral supply chain alliances—the EU can build a more secure and geopolitically balanced rare earth ecosystem. However, these partnerships must avoid China's exploitative "infrastructure-for-resources" model. Instead, the EU should emulate its 2021 Canada-EU Strategic Partnership around critical mineral supply chains, which ties resource access to environmental safeguards and local value addition (Kenigsberg & Sathanathan, 2021).

4.2.3 Promoting Demand-Side Innovation

Reducing reliance on rare earths through substitution and efficiency gains is equally vital. The EU should take advantage of its existing toolkits, such as Horizon Europe, to fund R&D for REE-free or REE-light technologies, such as solid-state batteries and sodium-ion alternatives. Tesla's iron-based (LFP) batteries, which use no rare earths, prove alternatives are viable (Jin & Lienert, 2023). Similarly, in renewable energy systems, Japan was the first country to apply the process of grain-boundary-diffusion reducing dysprosium use and cost, while maintaining thermal stability (Shanghai Metal Market, 2021). Public-private partnerships can drive rare earth innovation by scaling alternatives and recycling, as demonstrated by Siemens Gamesa's rare earth-free turbines made possible through EU Horizon grants, and Toyota's neodymium-reduced EV motors supported by Japan's state-funded innovation agency, NEDO. Lastly, with less than 1% of REE recycled in Europe (CINEA, 2025), the EU also needs urgent Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive

reforms to mandate recovery from end-of-life products like wind turbines and EV, thereby reducing primary demand and import dependency.

4.3 Collaborative Win-Win Strategies?

4.3.1 Joint Rare Earth Recycling Standards

China and the European Union could collaborate to establish a global rare earth recycling protocol by integrating the EU's Battery Regulation (2023) with China's "Zero Waste Cities" initiative (European Commission, 2024; Khan et al., 2024). A key consideration in this effort should be the standardization of recycling processes to ensure compatibility between Chinese and EU technologies, maximizing rare earth recovery rates (Dushyantha et al., 2020). Additionally, traceability mechanisms, such as blockchain-based digital product passports, could be implemented to monitor rare earth material flows and prevent illegal dumping or smuggling (European Commission, 2024). Environmental and labor safeguards must also be prioritized to avoid hazardous recycling practices, including uncontrolled acid leaching, which has been linked to soil and water contamination in informal recycling hubs (Zumsteg et al., 2022). A relevant precedent is the U.S.-Japan rare earth recycling partnership (2012), where both nations shared hydrometallurgical techniques to recover REEs from hybrid vehicle motors (U.S. Department of Energy, 2011). However, China and the EU must establish clear intellectual property (IP) protection agreements to prevent disputes over proprietary recycling technologies. Without such safeguards, concerns over forced technology transfers—a recurring issue in China's past collaborations—could undermine trust and hinder long-term cooperation.

4.3.2 Co-Investment in Third-Country Mining Projects

Collaborative investments in African rare

earth mines, such as Namibia's Lofdal deposit, could help diversify global supply chains while distributing financial risks between China and the EU (USGS, 2023). The China-EU Connectivity Platform (2015), originally focused on infrastructure development, could be strategically expanded to include joint mining ventures—aligning with its already considered goal of enhancing due diligence for minerals sourced from conflict-affected and high-risk areas, as outlined by the European Commission. Such an expansion would require embedding stringent ESG criteria to ensure compliance with bilateral and international responsible sourcing standards. This is even more important and challenging, after reports of severe ecological damage from illegal rare earth mining in Myanmar, partly due to unregulated operations, have led to deforestation and water pollution (FairPlanet, 2024). An interesting model to keep an eye on for future bilateral agreements is the EU-Canada Strategic Partnership on Raw Materials (2021), a blueprint for "friendly-shoring" — which aims to create more sustainable, responsible, and diversified supply chains for critical raw materials (CRMs), including rare earth elements (REEs). With more than 100 Canadian active mines across the world, many of which already have established raw material partnerships with the EU, this partnership is an incredible opportunity for the EU to diversify its REE supply chain through joint third country mining projects (Carry, 2024; Kenigsberg & Sathanathan, 2021).

4.3.3 Technology and Knowledge Sharing

The establishment of a China-EU Rare Earth Innovation Council could facilitate but also better regulate, knowledge exchange on sustainable extraction methods, considering that the EU needs China's refining capacity and China wants access to EU recycling technologies. This initiative could make sense in light of the U.S.-Australia Climate, Critical Minerals and Clean Energy Transformation Compact announced in May 2023, which promotes joint research and robust standards on clean processing

technologies (Prime Minister of Australia, 2023). However, technology sharing between China and the EU requires careful management of intellectual property rights. Historical concerns over China's alleged forced technology transfers, especially in strategic technological industries underscore the need for legally binding agreements to protect proprietary innovations. Furthermore, given the dual-use nature of REEs—essential for both civilian and military applications, such as aerospace alloys—safeguards must be implemented to prevent unintended military proliferation. A more feasible pathway to build trust between China and the EU in the rare earth sector would be to prioritize collaborative efforts in non-sensitive but strategically relevant areas, such as recycling rare earth elements (REEs) using biotechnologies like bioleaching or phytomining. This approach could be operationalized through jointly funded research grants, ideally embedded within academic or scientific frameworks to depoliticize cooperation. Crucially, any shared technologies or methodologies should be subject to independent third-party audits—ensuring transparency while protecting intellectual property (Interesse, 2024). A promising model for such cooperation already exists in the EU-funded BioClima Project, which was designed to strengthen EU-China collaboration on environmental monitoring and conservation strategies. By adapting this framework to the REE sector, both parties could leverage existing institutional experience in managing joint research while addressing critical gaps in sustainable rare earth recovery. The BioClima precedent demonstrates how shared scientific goals—when carefully delineated and externally verified—can create a foundation for trust without requiring premature integration of high-stakes industrial or defense-related technologies (KU Leuven, 2021).

Conclusion

The European Union's reliance on China for rare earth elements—a dependency exceeding 98% for permanent REE magnets and other critical applications (European Commission, 2023b)—places the bloc in a precarious position amid escalating geopolitical tensions. China's recent imposition of export controls on seven strategically significant REEs, including heavy rare earths like dysprosium and terbium, directly threatens the EU's green energy transition, defense manufacturing, and digital infrastructure ambitions (European Commission, 2023b). Unlike the U.S., which retains some domestic production capacity, the EU lacks meaningful mining or processing capabilities, leaving it uniquely vulnerable to supply disruptions (European Commission, 2023b).

This vulnerability is not hypothetical: historical precedents, such as China's 2010 REE export restrictions, which caused dysprosium prices to surge drastically (Bradsher, 2010), demonstrate how quickly market distortions can destabilize European industries. Today, China's near-monopoly over global rare earth processing (90% of global capacity) grants it substantial leverage, which Beijing has increasingly weaponized in trade disputes (International Energy Agency (IEA), 2023). The EU's recent CRMA acknowledges this risk, aiming to reduce dependence on single suppliers by mandating that at least 10% of annual consumption be sourced domestically by 2030 (European Commission, 2024). However, without accelerated investment in refining infrastructure and recycling technologies, the bloc remains at the mercy of Chinese export policies.

The EU's response must extend beyond legislative measures. Strategic partnerships with resource-rich nations—such as Greenland (which holds substantial rare earth deposits) and Canada (a key ally in diversifying supply chains)—are crucial but require long-term commitments and funding (European Commission, 2024). Additionally, circular economy initiatives,

including urban mining and rare earth recovery from electronic waste, could mitigate some dependency, though scaling these solutions remains a challenge.

Ultimately, the EU faces a defining choice: either accept continued subordination to China's REE dominance or aggressively pursue supply chain sovereignty. The latter path demands unprecedented coordination among Member States, industry leaders, and research institutions to develop alternative sources, foster innovation in material substitution, and secure access to global reserves. Failure to act decisively risks derailing the EU's climate neutrality goals and ceding strategic autonomy in an increasingly fragmented global economy.

References

- Adamas Intelligence. (2022). *Rare earth magnet market outlook to 2035*. <https://www.adamasintel.com/rare-earth-magnet-market-outlook-to-2035/>
- Alonso, E., Sherman, A. M., Wallington, T. J., Everson, M. P., Field, F. R., Roth, R., & Kirchain, R. E. (2012). Evaluating rare earth element availability: A case with revolutionary demand from clean technologies. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 46(6), 3406–3414. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es203518d>
- Andrew-Speed, P. Hove, A. (2023). *China's rare earths dominance and policy responses*. (China Energy Report No. 7) [Report]. Oxford Institute for Energy Studies. <https://www.oxfordenergy.org/wpcms/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/CE7-Chinas-rare-earths-dominance-and-policy-responses.pdf>
- Baskaran, G., & Schwartz, M. (2025). *The consequences of China's new rare earths export restriction*. CSIS. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/consequences-chinas-new-rare-earths-export-restrictions>
- Bauk, G., Caruso, A., Kamenopoulos, S., Mamula, N., Kennedy, J., Pitron, G., Chin, P., Kutsch, J., Conca, J., Lifton, J., & Zhang, M. Y. (2023). *China's rare earth subsidies and structural advantages: A comprehensive list of China's advantages that must be overcome for any U.S. or allied rare earth project's success*. Thorium Energy Alliance. <https://thoriumenergyalliance.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/ChinaSubsidiesStructuralAdvantages-ReleasedMay2.23.pdf>
- BGR Group. (2024). *China introduces new regulations to control rare earth minerals*. <https://bgrdc.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/China-Rare-Earth.pdf>
- Binnemans, K., Jones, P. T., Blanpain, B., Van Gerven, T., Yang, Y., Walton, A., & Buchert, M. (2013). Recycling of rare earths: A critical review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 51, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.12.037>
- Bradsher, K. (2010). Amid tension, China blocks vital exports to Japan. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2010/09/23/business/global/23rare.html>
- Business & Human Rights Resource Centre. (2023). *Europe: Local activists are determined to halt transition mineral projects, fearing the EU's push for mining independence will be a catastrophe for environmental law*. <https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/latest-news/europe-local-activists-are-determined-to-halt-transition-mineral-projects-fearing-the-eus-push-for-mining-independence-will-be-a-catastrophe-for-environmental-law/>
- Carry, I. (2024). *Critical raw materials partner Canada: An almost perfect match*. Stiftung Wissenschaft und Politik (SWP). <https://www.swp-berlin.org/publikation/critical-raw-materials-partner-canada-an-almost-perfect-match>

- Chen, S. (2023, December 21). *China's rare earth dominance could crumble in 10 years, CAS study forecasts*. *South China Morning Post*.
<https://www.scmp.com/news/china/science/article/3303167/chinas-rare-earth-dominance-could-crumble-10-years-cas-study-forecasts>
- Christiansen, F. G. (2025). *Greenland's rare earth minerals*. IEEE Spectrum.
<https://spectrum.ieee.org/greenland-rare-earth-minerals>
- Collins, E. (2025, May 16). *Recovering rare earth metals*. University of Kent.
<https://www.kent.ac.uk/research/engagement-and-impact/904/recovering-rare-earth-metals>
- Defence Express. (2025). Arleigh Burke and Virginia ships need lots of rare earths to make and for a good reason. *Defence Express*.
https://en.defence-ua.com/analysis/arleigh_burke_and_virginia_ships_need_lots_of_rare_earths_to_make_and_for_a_good_reason-13993.html
- Defense Production Act of 1950, Pub. L. No. 81-774, 64 Stat. 798 (1950).
<https://www.fema.gov/disaster/defense-production-act>
- Dushyantha, N., Batapola, N., Ilankoon, I. M. S. K., Rohitha, S., Premasiri, R., Abeysinghe, B., Ratnayake, N., & Dissanayake, K. (2020). The story of rare earth elements: Challenges and opportunities. *Minerals Engineering*, 122, 106–123.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0169136820300937?via%3Dihub>
- Edwards, T. M., Puglis, H. J., Lopez Duran, J., Bradshaw, L., Kent, D. B., & Farag, A. (2023). Ammonia and aquatic ecosystems – A review of global sources, biogeochemical cycling, and effects on fish. *Science of the Total Environment*, 907.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167911>
- Emont, J. (2025, June 12). China is still choking exports of rare earths despite pact with U.S. *The Wall Street Journal*.
<https://www.wsj.com/world/china/china-rare-earths-exports-2fd0dab4>
- European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). (2025, April 28). *LIFE INSPIRE: Mining valuable metals from our waste on a large scale by 2025*. European Commission.
https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/life-inspiree-mining-valuable-metals-our-waste-large-scale-2025-04-28_en
- European Commission. (2015). *REE4EU – Rare Earth Element recovery for Europe* [Project]. CORDIS EU.
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/680507>
- European Commission. (2020). *Critical raw materials resilience: Charting a path towards greater security and sustainability* (COM/2020/474). European Union (EUR-Lex).
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0474>
- European Commission. (2023a). *Critical Raw Materials Act: Ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials for the EU* (COM/2023/160 final). Publications Office of the European Union.
<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/57318397-fdd4-11ed-a05c-01aa75ed71a1>
- European Commission. (2023b). *Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials*. EUR-Lex.
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52023PC0160>
- European Commission. (2023c). *Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 on critical raw materials*. European Union (EUR-Lex). Official Journal of the European Union.
<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/1542/oj>

- European Commission. (2024). *European Critical Raw Materials Act*. European Union. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/green-deal-industrial-plan/european-critical-raw-materials-act_en
- FairPlanet. (2023). *Myanmar's illicit rare earth mining thrives amid insurgency*. <https://www.fairplanet.org/editors-pick/myanmar-illicit-rare-earth-mining-amid-insurgency/>
- Finnish Geological Survey (GTK). (2023). *Fennoscandian REE deposits GIS layer*. https://tupa.gtk.fi/raportti/arkisto/42_2023.pdf
- Gao, P., Wang, X., & Jia, T. (2023, June 2). 内蒙古包头稀土高新区：产业人才“双向奔赴”促发展 [Accelerating the construction of a "talent ecosystem" to promote mutual advancement of industry and talent]. *Guangming Daily*. https://news.gmw.cn/2023-06/02/content_36604127.htm
- Gauß, R., Burkhardt, C., Carencotte, F., Gasparon, M., Gutfleisch, O., Higgins, I., Karajić, M., Klossek, A., Mäkinen, M., Schäfer, B., Veluri, B., & Schindler, R. (2021). *Rare earth magnets and motors: A European call for action*. Rare Earth Magnets and Motors Cluster of the European Raw Materials Alliance. <https://erma.eu/app/uploads/2021/09/01227816.pdf>
- Geological Survey of Sweden (SGU). (2023). *Rare earth elements in Sweden* [Factsheet]. <https://www.sgu.se/globalassets/produkter/publikationer/2024/statistics-of-the-swedish-mining-industry-2023--sgu-2024-1.pdf>
- Germany Trade & Invest. (2025). *Mobility goes global: Germany's automotive industry in transition* (Publication No. 01/25). https://www.gtai.de/resource/blob/1866058/a56d0f9d9d25d71b95f0a719a0f27ec8/GTAI_MG_01_25_RZ_Web_final.pdf
- Go, J. Y. (2022, November 23). Can Europe break China's grip on rare earth magnets? *FDI Intelligence*. <https://www.fdiintelligence.com/content/0d10e4bc-1140-5d58-b4aa-1a545c9c3253>
- Godek, S. (2025). *China's germanium and gallium export restrictions: Consequences for the United States*. Stimson Center. <https://www.stimson.org/2025/chinas-germanium-and-gallium-export-restrictions-consequences-for-the-united-states/>
- Gschneidner, K. A. (2015). Rare earths: The fraternal fifteen. *Nature Chemistry*, 7(7), 538–542. <https://www.osti.gov/includes/opennet/includes/Understanding%20the%20Atom/Rare%20Earth%20The%20Fraternal%20Fifteen.pdf>
- KU Leuven. (2021). *BioClima: EU-China collaboration on biodiversity and climate monitoring* [Research project]. Research Portal, KU Leuven. <https://research.kuleuven.be/portal/en/project/3E250081>
- H2O Global News. (2025). What is zero liquid discharge? *H2O Global News*. Retrieved June 29, 2025, from <https://h2oglobalnews.com/what-is-zero-liquid-discharge/>
- Hale, E. (2025). Why China's rare earth exports are a key issue in trade tensions with U.S. *Al Jazeera*. <https://www.aljazeera.com/economy/2025/6/12/why-chinas-rare-earth-exports-are-a-key-issue-in-trade-tensions-with-us>
- Hart, C. (2025). *Mapping China's strategy for rare earths dominance*. Atlantic Council. <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/Mapping-Chinas-strategy-for-rare-earths-dominance.pdf>
- Hoyer, W. (2023). *Strengthening Europe's raw materials supply chains*. European Investment Bank.

- <https://www.eib.org/en/projects/priorities/raw-materials>
- Initiative For Responsible Mining Assurance (IRMA). (2018). IRMA standard for responsible mining IRMA-STD-001. <https://responsiblemining.net/>
- Innovation News Network. (2025). The Kvanefjeld project: Potential world-class supplier of rare earths. *Innovation News Network*. <https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/the-kvanefjeld-project-potential-world-class-supplier-rare-earths/39520/>
- Interesse, G. (2024). European businesses in China: Insights from the EU Chamber's position paper 2024/2025. *China Briefing*. <https://www.china-briefing.com/news/european-businesses-in-china-insights-from-the-eu-chambers-position-paper-2024-2025/>
- International Energy Agency (IEA). (2021). *The role of critical minerals in clean energy transitions*. <https://www.iea.org/reports/the-role-of-critical-minerals-in-clean-energy-transitions>
- International Energy Agency (IEA). (2023). *Critical minerals market review 2023*. <https://www.iea.org/reports/critical-minerals-market-review-2023>
- Jaussaud, C. (2025). La France va extraire du lithium [France to extract lithium]. *JournalAuto* (France). <https://journalauto.com/industrie/la-france-va-extraire-du-lithium/>
- Jin, H., & Lienert, P. (2023). Tesla to use iron-based batteries for Semi electric trucks in affordable electric car push. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/autos-transportation/tesla-use-iron-based-batteries-semi-electric-trucks-affordable-electric-car-2023-04-06/>
- Jordens, A., Cheng, Y. P., & Waters, K. E. (2013). A review of rare earth mineral processing. *Minerals Engineering*, 41, 97–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2012.10.017>
- Kenigsberg, A., & Sathananthan, G. (2021). Canada and EU announce critical minerals alliance. *Osler*. <http://www.osler.com/en/insights/updates/canada-and-eu-announce-critical-minerals-alliance/>
- Khan, S., Khan, A., Ma, Y., & Sadat, M. (2024). Green innovation practices and consumer resistance to green innovation products: Moderating role of environmental knowledge and corporate social responsibility. *Cleaner and Responsible Consumption*, 13, 100184. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2444569X22001159>
- Klinger, J. M. (2018). *Rare earth frontiers: From terrestrial subsoils to lunar landscapes*. Cornell University Press. <https://www.cornellpress.cornell.edu/book/9781501714597/rare-earth-frontiers>
- Li, X., Chen, Z., Chen, Z., & Zhang, Y. (2013). A human health risk assessment of rare earth elements in soil and vegetables from a mining area in Fujian Province, Southeast China. *Chemosphere*, 93(6), 1240-1246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.06.085>
- Liu, B. (2025). 2025年中国稀土回收行业现状分析及前景展望 · “磁材企业+回收平台”模式将广泛推广 [Analysis of the current status and future prospects of China's rare earth recycling industry in 2025: “Magnetic material enterprises + recycling platform” model to be widely promoted]. *Huaon*. <https://www.huaon.com/channel/trend/1081406.html>
- Liu, H. (2016). *Rare earths: Shades of grey*. China Water Risk. <https://www.chinawaterrisk.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/CWR-Rare-Earths-Shades-Of-Grey-2016-ENG.pdf>
- LKAB. (2023). Europe's largest deposit of rare

- earth metals is located in the Kiruna area.
<https://lkab.com/en/press/europes-largest-deposit-of-rare-earth-metals-is-located-in-the-kiruna-area/>
- Maçek, M. (2023, October 12). How the United States lost the rare earth materials war to China. *The New Republic*.
<https://newrepublic.com/article/194514/rare-earth-materials-china-trade>
- Mann, N. (2024). Ce que recouvre l'investissement de Solvay dans les terres rares à La Rochelle [What Solvay's investment covers in REE at La Rochelle]. *Usine Nouvelle*.
<https://www.usinenouvelle.com/article/ce-que-recouvre-l-investissement-de-solvay-dans-les-terres-rares-a-la-rochelle.N2213168>
- Merwat, S. (2025, April 16). *The new great game: How the race for critical minerals is shaping tech supremacy*. RBC Wealth Management.
<https://ca.rbcwealthmanagement.com/todd.wiebe/blog/4512911-The-New-Great-Game-How-the-race-for-critical-minerals-is-shaping-tech-supremacy>
- Ministry of Industry and Information Technology (MIIT). (2021). *Rare earth industry development plan (2021–2025)*. Chinese Government (Gov.cn).
<http://www.gov.cn/zhengce/zhengceku/2021-12/29/5665166/files/90c1c79a00b44c67b59c29392476c862.pdf>
- Hunt, A.P. (2025). Lynas becomes first producer of heavy rare earths outside China. *Bloomberg*.
<https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2025-05-15/lynas-becomes-first-heavy-rare-earths-producer-outside-china>
- Mining Review Africa. (2022). Namibian Lofdal rare earth project secures Japanese market. *Mining Review Africa*.
<https://www.miningreview.com/news/namibian-lofdal-rare-earth-project-secures-japanese-market/>
- Mining Technology. (2025). Sweden's LKAB discovers rare earth metals. *Mining Technology*.
<https://www.mining-technology.com/news/swedens-lkab-rare-earth-metal/>
- MP Materials. (2023). *Sustainability report 2022*.
<https://mpmaterials.com/sustainability/>
<https://www.neomaterials.com/neo-launches-construction-of-re-magnet-manufacturing-plant/>
- Nayar, J. (2021). Not so “green” technology: The complicated legacy of rare earth mining. *Harvard International Review*.
<https://hir.harvard.edu/not-so-green-technology-the-complicated-legacy-of-rare-earth-mining/>
- NEO Materials. (2023). *NEO launches construction of RE magnet manufacturing plant*. Neo Materials (NEO).
- Onstad, E. (2024). Recycling kick a long-term solution to EU rare earths challenge. *Reuters*.
<https://www.reuters.com/markets/commodities/recycling-kick-long-term-solution-eu-rare-earths-challenge-2024-06-27/>
- Pacheco, M. (2024). France, Germany, Italy seek private input for €2.5bn critical mineral investment. *Euronews*.
<https://www.euronews.com/green/2024/05/17/france-germany-italy-seek-private-input-for-25bn-critical-mineral-investment>
- Prime Minister of Australia. (2023). *Australia-United States climate, critical minerals and clean energy transformation compact*. Prime Minister of Australia.
<https://www.pm.gov.au/media/australia-united-states-climate-critical-minerals-and-clean-energy-transformation-compact>
- Qiao, Z. (2025). 研判2025！中国稀土回收行业发展现状及格局概况：需求规模快速扩张，未来国产化进程将继续加快 [Analysis of 2025! [Current status and industry landscape of China's rare earth recycling sector: Rapid expansion in demand scale,

- future localisation process to accelerate further.]. *China Industry Report*.
<https://www.chyxx.com/industry/1210295.html>
- Quest Metals. (2025). *How the U.S. can counter China's rare earth export ban by exploiting its high-purity quartz vulnerability*. Quest Metals Blog.
<https://www.questmetals.com/blog/how-the-u-s-can-counter-china-s-rare-earth-export-ban-by-exploiting-its-high-purity-quartz-vulnerability>
- Rare Earth Exchanges. (2025a). *German magnet leader VAC ramps up U.S. operations amid Chinese export halt*. Rare Earth Exchanges.
<https://rareearthexchanges.com/news/german-magnet-leader-vac-ramps-up-u-s-operations-amid-chinese-export-halt/>
- Rare Earth Exchanges. (2025b). *Germany accelerates rare earth resilience amid ongoing dependency on China*. *Rare Earth Exchanges (Germany)*.
<https://rareearthexchanges.com/news/germany-accelerates-rare-earth-resilience-amid-ongoing-dependency-on-china/>
- Scholvin, S., & Wigell, M. (2018). *Geo-economics as concept and practice in international relations: Surveying the state of the art* (FIIA Working Paper No. 102).
https://www.fiia.fi/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/wp102_geo-economics_oikea_issn.pdf
- Shanghai Metal Market. (2021). *The state encourages the development of high-performance permanent magnet industry and the downstream demand continues to increase*. *Metal.com*.
[https://news.metal.com/newscontent/101541417/\[minutes\]-the-state-encourages-the-development-of-high-performance-permanent-magnet-industry-and-the-downstream-demand-continues-to-increase](https://news.metal.com/newscontent/101541417/[minutes]-the-state-encourages-the-development-of-high-performance-permanent-magnet-industry-and-the-downstream-demand-continues-to-increase)
- Sinha, M. K., Jordaan, R., & Purcell, W. (2022). *Hydrometallurgical recovery of manganese from ferruginous manganese ore by reductive-acid leaching with sodium dithionite*. *Journal of Sustainable Metallurgy*, 8, 783–794.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40831-022-00529-5>
- Solki (n.d.). *Frequently asked questions*.
<https://www.sokli.fi/en/deposit/frequently-asked-questions.html>
- Solvay. (2022). *Solvay to develop major hub for rare earth magnets in Europe*. *Solvay Press Release*.
<https://www.solvay.com/en/press-release/solvay-develop-major-hub-rare-earth-magnets-europe>
- State Council of China. (2016, October 18). *Circular on rare earth industry development*. *Chinese Government (Gov.cn)*.
http://www.gov.cn/xinwen/2016-10/18/content_5120998.htm
- Tong, X., Wang, T., Li, J., & Wang, X. (2024). *Extended producer responsibility to reconstruct the circular value chain*. *Circular Economy*, 3(1), 100076.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cec.2024.100076>
- U.S. Department of Energy. (2011). *2011 Critical materials strategy* (Report No. DOE/PI-0009).
https://www.energy.gov/sites/default/files/DOE_CMS2011_FINAL_Full.pdf
- U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). (2011). *Mineral commodity summaries 2011: Rare earths*. U.S. Department of the Interior.
<https://pubs.usgs.gov/publication/mineral2011>
- U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). (2023). *Mineral commodity summaries 2023: Rare earths* [Report]. U.S. Department of the Interior.
<https://doi.org/10.3133/mcs2023>
- U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). (2024). *Mineral commodity summaries: Rare earths*.
<https://pubs.usgs.gov/periodicals/mcs2024/mcs2024.pdf>
- Waldersee, V., & Steitz, C. (2025, June 4). *Some European auto supplier plants shut down after China's rare earth curbs*. *Reuters*.

- <https://www.reuters.com/business/autos-transportation/some-european-auto-supplier-plants-shut-down-after-chinas-rare-earth-curbs-2025-06-04/>
- Walk the Street Capital. (2025). China's new environmental regulations set to boost rare earth prices. *Walk the Street Capital*.
<https://www.walkthestreetcapital.com/articles/chinas-new-environmental-regulations-set-to-boost-rare-earth-prices>
- Webber, J. (2025, June 25). Belfast magnet recycling start-up offers rare earth promise. *Financial Times*.
<https://www.ft.com/content/a8c8f655-1422-46ca-9d5e-30a5870bee4f>
- Wübbecke, J. (2013). Rare earth elements in China: Policies and narratives of reinventing an industry. *Resources Policy*, 38(3), 384–394.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2013.05.005>
- Xu, Z., Yang, J.-L., Zhao, Y., Hao, R., & Zhang, G.-L. (2023). Soil acidification in a tailing area of ionic rare earth in Southeast China. *Science of the Total Environment*, 884.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.163834>
- Zadeh, J. (2025). Rare earth reserves: Country distribution and importance in 2025. *Discovery Alert*.
<https://discoveryalert.com.au/news/rare-earth-reserves-country-distribution-importance-2025/>
- Zhao, M., Zhang, H., Han, H., Jiang, X., Yang, Y., & Li, T. (2025). Differential leaching mechanisms and ecological impact of organic acids on ion-adsorption type rare earth ores. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 362.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1383586625002989>
- Zhou, Q., & Brooke, S. (2022). China merges three rare earths state-owned entities to increase pricing power and efficiency. *China Briefing*.
<https://www.china-briefing.com/news/china-merges-three-rare-earths-state-owned-entities-to-increase-pricing-power-and-efficiency/>
- Zimmermann, A. (2025). China's got the world in a rare earth choke hold. *Politico EU*.
<https://www.politico.eu/article/china-rare-earth-materials-donald-trump-west-magnets-cars/>
- Zinkpot. (n.d.). *India in talks with Japan, China, Vietnam on rare earths export*.
<https://www.zinkpot.com/?page=news&news=india-in-talks-with-japan-china>
- Zumsteg, J., Cooper, J., & Brattemø, H. (2022). Lifecycle analysis of rare earth recycling. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 26(4), 1–15.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13245>

Audrey Berder

audreyberder@yahoo.com

Audrey Berder is a trilingual (French/English/Chinese) EU-China policy specialist focused on climate and energy geopolitics. A graduate of LSE and Fudan University's joint program, she brings hands-on experience from the OECD and ECB in developing sustainable policy solutions. Her multicultural background across five countries fuels her mission to bridge East-West divides through innovative green diplomacy.

Climate Cooperation or Challenge: European Media Perception of China in the Context of Climate Change

Marie Sophie MAYER

Abstract

The relationship between the European Union and China is increasingly characterized by economic competition and political challenges, leading the EU to frame China as a “systemic rival” (European Commission, 2019). Nevertheless, climate cooperation between the EU and China has become all the more crucial. After the U.S. announced its withdrawal from the Paris Agreement in 2017, both parties saw the opportunity to step in and take a leading role in the international climate agenda. On the one hand, both countries recognize the need for cooperation concerning climate change. However, on the other hand, rising economic and political challenges complicate cooperation. Considering this puzzle, it is important to evaluate if Member States’ views on China in the area of climate change have become more negative and dominated by other challenges, or if China is still seen positively in this area. Therefore, the paper aims to answer the following question: How does European media frame China in the context of climate change? To this end, this paper conducts a media analysis by looking at newspaper articles from Germany, Italy, and Poland. The aim is to identify the prevailing framing of China, ranging from a necessary partner in climate change to an economic or political threat. Developing an understanding of these perceptions is critical to examine the prospects of EU-China climate cooperation, whether it will become entangled in escalating economic and political tensions or whether, despite the fraught atmosphere, meaningful cooperation and joint action on climate change can still exist between the two actors. By combining both fields, the findings of the paper will contribute to the study of EU-China relations on climate change, as well as

European perceptions studies towards China.

Keywords: EU-China relations, climate cooperation, European perception, media frame analysis, interdependence, securitization

Introduction

As both China and the European Union have taken on greater roles in global politics, the importance of their relations has grown substantially. Official diplomatic relations started in 1975, initially being exclusively economic (Griese, 2006, p. 545). However, the establishment of political engagement did not take long to follow; the agreement of the EU-China Strategic Partnership was signed in 2003 (Dorussen et al., 2018, p. 288). While trade relations remain the most important strand of the EU-China relationship (Freeman, 2022), the issue of climate change cooperation has become an increasingly important area of cooperation in the last two decades (Gurol, 2022). EU-China climate cooperation was first institutionalized in 2005 with the establishment of the EU-China Partnership on Climate Change (Liu et al., 2019, p. 246). Cooperation on this front particularly gained momentum after the breakthrough of the Paris Agreement in 2015, with the EU presenting itself as a “lead actor” and China acknowledging its role and responsibility in the global climate agenda (Gurol, 2022, p. 118; von Lucke, 2023, p. 3). Cooperation was further advanced with the U.S. announcing its withdrawal from the Paris Agreement in 2017 (Gurol & Starkmann, 2021; von Lucke, 2023). In this context, Liu et al. (2019, p. 246) deemed EU-China cooperation a “cornerstone of multilateralism” and a potential “role model for other economies.” Cooperative elements, however, is only one aspect of the EU-China relationship.

Alternatively, as a consequence of globalization,

growing interdependencies, and new emerging security challenges (Gurol, 2022, p. 3), EU-China relations are becoming more strained, making cooperation difficult (Stec, 2022; Feng, 2022). The increasing importance of the technology market leads directly to further economic competition between the EU, the U.S., and China (Aktoudianakis, 2022, p. 14). Moreover, with the deepening U.S.-China rivalry, geopolitical tensions, and the Ukraine war, the EU finds itself in a new position—it has to redefine its role as well as its partnerships with China (Oertel, 2020; German Council on Foreign Relations [DGAP], 2022). This is also reflected in the EU's designation of China as a “cooperation partner”, “economic competitor”, and “systemic rival” (European Commission, 2019, p. 1). This affects EU-China relations, which are shaped by both shared interests and politico-economic challenges (Gurol, 2022). Furthermore, Chen and Gao (2022) observe securitization trends towards China among EU Member States. The challenging atmosphere is also reflected in the last two EU-China summits—both of which are rather unsuccessful and tense (Gurol, 2022, p. 11; Stec, 2022).

Nonetheless, climate cooperation seems to have fallen out of this trend. Lampe et al. (2022, p. 29) argue that “While recognizing the current tensions in the wider EU-China relationship, there is a strong joint interest to collaborate on climate action [between the two parties].” Overall, the partnership on climate change is expected to be shaped by both multilateralism as well as economic interests—it is at the intersection of common goals and ever-increasing economic rivalries. This discrepancy in interests give rise to question regarding the prospects of EU-China climate cooperation. To develop a more in-depth understanding of such dynamics, examining the European perceptions towards China is crucial. Overall, the paper aims to answer the following question: How does European media frame China in the context of

climate change? This study seeks to answer this question by conducting a media analysis of newspaper articles from Germany, Italy, and Poland. The aim is to identify the prevailing framing of China, ranging from a necessary partner in combating climate change to an economic or political threat. The findings will contribute to the discussion of EU-China relations by providing a framework of perception towards China in relation to climate change. This approach not only assess the context of major narratives being present in European media but also identify the prospects of EU-China partnership on climate change. The paper is structured as follows: First, the paper will provide an overview of key debates within EU-China relations and European perceptions on China. Based on the literature review, the paper will develop a framework comprising of different frames of perceptions towards China. Then, this framework will be applied to three different cases, namely discussions in German, Italian, and Polish newspaper articles, to identify their perception of China in the context of climate change. The last section provides a summary of the findings and a discussion of their implications on EU-China climate cooperation.

1. Literature Review

This paper builds on three strands of literature: the broader debate on EU-China relations, EU-China climate cooperation, and European perceptions of China. The following section provides an overview of the relevant literature, with a more detailed discussion of selected contributions.

Previous research agrees that the most important strand of EU-China cooperation is in the realm of economics (Smith, 2016; Michalski & Pan, 2017; Freeman, 2022). Freeman (2022, pp. 245–246) points out that both the EU and China agree on the fact that their relations are important and that the economic aspect is the most dominant one. With economic relations being the starting point of the EU-China relationship, scholars argued that spill-over effects could be observed with cooperation

extending from the economic to the security sector (Dorussen et al., 2018). Currently, EU-China cooperation consists of an economic, a political, and a security pillar (Gurol, 2022, pp. 1–2). While the EU initially see economic relations with China in a mostly positive light, the potential for conflict soon became clear (Freeman, 2022, pp. 250–251). Whereas the EU puts emphasis on economic partnership and opportunities with China, economic imbalances are increasingly noticed (Freeman, 2022, pp. 258–259). Thus, scholars identify a shifting perception of China within the EU shaped by economic competition (Freeman, 2022, p. 257; Lai, 2023).

Gurol (2022, p. 78), however, argues that EU-China relations have evolved beyond trade to becoming potential security partners. In his view, two co-existing yet contrasting visions have emerged in the EU's approach towards China. On the one hand, the EU acknowledges is China's rising global importance and its interdependence with China—the organization between the two actors, perceives China as a “necessary counterpart” (Gurol, 2022, p. 80). On the other hand, Gurol (2022, p. 80) notes that China is simultaneously—and increasingly—seen as a “rival” or “competitor” within the security field. In addition, Kelleher (2022, p. 22) highlights that, in recent years, the partnership between the EU and China has increasingly been perceived as imbalanced, leading the EU to take a more practical approach that aims for fairer cooperation via addressing asymmetries.

Chen and Gao (2022) observe that securitization moves vary across Member States. However, the prevailing view in most Member States is that China poses a security threat in the economic sphere, particularly in the technology sector (Chen and Gao, 2022, p. 207). With respect to the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), Lai and Cai (2022) note that public perceptions diverge even within Central

and Eastern European countries, despite their shared participation in the 16+1 format. This is also reflected by Turcsanyi's (2017, p. 719) work, who found different perceptions of China among Poland, Slovakia, and the Czech Republic but common interest in Chinese energy investments. In particular, he notes that the frequency of discussions on China's political system and human rights situation vary potentially depending on their moral sensitivity. Moreover, Rühlig et al. (2018, pp. 15–17) argue that policy approaches to China differ due to Member States' historical legacy, economic relations with China, and Chinese pressure.

As for exchanges on climate change, existing research deems it an area where congruences and differences between the two actors coexist: On the one hand, Scott (2009, p. 212) argued that among the many frictions in the EU-China relationship, the environment appears as a “convergent area” where consensus exists. Furthermore, he has pointed to emerging tensions between “[E]uropean commercial interests and environmental concerns” (Scott, 2009, p. 221). In fact, scholars often argue that both the EU and China share the same awareness and perception of the issue of climate change (Gippner, 2014; Bo et al., 2016; Gurol, 2022). Both perceive climate change as a security threat and acknowledge the need for common action and responsibility (Bo et al., 2016, p. 113; Gippner, 2014, p. 19; Gurol, 2022, pp. 120–122). Bo et al. (2016, p. 115) argue that these convergences facilitated climate cooperation between the two actors in its early stages. Institutionalized in 2005 with the EU-China Partnership on Climate Change, climate cooperation between the two actors takes place both globally and bilaterally.

On the other hand, cooperation is not only shaped by successes but also challenges. Here, Liu et al. (2019, p. 243) consider climate cooperation between the EU and China as double-edged. On the one hand, they see it as well-institutionalized, spanning multiple levels, successful in facilitating “exchange and understanding” (Liu et al., 2019, p.

248). However, they also acknowledge that the relationship is characterized by differences and challenges caused by differing political values, increasing competitiveness leading to economic conflicts and hindered technology transfer from the EU to China (Liu et al., 2019, pp. 249–250). Within this contrasting dynamic, Feng (2022, p. 78) claims that the EU hopes for increased cooperation in the matters of trade and climate change despite also being aware of increasing competition in the realm of technology and ideology.

In summary, there seems to have a general consensus among scholars that EU-China relations have become increasingly challenging in recent years. The EU and its Member States no longer see China merely as an economic trading partner, but also an economic and political competitor. Due to the close linkage of the climate change issue with trade, EU-China climate cooperation is affected by these growing tensions. However, the EU continues to have a strong desire to maintain and promote such cooperation, being aware of its necessity despite increasing competition. However, as possibilities for future cooperation become increasingly uncertain, assessing how EU Member States perceive EU-China climate collaboration bares strategic significance. While scholars have conducted studies on EU perception on China in the context of climate change (see Gippner, 2014), there has yet to be an exhaustive analysis at the member state level—such analysis will be crucial to provide further perspectives on EU-China climate cooperation. The paper therefore combines perception studies with the analysis of EU-China climate relations, aiming to assess whether climate change—as a traditionally “convergent area”—is affected by growing political tensions and economic conflicts between the EU and China, or if it remains a space for meaningful cooperation.

2. Theoretical Framework

To understand the current situation and

prospect of EU-China climate cooperation, this paper examines how European Member States frame China in the context of climate change. Analyzing perceptions is crucial, as framing influence policy outputs and are intertwined with them (Mišík, 2013; Freeman, 2022). Lai and Cai (2022, p. 306), drawing from social constructivist theories, argue that perceptions not only affect identity and interests but also policy decisions. Building on the literature on EU-China relations, this paper develops a theoretical framework comprising four different frames—understood as interpretive structures used by political actors, policymakers, and the media to construct meaning around complex phenomena—through which China is perceived in the climate context. The frames are derived from previous research on EU-China relations and their cooperation (see Gurol, 2022). They cover key aspects of the interdependence between the two regions, including both economic and political dimensions. The frames reflect two possible directions for framing China in climate change and shed light on the prospects for EU-China cooperation. On one hand, China may be seen as a necessary partner in climate change (interdependence frame), or as an economic partner offering trade opportunities for Europe (economic opportunity frame). On the other hand, China could also be perceived negatively as an economic or political threat (economic competition frame, securitization frame). The following section will outline each frame and present expectations for the results.

2.1 Interdependence Frame: China is Seen as a Necessary Partner for the EU in the Context of Climate Change

The EU and China has become increasingly aware of their interdependence in terms of trade as well as climate and energy security. As Gurol (2022, p. 125) notes: “a strong sense of ‘having no other choice’ than to cooperate” has emerged on EU side Feng (2022, p. 76) states that European countries have accepted the need for collaboration with China on climate change. Similarly, Liu et al. (2019, p. 248) point to various

initiatives and forms of EU-China climate cooperation that have been established on both the EU as well as national levels, which helps enhance dialogue and understanding. In addition, Liu et al. (2019, p. 251) stress that “cooperation is an optimal choice for both parties”— considering the urgency of climate action, the U.S. withdrawal from global climate governance, and the resulting momentum for the EU and China to position themselves more prominently on the international stage. Therefore, cooperating with China in combating climate change is self-evident for the EU. Such a view help cultivate a positive view on China, further hastening climate cooperation.

2.2 Economic Opportunity Frame: China is Seen as Creating Economic Opportunities for the EU in the Context of Climate Change

It can be argued that climate change and required responses are creating new economic opportunities for the EU. Liu et al. (2019, p. 245) state that China is a “large [...] export market for its [EU] clean energy technologies and services” which is growing further still, thereby creating more and more opportunities for the EU and its Member States. Gurol (2022, p. 128) also note that the “‘economization’ of climate and energy security” creates links between climate cooperation and technological development. In this regard, economic interdependence can be seen as a positive condition that facilitate further cooperation on energy and climate (Gurol, 2022, p. 126), which can help to further foster a positive view on China.

2.3 Economic Competition Frame: China is Seen as an Economic Competitor or Economic Threat in the Context of Climate Change

While some perceive EU-China cooperation on climate change as an economic opportunity, others view it in light of economic competition. Chen and Gao (2022, p. 204) argue that

economic institutions increasingly frame China as a threat, pointing to the dependence on imports such as raw materials, as well as the risk posed to the EU competitiveness in other markets. Freeman (2022, p. 246) states that the EU is troubled by an “unequal and unbalanced” relationship with China (see also Gurol, 2022, p. 51). Economic competition is thereby closely linked with the technology sector, which is particularly critical concerning climate change (Feng, 2022, pp. 78–79). Liu et al. (2019, p. 250) echo that China’s increasing competitiveness has caused tensions between the two actors: the EU is increasingly concerned about intellectual property rights, while limited market access to China curbed benefits for European companies, making cooperation less attractive (Liu et al., 2019, p. 250). Gurol (2022, p. 129) adds that geopolitical tensions are likely to increase energy competition and thus negatively influence EU-Chinese trade relations. With trade and climate being closely interlinked, this competition could shed a negative light on China and broader EU-China climate relations.

2.4 Securitization Frame: China is Seen as a Political Threat to the EU Challenging Climate Change Cooperation

Within this frame, China is increasingly seen as a political threat challenging EU-China climate cooperation. The strategic partnership between the EU and China includes a political dimension, where their political values and norms clash (Maher, 2016). Values such as human rights and democracy are core principles of the EU and are deeply rooted in its foreign policy approach, but they are at odds with China (Maher, 2016, p. 963). In that sense, despite what can be seen as a mutually beneficial climate cooperation, the fact that China is progressively seen as a geopolitical and political challenge by the EU, causes all areas of bilateral cooperation to be seen in a negative light. Chen and Gao (2022) note that there are securitization trends towards China among European Member States. The two scholars note how the EU is framing China as an

“existential threat to its core political values such as human rights, democracy and rule of law” (Chen & Gao, 2022, p. 205). Cooperation on climate change can be increasingly challenging due to the interconnectedness between the political and economic spheres (DGAP, 2022, p. 4). Poggetti and Shi-Kupfer (2018, p. 40) highlight the case of Germany, where among politicians and within the business sector, China is perceived as a challenger of European political values. Additionally, Lamy et al. (2022, p. 8) argue that “geopolitical developments have seriously limited the room for constructive cooperation between the EU and China.” The framing of a (geo-)political threat could affect how China is perceived in the context of climate change, hindering further collaboration in this field.

After presenting the different frameworks, expectations for the results are shared. Apart from potential differences among the countries, it is expected that negative framings—notably securitization and economic competition frames—would have gained importance over the previous years, which aligns with overall trends in the evolving EU-China relations. The economic competition frame is expected to have gained ground due to the interconnected nature of climate cooperation and economic interests, despite the two parties having a shared responsibility and interest in combating climate change. Besides, with the EU being increasingly aware of the geopolitical challenges—connecting trade agreements with politics and political expectations (Maher, 2016, p. 972)—it is expected that such a factor would have an impact on EU-China climate cooperation. Such framing would shed a negative light on China, weaken the prospects of cooperation in the area. Yet, in the long run, it remains to be seen whether there is a sustainable shift toward a more negative image of China, and even if so, whether this completely replaces the perception of China as a necessary

partner—it could also be a complementary view.

3. Methodology

Taking into account data availability and the research scope, the study will concentrate on European perception on China, understanding the increasingly complex EU-China dynamics from a European perspective. A media frame analysis will be conducted to analyze different existing frames regarding China in the context of climate change. The analysis draws on media discourses in newspaper articles from selected EU Member States, building on previous research on perception of EU-China relations (see Turcsanyi, 2017; Šimalčík, 2021; Lai & Cai, 2022; Lai, 2023). Following Neresini and Lorenzet (2016), media discourses are seen here as proxies of public opinion which is assumed to have a shaping role in policy-making (Burstein, 2003; Oehl et al., 2017). Details on the coding strategy are located in Table 1. The time frame of the analysis spans from 2015, the year of the Paris Agreement, to 2022, capturing the recent evolution of EU-China climate policy cooperation.

Three countries, Germany, Italy, and Poland, are selected for studying member-state-level perception of EU-China climate cooperation, which helps to present a representative picture of European media discourse. The three countries diverge in climate policy direction and their economic relationship with China. As such, they encompass a broad spectrum within the EU. In the overall Climate Change Performance Index 2023, which tracks the performance of European and other countries in the categories GHG Emissions, Renewable Energy, Energy Use and Climate Policy (Burck et al., 2022), Germany ranks 16th as one of the leading countries; Italy ranks 29th in the middle spectrum; while Poland ranks 54th, making it the country with the lowest score in the EU (Burck et al., 2022). As such, the selected countries reflect varying degrees of engagement in addressing climate change.

Their ranking remains consistent across the category of climate policy, which may highlight the perceived importance of climate issues among the public. This perception can, in turn, influence attitudes toward cooperation with China in this domain.

Moreover, the countries' economic interconnectedness with China varies, displaying a wide range of existing attitudes in European countries when engaging with China. Zenglein (2020) argues that the benefits of China's rise are the greatest for Germany. However, this also means that Germany is one of the most export-dependent countries from China (Zenglein, 2020). Hence, climate change has become a vital aspect of German-Chinese cooperation (Poggetti & Shi-Kupfer, 2018, p. 39). Montesano (2019, p. 150) argues that the economic relations are sensitive to normative disagreement due to Germany's strong value-based approach. This is echoed by Rühlig et al. (2018, p. 13) stating that the country's political leadership is active and vocal regarding policy action towards China. Such an approach is reflected by the current German government's decision to classify China as a "partner, competitor and systemic rival", similar to the position of the EU (Feng, 2022, p. 77). Italy also holds important economic relations with China and is the first G7 country to join the Belt and Road Initiative (Chen & Gao, 2022, p. 207). With considerable benefits from, and perhaps necessity for, Chinese investments, Italy has to trade off between maintaining its political values and its trade relations with China (Casarini et al., 2018, p. 52). However, Casarini et al. (2018, p. 53) assert that public opinion in Italy is rather unfavorable towards China which, in turn, supports a rather vocal strand in its China policy. Similarly, Poland's relationship with China is predominantly defined by economic considerations (Rajca, 2022). Poland has close ties to China because of its

participation in the Belt and Road Initiative and the 16+1 format, which was established in Warsaw (Rajca, 2022, p. 8; Montesano, 2019, p. 153). Public opinion was quite unfavorable towards China until stronger relations were established in 2008 (Szcudlik, 2018, p. 68). Recently however, geopolitical tensions between Poland and China have been growing due to Poland's alignment with the U.S. during the pandemic, which was further compounded by its anti-Russian stance on the Ukraine war (Rajca, 2022, pp. 8–10). Based on the outlined methodological and case selection, the analysis is carried out in the following section.

Table 1: Operationalization of Frames

Name of category	Content description	Category application	Examples of application	Delimitations
Interdependence frame	China is seen as a necessary partner for the EU in the context of climate change	multilateralism, China as partner, shared interests, emphasis on dialog and cooperation with China	"vital partner" (Gazeta Wyborcza [GW], 2021a), "essential partner" (Süddeutsche Zeitung [SZ], 2022e), "the fight against climate change is an example for shared interests" (SZ, 2021a)	China framed as necessary partner without reference to climate change
Economic opportunity frame	China is seen as creating economic opportunities for China in the context of climate change	EU-Chinese trade or investments, China creating economic opportunities for national/European companies, establishing companies, Chinese market open for EU	"climate battle actually offers an extraordinary opportunity" (La Corriere della Sera [CS], 2018b), "great business can be done with sun and wind" (SZ, 2018b)	China framed as economic opportunity without reference to climate change
Economic competition frame	China is seen as posing an economic competitor or economic threat to EU in the context of climate change	concerns about competitiveness of EU firms, unfair/imbalanced competition, economic conflict, dependence on China, China overtaking the EU, China taking the lead in economic sector, technological race	"fight for leadership in environmental policies and technologies" (CS, 2020d), "technological race" (GW, 2019a), "China [...] is considered to be Europe's biggest rival" (GW, 2021h)	China framed as economic threat without reference to climate change
Securitization frame	China is seen as a political threat to the EU in the context of climate change	China as systemic rival or political threat	"fight against climate change becomes an element of hegemonic confrontation" (CS, 2021e)	China framed as political threat without reference to climate change

Note. Author's own visualization.

4. Empirical Analysis

The findings are based on the analysis of 67 articles in total include pieces from Süddeutsche Zeitung (SZ, Germany), La Corriere della Sera (CS, Italy), and Gazeta Wyborcza (GW, Poland). For each of the selected cases, a national, non-tabloid newspaper was chosen that has the highest circulation and is available on LexisNexis Uni. To find the data, a keyword search was conducted for each newspaper in

the respective language, containing the keywords “climate” and “China.” To further narrow down the search to ensure a comparable number of articles across cases, specific inclusion criteria were applied: the time frame 01/01/2015 to 31/12/2022, a word count of more than 500 (only for Poland), and opinion pieces (only for Germany as including only opinion pieces for Italy and Poland would have resulted in a small n). Within the articles, which represented the unit of analysis, it was examined if one or more of the frames were prevalent. Articles containing none of the frames were excluded. Figure 1 shows the frequency of the frames according to the cases. The results of the analysis for each country are presented below, followed by a summary of the findings.

Figure 1: Frequency of Frames

Note. Author’s own visualization.

4.1 Germany

In the analysis of 23 articles from the *Süddeutsche Zeitung* (SZ), the interdependence (13) and the economic competition frame (12) were the most prevalent. The economic opportunity (5) as well as the securitization frame (3) were rather marginal. In addition, no major difference in the frequency of certain frames over time was visible.

The interdependence frame in the German articles emphasized China as a partner of the West on confronting climate change challenges (SZ, 2016a) and stressed their

shared interest (SZ, 2017c; SZ, 2021a). The similarities in climate action were described as a field of exception among other more fictitious topics (SZ, 2017a). The need for cooperation with China was especially present after the U.S. withdrawal from the Paris Agreement in 2017. Around that time, many articles picked up on this and stated the need to ‘stay together’ concerning the Paris Agreement (SZ, 2017b). Emphasis was put on the aspect that the EU and China are standing on the same side, in contrast to the U.S. (SZ, 2018). However, this did not change after the U.S. rejoined the international climate regime. From 2021 on, the analyzed articles called for further cooperation with China to achieve meaningful climate action. Notably, they have stressed collaboration between the U.S. and China, calling China an “essential partner” despite also being a systemic rival (SZ, 2022b; SZ, 2022d; SZ, 2022e). Following the most recent Conference of the Parties in 2022, reporting about China in the context of climate change peaked in German media and calls for the need of cooperation with China were reinforced. The articles championed the necessity of Chinese participation in the international climate regime, arguing that global climate protection measures are impossible without China (SZ, 2022f).

The second most dominant frame among analyzed articles is economic competition. The theme is most apparent when discussing competition for technological innovations and concerns about the German electric car industry. China is seen as a threat to the German car industry not only because it has surpassed Germany in electric vehicle production (SZ, 2015; SZ, 2017d), but also because it is emerging as a strong competitor in renewable energy and technology (SZ, 2017c). This dynamic has fostered economic dependencies and heightened anxieties within Germany regarding its reliance on China. Furthermore, the articles expressed concerns over the possibility that the German car industry has missed out on necessary changes

towards electromobility (SZ, 2017f). In line with this, China is repeatedly described as ‘in the lead’ and ‘overtaking’ Germany and Europe in economic terms (SZ, 2015; SZ, 2019). Furthermore, emphasis was often put on the competition over technologies between the EU, the U.S., and China (SZ, 2017c; SZ, 2021a). An additional dimension of this economic rivalry lies in China’s restrictive policies, especially those that hinder technology transfer (SZ, 2018).

However, China in the context of climate change is not only perceived as creating economic competition. Germany’s car industry can also benefit from China’s enormous market with abundant economic opportunities (SZ, 2019). As a consequence, China is also seen as an attractive investment market (SZ, 2021b). Interestingly, climate change is also framed as an economic opportunity for both China and the EU, which creates incentives to cooperate in connection to the interdependence frame (SZ, 2016b). Meanwhile, the securitization frame is hardly presented in the analyzed newspapers. Even if it appears in the context of climate change, it is strongly connected to the economic competition with China. Although not part of this analysis, China is more often framed as a political threat in the newspaper apart from the context of climate change. This suggests that in relation to climate change, which is closely connected to the economic realm, actors choose to concentrate on the economic consequences and draw a line from the political realm.

The analysis of the German newspaper *Süddeutsche Zeitung* showed no particular development in the direction of increased economic and political tensions with China regarding climate change. Instead, it demonstrated consistency in perceiving China as a necessary partner in climate change and an economic competitor in the green technology sector.

4.2 Italy

Similar to findings in the German newspaper, the interdependence (11) and economic competition frame (13) are most frequently found in *La Corriere della Sera* (CS). The economic competition frame was identified twice and the securitization frame once. Again contrary to expectations, there are no striking differences in the distribution of frames along the time span.

Although China is rarely framed as a partner in the context of climate change (CS, 2021b), its important role and the need for its contribution is acknowledged (CS, 2017a; CS, 2020a). China is regarded as a driving force for climate action (CS, 2016b). In addition, the Italian newspaper attributes growing importance and influence on China in the context of climate change: “Thanks to Donald Trump, China is now positioned as a world leader also in environmental protection and in defense of the climate agreement” (CS, 2017a). Furthermore, there are strong calls for further engagement of China in climate action, with certain accounts claiming that “without China [fighting climate change] is just a utopia” (CS, 2021d). Such rhetoric mostly addressed joint climate action on the international stage and stressed the need for cooperation between Italy and China (CS, 2017b; CS, 2020c).

Within the economic competition frame, it can be identified that fear exists for the increased economic influence of China—it is even perceived as a threat (CS, 2021a; CS, 2021c, CS, 2021e). Moreover, concerns about economic competition on climate change (technology) between the U.S. and China are expressed (CS, 2020d). It is even referred to as a war for technological dominance between the two (CS, 2018a). It can be stated that the economic competition frame occurs most of the time in the context of solar and other renewable energy technologies (CS, 2017c). The articles express concerns about a “solar race” and a changed balance in the economic renewable sector (CS, 2016a; CS, 2018d). Also, the consequences of

Chinese technology are looked at with concern (CS, 2018c). As a result, emphasis is placed on supporting the growth of the EU battery sector in order to reduce dependence on China (CS, 2020b). In addition, in contrast to the German media debate, the Italian economic competition frame relates more often to EU-China trade relations than between Italy and China. Nevertheless, China is still sometimes framed as a potential threat to the Italian economy (CS, 2021a).

The economic opportunity frame was identified twice, highlighting economic cooperation between the EU and China as well as the opening of the Chinese market for the EU (CS, 2020e). Climate change was further seen as an “extraordinary” strategic and economic opportunity for both actors (CS, 2018b).

Lastly, the securitization frame was only identified once. However, it is interesting that this is the case for the most recent article analyzed (CS, 2021e). Whereas other articles have identified China as a political threat outside the context of climate change, the connection between climate change and geopolitics was made only once. The article noted that “the fight against climate change becomes an element of hegemonic confrontation” (CS, 2021e).

The analysis of the Italian newspapers demonstrates a focus on EU-China trade relations when it comes to the economic competition frame, as well as a strong awareness that Chinese participation is needed for building an effective international climate regime.

4.3 Poland

The analysis of 20 articles from *Gazeta Wyborcza* (GW) showed a clear dominance of the interdependence frame (13), followed by the economic competition frame (6). The

economic opportunity frame was found once, and the securitization frame could not be identified at all. It should be noted that no articles from the years 2015 and 2016 could be found for the analysis. Instead, the selection of articles contains seven articles from 2020 and ten articles from 2021. This factor must be taken into account when considering the results.

Within the interdependence frame, similar to the German and Italian newspapers, the Polish newspaper stressed the shared commitment of the EU and China towards climate action after U.S. withdrawal (GW, 2017). Articles highlighted China’s climate declaration has a positive impact on global climate efforts, citing China’s initial heavy contribution to carbon emissions (GW, 2020b). The need for China to be involved in the global climate regime is expressed clearly: “without their involvement, the system is doomed to failure in the long run” (GW, 2020d). China is further called a “vital partner” (GW, 2021a). The dependency on China in the fight against climate change is also emphasized (GW, 2021e; GW, 2021f): “Without serious emission reductions in China, we will not win the fight against global warming.” (GW, 2021j) In addition, coordinated actions of the EU, China, and the U.S. for meaningful climate actions are seen as crucial (GW, 2020c). It is worth mentioning that in the articles, the interdependence frame is implicitly mentioned by warning from an increased use of coal plants by China (GW, 2020a) and the call for China “to do more” (GW, 2021e). Once again, there is a clear awareness that China must pursue a more climate-neutral path in order for global climate action to be effective.

The economic competition frame was also found in the newspaper, with certain articles framing China as “Europe’s biggest rival” in the hydrogen sector, which is necessary for building climate-neutral economies (GW, 2021h). The articles illustrate a renewable energy technology race between the EU, the U.S., and China (GW, 2019a, GW, 2019b). Lastly,

the climate opportunity frame was linked to portrayals of the EU as a climate power, influencing the technology sector through cooperation with China (GW, 2021i).

Interestingly, most of the references in the Polish newspaper focus on the international level, particularly on U.S.-China relations, while references to EU-China or Poland-China relations within the frames of interdependence and economic competition frame are scarce. The analyzed Polish newspaper articles showed China predominantly framed through the lens of interdependence, portraying it as necessary for global climate efforts, with a special focus on international and U.S. cooperation with China. Within the economic competition frame, the focus was mainly on competition in energy technology among the U.S., the EU, and China.

5. Discussion

The analysis leads to several findings. First, an overall shift towards a more negative framing of China in the context of climate change over time could not be found. According to the findings of this study, China was most often framed as an interdependent climate partner and economic competitor, while portrayals as an economic opportunity or political threat were less common.

Within the economic interdependence frame, China is seen as a necessary partner and ally in the fight against climate change. There is widespread awareness that China must contribute to global climate change. This is especially visible after the U.S. withdrawal from the Paris Agreement. Articles clearly expressed that in order to achieve meaningful climate efforts, China is needed in international collaborations. Often, there are calls for deepening cooperation. Consequently, it can be stated that climate cooperation with China is perceived positively, which creates

prospects for more climate cooperation in the future.

Regarding the second, economic competition frame, it can also be concluded that competitiveness plays an important part in the perception of China in the context of climate change. It is important to note that in the media discourse of different countries, the climate change issue is connected to different sectors of the economy. In the German newspaper, concerns mostly focused on the German car industry, the potential of a green transformation and renewable energy-related technologies. While the Italian debate highlights China as a competitor for the EU energy sector, the Polish debate is predominantly about the use and investment of coal in Poland and China. In all cases, the perception of China as a competitor in climate-related economic sectors is present, although with a country-specific focus. Country-specific divergence can potentially be a barrier to climate change cooperation with China if economic incentives and competition outweigh the perceptions of the benefits of climate cooperation with China.

In contrast to discussions on competition, the debate on economic opportunities created by climate change in regard to China has not been as pronounced. Although there is awareness of the economic opportunities created by climate change, these are overshadowed by perceptions of China posing an economic threat to European countries. Furthermore, contrary to the expectations, the securitization frame has not prevailed in the perception of China in the context of climate change. It seems that, unlike the economic sphere, the political relations with China are separated from the cooperation on climate change.

Although some articles showed securitization frames, they were not associated with the climate change debate and could, thus, not be included in the results of this paper. This puts forward the assumption that political realities are treated in a detached manner from the

discussion on climate cooperation.

Moreover, it is noteworthy that the European Union as an actor played a different role in the articles. While the Italian media debate concentrated on the EU's relationship with China, the Polish debate was dominated by a focus on the international level and the U.S.'s relations with China. In Germany, on the other hand, debates focused mostly on the national economy and relations with China as well as the broader EU-China relationship. This highlights the varying significance of the EU in national debates on climate cooperation and perceptions of China across Member States, reflecting differing degrees of European identity and nationally oriented perspectives in public discourse.

Lastly, no shift within the timeframe of certain perceptions of China is identifiable. As noted above, there is no particular change in the frequency of identified frames over time. The proposed assumption that the perception of China in the context of climate change shifted similarly to the general increasingly challenging view of China could not be verified. However, the clear salience of the economic competition frame can be seen as an indicator that there is awareness of the economic difficulties of EU-China climate cooperation.

Conclusion

The paper aimed to answer the question of how European media frames China in the context of climate change. The analysis of newspaper articles from Germany, Italy, and Poland showed that China is dominantly seen as a necessary partner on climate change as well as an economic competitor in particular in the climate-related technology sector. This indicates, firstly, that climate cooperation between the EU and China is based on a solid foundation of public support in European Member States, entails

a positive perception of China in this area, and makes further cooperation likely. Secondly, it shows how interlinked the topics of climate change and economy are and that this interconnectedness also poses challenges to EU-China climate cooperation. It is likely, however, that as long as the awareness of the urgency of the fight against climate change outweighs the economic concerns, EU-China climate cooperation can be enhanced and sustained. In light of recent geopolitical developments particularly in the U.S. it is worth considering whether the EU, amid growing pressure to assert greater strategic autonomy and uphold its sustainability agenda, might increasingly seek pragmatic engagement with China, especially if alignment with U.S. priorities becomes more difficult.

Nevertheless, the findings have to be seen in light of certain limitations. Although the cases were selected to make statements beyond the three cases only, it should be emphasized that this analysis cannot create a full picture of the European media debate on China in the context of climate change. Although it was deliberately decided to look at the national level to anticipate the limitation of treating "the EU as a unitary actor" (Gurol & Starkmann, 2021, p. 530), there are still many more cases, actors, and levels to be analyzed for a holistic picture to be formed. In this sense, it has to be recalled that the contribution of the findings is based on the claim that European media discourses serve as a proxy of public opinion which can eventually affect policy-making towards China. The author is aware of the limitations of this approach, thus further analysis should include additional sources such as government documents and expert interviews to capture more layers of European perceptions of China and their relevance for EU policy-making. Moreover, with the growing importance of newer media environments, future research could also explore social media and other non-traditional outlets, which may offer additional insights into how China is perceived in less formal and more publicly driven contexts.

Furthermore, it should be noted that the Chinese perception of EU-China climate cooperation has received no attention, even though understanding this viewpoint is crucial in order to evaluate the prospects of such collaboration. However, due to limited accessibility, the language barrier, and the scope of this paper, the analysis was confined to the European view on China; nonetheless, further research should be encouraged to address this gap.

To conclude, based on the analyzed perception of China, EU-China climate cooperation seems not to be caught up in geopolitical tensions and has despite certain economic fears on the European side potential for further effective partnership on climate change. The notion that there is no single, uniform image of the EU-China partnership was also emphasized in a recent statement by European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen (2023). Having examined the current European perceptions of China in the context of climate change, the future direction of EU-China relations remains uncertain. However, despite existing economic challenges, China is likely to continue being viewed as a critical partner in climate change cooperation, making continued collaboration in this area probable.

References

- Aktoudianakis, A. (2022). EU-China tech relations: Conditioning global tech standards adoption through market capitalisation. In I. Di Carlo (Ed.), *EU-China relations at a crossroads, Vol. I: Looking for a new modus vivendi* (pp. 12–15). European Policy Center. https://epc-web-s3.s3.amazonaws.com/content/PDF/2022/EU-China_Think-Tank_Compendium.pdf
- Bo, Y., Biedenkopf, K., & Chen, Z. (2016). Chinese and EU Climate and energy security policy. In E. J. Kirchner, T. Christiansen, & H. Dorussen (Eds.), *Security relations between China and the European Union* (pp. 102–123). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316563243.007>
- Burck, J., Uhlich, T., Bals, C., Höhne, N. & Nascimento, L. (2022). *Climate change performance index 2023: Results*. <https://www.germanwatch.org/sites/default/files/ccpi-ksi-2023-kurzfassung.pdf>
- Burstein, P. (2003). The impact of public opinion on public policy: A review and an agenda. *Political Research Quarterly*, 56(1), 29–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/106591290305600103>
- Casarini, N., Mariani, L., & Angiolillo, F. (2018). Political values in Italy's China policy: A "constructive approach." In T. Rühlig, B. Jerdén, F.-P. van der Putten, J. Seaman, M. Otero-Iglesias, & A. Ekman (Eds.), *Political values in Europe-China relations* (pp. 51–54). European Think-tank Network on China. https://meric.org/sites/default/files/2020-04/190108_ETNC_report_2018_updated_2019.pdf
- Chen, X., & Gao, X. (2022). Analysing the EU's collective securitisation moves towards China. *Asia Europe Journal*, 20(2), 195–216. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-021-00640-4>
- Di Carlo, I. (Ed.). (2022). *EU-China relations at a crossroads, Vol. I: Looking for a new modus vivendi*. European Policy Center. https://epc-web-s3.s3.amazonaws.com/content/PDF/2022/EU-China_Think-Tank_Compendium.pdf
- Dorussen, H., Kirchner, E. J., & Christiansen, T. (2018). Security cooperation in EU-China relations: Towards convergence? *European Foreign Affairs Review*, 23(3), 287–304. <https://doi.org/10.54648/EERR2018027>
- European Commission. (2019). *EU-China – A*

strategic outlook. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52019JC0005&from=EN>

- Feng, Z. (2022). Internal and external factors affecting China-EU relations. *China International Strategy Review*, 4(1), 74–90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42533-022-00108-z>
- Freeman, D. (2022). The EU and China: policy perceptions of economic cooperation and competition. *Asia Europe Journal*, 20(3), 245–264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-021-00609-3>
- German Council on Foreign Relations. (2022). *Managing risks in the EU-China economic relationship*. https://dgap.org/system/files/article_pdfs/dgap-policy%20brief-2022-33-en.pdf
- Gippner, O. (2014). Framing it right: China-EU relations and patterns of interaction on climate change. *Chinese Journal of Urban and Environmental Studies*, 2(1), 1450003. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2345748114500031>
- Griese, O. (2006). EU-China relations—an assessment by the communications of the European union. *Asia Europe Journal*, 4(4), 545–553. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-006-0087-x>
- Gurol, J. (2022). *The EU-China security paradox: Cooperation against all odds?* Bristol University Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/j.ctv269fw09>
- Gurol, J., & Starkmann, A. (2021). New partners for the planet? The European Union and China in international climate governance from a role-theoretical perspective. *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 59(3), 518–534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcms.13098>
- Kelleher, D. (2022). EU-China political relations, opportunities and challenges. In I. Di Carlo (Ed.), *EU-China relations at a crossroads, Vol. I: Looking for a new modus vivendi* (pp. 21–23). European Policy Center. https://epc-web-s3.s3.amazonaws.com/content/PDF/2022/EU-China_Think-Tank_Compendium.pdf
- Kirchner, E. J., Christiansen, T., & Dorussen, H. (Eds.). (2016). *Security relations between China and the European Union*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316563243>
- Lai, S. (2023). Not seeing eye to eye: perception of the China-EU economic relationship *Asia Europe Journal*, 17, 137-154. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-023-00658-w>
- Lai, S., & Cai, Y. (2022). Mapping perception of China in Central and Eastern Europe. *Asia Europe Journal*, 20(3), 305–327. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-021-00607-5>
- Lampe, F. A., Šipka, S., & Vandenbussche, T. (2022). From Brussels to Beijing: The key issues and tools for climate collaboration. In I. Di Carlo (Ed.), *EU-China relations at a crossroads, Vol. I: Looking for a new modus vivendi* (pp. 29–33). European Policy Center. https://epc-web-s3.s3.amazonaws.com/content/PDF/2022/EU-China_Think-Tank_Compendium.pdf
- Lamy, P., Fabry, E., & Redeker, N. (2022). *China and the role of Europe in a new world order*. Jacques Delors Institute. https://institutdelors.eu/content/uploads/2025/04/PP282_Evian-meeting-China_Fabry_EN.pdf
- Levy, K., & Révész, Á. (2022). No Common Ground: A Spatial-Relational Analysis of EU-China Relations. *Journal of Chinese Political Science*, 27(3), 457–491. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11366-021-09769-w>
- Liu, L., Wu, T., & Wan, Z. (2019). The EU-China relationship in a new era of global climate

- governance. *Asia Europe Journal*, 17(2), 243–254.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-018-00530-2>
- Maher, R. (2016). The elusive EU-China strategic partnership. *International Affairs*, 92(4), 959–976.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2346.12659>
- Michalski, A., & Pan, Z. (2017). Unlikely partners? The EU-China strategic partnership in a changing world order. In A. Michalski & Z. Zhongqi (Eds.), *Unlikely partners? China, the European Union and the Forging of a Strategic Partnership*. (pp. 1–10). Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3141-0_1
- Michalski, A., & Zhongqi, Z. (Eds.). (2017). *Unlikely Partners? China, the European Union and the Forging of a Strategic Partnership*. Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3141-0>
- Mišík, M. (2013). How can perception help us to understand the dynamic between EU Member States? The state of the art. *Asia Europe Journal*, 11(4), 445–463.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-013-0364-4>
- Montesano, F. S. (2019). EU-China security relations: discourse vs practice and the role of EU Member States. *The International Spectator*, 54(2), 139–158.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03932729.2019.1572356>
- Neresini, F., & Lorenzet, A. (2016). Can media monitoring be a proxy for public opinion about technoscientific controversies? The case of the Italian public debate on nuclear power. *Public Understanding of Science*, 25(2), 171–185.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662514551506>
- Oehl, B., Schaffer, L. M., & Bernauer, T. (2017). How to measure public demand for policies when there is no appropriate survey data? *Journal of Public Policy*, 37(2), 173–204.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0143814X16000155>
- Oertel, J. (2020). *The new China consensus: How Europe is rowing wary of Beijing*. European Council on Foreign Affairs.
https://ecfr.eu/publication/the_new_china_consensus_how_europe_is_growing_wary_of_beijing/
- Poggetti, L., & Shi-Kupfer, K. (2018). Germany's promotion of liberal values vis-à-vis China: Adapting to new realities in political relations. In T. Rühlig, B. Jerdén, F.-P. van der Putten, J. Seaman, M. Otero-Iglesias, & A. Ekman (Eds.), *Political values in Europe-China relations* (39-42). European Think-tank Network on China.
https://merics.org/sites/default/files/2020-04/190108_ETNC_report_2018_updated_2019.pdf
- Rajca, K. (2022). *The perspectives of Poland – China relations at a time of geopolitical tensions*. China-CEE Institute.
https://china-cee.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Working_paper-202211-Konrad-Rajca.pdf
- Rühlig, T., Jerdén, B., van der Putten, F.-P., Seaman, J., Otero-Iglesias, M., & Ekman, A. (Eds.). (2018). *Political values in Europe-China relations*. European Think-tank Network on China.
https://merics.org/sites/default/files/2020-04/190108_ETNC_report_2018_updated_2019.pdf
- Scott, D. (2009). Environmental issues as a 'strategic' key in EU–China relations. *Asia Europe Journal*, 7(2), 211–224.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-009-0227-1>
- Šimalčík, M. (2021). Image of China in Slovakia: Ambivalence, adoration, and fake news. *Asia Europe Journal*, 19(2), 245–258.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-021-00597-4>

- Smith, M. (2016). EU Diplomacy and the EU-China strategic relationship: framing, negotiation and management. *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, 29(1), 78–98.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09557571.2015.1118999>
- Stec, G. (2022). *EU-China summits: From cooperation to damage control*. MERICS. <https://merics.org/en/short-analysis/eu-china-summits-cooperation-damage-control>
- Szczudlik, J. (2018). Poland's modest approach to a values-based China policy. In T. Rühlig, B. Jerdén, F.-P. van der Putten, J. Seaman, M. Otero-Iglesias, & A. Ekman (Eds.), *Political values in Europe-China relations* (pp. 67–70). European Think-tank Network on China.
https://merics.org/sites/default/files/2020-04/190108_ETNC_report_2018_update_d_2019.pdf
- Turcsanyi, R. Q. (2017). Central European attitudes towards Chinese energy investments: The cases of Poland, Slovakia, and the Czech Republic. *Energy Policy*, 101, 711–722.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.09.035>
- Von der Leyen, U. (2023, March 30). *Speech by President von der Leyen on EU-China relations to the Mercator Institute for China Studies and the European Policy Centre*. European Commission.
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/speech_23_2063
- Von Lucke, F. (2023). The EU and China in the climate regime: Exploring different pathways towards climate justice. *Asia Europe Journal*, 429–435.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-022-00654-6>
- Zenglein, M. (2020). *Mapping and recalibrating Europe's economic interdependence with China*. Mercator Institute for China

Studies.

<https://merics.org/en/report/mapping-and-recalibrating-europes-economic-interdependence-china>

Appendix A

ID	Newspaper	Date	Title
GZ, 2017	Gazeta Wyborcza	2017, June 1	USA po raz drugi w historii uciekają od odpowiedzialności za globalne ocieplenie
GZ, 2019a	Gazeta Wyborcza	2019, August 22	Węgiel znika z Europy, ale na świecie ma się dobrze
GZ, 2019b	Gazeta Wyborcza	2019, October 10	Czarna księga PiS
GZ, 2020a	Gazeta Wyborcza	2020, March 26	Za Trumpa USA zamykają więcej węglowych elektrowni niż za Obamą
GZ, 2020b	Gazeta Wyborcza	2020, September 29	Xi Jinping zaskoczył deklaracją ws
GZ, 2020c	Gazeta Wyborcza	2020, October 10	Chiny czempionem w walce ze zmianami klimatu - prawda czy fałsz?
GZ, 2020d	Gazeta Wyborcza	2020, November 10	Joe Biden nie może być drugim Obamą
GZ, 2021a	Gazeta Wyborcza	2021, March 4	Magiczne słowo na "L"
GZ, 2021b	Gazeta Wyborcza	2021, April 22	Szczyt "największych niszczycieli klimatu"
GZ, 2021c	Gazeta Wyborcza	2021, June 2	Budynki odpowiadają aż za 25 proc
GZ, 2021d	Gazeta Wyborcza	2021, July 14	Jak zapobiec zmianie klimatu? Partia Razem popiera pakiet "Fit for 55"
GZ, 2021e	Gazeta Wyborcza	2021, August 3	Trump osłabił "odwęglowanie" Chin
GZ, 2021f	Gazeta Wyborcza	2021, August 15	Klimat nie wytrzymuje
GZ, 2021h	Gazeta Wyborcza	2021, September 22	Rządy na całym świecie stawiają na wodór
GZ, 2021i	Gazeta Wyborcza	2021, October 27	Dlaczego UE jest światową potęgą w dziedzinie klimatu?
GZ, 2021j	Gazeta Wyborcza	2021, October 30	Zieleniejący Xi
GZ, 2022	Gazeta Wyborcza	2022, December 9	MAE: Świat przechodzi z węgla na słońce
CS, 2016a	La Corriere della Sera	2016, March 14	Fotovoltaico E ora tutti al sole Cina in testa nell'anno dei record
CS, 2016b	La Corriere della Sera	2016, November 28	Ciima Le aziende Usa a Trump: 'Non tradire Parigi'
CS, 2017a	La Corriere della Sera	2017, January 18	Il nuovo ordine globale e il buonismo di davos
CS, 2017b	La Corriere della Sera	2017, February 25	Mattarella dalla Cina invita al dialogo: 'Stabilità essenziale'
CS, 2017c	La Corriere della Sera	2017, July 17	Il volto della cina ignorato; La potenza hi-tech
CS, 2018a	La Corriere della Sera	2018, January 15,	La Cina colma Il Vuoto lasciato Dagli Stati Uniti
CS, 2018b	La Corriere della Sera	2018, August 24	Come È possibile vincere la battaglia del clima; l'aumento delle temperature globali
CS, 2018c	La Corriere della Sera	2018, October 21	La Cina colma Il La Cina delle invenzioni lunari
CS, 2018d	La Corriere della Sera	2018, December 12	2018, l'anno peggiore dei gas serra

CS, 2020a	La Corriere della Sera	2020, January 13	Clima, l'Italia ha 300 idee Quanto ci costa non attuarle; Finanza Politica emergenze globali
CS, 2020b	La Corriere della Sera	2020, May 20	Alleanza Ue nelle batterie, parte la sfida a Cina e Usa L'Italia con Enel X e Faam
CS, 2020c	La Corriere della Sera	2020, December 14	Un super club del clima per un pianeta sostenibile
CS, 2020d	La Corriere della Sera	2020, December 21	Tra Cina e Russia le sfide inedite di Joe Biden; IL presidente Usa e un 2021 complicato
CS, 2020e	La Corriere della Sera	2020, December 31	Ue-Cina, intesa sugli investimenti Si aprono le porte tra i due mercati
CS, 2021a	La Corriere della Sera	2021, August 8	La svolta verde (e i timori); Il clima, l'economia
CS, 2021b	La Corriere della Sera	2021, August 15	Il futuro del pianeta è adesso; Clima e stili di vita
CS, 2021c	La Corriere della Sera	2021, November 1	'Misure concrete' sul clima: il G20 si impegna (senza data)
CS, 2021d	La Corriere della Sera	2021, November 1	Senza la Cina è solo un'utopia: più della politica, ci potrà aiutare la tecnologia
CS, 2021e	La Corriere della Sera	2021, November 10	Il mondo nuovo (e diviso); Noi, gli Usa e la Cina
SZ, 2015	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2015, December 12	Verkehr; Es stinkt was in Deutschland
SZ, 2016a	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2016, March 21	China; Furcht und Stille überall
SZ, 2016b	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2016, October 8	Klimaschutz, der Vertrag
SZ, 2017a	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, March 9	China, geplagte Großmacht
SZ, 2017b	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, June 2	Klima, Grotesker Alleingang
SZ, 2017c	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, June 2	Klima, Reich an Vernunft

SZ, 2017d	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, September 29	China, Peking entscheidet, alle folgen
SZ, 2017f	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, November 11	Autoindustrie, ein Sieg, der ihnen noch leid tun wird
SZ, 2018	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2018, May 24	China schwierige Freunde
SZ, 2017a	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, March 9	China, geplagte Großmacht
SZ, 2017b	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, June 2	Klima, Grotesker Alleingang
SZ, 2017c	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, June 2	Klima, Reich an Vernunft
SZ, 2017d	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, September 29	China, Peking entscheidet, alle folgen
SZ, 2017f	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2017, November 11	Autoindustrie, ein Sieg, der ihnen noch leid tun wird
SZ, 2018	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2018, May 24	China schwierige Freunde
SZ, 2019	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2019, March 20	Elektromobilität, Boss mit Weitblick
SZ, 2021a	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2021, July 27	China und USA, Nicht um jeden Preis
SZ, 2021b	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2021, November 16	Klimaschutz, Indien braucht Perspektiven
SZ, 2022a	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2022, April 24	Erneuerbare Energien, in Sachsen steht ein Windrad
SZ, 2022b	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2022, June 10	Klimaschutz, Hauptsache behutsam
SZ, 2022c	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2022, August 24	Grüner Wasserstoff, es wird Zeit
SZ, 2022d	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2022, November 12	Klima, das Experiment
SZ, 2022e	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2022, November 15	Handelspolitik, jenseits von China
SZ, 2022f	Süddeutsche Zeitung	2022, November 21	Klimagipfel, weniger als nichts

Marie Sophie Mayer

marie.sophie.mayer@googlemail.com

Marie Sophie Mayer is a Graduate of the Research Master in European Studies at Maastricht University and holds a Bachelor in Political Science of LMU Munich. She gained valuable professional experience at the United Nations, the European Commission and the Munich Security Conference, focusing on sustainable development, global governance, public policy and science for policy. Her research interests circle around international and European politics, environmental governance and security studies.

Navigating the Evolving Landscape: Intellectual Property and Technology Transfer in China's Electric Vehicle Industry

Carolina Fabara

Abstract

China's evolving regulatory landscape for technology transfer and intellectual property (IP) protection has profoundly shaped foreign direct investment (FDI) strategies in its automotive sector, particularly for electric vehicles (EVs). Since the late 1970s, China has used joint venture (JV) requirements to facilitate technology transfer from foreign automakers, aiming to accelerate domestic industry modernization. While this "market access for technology" strategy initially led to over-reliance on foreign technology, recent reforms have shifted toward innovation-driven growth. Amendments to patent laws, the establishment of specialized IP courts, and stricter enforcement mechanisms have improved IP protection, aligning China more closely with international standards such as the WTO's TRIPS Agreement. These changes have increased foreign investor confidence, prompting global automakers, especially German firms, to expand localized R&D and production. However, challenges remain—security screenings, data localization mandates, and export controls on advanced battery technologies create significant compliance burdens and limit technology sharing. Regional disparities in enforcement and persistent risks of forced technology transfer further complicate the investment environment. Despite these hurdles, China's dual strategy of protecting foreign IP to attract investment while supporting domestic champions like BYD and CATL has propelled it to the forefront of the global EV industry. The regulatory balance between fostering innovation, safeguarding national interests, and ensuring fair competition continues to define China's role as a collaborator and

competitor in the global automotive industry.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Electric Vehicles (EVs), Intellectual Property (IP) Protection, Technology Transfer, Regulatory Framework

Introduction

This study examines how China's evolving technology transfer regulations and intellectual property (IP) enforcement mechanisms have shaped foreign direct investment (FDI) strategies in its automotive sector. Recent amendments to patent laws, administrative licensing frameworks, and strengthened enforcement mechanisms—including heightened infringement penalties and specialized IP courts—demonstrate alignment with international standards. The government's shift from subsidies to innovation-focused policies, such as standardized vehicle testing and electric vehicle (EV) infrastructure mandates, prioritizes market-driven ecosystems. These reforms have increased foreign investor confidence, particularly among German automakers adopting localized research and development (R&D). However, tightened security screenings create significant hurdles, including prolonged cybersecurity reviews, stringent data localization requirements, and expansive national security interpretations that delay approvals and raise compliance costs. Foreign firms must weigh enhanced IP protections against risks including forced technology sharing, retroactive regulatory scrutiny, and ambiguous security thresholds. Sector-specific impacts emerge: component manufacturers benefit from clearer IP rules, while connected and autonomous vehicle firms face disproportionate security barriers. Effective strategies involve decoupling core technologies from market-specific adaptations while leveraging improved legal recourse, underscoring the complex balance between China's regulatory

advancements and persistent geopolitical challenges.

1. The Chinese Regulatory Environment, Foreign Direct Investment, and Technology Transfer

Foreign direct investment (FDI) serves as a primary channel for transferring advanced technologies from developed to developing countries, playing a pivotal role in the modernization of host economies (Borensztein et al., 1998). When multinational corporations establish subsidiaries abroad, they not only bring in capital and managerial expertise but also introduce cutting-edge technologies and processes. A crucial aspect of this technology transfer occurs through the hiring and integration of local staff within these foreign subsidiaries (Minbaeva et al., 2003). By employing local workers, foreign firms gain valuable insights into the host country's market dynamics and cultural nuances, which can enhance their operational effectiveness and competitiveness. Simultaneously, local employees benefit from direct exposure to new technologies and international best practices introduced by their foreign employers, facilitating skill development and knowledge diffusion within the local workforce. This reciprocal relationship underscores how FDI-driven hiring practices are intrinsically linked to broader technology transfer objectives, as both the foreign investor and the host economy stand to gain from the exchange of knowledge and expertise fostered through these collaborations.

The employment and integration of local employees within overseas subsidiaries is a vital avenue for knowledge transfer. In the Chinese automobile industry, where joint ventures between international automakers and local businesses have been crucial in promoting a two-way flow of information and expertise, this dynamic is especially noticeable. Hiring local employees gives multinational corporations (MNCs) crucial

insights into China's distinct market conditions, consumer preferences, and cultural background. Foreign automakers can improve their competitiveness and operational efficiency by customizing their goods, services, and management techniques to better suit the Chinese market thanks to this local knowledge (Buckley et al., 2007). For instance, multinational automakers in China have improved their market acceptance and success by modifying their vehicle designs and marketing plans in response to input and knowledge from their local employees.

On the other hand, working in foreign-owned automotive subsidiaries exposes local workers directly to cutting-edge manufacturing technologies, global industry standards, and international management practices. Chinese employees acquire new management and technical skills through daily collaboration with international specialists, mentorship, and on-the-job training that are sometimes absent in domestic-only companies. In addition to improving individual career possibilities, this helps spread best practices and information throughout China's automotive sector as workers pass their knowledge on to other local businesses or start-ups (Buckley et al., 2007).

Since FDI was first allowed in China in 1978, the government has mandated that foreign companies enter the market mainly through joint ventures (JVs) with local partners. This policy was put in place to help domestic industries close technological gaps and facilitate technology transfer (Fuchs et al., 2021). The Sino-Foreign Equity Joint Venture Law of 1979 codified this strategy, offering the legal foundation for such partnerships and encouraging foreign investment, particularly in fields that sought cutting-edge technology. These joint venture regulations became especially important in the automotive industry, where Western automakers were required to establish joint ventures with Chinese businesses between 1994 and the late 2010s, with the Chinese partner owning at least 50% of the joint venture (Fuchs et al., 2021). The

objective was to enable domestic manufacturers to get international technological expertise, therefore mitigating technological uncertainties and expediting the advancement of China's automobile sector.

Notwithstanding the incremental easing of ownership limitations—culminating in the removal of foreign ownership caps for new energy vehicles (NEVs) in 2018 and for all passenger vehicles by 2022—joint ventures remain predominant, particularly in the EV sector (Cheng, 2021; Koty, 2018). During this transition period, the regulatory environment shifted from mandating joint ventures toward permitting the creation of wholly foreign-owned enterprises (WFOEs). Such a decision granted foreign automakers the legal right to establish fully controlled subsidiaries. Despite the legal feasibility of WFOEs, numerous foreign automakers continue to establish joint ventures to leverage the expertise of Chinese partners in local supply chains, regulatory compliance, and alignment with state innovation objectives (Azure Group China, 2024). As a result, during the transition period, legacy joint ventures and new WFOEs coexisted, as international businesses balanced the benefits of local partnerships with the desire for autonomy and intellectual property protection while navigating China's intricate market environment. For example, joint venture activity has increased recently as international manufacturers seek to tap into China's sophisticated EV ecosystem, access to pre-existing supplier networks, and benefit from policy incentives designed to support local innovation and quick market adaptation.

China's combination of regulatory requirements (such as JV structures) and substantial economic incentives for "encouraged" sectors has been highly effective in attracting foreign technology and accelerating its adaptation and diffusion within the country. Domestic laws and regulations have stimulated technology transfer—by providing incentives to

international corporations, the Chinese state accelerated the process of technological adaptation. These benefits include entry to China's vast market and measures that fall under the "encouraged" section of the Catalog Guiding Foreign Investment in Industry (State Council of the People's Republic of China, 1995). The Catalog remains a key tool for targeting specific high-tech and strategic industries, offering foreign firms both access to the Chinese market and tangible policy benefits in exchange for technology transfer and local investment. Tax deductions or reductions, as well as advantageous financing alternatives for large-scale projects, are also available to foreign enterprises. Furthermore, businesses situated in high-tech zones and those that qualify as high-tech and new-technology enterprises are eligible for additional financial support. According to PwC China (2024), the standard corporate income tax (CIT) rate is 25%, but this can be reduced to 15% for qualifying high-tech and new-technology enterprises (HNTEs) and for companies located in designated zones such as the Hainan Free Trade Port and other Special Economic Zones (SEZs) if they meet certain criteria. For example, a foreign-invested company in Shanghai that obtains HNTE status can reduce its CIT rate from 25% to 15%, resulting in substantial annual tax savings.

Although there are regional differences in FDI investment incentives, they have stimulated the introduction of high-tech FDI and have played a critical role in acquiring technology. For example, the Shanghai Municipal People's Government offers FDI incentives, providing additional incentives to individuals who attract high-tech industries and any of the world's leading 500 companies to invest in China (Lee et al., 2003). Investment incentives are only applicable to sectors designated by the government. Regions in Eastern and Southern China such as Shanghai, Guangdong, and Jiangsu have historically attracted the bulk of FDI due to early market liberalization, superior infrastructure, skilled labor, and proximity to international markets (Wei et al., 2007). To maintain their competitive

edge and attract high-value projects, these regions offer targeted inducements, especially for high-tech and advanced manufacturing sectors.

Despite these targeted incentives, alongside improvements in the investment environment, foreign companies—particularly German firms—continue to face significant regulatory and operational challenges in China. The German Chamber of Commerce in China (2022) has highlighted that only 6% of German businesses reported clear contractual duties, and 24% felt forced to share technology in order to retain their market access. Additionally, more than 50% of German businesses operating in China have localized R&D operations, in part to reduce IP risks and meet regulatory requirements (German Chamber of Commerce in China, 2022). These businesses can develop closer relationships with their customers, react quickly to market changes, and adjust to changing regulatory environments owing to local R&D facilities. In order to successfully navigate administrative procedures and obtain market access, this strategy also aids in forging closer ties with regional suppliers, partners, and government organizations. Therefore, in China, regions compete for high-tech investment by offering significant incentives, especially to projects that promise advanced technology transfers, local R&D, and stronger alignment with China's industrial priorities. For foreign businesses, this creates a complex calculus: balancing the risks of IP exposure and regulatory compliance against the substantial benefits offered for deeper localization and technological collaboration, as well as legislative changes implemented to improve the business climate for international corporations.

To regulate issues concerning technology transfer, it is important for the Chinese state to take into account both codified legal frameworks and practical considerations. Such actions include refining licensing practices

related to technology transfer guaranteeing that IP laws can be properly enforced. Additionally, given the legality of reverse engineering under Chinese law, companies should implement strong contractual safeguards to reduce risks. China's regulatory environment demands a dual focus: adhering to progressive laws like the Foreign Investment Law while anticipating practical hurdles. Foreign firms must craft licensing agreements that preempt ownership disputes, comply with filing rules, and deter reverse engineering through enforceable contracts. Ultimately, combining legal vigilance with strategic partnerships remains key to navigating this landscape.

While China's domestic legal reforms and corporate strategies reflect efforts to balance innovation incentives with market access, these measures cannot be fully assessed without contextualizing them within global intellectual property norms. This necessitates examining China's alignment with the World Trade Organization's (WTO) Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Agreement), a framework that underpins international IP standards and shapes how nations reconcile domestic priorities with transnational obligations. TRIPS compliance not only illuminates the structural evolution of China's IP regime but also highlights persistent gaps between legislative commitments and enforcement realities, particularly in contentious areas like forced technology transfer and reverse engineering.

2. Navigating the TRIPs Agreement: A Comprehensive Overview of IPR Protection

TRIPS is the most comprehensive multilateral agreement on intellectual property rights (IPR) to date, administered by the WTO (TRIPS Agreement, 1994). It establishes minimum standards for the protection and enforcement of various forms of IPR, including patents, copyrights, trademarks, industrial designs, geographical indications, trade secrets, and undisclosed information (TRIPS Agreement,

1994). It demands effective enforcement of IPR through civil, administrative, and criminal procedures. Furthermore, the agreement codified dispute settlement procedures to resolve IPR-related disputes between WTO members (TRIPS Agreement, 1994). These measures promote innovation and empower law enforcement to legitimately and morally access and employ new technologies. Most notably, TRIPS better safeguards cross-border technology transfer by clarifying protective measures for the technology IP owners. In Article 7., the WTO makes it clear that the goal of IP rights protection is to promote innovation, technology transfer, and balance rights and obligations:

The protection and enforcement of intellectual property rights should contribute to the promotion of technological innovation and to the transfer and dissemination of technology, to the mutual advantage of producers and users of technological knowledge and in a manner conducive to social and economic welfare, and to a balance of rights and obligations. (TRIPS Agreement, 1994)

Article 8.2 recognizes that WTO members need to adopt appropriate measures to prevent practices that adversely affect the international transfer of technology. This clause implies the WTO permits countries to employ measures against IP rights abuse or anti-competitive practices, so long as the measures comply with the Agreement (TRIPS Agreement, 1994). This provision acts as a corrective mechanism within TRIPS, enabling countries to enforce IP rights in ways that prioritize equitable technology access, fair competition, and public welfare. Its relevance is heightened in contexts where IP concentration threatens developmental or environmental goals.

Article 66.2 regarding Least-Developed Country (LDC) Members mandates developed

country (DC) members to incentivize their enterprises and institutions to carry out and advocate for technology transfer to LDC members. This article aims to assist LDCs in building a solid technological foundation. However, the vague language of the provision and the private nature of intellectual property rights complicates the implementation of this requirement. To address these shortcomings in relation to the EV sector, China has adopted a dual strategy of aggressive incentives and structured IP frameworks while avoiding the use of coercive tactics. China's unique status as both a developing country and an emerging global power allows it to navigate international obligations with flexibility, selectively invoking its developmental challenges or economic strengths as needed—a dynamic that complicates a straightforward application of Article 66.2. By clarifying obligations, aligning subsidies with measurable outcomes can facilitate meaningful technology transfer without undermining private IP rights. This approach would not only aid LDCs but also create new markets for developed countries firms in emerging green economies.

China's evolving legal framework for IP and FDI reflects strategic alignment with global norms, such as the WTO's TRIPS Agreement, while simultaneously advancing domestic innovation goals. Recent legislative reforms, including the 2020 Foreign Investment Law (FIL), explicitly prohibit forced technology transfer and strengthen IP protections for foreign investors, addressing long-standing criticisms from Western partners (Raslan, 2024). These measures align with TRIPS Article 8.2 by curbing anti-competitive practices, though enforcement inconsistencies persist, particularly in local courts favoring domestic firms. China's specialized IP courts and enhanced punitive damages, up to RMB 5 million for trade secret violations, demonstrate compliance with TRIPS enforcement standards, yet gaps remain in translating legal reforms into uniform practice (Interesse, 2024).

The relationship between FDI and IP is key to

China's desire to move from technology importer to global innovator. While TRIPS Article 66.2 stresses technology transfer to least-developed nations, China has flipped this dynamic through the use of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), exporting its tech standards while utilizing international R&D inflows (TRIPS Agreement, 1994). China's BRI-driven tech exports and developing-country status create a dual dynamic where it functions both as a recipient of foreign R&D—like a least developed country—and a provider of technology—like a developed country. This exposes a gap in TRIPS, which was designed for a binary DC-LDC framework, not for ascendant economies reshaping global tech hierarchies through initiatives like the BRI.

This evolving role is reflected in China's recent domestic policy reforms. High-tech and green industries are given priority on the 2024 Negative List for Foreign Investment, which steers FDI toward fields like EVs and AI to support domestic innovation (National Development and Reform Commission [NDRC] & Ministry of Commerce [MOFCOM], 2024). The Negative List specifies sectors where foreign investment is restricted for example equity caps or prohibited. Industries not on the list are fully open to foreign investors. (NDRC & MOFCOM, 2024). The 2024 list removed all manufacturing restrictions, including EVs, semiconductors, and green energy sectors, which are now fully accessible to foreign capital. These sectors are excluded from the Negative List, meaning foreign firms can invest without ownership limits or mandatory joint ventures. China is now ranked as the world's second-largest R&D spender, with seven of the top ten research institutes worldwide being Chinese. This is due to a dual policy of preserving foreign intellectual property to attract investment while funding local R&D (Interesse, 2024). This dual strategy protecting foreign IP to attract FDI while channeling resources into local R&D has positioned China as both a collaborator and competitor in the global EV race, epitomizing

its transition from technology follower to innovator.

China's journey from technology importer to innovator has been underpinned by a dual legal evolution: aligning domestic IP frameworks with international standards while tailoring reforms to serve national innovation objectives. This development illustrates China's balancing act, which continues to define its status as both a partner and a rival in the global intellectual property landscape: using international accords like TRIPS to integrate into global value chains while improving legislation to support domestic R&D.

3. Advancements in IPR Protection: China's Evolving Domestic Legislation

In recent years, statutory laws on IPR in China have been converging with international standards. China joined several international organizations and agreements, promulgating domestic legislation alongside. China's modern IP Rights regulatory regime dates back to the 1980s. The regime consists of the 1982 Trademark Law, the 1984 Patent Law, and the 1990 Copyright Law. The Trademark Law protects distinctive markings used to identify goods and services. The Patent Law protects inventions and grants exclusive rights to IP rights holders. Meanwhile, the Copyright Law protects original literary, artistic, and scientific works. Nonetheless, even though basic IP rules are established, China continues to have serious difficulties with implementing the laws throughout the 1980s and beyond. Proliferating IP infringements caused by inadequate enforcement measures and local protectionism made certain investors reluctant to enter the Chinese market. Over time, particularly as China's automotive sector shifted toward EVs, these laws underwent significant evolution to address the needs of FDI and to align with international standards.

China's 2001 WTO entrance and pressure from trading partners prompted the first legislation to focus on conformity with international standards,

including the TRIPS Agreement. Prior to reforms, foreign investment was discouraged by local protectionism, lax enforcement, and widespread infringement, especially in technology-intensive industries. By the 2010s, China's strategic focus on EVs supported by subsidies, R&D funding, and infrastructure investments spurred changes, including stricter enforcement mechanisms like specialized IP courts and punitive damages (up to ¥5 million) for infringement. These changes facilitated landmark investments, such as Tesla's 2018 WFOE in Shanghai, which combined access to China's market with enhanced IP safeguards.

China's intellectual property reforms, like the 2023 Patent Law amendments that allow for delayed examination and more stringent good-faith filing requirements, decreased the risk of forced technology transfers for foreign automakers like BMW and Volkswagen and encouraged FDI in localized R&D and production (Patent Law of the People's Republic of China, 2023; Fuchs et al., 2021). German automakers took advantage of loosened JV regulations by expanding their partnership stakes such as BMW's 75% ownership in Brilliance Auto and using China's EV supply chains for autonomous driving and battery technology (Jakóbowski & Oertel, 2025; Laurucci, 2023). However, these reforms coexisted with residual challenges: despite abolishing foreign ownership caps for passenger EVs in 2022, legacy JVs remained prevalent due to local partners' market expertise, and domestic firms like BYD and CATL outpaced foreign rivals in LFP battery patents (62,000 by 2024) and cost efficiency (Grünecker, 2024; Ezell, 2024).

By 2024, China emerged as a global EV patent leader, filing 62,000 charging-related patents, while domestic firms like BYD and CATL leveraged state-backed R&D to dominate battery technologies such as lithium iron phosphate (LFP) cells (Grünecker, 2024). However, tensions persist between China's

dual role as an IP collaborator (via initiatives like the Belt and Road) and competitor, exemplified by its rise as the world's largest EV exporter amid ongoing allegations of forced technology transfers. This evolution underscores how China transformed its IP regime from a barrier to a catalyst for innovation, balancing TRIPS Agreement compliance with domestic priorities to achieve technological leadership.

Despite improved mechanisms to protect foreign IP rights, domestic strategic R&D investments and partnerships between corporations, entrepreneurs, and universities are supported by the state. China's 2025 restrictions on exporting LFP preparation and lithium extraction technologies (MOFCOM, 2025) prevent foreign competitors from replicating advanced battery formulas. This protects domestic firms' IP while allowing them to scale production for global EV markets. Utilizing these regulations, domestic companies such as BYD and CATL were able to develop the first lithium iron phosphate (LFP) battery technologies, which are more affordable, safer, and have longer lifespans than conventional lithium-ion cells (Carbon Credits, 2024). Ultra-fast charging (300 miles in 5 minutes) and 15-year or 1.5-million-kilometer warranties are made possible by CATL's innovations, such as its M3P chemistry and Shenxing LFP cells (Lambert, 2025). In the meantime, BYD surpassed Tesla in global EV sales by 2024 thanks to its vertically integrated supply chain and emphasis on LFP innovation (Carbon Credits, 2024). China's patent leadership extends beyond hardware to smart charging infrastructure, with firms like Aulton developing data-connected high-performance stations (Grünecker, 2024). These efforts are supported by subsidies, specialized IP courts, and punitive damages for infringement, which strengthened domestic innovation ecosystems (Ezell, 2024). To illustrate, high-tech enterprises enjoy a 15% corporate income tax rate (vs. 25% standard), saving firms over \$370 billion in 2024. R&D-focused companies also benefit from a 200% super deduction on qualifying R&D expenses, incentivizing innovation-driven investments

(Huld, 2023).

The Cybersecurity Law (CSL) (2017), Data Security Law (DSL) (2021), and Personal Information Protection Law (PIPL) (2021) are the foundation of China's data localization regulations, which require that data produced by EVs, such as vehicle telematics, user behavior, and geographic data, be stored domestically and prohibit cross-border transfers without permission from the government (Cyberspace Administration of China [CAC], 2021; Skadden, Arps, Slate, Meagher & Flom LLP, 2021). The 14th Five-Year Plan (2021–2025), which emphasizes "*digital China*" and technical sovereignty, is in line with these regulations. Its goal is to strengthen control over vital data in order to support domestic innovation in high-tech industries like EVs (Koty, 2018).

Localized adaptations are used by German automakers such as Volkswagen and BMW to comply with these restrictions. In order to meet DSL regulations and expedite the development of cost-effective EVs, Volkswagen consolidated its EV R&D in Hefei, Anhui, creating a data-compliant hub for its Modular Electric Drive Matrix (MEB) and China Main Platform (CMP) (Fuels & Lubes, 2024). In order to comply with the Personal Information Protection Law's (PIPL) requirements for personal information permission, BMW and Tencent collaborated to develop autonomous driving technologies that are suited to China's data regulations (Symonds, 2019). The development of the BMW Group China High Performance D³ platform, a cutting-edge data-driven development hub situated in China, lies at the heart of this partnership. Tencent ensures that all activities completely adhere to Chinese rules on data security and privacy by providing the platform with the IT architecture, cloud computing, big data analytics, and security expertise it needs. This is especially crucial as Chinese laws mandate that domestically generated automobile data be processed and stored locally, and foreign

businesses are not allowed to host such data on their own without a domestic partner. BMW can process the enormous volumes of driving and environmental data required for the verification and development of Level 3 and Level 4 autonomous driving systems by utilizing Tencent's capabilities. This allows BMW to modify these technologies to meet the particular traffic conditions and legal requirements of China. In addition to speeding up BMW's R&D for autonomous vehicles in its biggest international market, the agreement establishes a standard for cross-industry collaboration under China's developing data and automotive innovation laws (BMW Group, 2024; Liao, 2019; Reuters, 2025).

China's regulatory framework—characterized by strict export controls on advanced battery technologies, comprehensive data localization requirements, and targeted industrial policies has been instrumental in enabling domestic champions like BYD and CATL to dominate the lithium iron phosphate (LFP) battery sector (MOFCOM, 2025; State Council Information Office, 2024). By mandating that sensitive R&D data and core manufacturing techniques remain within national borders, these regulations not only protect intellectual property but also create high barriers for foreign competitors seeking to replicate Chinese advancements (Reuters, 2025). However, these same export and data restrictions also limit the global integration of Chinese research and development, effectively siloing innovation within the domestic market (Groenewegen-Lau & Gunter, 2025). This dual approach illustrates the Chinese state's strategy: on one hand, leveraging data control and technology protection to spur indigenous EV innovation and secure global leadership in LFP patents as exemplified by BYD's hegemony; on the other, attracting foreign investment and collaboration through increasingly clear and predictable regulatory guidelines (UN Trade and Development [UNCTAD], 2024; Reuters, 2025). This regulatory architecture provides both a shield for domestic innovators and a structured pathway for foreign firms to participate in China's rapidly evolving electric vehicle ecosystem.

Overall, by aligning IP reforms with sector-specific goals, for example EV infrastructure in the 14th Five-Year Plan, China transformed its regulatory framework into a catalyst for both indigenous innovation and foreign collaboration, ensuring its dual rise as a protector of foreign IP and a leader in EV technology exports. By explicitly linking IP protection and enforcement with national priorities, such as the rapid buildout of EV infrastructure and the development of new energy vehicle clusters, China has created a regulatory environment that both incentivizes domestic innovation and reassures foreign investors about the safety of their technology and know-how.

In addition to requiring more stringent quality control, higher standards for new energy vehicles, and quicker charging infrastructure deployment, the 14th Five-Year Plan lays out goals for high-value invention patents, patent-intensive industries, and international intellectual property cooperation. These policies have created an innovation ecosystem in which foreign companies are more inclined to cooperate, invest, and license technology because they know their intellectual property will be better protected, and Chinese companies are encouraged to develop core technologies and compete internationally (State Council of the People's Republic of China, 2021; National Intellectual Property Administration, 2021). This dual rise as a protector of foreign intellectual property and a leader in electric vehicle technology exports is further reinforced by administrative and judicial reforms, such as specialized IP courts, punitive damages for infringement, and streamlined legal recourse for rights holders. At the same time, sectoral policies like purchase subsidies, infrastructure investment, and clear technical standards have made China the world's largest EV market and a global exporter of EV technology (Reuters, 2025; Ezell, 2024). This dual rise as a protector of foreign intellectual property and a leader in electric vehicle technology exports is further

reinforced by administrative and judicial reforms, such as specialized IP courts, punitive damages for infringement, and streamlined legal recourse for rights holders. At the same time, sectoral policies—like purchase subsidies, infrastructure investment, and clear technical standards have made China the world's largest EV market and a global exporter of EV technology (Ezell, 2024; CIELA Insights, 2024; Reuters, 2025).

4. Balancing Development and Security: Major State Plans and Documents strategizing IPR protection

China's transition from growth driven by subsidies to competition driven by innovation is highlighted by the interaction of top-down policies (such as Belt and Road tech exports), mid-term industrial targets, and bottom-up pilot programs. In the midst of increasing examination of IP enforcement loopholes and geopolitical concerns, China has positioned itself as both a collaborator and a competitor, as seen by its dominance in worldwide EV exports (40.9% penetration in 2024) (Argus Media, 2025; Jakóbowski & Oertel, 2025). As China's EV industry develops into a dual engine of FDI attraction and indigenous disruption, it is still crucial for manufacturers to strike a balance between technology sharing and IP protection.

The 14th Five-Year Plan National IP Protection and Application Plan and China's 2021 Guidelines for Building a Powerful Country with Intellectual Property Rights (2021–2035) signaled a strategic shift in bringing legal frameworks into line with technological aspirations, especially in the EV industry. The 2021 Guidelines outlined two goals: establishing China as a global leader in intellectual property governance through programs like the Belt and Road Initiative and bolstering domestic IP systems, including the establishment of specialist tribunals and the imposition of punitive damages. (China Justice Observer, 2021; Lung Tin Intellectual Property Agent Ltd., 2021). At the same time, the 14th Five-Year Plan established quantitative goals, such as increasing the GDP contribution of

patent-intensive industries to 13% by 2025 and obtaining 12 high-value invention patents per 10,000 people. These goals will directly encourage innovation and technological advancement in industries such as EVs (China National Intellectual Property Administration, 2021; State Council Information Office, 2021).

Meanwhile, IP reforms under the Guidelines for Building a Powerful Country with Intellectual Property Rights (2021–2035) are driven by two interconnected strategic goals (Central Committee of the Communist Party of China & State Council of the People’s Republic of China, 2021). First, they aim to accelerate the economic transition from manufacturing-based growth to innovation-led development, particularly in high-value sectors like EVs and artificial intelligence (AI). For instance, BYD’s global patent filings surged by 40% in 2023 after reforms strengthened IP safeguards, enabling the company to dominate EV battery innovation and expand into European markets (Raslan, 2024). Second, the reforms prioritize global integration by aligning China’s IP regime with international standards, such as the Hague Agreement and TRIPS, to attract FDI. Tesla’s Shanghai Gigafactory exemplifies this shift, operating as a wholly foreign-owned enterprise with full IP control over its battery and autonomous driving technologies, a departure from earlier joint venture requirements (Bailey, 2020).

Both the National Plan and the Guidelines seek to provide a safer environment for foreign investors by bolstering IP protection and refining law enforcement procedures. Such a guarantee reduces the danger of intellectual property theft and infringement, making it essential for businesses thinking about joining or growing in the Chinese market. While the former presented concrete, achievable measures in the short term, the latter offered a comprehensive framework for the sustainable development of IP protection in China. By strengthening legislative safeguards, promoting technology transfer, and fostering

market trust, the two documents work together to create an environment that is favorable for FDI.

Meanwhile, both documents envisioned broader goals that are fundamentally connected to the “Measures on the Transfer of Intellectual Property Rights to Foreign Parties (Pilot)”. The 2018 Measures on the Transfer of Intellectual Property Rights to Foreign Parties (Pilot) and their connection to broader Chinese policy frameworks like the Made in China 2025 initiative and the National Medium- and Long-Term Program for Science and Technology Development (2006–2020) are critical to understanding China’s dual strategy of safeguarding national security while advancing indigenous innovation.

5. Navigating New Regulations: The Pilot Measures on IP Transfers to Foreign Entities

Published on March 29, 2018, the “Measures on the Transfer of Intellectual Property Rights to Foreign Parties (Pilot)” (Measures, hereafter) tightened scrutiny over the transfer of IPR to foreign parties on grounds of public interest or national security (State Council General Office, 2018). As national defence and national security are managed differently, technologies linked to the former are not regulated under the Measures. Security assessments are required for certain forms of technology transfers, which tighten requirements for Chinese IP to be transferred over to foreign firms. For instance, if a Chinese tech company wants to license its AI algorithm or share source code with a foreign partner, it must first demonstrate to regulators that the transfer does not endanger national security, economic interests, or public safety.

The Measures mandated security assessments before exporting novel plant varieties, computer software copyrights, integrated circuit layout designs, and patents. This is in line with China’s current Catalog of Technologies Prohibited and Restricted from Export, which prohibits the export of technologies that the country deems

essential to economic growth or national security. Since foreign acquisitions of Chinese businesses are regarded as a type of intellectual property transfer, they are also regulated by the Measures. Here, “foreign acquisitions” cover both foreign parties’ acquisition of Chinese-foreign joint enterprises and their IP rights (UNCTAD, 2024). Given how much the EV industry depends on cutting-edge technologies, the Measures will likely hinder foreign tech development. Manufacturers will have to deal with the extra review procedure when entering into joint ventures or agreements for technology transfer with Chinese partners. To comply with the Measures, enterprises may need to do proactive IP due diligence and thoroughly evaluate IP rights involved in their China activities. To uncover any hidden problems or hazards, they need to go over existing technology transfer and joint venture agreements.

In China, the EV industry serves as a hub for both global investment and indigenous innovation. The Measures ensure that any transfer of EV-related technologies from Chinese enterprises to foreign corporations is thoroughly considered. This is especially important as China wants to be a leader in EV manufacturing and technology (UNCTAD, 2018). The Measures ensure that technology transfer supports China’s goals of increasing its indigenous innovation capacity, allowing international enterprises to contribute to the expanding Chinese EV industry while safeguarding domestic interests through security evaluations.

The law enforcement capabilities can create risks for foreign companies transferring technology to China. It is therefore crucial for companies to conduct thorough due diligence, understand the local legal framework, and seek professional advice when engaging in technology transfer with Chinese partners. Additionally, China’s policies on technology transfer are also influenced by other factors

like: national security concerns, industrial development goals, FDI regulations. Understanding these broader aspects is essential for a complete picture of the technology transfer scenery in China. Although the Measures are mainly concerned with IP export, they also have an indirect impact on imports since they create a more restrictive environment for technological transactions. These regulations may have an impact on the choices foreign businesses make about how to invest and operate in China.

6. Improving Enforcement Mechanisms

Despite stated policy advances, certain lines of critique persist: enforcement remains inconsistent, particularly in rural regions where local authorities often prioritize economic growth over IP compliance. The U.S.-China Business Council reports lingering challenges in trade secret protection, with 34% of member firms experiencing IP infringement in 2024, underscoring the gap between legislative progress and on-the-ground implementation (China National Intellectual Property Administration, 2023). This enforcement asymmetry underscores the delicate balance manufacturers must strike as China’s EV industry evolves into a dual engine of FDI attraction and indigenous disruption. While improved IP laws and specialized courts in urban centers like Shanghai and Shenzhen provide clearer recourse for multinationals, the rural-urban enforcement divide compels firms to adopt hybrid strategies sharing non-core technologies to access markets while ringfencing proprietary systems through contractual safeguards and blockchain-based IP tracking.

To handle complex cases, especially in technology sectors like patents and trade secrets, China established its first specialized IP courts in Beijing, Shanghai, and Guangzhou in 2014 (Hogan Lovells, 2014; Jiang, 2024). By 2019, the Supreme People’s Court established a national-level Intellectual Property Court to decide appeals of highly technical cases nationwide, establishing a “leapfrog appeal” system (World Intellectual

Property Organization, 2019). By 2022, 21 specialized IP adjudication organs were operating in cities such as Chengdu, Nanjing, and Wuhan (Managing IP, 2022). These courts prioritize cross-regional remote litigation platforms and employ technical investigators to expedite the process.

These changes are in line with China's dual goal of encouraging domestic innovation and drawing in state-of-the-art automotive FDI. With 78% of foreign-litigated cases ending favorably in 2023, German automakers such as Volkswagen and BMW have taken use of the specialist courts to defend EV-related patents (Lin & Liu, 2025; CIELA Insights, 2024). For example, Volkswagen's 2025 patent invalidation challenge against Denso Corporation in China underscores the strategic reliance on these courts to resolve high-stakes automotive IP disputes (Ma, 2025). This case highlights foreign firms' growing reliance on China's specialized IP tribunals to resolve high-stakes disputes, signaling confidence in its legal system despite historical skepticism. By contesting Denso's patents, Volkswagen aims to secure supplier flexibility while testing China's enforcement balance between domestic innovation and foreign IP rights.

However, a persistent worry for the stability of FDI is that the system's efficacy depends on persistent enforcement against counterfeiting in China's extensive car parts supply chain. China's IP framework exemplifies a tension between progressive central reforms and uneven local implementation, creating a dual system where foreign firms navigate both opportunities and risks. Centralized measures such as specialized IP courts in Beijing, Shanghai, and Guangzhou, these courts employ technical investigators, remote litigation platforms, and streamlined procedures to resolve complex cases, particularly in sectors like EVs. For instance, the Supreme People's Court (SPC, 2024) reported a 117% year-on-year increase in punitive damages applications in 2023, with total awards exceeding ¥1.1

billion (\$150 million), signaling heightened deterrence against infringement. Foreign firms, including German automakers like Volkswagen, have increasingly leveraged these tribunals to defend patents, as seen in high-profile cases involving EV powertrain technologies.

Yet, provincial authorities often prioritize short-term economic growth over IP compliance, leading to fragmented enforcement. For instance, while German automakers like BMW successfully defended EV battery patents in central courts, rural supply chains in Anhui and Jiangsu remain hubs for counterfeit auto parts, undermining foreign firms' competitive edge (U.S.-China Business Council, 2023). To stabilize FDI, China must standardize enforcement through mechanisms like cross-provincial IP task forces, reduce coercive localization mandates, conditioning EV subsidies on data-sharing with domestic partners, and enhance transparency in BRI tech collaborations by adopting reciprocal IP terms. By addressing these areas, China can reassure German automakers that their IP and market access are secure, stabilizing FDI amid escalating EU-China trade tensions over EV tariffs.

Conclusion

China's evolving landscape of IP law enforcement, technology transfer regulations, and FDI policies presents a complex challenge to foreign automakers. The Chinese government's recent restrictions on EV technology transfers in overseas investments underscore its strategic focus on preserving critical technologies within its borders. This approach, coupled with China's rapid advancements in EV technology and its dominant market position, has created significant hurdles for foreign companies seeking to compete in the Chinese market. The situation necessitates a delicate balance for foreign investors, who must navigate China's regulatory framework while protecting their intellectual property and maintaining their competitive edge in the world's largest and most dynamic EV market.

China's evolving IP regime, anchored by the 14th Five-Year Plan National IP Protection Plan and the 2021–2035 Intellectual Property Strategy Guideline, has reshaped FDI strategies, innovation ecosystems, and technology transfer dynamics in its automotive sector. Reforms such as specialized IP courts, streamlined dispute resolution, and punitive damages have mitigated historical risks of forced technology transfers, particularly for German automakers. Concurrently, the shift from direct subsidies to normative policies including EV charging infrastructure mandates and standardized testing protocols has fostered a structured yet competitive market, enabling domestic leaders to vie with global firms through advanced IP portfolios. This dual framework balances regulatory predictability with strategic market access, reflecting China's broader alignment with global innovation standards while retaining domestic competitive advantages.

Foreign automakers in China face persistent challenges, including uneven local IP enforcement and geopolitical tensions over technology exports, despite the National Plan for IP Rights (2021–2025) aiming to enhance transparency. China's dual role as both a strategic protector of domestic EV innovations evident in export controls and a global collaborator compels firms to balance cooperation with vigilance. To thrive, international companies must leverage China's IP reforms for localized production while safeguarding core technologies through strategic alliances and selective patenting. This regulatory landscape underscores the critical balance between IP-driven innovation and fair trade, shaping high-tech FDI as China cements its dominance as the world's leading EV exporter.

Stronger judicial and administrative safeguards, the imposition of punitive fines for infringement, and expedited dispute resolution procedures are some recent

developments in China's intellectual property framework. In order to boost investor confidence and encourage innovation, the National Plan for Intellectual Property Rights (2021–2025) seeks to further improve the caliber of IP protection, encourage increased agency cooperation, and increase the effectiveness of enforcement. Better legal remedies for copyright holders and a more stable business climate for international investors are the results of these initiatives. Despite these advances, significant challenges remain in balancing technology transfer requirements with the protection of foreign investors' interests. To further improve the environment for FDI and technology transfer, China could consider the following steps:

1. Increase transparency and predictability in the application of technology transfer regulations, ensuring that foreign investors clearly understand compliance requirements and the scope of protected technologies.
2. Strengthen independent judicial oversight to address disputes involving forced technology transfer or IP infringement, providing foreign companies with greater legal recourse.
3. Encourage voluntary, market-driven technology partnerships rather than mandatory transfer arrangements, fostering mutual benefit and innovation.

By adopting these measures, China can further solidify its reputation as a global innovation leader while attracting high-quality foreign investment and promoting sustainable, equitable technology exchange.

References

- Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights. (1994). Marrakesh
- Agreement Establishing the World Trade Organization, Annex 1C, 1869 U.N.T.S. 299.
https://www.wto.org/english/docs_e/legal_e/27-trips_01_e.htm

- Argus Media. (2025, January 15). *China's EV exports surge to 40.9% global market share in 2024*.
https://www.argusmedia.com/en/news-and-insights/latest-market-news/2650730-china-expands-ev-charging-infrastructure-in-2024?utm_source
- Azure Group China. (2024, October 14). *The difference between a WFOE and a joint venture (JV)*.
<https://www.azuregroupchina.com/the-difference-between-a-wfoe-and-a-joint-venture-jv/>
- Bailey, C., Clark, D., Jiang L., Tian, A. (2020). *Software Copyright Litigation in China: How have foreign companies fared in Chinese courts?* CIELA.
<https://rouse.com/media/my0hg1wu/ciela-software-copyright-litigation-in-china-how-have-foreign-companies-fared-in-chinese-courts.pdf>
- BMW Group. (2024, March 21). *BMW Group continues to increase investment in future mobility to accelerate innovation in China*.
<http://www.bmw-brilliance.cn/cn/en/news/news/2024-3-21-1.html>
- Borensztein, E., De Gregorio, J., & Lee, J.-W. (1998). How does foreign direct investment affect economic growth? *Journal of International Economics*, 45(1), 115–135. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996\(97\)00033-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996(97)00033-0)
- Buckley, P. J., Clegg, J., & Wang, C. (2007). Is the relationship between inward FDI and spillover effects linear? An empirical examination of the case of China. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 38(3), 447–459.
https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230248328_9
- Carbon Credits. (2024, July 6). *EV wars and breakthroughs: BYD to overtake Tesla, CATL's new lithium battery with 1.5m km range*.
<https://carboncredits.com/battery-wars-byd-to-beat-tesla-in-2024-ev-sales-catl-new-lithium-battery>
- Central Committee of the Communist Party of China & State Council of the People's Republic of China. (2021). *Guidelines for building a powerful country with intellectual property rights (2021–2035)*
<http://www.zyip.com/en/show-982.html>
- Cheng, E. (2021, December 27). *China to remove foreign investment limit for passenger car manufacturing*. CNBC
<https://www.cnbc.com/2021/12/27/china-to-remove-foreign-investment-limit-passenger-car-manufacturing.html>
- Carbon Credits. (2024, July 6). *EV wars and breakthroughs: BYD to overtake Tesla, CATL's new lithium battery with 1.5m km range*.
<https://carboncredits.com/battery-wars-byd-to-beat-tesla-in-2024-ev-sales-catl-new-lithium-battery>
- Central Committee of the Communist Party of China & State Council of the People's Republic of China. (2021). *Guidelines for building a powerful country with intellectual property rights (2021–2035)*
<http://www.zyip.com/en/show-982.html>
- Cheng, E. (2021, December 27). *China to remove foreign investment limit for passenger car manufacturing*. CNBC
<https://www.cnbc.com/2021/12/27/china-to-remove-foreign-investment-limit-passenger-car-manufacturing.html>
- China Justice Observer. (2021, November 8). *China to build a powerful country with intellectual property rights*.
<https://www.chinajusticeobserver.com/a/china-to-build-a-powerful-country-with-intellectual-property-rights>
- China National Intellectual Property Administration. (2021, November 30). Policy briefing of the State Council releases information about the National Plan for Protection and Application of Intellectual Property Rights During the 14th Five-Year Plan Period
https://english.cnipa.gov.cn/art/2021/11/30/art_2173_171773.html
- CIELA Insights. (2024). *Exploring the Chinese litigation landscape: Is it fair for foreign companies?* [Fact sheet]. Rouse.
<https://rouse.com/media/ubqp2tut/ciela-insights-1-invention-patent-litigation.pdf>
- Cyberspace Administration of China. (2021). *Regulation on Management of Automobile Data Security*.
- Ezell, S. (2024, July 29). *How innovative is China in the electric vehicle and battery*

- and industries? Information Technology Innovation Foundation.
<https://itif.org/publications/2024/07/29/how-innovative-is-china-in-the-electric-vehicle-and-battery-industries/>
- Fuchs, M., Guenther, J., & Schmid, S. (2021). Training activities in subsidiaries of foreign multinational companies: Local embeddedness in Germany? *International Journal of Training and Development*, 25, 15.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ijtd.12244>
- Fuels & Lubes. (2024, August 21). *Volkswagen China centralises EV development in Hefei, Anhui*.
<https://www.fuelsandlubes.com/volkswagen-china-centralises-ev-development-in-hefei-anhui/>
- German Chamber of Commerce in China. (2022). *Rocky Roads Ahead: Business Confidence Survey 2022/23*.
<https://api.china-bw.net/uploads/cnbw-web/originals/e2d371d7-2888-4410-a8c7-5e46722d6197.pdf>
- Groenewegen-Lau, J., & Gunter, J. (2025, June 24). *The trade-offs of innovating in China in times of global technology rivalry* [Report]. Mercator Institute for China Studies.
<https://merics.org/en/report/trade-offs-innovating-china-times-global-technology-rivalry>
- Grünecker. (2024, October 9). *Grünecker patent study in the Handelsblatt: China dominates in electric car charging technology*.
<https://gruenecker.de/en/insights/gruenecker-patent-study-in-the-handelsblatt-china-dominates-in-electric-car-charging-technology/>
- Hogan Lovells. (2014). *Specialized IP courts in Beijing, Shanghai and Guangzhou: Paving the way to more efficient IP litigation?* [Briefing note].
https://www.hoganlovells.com/-/media/hoganlovells/pdf/publication/10222014specialised-ip-courts-in-beijing-shanghai-guangzhouships49649v3_pdf.pdf
- Huld, A. (2023, September 5). *Qualifying for China's pre-tax super deduction for R&D expenses – A case study review*. China Briefing.
<https://www.china-briefing.com/news/qualifying-for-chinas-pre-tax-super-deduction-for-rd-expenses-a-case-study-review/>
- Interesse, G. (2024, August 13). *China's IP protection development: A comprehensive overview*. China Briefing.
<https://www.china-briefing.com/news/chinas-ip-protection-development-a-comprehensive-overview/>
- Jakóbowski, J. & Oertel, J. (2025). *Electric shock: The Chinese threat to Europe's industrial heartland* [Policy brief]. European Council on Foreign Relations.
<https://ecfr.eu/publication/electric-shock-the-chinese-threat-to-europes-industrial-heartland/>
- Jiang, J. (2019, August). *China specialized IP courts: Substance or theater? Part I*. Licensing Executives Society International.
<https://lesi.org/article-of-the-month/china-specialized-ip-courtssubstance-or-theaterpart-i/>
- Koty, A. C. (2018, April 18). *China's auto industry: Foreign ownership limits scrapped*. China Briefing.
<https://www.china-briefing.com/news/chinas-auto-industry-foreign-ownership-limits-scrapped>
- Lambert, F. (2025, April 21). *CATL unveils EV battery charges as fast as pumping gas*. Electrek.
<https://electrek.co/2025/04/21/catl-unveils-ev-battery-charges-as-fast-as-pumping-gas/>
- Laurucci, A. (2023). *The German automotive FDI in China: EVs, innovation and competitiveness*. European Institute for Asian Studies.
<https://eias.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/EIAS-Policy-Brief-No-06.2023-German-Automotive-FDI-in-China-1.pdf>
- Lee, S., Lee, K., & Ryu, J. (2003). Technology transfer of foreign direct investment in China. *Geography*, 88, 289–299.
<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:127095125>
- Liao, S.. (2019, July 20). Tencent, BMW team up on autonomous driving data center in China. *Yicai Global*.

- <https://www.yicaiglobal.com/news/tenant-bmw-team-up-on-autonomous-driving-data-center-in-china>
- Lin, Z. & Liu, J. (2025, January 23). *China intellectual property enforcement trends positive for foreign entities*. Spruson. <https://www.spruson.com/china-intellectual-property-enforcement-trends-positive-for-foreign-entities/>
- Lung Tin Intellectual Property Agent Ltd. (2021, September 28). China issues outline for building an intellectual property rights powerhouse (2021–2035). <https://www.lungtin.com/en/news/industry-news/20210928/2867.html>
- Ma, M. (2025, April 10). Volkswagen challenges Denso's patents in China [Substack newsletter]. *Michael's Substack*. <https://michael7924.substack.com/p/volkswagen-challenges-densos-patents>
- Managing IP. (2016, October 31). *China's evolving specialist courts*. <https://www.managingip.com/article/2a5c0ozcuhm91lmkw68e9/chinas-evolving-specialist-courts>
- Minbaeva, D., Pedersen, T., Björkman, I., Fey, C. F., & Park, H. J. (2003). MNC knowledge transfer, subsidiary absorptive capacity, and HRM. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 34(6), 586–599. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.jibs.8400056>
- Ministry of Commerce of the People's Republic of China. (2025). Regulations on the Export Control of Lithium Iron Phosphate Preparation and Lithium Extraction Technologies.
- National Development and Reform Commission & Ministry of Commerce. (2024). *Special administrative measures (Negative List) for foreign investment access (2024 Edition)*. <https://www.ndrc.gov.cn/xxgk/zcfb/fzggwl/202409/P020240907514493057643.pdf>
- Parker, D., Wei, Y., Liu, X., & Vaidya, K. (1999). The regional distribution of foreign direct investment in China. *Regional Studies*, 33(9), 857–867. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343409950075498>
- PwC China. (2024). *Overview of PRC taxation system*. <https://www.pwccn.com/en/services/tax/accounting-and-payroll/overview-of-prc-taxation-system.html>
- Raslan, R. A. A. (2024). Climbing up the Ladder: Technology Transfer-Related Policies in China's Foreign Investment Law and the Influence of International Agreements, *Utrecht Law Review*, 20(1), 111–119. <https://doi.org/10.36633/ulr.922>
- Reuters. (2025, January 2). *China proposes further export curbs on battery, critical minerals tech*. <https://www.reuters.com/technology/china-proposes-further-export-curbs-battery-critical-minerals-tech-2025-01-02/>
- Skadden, Arps, Slate, Meagher & Flom LLP. (2021). *China's new data security and personal information protection laws: What they mean for multinational companies*. [memorandum] https://www.skadden.com/-/media/files/publications/2021/11/chinas_new_data_security_and_personal_information_protection_laws_what_they_mean.pdf
- State Council General Office (2018). *Measures on the transfer of intellectual property rights to foreign parties (Pilot)*. https://www.gov.cn/zhengce/content/2018-03/29/content_5278276.htm
- State Council Information Office. (2021). *Outline and the plan for intellectual property rights protection and application for 2021-2025*. State Council Information Office. https://english.cnipa.gov.cn/art/2021/11/30/art_1340_171772.html
- State Council Information Office. (2024, July 10). *China's new energy vehicle industry development report*. <http://english.scio.gov.cn>
- State Council of the People's Republic of China. (1995). *Provisional regulations on guiding the direction of foreign investment [Interim Provisions]*. <https://www.gov.cn/gongbao/shuju/1995/gwyb199517.pdf>
- State Council of the People's Republic of China. (2021). *The outline of the 14th five-year plan for economic and social development and long range objectives through the year 2035 of the People's Republic of China*.

- <https://en.ndrc.gov.cn/policies/202203/P020220315511326748336.pdf>
- Supreme People's Court Intellectual Property Tribunal. (2024). Intellectual property protection by Chinese courts in 2024. People's Court Press.
<https://ipc.court.gov.cn/zh-cn/news/view-4233.html>
- Symonds, D. (2019, July 23). *Tencent to create BMW's autonomous driving platform in China*. Autonomous Vehicle International.
<https://www.autonomousvehicleinternational.com/news/software/tencent-to-create-bmws-autonomous-driving-platform-in-china.html>
- Tian, J., Wang, P., & Zhu, D. (2024). Overview of Chinese new energy vehicle industry and policy development. *Green Energy and Resources*, 2(2), 100075.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gear.2024.100075>
- Wei, K., Yao, S., & Liu, A. (2007). *Foreign direct investment and regional inequality in China* (GEP Research Paper No. 2007/32). University of Nottingham.
<https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/gep/documents/papers/2007/07-32.pdf>
- UN Trade and Development. (2024, April 8). *China removes all access restrictions to manufacturing sector from the Negative List*.
<https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/investment-policy-monitor/measures/4786/china-removes-all-access-restrictions-to-manufacturing-sector-from-the-negative-list-for-foreign-investment>
- U.S.-China Business Council. (2023). 2023 China business environment survey report.
<https://www.uschina.org/articles/2023-member-survey-2/>
- World Intellectual Property Organization. (2019). *Judicial administration structure for IP disputes: China*.
<https://www.wipo.int/en/web/wipolex/judicial-administration-structure/cn>

Carolina Fabara

abogadacfabara@gmail.com

Carolina Fabara is an Ecuadorian lawyer, PhD in International Law, and specialist in business and economic law. She is international and national speaker, business consultant, and founder of the NGO Umalliq, with research focusing on business law, international investment, gender equality, and corporate internationalization.

Ecocide as a Threat to Global Security: Exploring the Recognition of Ecocide as an International Crime and its Implications

Agata Bidas

Environmental Crime, Rome Statute

Abstract

As environmental degradation continues to worsen, the idea of ecocide is gaining attention as a major global security concern. This paper argues that ecocide, defined as severe, widespread, or long-term damage to the environment, presents a significant threat to global stability and should be recognized as an international crime. The paper explores the history of discussions around ecocide, tracing its connections to the concept of genocide and earlier attempts to criminalize environmental destruction in international law. It then examines current efforts to incorporate ecocide into international law, focusing on the proposal to add it as a fifth crime to the Rome Statute. While acknowledging the potential benefits of this step, the paper also critically evaluates the challenges involved, including the International Criminal Court's limited membership and the difficulties in agreeing on a universal definition. By looking at examples such as the Vietnam War, the draining of the Mesopotamian Marshes, and the destruction of the Nova Kakhovka dam, this analysis shows how ecocide contributes to humanitarian crises, resource scarcity, and regional instability. The paper concludes that recognizing ecocide as an international crime, whether through amending the Rome Statute or establishing a specialized environmental court, is crucial for deterring widespread environmental destruction and promoting global environmental justice, though achieving this requires significant international cooperation, especially from major global powers.

Keywords: Ecocide, International Criminal Court (ICC), International Law, Global Security,

Introduction

In an era of escalating environmental degradation and geopolitical instability, the concept of "ecocide" is gaining increased interest as a pressing global issue requiring urgent regulation and possible recognition as an international crime. Ecocide, defined by the Independent Expert Panel as "*unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts,*" (Stop Ecocide International, 2021, Article 8 ter) has been discussed primarily in terms of its environmental impact. However, its broader implications for global security and geopolitics must be further explored.

This paper argues that ecocide poses a significant threat to global security and should therefore be defined and recognized in international law. This paper will analyze various ways to achieve this and the potential implications for international security. One possibility that is believed to have gained the most support is recognizing ecocide as an international crime by adding it to the list of crimes that can be prosecuted by the International Criminal Court (ICC). However, the possible benefits and drawbacks of this strategy will also be examined, considering the difficulties posed by the fact that two of the world's most powerful nations—China and the United States—are neither parties to the Rome Statute nor recognize the International Criminal Court. Even though adding ecocide to the Rome Statute might be a big step, more international cooperation and commitment are needed for it to be effective.

1. History of the Term "Ecocide"

The term "ecocide" was first introduced in the

early 1970s by Yale botanist Arthur Galston, who described the environmental destruction caused by the US military's use of herbicidal chemicals during the Vietnam War (Bertram, 2024). As part of Operation Hades, between 1961 and 1971, the US Army sprayed over 73 million liters of chemical agents on Vietnamese territory in an attempt to eliminate the vegetation that provided cover for Viet Cong forces in "enemy territory." The military also deliberately targeted crops with a range of defoliants. The poisonous spray, known as Agent Orange, contained the hazardous substance dioxin in approximately 45 million liters, leading to a slow-moving disaster in Vietnam with serious long-term effects on the country's ecology, economy, and health (von Meding, 2017).

However, discussions about environmental crimes began long before the Vietnam War. Etymologically, the term ecocide is linked to genocide, which was introduced in the 1930s by Raphael Lemkin, a Polish Jewish lawyer, and included in the 1948 UN Genocide Convention (hereby referred to as "the Convention") (Nowak, 2023). Lemkin's concept of genocide included two forms: physical genocide, committed by killing individuals, and cultural genocide, committed by undermining the way of life of a particular group (Nowak, 2023). His definition identified the destruction of a people by factors not directly involved in killing (Higgins et al., 2012). According to Lemkin, acts of genocide return humanity to the dark ages, shock the conscience of humanity and raise serious concerns about the future of civilization (Nowak, 2023).

Therefore, the concept of ecocide is based on the same principle as genocide. It can result in cultural damage and destruction. Like genocide, ecocide can be direct or indirect; it can involve the destruction of a territory or the undermining of a way of life—both environmental and cultural (Higgins et al., 2012). Lemkin saw the destruction of culture

as an important form of group destruction. For him, culture is part of the collective memory, and the destruction of a particular group's culture leads directly to the destruction of that group. He viewed national cultures as important elements of world culture. Thus, the destruction of a group is the destruction of part of the culture of humanity (Higgins et al., 2012). According to Lemkin, it is the shared culture of a social group that gives rise to the *genos* in acts of genocide. Lemkin claimed that "cultural genocide is the most important part of the Convention," although cultural genocide was ultimately not included in the legal definition of genocide (Higgins et al., 2012, p. 8).

According to Galligan (2021), cultural genocide described by Lemkin, is key to the ecocide-genocide connection. Lemkin emphasized that "culture integrates human societies" and is "necessary for realizing material needs," (Galligan, 2021, p. 1007) which means that destroying a group's culture, including its connection to the environment, can be genocidal. Therefore, ecocide can be seen as a form of cultural destruction.

During reviews of the Convention's effectiveness, the first attempts were made to criminalize environmental destruction under international law (Higgins et al., 2012). In this context, Richard A. Falk prepared the draft of the International Convention on the Crime of Ecocide, which was included in a study by the UN Sub-Commission on Prevention of Discrimination and Protection of Minorities. He described the US war in Indochina as the first modern instance where the environment was deliberately targeted for systematic destruction in war (Falk, 1973).

Moreover, Falk (1973) linked ecocide and genocide, stating that "Just as counterinsurgency warfare tends toward genocide with respect to the people, so it tends toward ecocide with respect to the environment" (Falk, 1973, p. 80). He also notices the need to acknowledge that "man has intentionally and unintentionally inflicted irreparable damage to the environment

in times of war and peace" and that "we are living in a period of increasing danger of ecological collapse" (Higgins et al., 2012, p. 9). Moreover, he emphasized that most victims of environmental crime are Global South nations, which reinforces global inequalities and shows that environmental protection should be a human rights issue (Falk, 1973).

Falk's proposal of the Ecocide Convention mainly addresses ecocide as a deliberate war crime and does not specify provisions during peacetime. By this time, a majority of UN Member States supported ecocide as a crime during peacetime. However, the draft International Convention on the Crime of Ecocide was shelved for unknown reasons (Higgins et al., 2012).

Between 1984 and 1996, the International Law Commission (ILC) considered including environmental damage and ecocide in the list of Crimes Against Peace. However, in 1996, at a meeting of the ILC, Chairman Ahmed Mahiou decided to remove ecocide as a separate provision. The final article adopted by the ILC and amended by the Drafting Committee refers to intentionally causing "widespread, long-term, and severe damage to the natural environment" within a war context (Higgins et al., 2012, p. 3). This was the last reference to a crime against the environment that made it into the Rome Statute (Higgins et al., 2012). Speculations exist about why the provision criminalizing ecocide was not included. For example, Higgins quotes Christian Tomuschat, a long-term ILC member, who suggested that:

[One] cannot escape the impression that nuclear arms played a decisive role in the minds of many of those who opted for the final text which now has been emasculated to such an extent that its conditions of applicability will almost never be met even after humankind would have gone through disasters of the most atrocious kind as a consequence of conscious action by

persons who were completely aware of the fatal consequences their decisions would entail. (Higgins et al., 2012, p. 3)

2. Current Approaches to Integrating Ecocide into International Law

After the Rome Statute failed to include it as a stand-alone provision, ecocide has been largely ignored in policy discussions for the past few decades. However, in recent years, it has regained attention due to the intensifying climate crisis, the rise of environmental justice movements, and increasing recognition of environmental destruction as a threat to peace and human rights (van den Heede, 2023). Interest significantly increased in 2010, when Scottish lawyer Polly Higgins proposed that ecocide be considered the "fifth international crime against peace," and a transnational civil society campaign to enshrine ecocide in national and international law was initiated by Higgins' proposal (Bertram, 2024, para. 4). Higgins defined ecocide as "the extensive damage to, destruction of or loss of ecosystem(s) of a given territory, whether by human agency or by other causes to such an extent that peaceful enjoyment by the inhabitants of that territory has been severely diminished" (van den Heede, 2023, p. 435).

In 2021, the Independent Expert Panel for the Legal Definition of Ecocide (IEP), established by the Stop Ecocide International Foundation, developed a new definition of ecocide with the objective of establishing a definition that could serve as the basis for an amendment to the Rome Statute, that would add ecocide to the list of the international crimes next to genocide, war crimes, crimes against humanity and crimes of aggression (van den Heede, 2023). The Panel defined ecocide as "unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge of likely severe, widespread, or long-term environmental damage" (*Stop Ecocide International, 2021, Article 8 ter*).

While the definition was in general positively received, as it emphasizes the need for

international legal frameworks to address the serious environmental damage that can happen in times of both peace and war, as well as the purpose behind environmental damage, connecting it to intentional acts that may have far-reaching and protracted effects, it also sparked some criticism in the literature (Heller, 2021). For example, Heller notices that the concept of genocide, on which ecocide is based, is legally defined as acts committed with the intent to destroy, in whole or in part, a national, ethnical, racial or religious group. This specific targeting is a core element of genocide. Ecocide, on the other hand, focuses on the destruction of the environment, which may not always be aimed at harming a particular group. Therefore, the broad nature of environmental damage makes it difficult to classify under the narrowly defined scope of ecocide, leading to challenges in legal interpretation and enforcement. In addition, proving the specific intent behind ecocide can be difficult, as environmental damage, according to the IEP definition, may result from negligence or reckless acts rather than a deliberate intent to destroy a group, as it is a case for genocide (Heller, 2021).

Therefore, Heller proposes an alternative approach to defining ecocide that does not rely on the framework of genocide. Heller suggests focusing on the environmental damage itself and argues for a clear, stand-alone legal definition that treats serious environmental damage as an international crime. This approach aims to avoid the complications arising from the link between genocide and ecocide and to ensure that ecocide is recognized and prosecuted on its own merits, reflecting the urgent need to protect the environment from widespread and intentional damage (Heller, 2021).

2.1 Proposal to Include Ecocide in the Rome Statute

In February 2024, the Office of the Prosecutor launched a public consultation on a new policy

initiative to advance accountability for environmental crimes under the Rome Statute, and the prosecutor Khan stated: "Damage to the environment poses an existential threat to all life on the planet" (The Office of the Prosecutor, 2024).

The discussion on including the ecocide as the fifth crime intensified when Vanuatu, Fiji, and Samoa proposed amendment to the Rome Statute to include a Crime of Ecocide in September 2024, defining ecocide as "unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts," using the Independent Expert Panel definition from 2021 (Eco Jurisprudence Monitor, 2024). The main reason to come up with this proposal was that "a crime to protect the environment in peacetime as well as conflict is of fundamental importance, not only to cover the inadequacies of existing law, but also to promote a shift in mindset in both contexts to reflect an understanding of the severity of the danger posed by grave environmental harms" (Permanent Mission of the Republic of Vanuatu to the UN, 2024).

Vanuatu's Special Envoy on Climate Change and the Environment, Ralph Regenvanu, emphasized during the Session of the Assembly of States Parties to the Rome Statute in December 2024 that to protect the environment and human rights, enforceable standards and international cooperation are needed. He stressed that "to adequately protect the environment, upon which all human rights ultimately depend, enforceable standards are required, as well as meaningful international cooperation through domestic, regional and international spheres. The Rome Statute, as well as the fora provided by the International Criminal Court more generally, offer legitimate tools for ensuring effective collective action in this regard" (Regenvanu, 2024).

Vanuatu's initiative is a key example of growing support towards recognizing ecocide as a

crime. According to Root, including ecocide in the Rome Statute would provide a powerful legal tool to hold individuals and corporations accountable for severe environmental harm, particularly when they act with reckless disregard for the consequences. Once added to the Rome Statute, ecocide could be prosecuted in any ratifying jurisdiction where there's a connection to the case, expanding the scope of enforceability globally (Root, 2024).

However, this proposal might face numerous challenges. Amending the Rome Statute to incorporate ecocide necessitates a two-thirds majority vote among the Assembly of States Parties, which comprises 125 Member States (ICC, 2024). This high threshold means that gaining sufficient support is a difficult task, particularly given the varying national interests and priorities. Some countries, including major powers such as the United States, China, and India, are not parties to the Rome Statute, which further complicates efforts to achieve universal support for the amendment (Andrade, 2024). Therefore, Andrade (2024) claims that criminalizing ecocide at the international level presents challenges that could potentially weaken the system of international law. The non-universal membership of the International Criminal Court (ICC), with key countries like the U.S., China, and Russia not being signatories, means that even successful adoption of an ecocide amendment would lack global support. Furthermore, defining ecocide is a complex task, with disagreements over what constitutes mass environmental harm, leading to the risk of diluting the definition for broader acceptance. Therefore, according to Andrade (2024), this could fragment the international legal system, undermining its credibility and effectiveness in addressing environmental destruction.

3. National Regulations on Ecocide

This definition, proposed by the Independent Expert Panel, sparked discussions and in many

cases led to the introduction of ecocide legislation in various parliaments around the world, particularly in the EU, where an increasing number of states have included "ecocide" in their criminal codes. For example, in August 2021, France codified ecocide, followed by Belgium, which adopted a comprehensive ecocide law based on the IEP definition, marking a significant development in Western legal systems (Bertram, 2024). The criminalization of serious, widespread and long-term environmental damage is a notable legislative achievement of the Belgian ecocide law, which is set out in Article 94 of the new Criminal Code. The Belgian law imposes a higher mens rea threshold for *dolus indirectus*, requiring knowledge of severe, widespread and long-term damage, as opposed to the Independent Expert Panel's definition, which only requires knowledge of a substantial likelihood of damage. It is difficult to prosecute under this strict requirement. Furthermore, the law's applicability is limited to violations of binding international instruments or federal legislation, which may exclude many regional environmental protections and reduce its effectiveness (Bertram, 2024).

In addition to individual countries, the debate about criminalizing eco-violence is also taking place within the European Union, where the revised Environmental Crime Directive (ECD), approved by the EU Parliament and Council in November 2023, marks one of the latest developments. The ECD, which was passed by the Parliament in February 2024 and entered into force on 20 May 2024 (European Commission, 2024), makes several prohibited behaviors illegal and increases the severity of penalties for acts that result in "widespread and substantial damage that is either irreversible or long-lasting" (Bertram, 2024, para. 30). This directive lowers the mens rea threshold to facilitate prosecution by adopting a cumulative threshold of "serious, widespread and long-term damage" similar to Belgian law (Bertram, 2024, para. 30). It also includes a more lenient definition of unlawfulness and specifies serious negligence for certain conduct. The push for a new international

environmental crime will be aided by the requirement that EU Member States update their environmental criminal laws if the proposal is adopted (Bertram, 2024).

Adopted on 26 March 2024 and published on 30 April 2024, the EU became the first international body to successfully incorporate the idea of ecocide, rather than the term itself, into its new Directive on the Protection of the Environment through Criminal Law. The directive sets out minimum requirements and penalties for a range of environmental offenses. Although not classified as “ecocide,” certain offenses may be considered “qualified offenses” if they are intentional and cause extensive and long-lasting damage to ecosystems, habitats, or the quality of air, soil, or water. The preamble to the Directive suggests that this could include acts that are similar to ‘ecocide’ (Colin et al, 2024).

While, as described, many states are discussing the criminalization of ecocide in their penal codes, some have recognized ecocide for decades, but enforcement in these countries has been weak (Bertram, 2024). Vietnam, for example, was the first country to incorporate the crime of ecocide into its domestic law, having been the first to experience ecocide during the Vietnam War. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, many newly formed states included ecocide as a named crime against peace in their criminal codes, including Armenia, Belarus, the Republic of Moldova, Ukraine and Georgia (Higgins et al., 2012). It is important to stress that these states included ecocide in their criminal codes under the influence of the Draft Code of Crimes against the Peace and Security of Mankind, when ecocide was first proposed for international adoption and named as a crime against the peace and security of mankind, which was discussed in the previous chapters (Higgins et al., 2012). However, all these legislative efforts to codify ecocide show its importance in maintaining global peace and security.

Examining how the regulations look in China is also insightful because China is one of the major polluters and plays an important role in global environmental governance. Currently, the concept of “ecocide” is not recognized in law and has not been mentioned in any recent legislative proposals. However, China has environmental protection laws and environmental crimes. Traditional air and water pollution, illegal waste disposal and illegal poaching of endangered animals are just a few examples of these offenses (Colin et al, 2024). However, China is formally pursuing a “green” transformation, incorporating ecological initiatives into its political strategy in response to the severe ecological degradation the country faces, symbolized by widespread smog and natural disasters (Clement, 2021).

4. Ecocide and International Security: Global Examples and Implications

Ecocide has significant implications for international security. However, due to the lack of a universally agreed-upon definition, the term is used in literature not as a legal term but as a descriptor for extensive damage and destruction of ecosystems. Examining examples from different regions helps to understand how ecocide poses a threat to international security. The Vietnam War is a key example, as it sparked increased international discussion about ecocide. The US military's use of herbicidal warfare during the Vietnam War— specifically, Operation Ranch Hand—devastated the environment and had a significant impact on international security (Zierler, 2011). Herbicide use resulted in widespread ecological destruction, contaminated soil and water, long-term health issues, and community displacements, in addition to its goal of destroying crops and forests to deny the Viet Cong food.

Degradation of the environment affected local economies, increased social tensions, and threatened regional stability, which has an effect on international security (Zierler, 2011). The situation involving the Marsh Arabs in Iraq is another noteworthy instance that is regarded

as ecocide in the literature (Zierler, 2011). To punish the Marsh Arabs after the Gulf War, Saddam Hussein's regime purposefully drained the Mesopotamian Marshes, which resulted in thousands of people being uprooted and the destruction of a distinctive cultural legacy. This act of environmental warfare fueled insurgencies and sectarian tensions while also exacerbating regional instability and creating a humanitarian crisis. The world community mobilized efforts to restore the marshes and resettle displaced populations after recognizing this act as ecocide.

Another instance of ecocide is thought to have occurred in Iraq between 2014 and 2017, when Daesh destroyed natural resources and set fire to oil wells, among other environmental atrocities (Abad Castelos, 2023). These activities contributed to resource scarcity, community displacement, increased competition and conflict, and long-term ecological impacts, in addition to widespread environmental degradation and health risks. The depletion of natural resources significantly threatened regional and global security and damaged local economies and peace initiatives.

The examples described took place during a military conflict as acts of environmental warfare. However, there are also examples in the literature that suggest that ecocide can also occur in peacetime. For example, Mwangi (2007) describes the Lesotho Highlands Water Project as an ecocide. The project was initiated in the 1980s as a joint venture between Lesotho and South Africa, with serious environmental and social consequences. The author claims that it led to the loss of arable land, increased soil erosion and destroyed the habitats of numerous species, displacing thousands of households and causing economic hardship and social instability. The depletion of community resources and long-term environmental degradation exacerbated these problems. A very different example is

described by Walters (2022). The author argues that the bushfires that occurred in Australia in 2019 and 2020 can also be described as ecocide because the government's failure to act on expert advice and climate warnings can be seen as gross negligence, which contributed significantly to the scale of the disaster. The bushfires caused unprecedented damage, including loss of life, destruction of homes and massive environmental degradation (Walters, 2022). However, this example raises the question of whether these bushfires constitute ecocide and highlights the need for legal frameworks to hold political leaders accountable for environmental destruction.

Another case documented in academic works is the plight of Nauru, a tiny Pacific island nation that has experienced extreme environmental degradation as a result of extensive phosphate mining and climate change. The author refers to this phenomenon as ecocide (Kanngieser, 2020). Soil erosion, water pollution and loss of biodiversity caused by mining have created unfavorable living conditions. Displacement, inadequate access to food and water, and poor health are the results of these environmental stresses. Potential migration from Nauru due to climate change poses a threat to regional stability and illustrates the convergence of geopolitical strategy and natural disasters.

China has also been accused of ecocide. The country's construction of dams on the Mekong River has caused serious environmental damage, resulting in crop failures and humanitarian emergencies in downstream countries (Quang & Borton, 2020). The problem is exacerbated by the lack of legally binding frameworks for cooperation, leading to serious ecological damage and international disputes over water resources. In addition, the creation of artificial islands in the South China Sea poses a serious risk to marine ecosystems, possibly even leading to ecocide. Construction and dredging activities may result in centuries-old coral reefs being covered in sediment, jeopardizing ecosystems that are essential for the preservation of fish stocks in

the area (Langenheim, 2015). Environmental damage might exacerbate territorial disputes and geopolitical tensions.

The most recent ecocide discussed in the literature, occurring again during a war, is the destruction of the Nova Kakhovka dam in Ukraine in June 2023, when Russia was accused that its actions unleashed a catastrophic flood resulting in the immediate deaths of 50 people and the displacement of tens of thousands of civilians (Kostin, 2024). Vital resources, including drinking water reservoirs for over a million people and hundreds of thousands of hectares of farmland, were contaminated, and dangerous substances such as landmines, industrial chemicals and 150 tonnes of industrial lubricants polluted the Dnipro River, causing severe long-term ecological damage (Kostin, 2024). Moreover, the spill caused unprecedented damage to critical habitats, including those listed under the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands of International Importance, such as the UNESCO Black Sea Biosphere Reserve (Kostin, 2024).

Since Russia denied its involvement, several criminal proceedings were initiated. As of April 2025, investigations into the destruction of the Kakhovka Dam are being conducted by the International Criminal Court and the Ukrainian Prosecutor General's Office, focusing on potential charges of war crimes, environmental crimes, and crimes against humanity (Hansen, 2023). While Ukraine has identified a Russian general as a suspect (Formusek, 2024) the investigations face challenges due to the ongoing conflict and limited access to the dam site, which is under Russian control. The UN Commission of Inquiry on Ukraine is also investigating the incident and its impact on the civilian population (UNHCR, 2023). However, while accountability for perpetrators might be difficult to achieve, the ongoing investigations show the importance of strong regulations of environmental crime.

In conclusion, these cases—occurring in times of both peace and conflict—highlight the urgent need for an internationally recognized definition of ecocide to hold perpetrators accountable. The reported environmental damage draws attention to important security implications, such as humanitarian emergencies and displacement. Displacement caused by environmental degradation often leads to refugee crises, putting pressure on humanitarian aid and international relations. Another effect of environmental degradation is regional instability, as it can increase tensions, fuel conflicts and threaten stability. Lack of resources increases rivalry and hostilities over the few remaining resources and impacts livelihoods and health, causing social unrest and economic hardship. The combination of geopolitical maneuvering and environmental disasters shows us that there is a need to manage resources more fairly and work together internationally. Moreover, referring to Lemkin's view that genocide is inherently colonial (Galligan, 2021) ecocide is also very often a result of colonial and extractivist practices, which devastate already vulnerable communities, as the described examples have shown. Ecocide could be seen as a systematic outcome of colonial domination and not only isolated environmental harm (Galligan, 2021). Therefore, recognizing ecocide as an international crime could not only contribute to international security but also acknowledge its historical injustice to achieve a more sustainable global order.

5. Discussion

The examples described in the previous chapter underscore the urgent need for a clear, internationally recognized definition of ecocide that applies in both wartime and peacetime. As Kostin (2024) notes, without a universal standard, perpetrators of serious environmental damage can evade justice by exploiting inconsistencies between national legal systems, while the prospect of international prosecution can act as a powerful deterrent. Currently, some aspects of environmental crimes are included in the Rome Statute, but these provisions are

limited to wartime and do not specifically address ecocide. Article 8(2)(b)(iv) of the Rome Statute and Article 35(3) of the First Additional Protocol to the Geneva Conventions of 1977 were pioneering in establishing a framework for recognizing ecocide as a war crime, criminalizing intentional attacks that cause excessive environmental damage relative to the military advantage gained (Bray, 2023). However, this provision has never been used by the International Criminal Court.

However, the destruction of the Nova Kakhovka dam has reignited the debate on environmental crimes, suggesting that the ICC may need to prove its ability to deal with such crimes. This event has been described as “ecocide” by various parties, including the Ukrainian government. The ICC has launched an investigation into this event, which could potentially mark its first investigation into environmental crimes, representing a significant step forward for international criminal justice (Hansen, 2023).

At the same time, as noted above, there is a proposal for a definition of ecocide prepared by the IEP, which argues for its inclusion as a fifth, independent crime, even in peacetime, in the Rome Statute, to be prosecuted by the ICC. However, there is an ongoing debate about whether the ICC is the most appropriate institution to investigate ecocide. Hosa (2023) argues that criminalizing environmental damage at the international level is complex, noting that proving intent in environmental crimes is challenging. The ICC has also been criticized for its limited jurisdiction, as major global powers such as the US, China, and Russia are not parties to the Rome Statute, and its trials could potentially prolong conflicts. In addition, the ICC has been accused of bias, particularly against African nations, and of lacking the political will to prosecute crimes committed by Western powers (Faizi, 2021). Its limited geographical jurisdiction further limits its effectiveness. Of the 193 UN Member

States, only 125 have ratified the Rome Statute (ICC, 2024). Another important weakness of the ICC is that it lacks its own enforcement mechanism, which means that state parties have to be willing to cooperate with the Court.

Furthermore, since the ICC has typically handled a small number of cases, adding ecocide to its mandate could lessen its effectiveness due to capacity and financial limitations (Van Den Heede, 2023). ICC judges are primarily experts in criminal law, not environmental law. They will mainly rely on outside experts to interpret scientific evidence because they lack experience with environmental matters; this could complicate proceedings and result in misunderstandings or misinterpretations (Van Den Heede, 2023).

To address these issues, some authors suggest establishing alternative institutions such as an International Environmental Court, proposed by Murphy (2000). According to the author, this court, set up through a new international treaty, could have broad jurisdiction and apply international environmental law to various disputes, including transnational environmental damage, international environmental treaties, and ecocide (Murphy, 2000). Another proposal advocates establishing an International Court for the Environment attached to the International Court of Justice. This court would handle disputes involving state and non-state actors, issue emergency measures, mediate conflicts, and enforce global environmental treaties. Such an institution could address the pressing challenges of climate change and environmental degradation on a global scale, filling the gaps in existing international legal frameworks (Hockmann, 2009; Merz et al., 2014).

The last proposal worth mentioning is an Environmental Security Council, proposed by Faizi (2021). The author advocates the creation of an Environmental Security Council as an independent multilateral body under the UN to address the growing number of environmental crimes. According to Faizi, the ESC would have

judicial powers to prosecute ecocide and policy-making powers for global environmental management. It would consist of a judicial wing, modeled on the International Criminal Court, and a technical/policy wing, in which all willing UN Member States would participate on a “one country, one vote” basis. The ESC could draw its legal basis from existing instruments such as the Convention on Biological Diversity and would be created by a treaty negotiated in the UN General Assembly (Faizi, 2021).

In conclusion, recognizing ecocide as an international crime is necessary to tackle current global challenges, but it requires political will as well as a thorough legal framework. To deter environmental crimes and promote global environmental justice, ecocide must be successfully prosecuted, whether through the ICC or a specialized environmental court. But because ecocide is a global problem that affects many different regions and transcends national boundaries, achieving this goal will require the cooperation of all major world powers, including the US, China, and the EU. China aims to be a leader in climate action, as evidenced by its environmental policies, which are designed to influence international norms and practices (Hurri, 2023). According to Hurri (2023), China is aiming to shape international climate policies and strengthen its position in international climate governance as a part of its broader efforts to enhance its global influence. However, the model of 'ecological totalitarianism', defined by Clement as a state-led system where environmental policies become a tool of authoritarian governance, limiting civil liberties while achieving environmental goals, China presents, raises questions about how to balance personal freedoms with environmental sustainability (Clement, 2021).

It is also important to remember that China and the US do not recognize the ICC and are not parties to the Rome Statute, which limits

the Court's ability to prosecute cases of ecocide. China's preference for national sovereignty over international jurisdiction and the US's concerns about potential political bias and sovereignty all play a role in their non-participation. For a global solution to be effective, these views must be included. Although not sufficient on its own, the inclusion of ecocide as a fifth international crime in the Rome Statute would be a significant step. For ecocide to be effectively addressed and prevented, there must be widespread international cooperation and commitment.

Conclusion

The essay has discussed the history and the evolving discourse on ecocide, highlighting its growing relevance. Although the origins of ecocide lie in environmental destruction in wartime, the growing awareness within the international community about climate change issues indicates the need to broaden the concept and apply it also during peacetime, as a crime that is so relevant that it should be prosecuted regardless of the context of war. However, although the Rome Statute and the Geneva Conventions recognize some environmental damage during warfare, the concept of ecocide remains underrepresented in international law. Therefore, many proposals were discussed on how to give ecocide more relevance in international law.

The debate also shows the need for an internationally recognized definition of ecocide and its wider application outside times of war. In addition to strengthening the legal framework, the international criminalization of ecocide would act as a deterrent to serious environmental damage. To promote environmental justice and protection on a global scale, ecocide must be recognized under international law and incorporated into any new or existing legal framework.

The effective management of ecocide requires the creation of thorough legal frameworks as well as specialized institutions to deal with complex

environmental problems. To ensure a sustainable and equitable future for all, the international community must take decisive action to fill the gaps in current legal systems and support strong mechanisms for the prosecution of environmental crimes.

References

- Abad Castelos, M. (2023). Towards a holistic consideration of crimes against nature committed in times of armed conflict: A critical approach to the case of Iraq. *International Journal for Crime, Justice and Social Democracy*, 12(3), 77–92. <https://doi.org/10.5204/ijcjsd.2707>
- Andrade, R. C. (2024, September 1). *The time to criminalize ecocide is here, but a fifth international crime could hurt the very system from which it draws power and legitimacy*. *Opinio Juris*. <https://opiniojuris.org/2024/09/06/the-time-to-criminalize-ecocide-is-here-but-a-fifth-international-crime-could-hurt-the-very-system-from-which-it-draws-power-and-legitimacy/>
- Bertram, D. (2024). *Ecocide à la Bruxelloise*. *VerfBlog*. <https://doi.org/10.59704/6637da4a696d9542>
- Bray, R., & Pocar, F. (2023). *ELI report on ecocide: Model rules for an EU directive and a council decision*. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4613645>
- Clement, A. (2021). *Ecological policy with a Chinese twist*. Groupe d'études géopolitiques. <https://geopolitique.eu/en/articles/ecological-policy-with-a-chinese-twist/>
- Colin, N., Van Dyck, S., & Arnoldy, M. (2024). *Ecocide out of the woods: Update from Europe and beyond*. *Passle*. <https://riskandcompliance.freshfields.com/post/102jay8/ecocide-out-of-the-woods-update-from-europe-and-beyond>
- Eco Jurisprudence Monitor. (2024, November 20). *Vanuatu, Fiji, and Samoa proposed amendment to the Rome Statute to include a Crime of Ecocide*. <https://ecojurisprudence.org/initiatives/vanuatu-fiji-and-samoa-proposed-amendment-to-the-rome-statute-to-include-a-crime-of-ecocide/>
- European Commission. (2024, April 11). *Environmental Crime Directive*. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/law-and-governance/environmental-compliance-assurance/environmental-crime-directive_en
- Falk, R. (1973). Environmental warfare and ecocide—Facts, appraisal, and proposals. *Bulletin of Peace Proposals*, 4(1), 80–96.
- Faizi, S. (2021). Ecocides: On the need for an Environmental Security Council (ESC). *Capitalism Nature Socialism*, 32(3), 36–42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10455752.2021.1959859>
- Fornusek, M. (2024, June 7). Ukraine charges Russian general over Kakhovka dam destruction. *The Kyiv Independent*. <https://kyivindependent.com/ukraine-charges-russian-general-over-kakhovka-dam-destruction/>
- Galligan, B. P. (2021). Re-theorising the genocide–ecocide nexus: Raphael Lemkin and ecocide in the Amazon. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 26(6), 1004–1031. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13642987.2021.1994402>
- Gillett, M. (2023). *The Kakhovka Dam and ecocide: A convergence of international criminal law, international humanitarian law, international environmental law, and international human rights law?* *VerfBlog*. <https://doi.org/10.17176/20230703-231049-0>
- Hansen, T. O. (2023). *Could the Nova Kakhovka Dam destruction become the ICC's first environmental crimes case?* *Just Security*. <https://www.justsecurity.org/86862/could-the-nova-kakhovka-dam-destruction-become-the-iccs-first-environmental-crimes-case/>

- Heller, K. J. (2021). *Skeptical thoughts on the proposed crime of “ecocide” (that isn’t)*. *Opinio Juris*.
<http://opiniojuris.org/2021/06/23/skeptical-thoughts-on-the-proposed-crime-of-ecocide-that-isnt/>
- Higgins, P., Gauger, A., Rabatel-Fernel, M. P., Kulbicki, L., & Short, D. (2012). *Ecocide is the missing 5th crime against peace*. Human Rights Consortium, University of London. https://space.sas.ac.uk/4686/1/Ecocide_is_the_missing_5th_Crime_Against_Peace.pdf
- Hockman, S. (2009). An international court for the environment. *Environmental Law Review*, 11(1), 1–4.
<https://doi.org/10.1350/enlr.2009.11.1.036>
- Hosa, J. (2023). *The dam has burst: How Russia’s war on Ukraine could make ecocide an international crime*. European Council on Foreign Relations. <https://ecfr.eu/article/the-dam-has-burst-how-russias-war-on-ukraine-could-make-ecocide-an-international-crime/>
- Hurri, K. (2023). The roles they play: Change in China’s climate leadership role during the post-Paris era. *Globalizations*, 20(7), 1065–1082.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2023.2186107>
- International Criminal Court. (2024). *The states parties to the Rome Statute*.
<https://asp.icc-cpi.int/states-parties>
- Kanngieser, A. (2020). Weaponizing ecocide: Nauru, offshore incarceration, and environmental crisis. *The Contemporary Pacific*, 32(2), 492–502.
<https://doi.org/10.1353/cp.2020.0042>
- Langenheim, J. (2015, July 15). *Preventing ecocide in South China Sea*. *The Guardian*.
<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/the-coral-triangle/2015/jul/15/preventing-ecocide-in-south-china-sea>
- Kostin, A. (2024). *Ecocide as a weapon of war*. International Bar Association.
<https://www.ibanet.org/Ecocide-as-a-weapon-of-war>
- Merz, P., Cabanes, V., & Gaillard, E. (2014). Ending ecocide – The next necessary step in international law. In *18th Congress of the International Association of Democratic Lawyers* (Vol. 4).
- Murphy, S. D. (2000). Does the world need a new international environmental court? *The George Washington International Law Review*, 32(3), 333.
- Mwangi, O. (2007). Hydropolitics, ecocide and human security in Lesotho: A case study of the Lesotho Highlands Water Project. *Journal of Southern African Studies*, 33(1), 3–17.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03057070601136509>
- Nowak, E. (2023). Ecocide. Towards the new category of international criminal law. *Przegląd Sejmowy*, 4(177), 63–90.
<https://doi.org/10.31268/PS.2023.198>
- OHCHR. (2023, September). *Update by the chair of the Independent International Commission of Inquiry on Ukraine*.
<https://www.ohchr.org/en/statements-and-speeches/2023/09/update-chair-independent-international-commission-inquiry-ukraine>
- Permanent Mission of the Republic of Vanuatu to the United Nations. (2024, November). *Proposal – Independent crime of ecocide: Explanatory notes*.
<https://ecojurisprudence.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Vanuatu-Proposal-Rome-Statute.pdf>
- Quang, N. M., & Borton, J. (2020). Ecocide on the Mekong: Downstream impacts of Chinese dams and the growing response from citizen science in the lower Mekong Delta. *Asian Perspective*, 44(4), 749–766.
<https://doi.org/10.1353/apr.2020.0032>
- Regenvanu, R. (2024, December 3). *Vanuatu’s statement at the twenty-third session of the Assembly of States Parties to the Rome Statute*.

International Criminal Court.
https://asp.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/asp_docs/AS P23-GD-VUT-3-12-ENG.pdf

- Root, R. (2024, October 14). *Climate crisis: Push for ecocide to be added to Rome Statute*. International Bar Association.
<https://www.ibanet.org/ecocide-rome-statute>
- Sharma, R. (2025, January 16). Ecocide as the fifth international crime: Is the Rome Statute compatible with ecocide? *Völkerrechtsblog*.
<https://doi.org/10.17176/20250116-225415-0>
- Stop Ecocide International. (2021). *Legal definition of ecocide drafted by Independent Expert Panel*. Article 8 ter
<https://www.stopecocide.earth/legal-definition>
- The Office of the Prosecutor. (2024). *The Office of the Prosecutor launches public consultation on a new policy initiative to advance accountability for environmental crimes under the Rome Statute*. International Criminal Court.
<https://www.icc-cpi.int/news/office-prosecutor-launches-public-consultation-new-policy-initiative-advance-accountability-0>
- Van Den Heede, O. (2023). Ecocide as the fifth core crime in the Rome Statute. *International Law and Politics*, 55, 435–445.
- Von Meding, J. (2017, September 27). Agent Orange: How U.S. chemical warfare in Vietnam unleashed a slow-moving disaster. *The Conversation*.
<https://theconversation.com/agent-orange-exposed-how-u-s-chemical-warfare-in-vietnam-unleashed-a-slow-moving-disaster-84572>
- Walters, R. (2022). Ecocide, climate criminals and the politics of bushfires. *The British Journal of Criminology*, 63(2), 283–303.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azac018>
- Zierler, D. (2011). Conclusion: Ecocide and international security. *In the invention*

Agata Bidas

agata.bidas@gmail.com

Agata Bidas is a law graduate from the University of Warsaw and a current master's student in Development Studies at the University of Vienna. Passionate about international law and international relations, her research focuses on international security, nuclear governance, climate policies as well as human rights. Additionally, Agata is an active member of the International Community NGO based in Vienna, where she works on civil society engagement with the EU and international policies.

European Youth Perspectives on International Relations of China (EYPIC)

EYPIC is the culmination of numerous generously donated hours of hard work and dedication by the Coordinating Committee and the Editorial Team at European Guanxi. On behalf of the European Guanxi Editorial Board, we extend our utmost gratitude to all of the individuals who have devoted their time, effort, and passion to this project.

European Guanxi represents a dedication to developing an empowered network of young European professionals, scholars, and students who will impact the dynamics of the EU-China relationship on all fronts. This involves a commitment to connecting young people with one another in the domain of EU-China relations, providing a broader platform to foster debate, discussion, and timely analysis.

To learn more about European Guanxi's mission and values, please visit our website: <https://www.europeanguanxi.com/>

The articles in this volume do not necessarily reflect the opinions of European Guanxi, its leadership, members, partners, or stakeholders, nor those of the editors and Coordinating Committee of this journal. They have been formulated by the authors in their full capacity, and shall not be used for any other purposes other than those they are intended for. European Guanxi assumes no liability or responsibility deriving from the improper use of the contents of this report. Any false facts, errors, and controversial opinions in the articles are proper and exclusive of the authors. European Guanxi or its staff and collaborators cannot be held responsible or legally liable for the use of any and all information contained in this document.

Front Cover: Temple of heaven, Chinese architecture, Beijing image. Free for use. ©jonleong64 / Pixabay Content License / pixabay

Foreword Reference: European External Action Service. (2023, December). *EU-China relations factsheet*. European Union. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/2023/EU-China_Factsheet_Dec2023_02.pdf

Barcelona – Volume 2, Issue 1 (July 2025)

© European Guanxi 2020-2025

163

European
Guanxi

European
Guanxi

European Youth Perspectives on International Relations of China

Volume 2, Issue 1 (July 2025)